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Extended Version of Report Overview

Title: Extended Version of the Report on Libraries or Other University Units as Supporting Centres for Mainstreaming Open Science

Work Package: WP 5 – Mainstreaming Open Science [Months: 1-35]

Extended Version of Report Overview: Extended Version of the Report on Libraries or Other University Units as Supporting Centres for Mainstreaming Open Science presents results from the works undertaken within Task 5.3, detailing the content presented in the Deliverable 5.3.

The report is segmented into three textual description parts, each delving into specific aspects: Case #1 Research Data Management and FAIR Data, Case #2 Responsible Publishing, Case #3 Citizen Science.

The report presents a comprehensive examination of methodologies, milestones, limitations, conclusions, and datasets collected, including training catalogues, repositories, lesson plans, as well as descriptions of good practices in open science.

In addition to the main text, the report includes thirteen appendixes. These provide various visualisations of universities' RDM units in the data lifecycle, a list of skills of the research data professions, a bibliometric analysis on scientific publications within the 4EU+ Alliance.

Additionally, the report includes a detailed account of citizen science interviews, accompanied by a guide and summary. Moreover, a list of figures, tables, and visualisations to aid in navigating the main body of the text has been added.

The written report is complemented by a multimedia presentation of a developed toolkit for Open Science advocacy (available [here](#)).

The main objective of Task 5.3 was to explore and understand the involvement of university libraries in supporting Open Science (OS) and assisting researchers in three selected and previously mentioned cases. Although we had initially planned to investigate the involvement of libraries only, once the work began we decided to include other university units in the analysis that support the development of Open Science. Following this adjustment, we have decided to explore how university libraries and other university units help researchers publish research outputs, prepare research data management plans, and support open citizen science projects. Advising on open access publishing, research data management and citizen science requires specialised knowledge, and we intend to explore how university staff acquire and utilise this expertise.

Task 5.3 aimed to identify and collect best practices from the 4EU+ Alliance universities, seeking inspiration from proven ideas and strategies for effectively meeting the needs of scientists in the context of Open Science.

The report provides firm recommendations regarding the potential roles of support centres (libraries or other units) for Open Science, based on the solutions and practices observed at our universities.

As part of our project, we developed a toolkit for Open Science advocacy. This toolkit could serve as a resource for promoting and facilitating Open Science practices and initiatives.

Dissemination level: Public

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AAM	Author Accepted Manuscript
AIR	Institutional Research Repository, the University of Milan
APC	Article Processing Charge
API	Application Programming Interface
BPC	Book Processing Charge
CAS	Czech Academy of Sciences
CDHN	The Research Data & Digital Humanities Team
CE	Copy editing
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
CoARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
COPE	Committee on Publication Ethics
CS	Citizen Science
CTS	Core Trust Seal
CTU	Center for Educational Innovation and Multimedia Technologies
CU	Charles University
CURIS	Copenhagen University Research Information System
DAG	Data Analysis Gateway, University of Copenhagen
DeiC	Danish e-Infrastructure Consortium
DFG	German Research Foundation
DH	Digital Humanities
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoC	Declaration of Consent
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DPAQVPOS	Performance, Quality Assurance, Assessment, and Open Science Policy Division
DPO	Data Protection Officer

DTU	Technical University of Denmark
EC	European Commission
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
ECTS	European Credit Transfer System
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable - Accessible - Interoperable - Reusable
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HEL	High Performance Environment for Learning, University of Copenhagen
HFDH	Heidelberg Forum for Digital Humanities
HPC	High-Performance Computing
HU	University of Heidelberg
ICM UW	Interdyscyplinarne Centrum Modelowania Matematycznego Uniwersytetu Warszawskiego - Interdisciplinary Centre for Mathematical and Computational Modelling, University of Warsaw
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
INRAE	National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment
IP	Intellectual Property
IRIS	Research Information System, University of Milan
IT	Information Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
KUB	Københavns Universitetsbibliotek / Copenhagen University Library
LDW	Love Data Week
MODI	MPI [Message Passing Interface] Oriented Development and Investigation, University of Copenhagen
NDI	National Data Infrastructure, Czech Republic

NGO	Non Governmental Organisation
NMD	National Metadata Directory, Czech Republic
NRP	National Repository Platform, Czech Republic
OA	Open Access
OAB	Observatoire Agricole de la Biodiversité
OAW	Open Access Week
OBP	Open Book Publishers
OJS	Open Journal Systems
OLH	Open Library of Humanities
OMP	Open Monograph Press
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe
OS	Open Science
PID	Persistent Identifier
POD	Print-on-Demand
PURL	Persistent Uniform Resource Locator
RDM	Research Data Management
Re3data	The Registry of Research Data Repositories
SARA	Archives and Records Department, Sorbonne University
SCOAP3	Sponsoring Consortium for Open Access Publishing in Particle Physics
SIF	Sensitive Information Facility
SPOC	Small Private Online Course
SSC	Scientific Software Centre, Heidelberg University
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics
SU	Sorbonne University
TA	Teaching Assistant
TDM	Text and data mining

TTO	Technology Transfer Office
UCPH	University of Copenhagen
UM	University of Milan
URN	Uniform Resource Name
UW	University of Warsaw
VoR	Version of Record

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1. Introduction

Task 5.3 University Libraries or Other University Units as Centres of Support for Open Science

The degree of commitment to open publishing at European universities still varies widely. This situation also applies to the 4EU+ Alliance. The idea of open publishing is being increasingly promoted at the national level in individual countries. On the other hand, the idea of Open Science can constitute a barrier for researchers if they are left without support from their institution. In this sense, a university library and/or other university units can play a significant role in promoting the idea of Open Science even when there are no institutional solutions to promote it. In this context exploring the role of libraries and/or other units as supporters and facilitators of openness in science, and in publishing in particular, as well as developers of tools for advocating and implementing openness in scientific publication at universities, was one of the main tasks of WP5. The practical aspect of the activities, including the services and training courses conducted at the 4EU+ Alliance universities, was of particular interest.

In Task 5.3 we have investigated the commitment of university libraries and other university units to provide practical help for researchers. Additionally, we collected examples of the best practices to create a toolkit that can serve as a universal manual in the area of mainstreaming Open Science in the academic milieu. Given that advising on publishing and/or preparing research data management plans requires expertise and specialist skills, we also explored specialist insights of academic librarians.

In order to provide firm recommendations regarding the potential functions of libraries and/or other university units as support centres, we examined the diverse support mechanisms within each of the six 4EU+ Alliance universities. Our objective was to identify well-developed best practices so that university libraries/other units aspiring to evolve into support centres for Open Science, could develop and provide valuable and expert assistance.

As an integrated part of Tasks 5.3, we have developed a toolkit for Open Science advocacy¹.

1.1. Context of Task 5.3

The report consists of three separate parts (Part 1-3), each dedicated to a specific case study:

[Case #1 explores Research Data Management \(RDM\) and FAIR \(Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse\) Data,](#)

[Case #2 delves into Responsible Publishing,](#)

and [Case #3 investigates Citizen Science.](#)

The process of selecting these three cases is described in Deliverable 5.1 (Protocol, mainstreaming Open Science – Report).

1.1.1. Case #1 Research Data Management (RDM) and FAIR Data

In the process of discussion on Task 5.3 Case #1 the key topics were determined. These are FAIR data and RDM. We analysed them and chose the best practices as examples to create

¹ See: <https://view.genial.ly/64c0e8a403f8240011e98b6c>

further guidelines. We explored existing projects and support models, but significant differences have emerged with respect to institutional solutions in this matter. Gaps in infrastructure development often limit and negatively impact research practice. These barriers between the 4EU+ Alliance universities were also taken into account and analysed.

The obligation to prepare a data management plan (DMP) for a research project is a challenge for researchers applying for grants. Each plan is different, but some problems are common, e.g. preparation of metadata, selection of software, choice of storage location, as well as ethical and legal issues. Task 5.3 Case #1 has provided a comprehensive understanding of the current landscape and practices in the 4EU+ universities in regard to RDM and FAIR Data.

In the context of RDM, the EOSC (European Open Science Cloud) should also be mentioned. It is one of the ambitions (formerly a pillar) of [the European Union's Open Science policy](#). In our effort to explore deeper into the EOSC topic, we collectively recognized a significant challenge: the diverse organisational structures within European member countries and a wide and varied national context that affects the operation of higher education institutions. Presently, there exists a disparity in the eagerness of various European countries to engage with EOSC. There are no mechanisms that can engage less prepared universities yet.

As our report shows, Case #1, the development of EOSC within universities follows stages and the 4EU+Alliance is at the beginning of this road. First, universities slowly recognize the importance of data management, ensuring dataset sustainability, preserving data sovereignty, and creating a regulated and secure environment. Many universities are in the process of constructing data repositories or updating to newer software versions. We can assume that over time, due to the intensified needs of researchers for international cooperation, the established repositories will be merged. In the final stage, universities embrace sharing data, and EOSC plays a key role. EOSC is a step toward improving global research. However, at the current stage, universities need more support to handle its implementation, especially at the national level, to create a national representative to coordinate all on-the-ground EOSC-related activities. As a result, it was difficult to take more advanced and common action in this area. Our assessment of the situation and the level of involvement of the various universities of our Alliance can be found in **Deliverable 5.1 (Protocol, Mainstreaming Open Science – Report)**.

1.1.2. Case #2 Responsible publishing

The issues that have been selected for detailed analysis in Task 5.3 are strictly based on the guidelines contained in the EU's Open Science policy mentioned above. The most important of these, related to Case #2, include the following:

- provision that beneficiaries retain the intellectual property rights they need to comply with their open access obligations,
- promotion and adoption of open science practices,
- development of new indicators for evaluation research and rewarding researchers,
- funding the development of an open access publishing platform.

The future of scholarly communication is based on responsible publishing. In Case #2 we provide an overview of the key dimensions that focus on making research open, considering,

in particular, the role of libraries and other university units in shaping the scientific publishing system of the future.

1.1.3. Case #3 Citizen Science (CS)

The changing academic landscape, including the increased interdisciplinarity and involvement of citizens in research, makes it necessary to open up science to a wide audience. Citizen Science (CS) has become one of the pillars of Open Science. Case #3 has been dedicated to this issue. Our task was, in particular, to analyse what CS projects are being carried out at the 4EU+ Alliance universities or, more broadly, in the Alliance university countries. Since CS can play an important part in genuine scientific discovery, it is necessary to learn about the activities undertaken in this field at the 4EU+ Alliance universities, compare experiences, or, in the case of the universities not yet involved in such activities, learn how to conduct them. The involvement of the public in scientific research demands support. It is essential to learn what requirements are needed in relation to conducting the research, the infrastructure, and funding. Findings from Case #3 can contribute to clarifying what kind of support is desired from university libraries and other university units in this field.

1.2. Objectives

The primary aims of Task 5.3 were to focus on and investigate the subsequent matters:

- existing tools and solutions for support of mainstreaming Open Science at each of the 4EU+ Alliance universities,
- role of libraries in shaping the scientific publishing system of the future,
- education and advocacy initiatives at each 4EU+ Alliance university, to establish best practices.

The analysis of the assumptions made was to identify the lessons to be learned by the 4EU+ Alliance universities and their libraries, in particular. The lessons learned are the following:

- how to establish new procedures/solutions in our institutions,
- how to improve the existing solutions,
- a deep analysis of what we have already implemented in regard to open science advocacy and what new ideas or solutions can be found to develop it.

The specific objectives of Task 5.3 Case #1 were to investigate the critical moments of DMP development. Partner universities have different experiences in supporting the preparation of DMPs. The aim was to describe good practices and develop recommendations based on them. In the end, a toolkit has been established to develop successful data management plans (DMPs).

In Task 5.3 Case #2, we concentrated on aspects concerning the tools and support involved in scientific publishing, which we termed **responsible publishing**, i.e. publishing that provides open access to texts for a broad audience, takes into account the publication costs, typically funded by public resources, and prioritises the retention of copyright principles.

We aimed to analyse the ways in which each of the six universities within the 4EU+ Alliance facilitates scientific publishing in relation to:

- infrastructure (repositories),
- legal assistance in concluding publishing agreements,
- selection of journals to avoid predatory publishers,
- and support in terms of publication fees (APCs/BPCs - article/book processing charges).

It was also necessary to examine the current state of scientific publishing in the 4EU+ Alliance. For this reason, a bibliometric analysis of the publications of our six universities in 2021-2022 has been performed, with particular emphasis on open access publishing. This has been the basis for the formulation of conclusions and the development of recommendations for support centres.

Raising awareness about responsible scientific publishing demands education and advocacy undertakings which were other objectives of Case #2.

Task 5.3, Case #3, was concerned with identifying best practices for supporting Citizen Science projects at the 4EU+ Alliance and other universities. Our goal was to draft recommendations on how to support CS projects and researchers applying CS methodologies. A qualitative approach was selected to learn more about which skills and funding requirements are applied to Citizen Science projects. Consequently the recommendations are based on an investigation of:

- three CS projects from across Europe from three different research disciplines,
- interviews about which competencies researchers and research support staff should have to carry out and support CS projects,
- reflections about the extent support and training for CS projects should be offered at universities,
- and discussions with the leaders CS projects about the funding landscape in Europe.

1.3. Conclusions / Recommendation

1.3.1. Case #1 Research Data Management and FAIR Data

1.3.1.1. Executive Summary

The conducted activity on RDM and FAIR data under the TRAIN4EU, WP5 Mainstreaming Open Science Task 3 has provided a comprehensive understanding of the current landscape and practices in the 4EU+ universities. The examination of RDM support services in the first step uncovered a trend of generalist services functioning at the university level. These services are complemented by specialised disciplinary support within local RDM units, which may vary from one institution to another. This decentralised approach corresponds with the diversity of research data and its unique requirements within different academic contexts.

The consistency observed in RDM services across the Alliance universities presents an opportunity for potential collaborations and knowledge-sharing between the Alliance partners. By pooling resources, expertise, and practices, the universities can enhance their RDM capabilities and contribute to the advancement of RDM practices.

RDM services also evolve with the demands of society, giving rise to new data-related professions. While these roles are still adjusting to the evolving landscape, they play a crucial part in developing and disseminating best practices for RDM within institutions. Among the 4EU+ Alliance, although the implementation of these professions is not yet uniformed across institutions, and their practical applications are far from having a defined structure, universities continually seek to refine their strategies to meet these needs, as demonstrated in the second step.

Ensuring the success of RDM strategies requires the implementation of proper training programs. Therefore, in the third step, an inventory of RDM training programs within universities was conducted, with a focus on identifying gaps within each institution to address missing areas. Tracking the training sessions provided by various faculties is a common challenge due to their extensive and diverse characteristics, which can sometimes lead to redundancy. Sharing training sessions could prove beneficial, allowing us to leverage the expertise of each member of the Alliance.

Finally, a specific mention of available data repositories among the 4EU+ universities and their key characteristics has been chosen as it represents an important area of RDM. Most of the universities use the Dataverse platform as it aligns with FAIR principles. It supports Findability through DOI assignment and Re3data integration, increasing the discoverability of valuable research data. Universities using Dataverse typically have well-defined terms of use and access policies. These policies ensure that data is accessible to authorised users while maintaining data security and compliance with an option to embargo, if necessary. Supporting various types of datasets and data formats contributes to the interoperability of datasets stored in repositories. It promotes reusability by facilitating proper data documentation, long-term data preservation, citation through DOIs, and data sharing.

Financial strategies for creating and sustaining these repositories varied among universities, same as long-term preservation plans in their consideration and implementation. While some repositories have detailed financial solutions and long-term preservation plans, others may still be in the process of developing or considering these aspects.

However, the interoperability among Alliance members can be ensured due to the shared use of the same data repository solution, Dataverse, and their mutual commitment to RDM and FAIR data principles. This commonality in data infrastructure and principles facilitates FAIR data creation between Alliance partners, encouraging a collaborative environment for research and data-driven initiatives.

1.3.1.2. Recommendations Case #1

1.3.1.2.1. Recommendation on RDM services

- **Conduct a comprehensive inventory of the RDM services within the university**, assigning them to each stage of the data lifecycle. This inventory will serve as a visual representation of the support type offered by RDM services.

- Consider opportunities to **foster collaboration**, shared learning, and mutual benefits between local and transversal RDM services.
 - Establish an interconnected infrastructure, such as **the Research Data Helpdesk**, at the individual university level, and subsequently extend this collaborative framework across Alliance members.

1.3.1.2.2. Recommendation on RDM job profiles

- **Define the required skills and competencies for RDM professionals** based on the identified RDM services in the previous stage. This will ensure that RDM staff possess the necessary expertise to support RDM effectively.
- Explore which **support services** provide more comprehensive RDM support **throughout the data lifecycle**.
- Investigate whether these existing RDM services can adapt to address new data-related needs. If not:
 - **Compare these unmet needs** with the skills and competencies of newly emerging data roles. Determine if these roles are already encompassed within the existing job titles.
 - **Promote the establishment of data-driven professions** designed to address the changing landscape of RDM. These roles should be equipped to handle emerging challenges in RDM.
 - **Engage key stakeholders, particularly researchers, in the development and implementation of these new data-driven professions.** Ensure that their input and needs are considered to create job profiles that effectively support RDM and include them to the process, such as creating data championship programs, if possible.

1.3.1.2.3. Recommendation on RDM training

- **Evaluate existing training sessions offered by RDM support units** to identify areas of improvement, gaps, and emerging needs. This assessment should inform the enhancement of training programs.
- **Develop a survey questionnaire** for researchers to gather insights into their specific requirements for RDM training. This survey should encompass a wide range of topics, from basic data management to advanced data sharing and preservation.
- **Establish collaborative RDM training initiatives and courses in coordination with relevant stakeholders.** This collaboration can involve multiple universities, research institutions, and experts in the field to create comprehensive and effective training resources.

1.3.1.2.4. Recommendation on Data repositories

- **Conduct a comprehensive review of data repositories** used by Alliance members to determine if these repositories extend their services to external users. This

assessment will help identify potential opportunities for collaboration and resource sharing.

- **Establish a framework for promoting and ensuring best practices in data curation and moderation** within the Alliance data repositories. This framework should include guidelines for topics like metadata standards, quality control, and data preservation to enhance the overall quality and utility of the stored research data.
- **Facilitate knowledge exchange** among Alliance members **to leverage each other's experiences and expertise in long-term data preservation**. This collaborative approach will help ensure the sustainability and integrity of valuable research data over time.

1.3.1.2.5. How the 4EU+ University Alliance can expand its collaboration and focus on RDM services

- Strengthen collaboration between RDM support units within the 4EU+ Alliance.
- Coordinate RDM services between local (unit, laboratory) and transversal (university) levels in each institution.
- Support the development of new job profiles to address emerging RDM issues in the local context.
- Identify whether national or international initiatives are underway, e.g., EOSC, and communicate about them to university authorities and researchers.
- Implement data champion programs.
- Develop joint RDM training courses within the 4EU+, such as a joint program or summer school.
- Develop joint training courses on the ethical and legal aspects of RDM and on reproducibility.
- Support the creation and maintenance of each partner's data repository.
- Provide sustainable funding for long-term data preservation (beyond 10 years).
- Consider CoreTrustSeal (CTS) certification for all the 4EU+ repositories.

1.3.2. Case #2 Responsible Publishing

1.3.2.1. Executive Summary

The scientific publishing system of the future should give free (open) access to valuable scientific knowledge. To achieve greater openness of science, changes are required in the publication policies concerning the preservation and accessibility of completed scientific achievements, as well as the handling of research data. Responsible open publishing refers to

the ethical and sustainable practices and principles associated with open access publishing in scholarly and scientific communication. It encompasses a set of values and actions aimed at ensuring that open publishing serves the best interests of researchers, the academic community, and the broader public.

Responsible open publishing promotes first of all, accessibility, but also transparency, quality and integrity, diversity and inclusivity, ethical standards, long-term preservation, sustainability, protection of intellectual property, and community engagement, to name the most important. Responsible open publishing aims to strike a balance between openness, quality, and ethical conduct. It recognizes the potential benefits of open access while addressing the challenges and potential risks associated with the transition to open publishing models. Ultimately, it seeks to create a publishing ecosystem that fosters the dissemination of knowledge while upholding the highest standards of scholarly communication.

Publishers' approaches are changing in favour of free (open) publishing, but these are insufficient, especially due to the rising costs of open publications. It is therefore necessary to consider what actions academic libraries or other university units can take to enable scientists to promote knowledge and scientific achievements to all interested parties in a responsible manner. Universities, as well as taking responsibility for their own impact on society as an organisation, raise awareness about the necessity of opening science.

To this end, a variety of activities are undertaken, ranging from training for the academic community to the creation of tools that can be used to make the achievements of science available to the general public in a responsible manner. There are still questions about publication ethics and policies at individual universities and in individual countries, which are closely connected to the evaluation of scientific achievements. Hence, nowadays the strong involvement of universities in activities recently established by the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA).

In addressing this topic, and identifying strengths and areas for improvement, we focused on the situation at the universities of the Alliance. It was necessary to make a comparative analysis of the open publishing landscape within collected data among the 4EU+ Alliance universities. We did an overview of the key dimensions, which are:

- **Publication practices of authors affiliated with the 4EU+ Alliance universities.** We used bibliometric methods to analyse peer-reviewed open access publications from 2021-2022. We explored the number of publications, open access publications routes, research fields, co-authored practices, publishers, funders, and publication costs.
- **Various Types of Support for Open Publishing.** This dimension involved investigating the availability of different forms of support, including legal, technical, and financial assistance for authors engaged in the open publishing process.
- **Training Courses and Online Resources.** We explored the existence of training courses, online guidelines, and materials offered by the universities. These resources covered various aspects of open access publishing, including the evaluation of open access journals, addressing predatory journals, understanding white-listing and transformative agreements for open access journals, as well as information on Article Processing Charges (APCs) and Book Processing Charges (BPCs), fee discounts, and rules governing participation in publication programs.

- **Repositories and Publishing Platforms.** In this dimension, we assessed the level of support provided to authors throughout the submission, peer review, and publication process, with a focus on repositories and open access publishing platforms that are available at Alliance universities.

We captured our achievements from those fields. That enabled us to operate with specific examples, make comparisons, and draw conclusions. The aim was to develop general guidelines that other European universities can use in the future. We demonstrate the steps we took collectively in the description of case studies of each of the 4EU+ Alliance universities.

This analysis allowed us to:

- **Identify Differences and Similarities,** by comparing the practices and approaches of each university, we were able to identify areas of variation and commonalities. This helped us understand the diversity of open publishing support and policies within the Alliance.
- **Assess Best Practices,** through comparative analysis, we could pinpoint best practices and successful strategies that individual universities had implemented. These practices could serve as models for others to follow.
- **Promote Collaboration,** through comparative analysis, we can highlight opportunities for collaboration and knowledge sharing among universities. It encourages the exchange of ideas and experiences to enhance open access publishing support.
- **Facilitate Decision-Making,** the results from the comparative analysis were used to support our decision-making process and provide evidence-based recommendations. This allowed us to draw conclusions based on real-world practice.

1.3.2.2. Recommendations Case #2

1.3.2.2.1. Recommendation on publishing practices

- Researchers, especially in the social sciences and humanities, should be encouraged to **increase the visibility of research results**, by promoting open access publishing and the use of DOIs or other Persistent Unique Identifiers (PIDs) for publications, e.g. Handle, PURL, or URN. Selecting journals or publishing platforms that offer DOIs should be the standard.
- Periodic **evaluation of researchers** should take into account the publication in OA as an important aspect of practising Open Science. The use of the green route to open access (repositories) should be given special recognition. The publication should also have in mind other research outputs like software, providing documentation to data which are made available to the public.
- **Publishing books in open access requires different business models** to those used for scientific journals, as book publishing is more expensive and time-consuming. Some of the recently proposed models consist of freemium, selective open access, and crowdfunding, in addition to established models such as author payment or university presses. The support centres should particularly assist art, humanities, and social science

researchers in understanding new models of publishing monographs and their impact on the academic market.

- It is crucial to **alert researchers about the risks associated with publishing through publishers of uncertain reputations**, even if these publishers are listed on government whitelists. Irresponsible publishing in predatory journals can lead to losing scientific credibility and cutting off access to leading international research groups. Government white lists are in use in Poland and France (other countries in Europe: Norway; outside Europe: South African, India, Australia).

1.3.2.2.2. Recommendation on tools and support solutions

- Work on **support framework that would regulate joint publication process** across the 4EU+ Alliance members and/or at European level, if possible:
 - Establish a working group or a committee comprising representatives from the Alliance universities to develop joint publication regulation documents.
 - Collaborate with legal and academic experts to ensure that the documents adhere to legal and ethical standards.
 - Consider creating a central platform (possibly the 4EU+ Alliance website) to house these documents for easy access and reference by researchers and academic staff across the Alliance.
- **Strive to ensure an equal level of knowledge of employees from science support units** at the Alliance universities – exchange of experience, mutual training, creation of a knowledge base collecting information on solutions applied at partner universities:
 - Organise regular workshops, webinars, and seminars where employees from science support units can share best practices and experiences related to open access publishing.
 - Create a knowledge-sharing platform or intranet where information on solutions and practices from partner universities can be documented and accessed by all members.
 - Encourage cross-institutional training and exchanges of staff to foster a collaborative spirit and mutual learning.

- **Prepare a joint campaign** of tools useful for open publishing:
 - Develop a joint promotional campaign to raise awareness of open access publishing tools and resources. This campaign can include webinars, social media initiatives, and information sessions.
 - Collaborate with libraries, research offices, and academic departments to effectively promote these tools to researchers and authors.
 - Highlight the benefits of open access publishing, such as increased visibility and impact of research.
- **Develop mentoring and support to early career researchers and doctoral students** interested in publishing in open access:
 - Establish mentorship programs that pair early career researchers and doctoral students with experienced academics who have expertise in open access publishing.
 - Provide training and resources specific to the needs of early career researchers, including guidance on selecting open access journals, understanding copyright, and navigating publishing fees.
 - Offer financial support or grants to early career researchers to cover open access publication fees.
- **Develop common tools for monitoring and evaluation:**
 - Establish mechanisms for monitoring the effectiveness and impact of these initiatives, gathering feedback from researchers, and making adjustments as needed.

1.3.2.2.3. Recommendation on education and advocacy undertakings

- In the context of scientific cooperation and publishing in the Alliances – **to create an offer of courses on scientific publishing raising recent developments** by the member universities and their respective units.
- Across the 4EU+ Alliance – **to develop similar or common principles for the structure of training and to target the same audiences:** students, doctoral students, and academics.
- At individual universities, which are at the early stage of adoption – **to advocate for and establish institutional open access and open data policies** that encourage and support researchers in sharing their work openly, referring to achievements and regulations undertaken at other alliance member universities.
- **Support centres should emphasise and communicate the benefits of open publishing** to researchers, not only in terms of benefits to the authors themselves

(increased number of citations) but **also in terms of socially responsible publishing**.
The public must have access to research results.

1.3.2.2.4. How the 4EU+ University Alliance can expand its collaboration and focus on Responsible Publishing

Currently existing solutions to support responsible publishing vary within the 4EU+ Alliance. These differences are due to the varying degrees of development of the infrastructure, but also to differences in regulations and publication requirements at institutional and national levels. The 4EU+ Alliance universities, and libraries in particular, can continue to cooperate on:

- co-creating guidelines on publishing issues based on best practices at their university and in their country,
- building common infrastructures, e.g. repositories, and promotion,
- encouraging university presses to co-operate in the publication of books using new models of publishing,
- strengthen the Alliance's collaborative network by encouraging co-publications within the Alliance not only in the fields of science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM), but also in the field of social sciences and humanities (SSH)
- advocating for the inclusion of Open Science practices in the curriculum, regular evaluation of researchers, calls for internal projects, and internal funding programmes.

1.3.3. Case #3 Citizen Science (CS)

1.3.3.1. Executive Summary

The aim of Task 5.3 Case #3, was to investigate examples of good practices concerning CS projects and support units at the 4EU+ Alliance and other universities to draft recommendations on how to support CS projects. The approach is described briefly with regard to the following points:

1. obtaining an overview of good-practice cases in CS across Europe, preferably covering different research disciplines,
2. investigating what competencies researchers and research support staff should have to carry out and support CS projects, as well as what training is required to develop these competencies,
3. investigation to what extent support and training for CS projects should be offered at universities and how this support could be organised,
4. investigation how Citizen Science projects can be funded in Europe.

These four themes have been investigated through interviews with three citizen science projects and desk-top research. Findings are collected in three short milestone reports. Task 5.3 Case#3 enabled us an in-depth analysis of the conditions, circumstances, and requirements that exist when scientists use CS. The investigation creates a good foundation for finding out what kind

of support is needed and desirable in other CS projects. Not every CS project needs the same kind of support. Findings from this task will contribute to clarifying what support is desirable from university libraries and other potential support units that are or can be provided by the university. The results will make it easier to prioritise what will or can be the best support in other CS projects.

1.3.3.2. Recommendations Case #3

1.3.3.2.1. Recommendation on support

- **University libraries, university IT support, and data stewards need to collaborate** to provide technical support in concretely developing and setting up suitable platforms/databases/infrastructures for CS projects. Furthermore, they need to **facilitate user experience tests in platform development in CS projects**. Such platforms have the responsibility to balance the data collection process, depth of data, and technical platform to the needs of researchers, scientific integrity, and amateur contributors.
- **Provide training in communication strategies** as well as in how to conduct stakeholder analysis or how to gain a budget for a communication officer in the CS project application.
- Take advantage of the opportunities to **use university libraries and public libraries** as relevant platforms to reach new target groups who can be involved in CS projects for the benefit of democratisation of knowledge, research, and the population's interest in science.
- Based on the fact that in one of the investigated CS projects no support was provided from the university's IT department or the university as such, it is considered to be beneficial to **create a place where resources related to CS are gathered**. This could also strengthen progress and synergy with respect to other CS projects within the university.
- For countries without a tradition of and experience with CS consider **supporting top-down initiatives** such as nationwide CS projects.

1.3.3.2.2. Recommendation on infrastructure

- Recognise that **CS projects are different from other research projects and hence require other forms of support**. University policy documents must clarify how the university will benefit from CS projects to be able to advocate for investment in resources for citizen science projects.
- **Support for CS projects could include a single point of contact for CS (SPOC)** at the university or national competence centre. Support at the SPOC could be provided in two streams, human infrastructure and technical infrastructure.
 - **Human infrastructure:** a “hub” (a lab or an office) that offers advice on how to design a CS project, where to find funding, recruitment and retention of citizens, communication and promotion strategies, and how citizens and other stakeholders feel validated in their contribution to the project. Furthermore, the hub could provide knowledge of applications and technical

solutions for data collection and handling, including expertise in ethical and legal considerations with respect to data collected by citizens.

- **Technical infrastructure:** provide safe storage for data and data collection devices for researchers to use in the training and promotion of projects. In particular, guidance on how to build an easy-to-use platform that citizens can use to deliver relevant, quality data and that researchers can use to process the data and provide sustainable outcomes.
- It is a core responsibility of the university to promote research. **A communication channel should be provided by the university or between universities where researchers and citizens are able to exchange knowledge, interests, projects, and recruitment.** This could be the face of the university in society and contribute to reducing the distance between research institutions and citizens, increasing trust in science and in the application of results.
- **Invest in the education or up-skilling of communication experts.** Continued communication is essential throughout a CS project and requires skills in science communication across diverse groups of stakeholders. The following profiles are identified as key performers in CS projects which require **professionalisation and identification of a minimum viable skill set:**
 - **A CS Steward:** the CS steward has an advisory role and provides guidance on how to run the CS project and identify target groups in the community and design the CS project to fit them. **The steward would have knowledge about user experience (UX) and the design of data collection and delivery tools**, and act as a facilitator who could create connections between persons who want to contribute to CS projects and researchers who have a CS project that needs volunteers.
 - **CS “champions”.** Students or members of the community (citizens) who help with the face-to-face promotion of the project. The champion goes from library to library, from museum to museum, and talks about the CS project to the public.
 - **A “Community manager” (facilitator).** A project member (researcher or administrator) with the responsibility and people skills to continuously work with the community and navigate between stakeholders throughout the project. They would ensure communication with the community, nurture relationships with stakeholders, gather up and solve issues, collect results, and make sure the community is heard and valued in the project.

1.3.3.2.3. Recommendation on funding models

- **Develop standardised and transparent quality criteria** for CS projects to classify CS projects in funding rounds.
- **Develop templates in EU funder grant applications, such as Horizon Europe, that fit the description and elements of a CS project.**
- Pool positions of project “facilitators” from several projects to then compile a full position **CS community manager who could supervise the communication of**

multiple CS projects. Community management could also be in cooperation with interested partner organisations or NGOs.

- Funding opportunities that support conditional financing of long-term projects. **Conditional financing, that is, the project continues to reach goals and have momentum, would secure funding and safeguard not only the maintenance but also the evolution of the project.**
- **Develop funding models that are specifically designed to support CS projects,** that is the research, the citizens, and the technical and human infrastructures that are unique to CS projects. **However, CS funding should not be limited exclusively to specific funding schemes.** Rather, it must also be possible to apply for CS projects in the regular funding programs of third-party funders.

1.3.3.2.4. How the 4EU+ University Alliance can expand its collaboration and focus on Citizen Science

In the future the universities in the 4EU+Alliance can work together to broaden the vision of citizen science by investigating additional support opportunities, such as academics with expertise in socio-management areas dealing with external and internal partners, as well as practitioners like science managers and facilitators. The focus could be on shared opportunities while respecting local diversity to foster academic-non-academic relationships. As such, the recommendations in the TRAIN4EU for new directions for supporting CS are:

- strengthening communication between CS communication, science communication, and citizens,
- sharing experiences and lessons learned regarding human and technical support infrastructure,
- enhancing public engagement through CS contributing to a more open and inclusive R&I system, leading to stronger knowledge circulation and inclusiveness among citizens and in communities, as well as increased alignment of strategic research with society needs, expectations and values,
- advocating for supportive policies and frameworks at institutional and national levels to promote CS,
- engaging with policymakers and relevant stakeholders to advocate for policies that foster knowledge sharing between EU projects that include CS.

CS projects are conducted only in limited numbers at each university. Therefore, knowledge exchange with similar initiatives is not straightforward. The 4EU+ Alliance could enable such interactions and sharing of know-how between CS projects by establishing an open CS forum for researchers from partner institutions interested in CS methods. Such a forum could be used to establish contacts in the respective partner countries to involve citizens from different countries in CS projects.

2. Part 1 – Case #1 Research Data Management (RDM) and FAIR Data

RDM is a key concept for organising data throughout its life cycle (from collection and storage to sharing and archiving). RDM is essential for funded research projects and is now a requirement for most funders. It is also fundamental for institutions to be able to identify and valorize the datasets produced by researchers. Academic libraries, which are actors in collections management, have an important role to play in supporting services related to RDM. The principles retained for good data management and data sharing, if possible, are called the FAIR principles: the data must be findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable.

2.1. Objectives

The main goal of Case #1 was to explore the RDM training programs offered by the 4EU+ universities as well as training requirements and gaps to create a comprehensive lesson plan, which was one of the objectives of this activity.

Case #1 Research Data Management and FAIR Data:

- objective #1 – to deliver clear information on OS policies and to implement solutions based on national and European background (examples of European regulations: Commission Recommendation 2012/417/EU²; Commission Recommendation 2018/790/EU³; Directive 2019/1024/EU⁴),
- objective #2 – to mainstream FAIR data as part of OS research culture through courses, tutorials, and support services,
- objective #3 – to introduce OS principles in the research lifecycle.

2.2. Methodology and Data Collection

Building upon previous documents (WP 5 Deliverable 5.1 and 5.2), Case #1 involves the identification of the RDM ecosystem in the 4EU+ Alliance. It is organised into 4 steps covering topics such as RDM services, RDM job profiles, RDM training programs and data repositories within 4EU+ Alliance members.

1. RDM services in universities

Initially, an analysis of RDM support units followed by their services was conducted in the form of benchmark organising around the data lifecycle. Implementing research data lifecycle as a medium allowed to map RDM units to data lifecycle phases covering various support

² [Commission Recommendation of 17 July 2012 on access to and preservation of scientific information.](#)

³ [Commission Recommendation \(EU\) 2018/790 of 25 April 2018 on access to and preservation of scientific information](#)

⁴ [Directive \(EU\) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information \(recast\)](#)

services. From the obtained results, pivot table and visualisation were created for better illustration.

2. RDM job profiles

After reanalyzing this benchmark, the keywords corresponding to the skills and competencies were emphasised and then classed into two groups – Hard skills, which require an expertise; and Soft skills, which are matched with personality traits.

Skills were associated with RDM units, but some units with similar services in different domains led to repetitive information. To address this, RDM units were grouped into general ideal types, facilitating the development of job profile templates. Some units, like Library and Data & Computer Centre, offered customised support services, making job profile development more complex.

An internal workshop was organised to discuss emerging data roles in 4EU+ institutions.

3. RDM training programs

The same benchmark was used as a reference to list RDM training programs. A dedicated column for RDM training was added, including sub-columns related to training programs. An exhaustive list was conducted with the aim to examine if RDM units provided comprehensive training or focused on specific aspects.

During the bilateral meetings, participants were asked whether they regarded these units as providers of RDM training in their universities. Subsequently, they were requested to identify any gaps in their institution's RDM training programs, to specify where training is most needed, and to highlight the challenges associated with RDM training. From the highlighted subjects, lesson plans were then developed covering these missing areas.

4. Data repositories

For the last part, another benchmark was created to list existing data repositories in 4EU+ universities, using parameters similar to works conducted on listing repositories. After collecting information, bilateral meetings were organised with each university, during which additional columns were suggested to be added to the benchmark. Financial solutions employed by each data repository were discussed to understand the options for creating such repositories. Furthermore, long-term preservation options for the data repositories were addressed, exploring whether each repository had considered this aspect and how they planned to sustain long-term preservation.

Each topic has been concluded with a milestone:

1. RDM services in universities

Milestone 1. A map of RDM services in the 4EU+ universities and connections with academic libraries.

2. RDM job profiles

Milestone 2. Job profile templates for RDM actors, particularly for new emerging roles such as data engineer, data scientist, data steward and data librarian.

3. RDM training programs

Milestone 3. Lesson plans covering the missing subjects in the 4EU+ universities.

4. Data repositories

Milestone 4. A list of existing data repositories in the 4EU+ universities followed by funding and long-term preserving solutions.

2.3. Description

2.3.1. RDM services in universities – A map of RDM services in the 4EU+ universities and connections with academic libraries (Milestone 1)

The following description delineates the steps implemented, the investments undertaken, and the impact achieved. The sample content has been grouped into four areas:

1. Scope and objectives, outlining key characteristics of the projects and the drivers behind good practices as well as possible relations with other policy initiatives,
2. Implementation, illustrating steps and potential challenges and barriers encountered in the practice development of good practices,
3. Capacity, highlighting organisational units and members of the staff involved at the institutional level, sources of funding, and possible collaborations with other academic institutions and private actors,
4. Impact, describing the processes used to evaluate the effectiveness of their initiatives, next steps for their further development and potential lessons learned.

Milestone 1. A map of RDM services in the 4EU+ universities and connections with academic libraries.

The activity on research data management within Task 5.3 included the following issues:

- identification of possible collaborations between the RDM support services of the six universities of the 4EU+ Alliance,
- study on the activities of the staff working on this topic,
- training for staff and researchers.

At first, it was necessary to identify RDM stakeholders in the six universities to understand how research data support is organised. The existing institutional solutions have already been described in tasks 5.1 and 5.2. They have been used to benchmark the universities' websites to create a map of the RDM services of each institution. Also, a short interview was conducted within the WP5 contacts to verify that we have taken into account all existing structures. We have already seen that not all institutions are organised in the same way. Some have created data labs (e.g. the KBU Datalab), central and decentral support units, while others have a university library that provides support for data management. We have listed the different types of organisation with their strengths and their collaboration with each other.

2.3.1.1. Connection to previous tasks

As a first stage of SU activity on the RDM topic in Task 5.3, our objective was to identify stakeholders around RDM within the 4EU+ Alliance. We worked with the material collected in previous tasks. Task 5.1 defined the work themes, including those on RDM and FAIR data. The different use cases proposed on RDM particularly highlighted the importance of focusing on FAIR principles and best practices in this area. The SWOT matrices helped us to illustrate the opportunities and weaknesses identified by the six universities, for example, the need to develop the support staff skills which we will address in the second stage. The work done in Task 5.2 helped us learn about the national open science policies in the countries of the Alliance members and outline the institutional policies of the six universities. The information collected in Task 5.3 served as a useful document, especially for tracking best RDM practices from the Alliance perspective. Therefore, this activity builds on all of this material to illustrate the RDM service ecosystem in the 4EU+ Alliance.

2.3.1.2. Methodology

First, we made an inventory of the services, already identified in the previous tasks, and did further research on the websites of each university to see if there were other services to be added. From these elements, we created a benchmark organised around the data lifecycle.

The idea of using data lifecycle as a medium to depict the RDM ecosystem in the 4EU+ Alliance occurred during the creation of the first visuals. Research data lifecycle is implemented as a tool that can be used to map different phases, from Search/Reuse to Share, and see how they connect to each other. The use of a data lifecycle allows a transition from a short-term to a long-term perspective in data management.

The Research Data Management Lifecycle

Figure 1. RDM lifecycle by UC Santa Cruz University Library (original page)

Inspired by the schema in Figure 1, we created a prototype, seen in Figure 2, placing the university in the centre of the data lifecycle. Using the data lifecycle as a tool helped us better structure RDM units while covering different support services.

Figure 2. The 4EU+ data lifecycle prototype

Once this initial foresight work was completed, we then conducted bilateral interviews with group members at each university to verify with them that assigning RDM units to each data lifecycle step was consistent for their university. These interviews were very useful in completing the elements we had already identified, making corrections to their description, and

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adding new ones if we had missed any. The results of this part can be seen in the “RDM in each university” section (2.3.1.3.).

Finally, from the results obtained, we created a pivot table (see Table 7) that regroups RDM support services around the data lifecycle. This choice allowed us to clarify the corresponding services in each university. From this table, we also prepared general visualisations, as seen in the section 2.3.1.4. RDM and 4EU+. The categorization of RDM services into different colours enabled us to create a comprehensive overview of the 4EU+ Alliance. The size of the circle was calculated on the basis of the occurrence of the same type of RDM services.

2.3.1.3. RDM in each university

We identified various departments and/or services involved in RDM within the 4EU+ Alliance around the data lifecycle schema. Determining a schema to follow in advance has allowed us to more easily construct repetitive patterns. Then, for each university, we successively created corresponding visuals accompanied by a summary table, which can be found below in the sub-sections (see visualisations in [5.1. Appendix 1. Task 5.3, Case #1 Research Data Management and FAIR Data. Visualisations of the universities' RDM units in a data lifecycle](#)).

We noticed that several different RDM services have already been collaborated with each other covering diverse needs. Some others, from their beginning, have been established as mixed units between distinct services. Although RDM services have a different designation in the 4EU+ universities, we remarked that they provide the same support type.

The levels of resources and staff involved in these services are predicted to vary from one to another. However, during this stage, these aspects were not further analysed.

We can conclude that these services are now essential for accompanying researchers in their various projects and helping to build a natively digital scientific heritage.

Charles University (CU)

Table 1. RDM units at Charles University

CU Centre for Knowledge and Technology Transfer
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● questions on legal issues connected with commercialisation or patenting
CU Computer Science Center
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● providing support services in collaboration with national infrastructures (MetaCentrum NGI, CESNET, and e-INFRA CZ): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ big data analysis, HPC, data process and scientific calculation ○ offering data storage infrastructure ○ software & applications installation, assistance and configuration of management applications, etc.
CU Central Library - Open Science Support Centre
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● covering general aspects of data search/reuse ● providing general assistance and training sessions on DMP and FAIR data

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● assisting with organisation and description of research data & metadata and FAIRification ● training sessions for storing research data ● general support and training for depositing data ● helping research data publication (repositories, data papers, etc.)
CU Central Library Support
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● providing support to search information in databases and a help desk for assistance
CU Ethics Commission
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● assistance for covering ethical aspects to consider during the data lifecycle ● consultation on ethical issues relevant to data sharing
CU Grant Agency (GA UK)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● supporting researchers in the preparation of grant applications (intellectual property, stakeholders, etc.) and proposing an optional requirement for DMP
CU Faculty IT Departments
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● assistance of costs & technical aspects (equipment, storage, servers, data security, etc.) ● providing consultancy on tools & software ● consultation on large data processing ● consultation on storing research data ● providing consultation on archiving research data and support with collaboration CESNET storage services for long term backup
CU Open Science Support Centre - Copyright & Open Science Lawyer
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● assistance on legal aspects of data sharing (licences, agreements, copyrights, etc.) ● questions on legal aspects of open access and open data (interpretation of licence agreements, using third-party data in regard to data management, etc.)
CU Special working group
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● raising awareness and connecting different parts of RDM unit and researchers
CU University Data Protection Officer
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● consultation and assistance on legal constraints for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ data storage ○ data sharing ○ personal & sensitive data protection and its processing

The University of Copenhagen (UCPH)

Table 2. RDM units at the University of Copenhagen

UCPH Data Protection Officer
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● consultation and assistance on legal constraints for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ data storage ○ data sharing ○ personal & sensitive data protection and its processing
UCPH Datalabs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● offering data processing (e.g. design, modelling, and calculations) and data analysis ● providing advice and courses for data collection (text, data, signals, images)
UCPH Ethics Committee
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● assistance for covering ethical aspects to consider during the data lifecycle ● consultation on ethical issues relevant to data sharing
UCPH IT Department
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● covering costs & technical aspects (equipment, storage, servers, data security, etc.) ● offering support on customised research applications and consultancy ● consultancy of IT security and services: providing customised service solutions for storage, back-up and access
UCPH Library Datalab (KUB)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● providing guidance for some specific databases and keeping overview of recommended databases ● assisting researchers with tools and methods for harvesting data (e.g. text and data mining) ● proposing tools and training for analysing data
UCPH Office of Research Services (F&I Research Services, RDM and Information Security)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● helping DMP writing in funding proposal, assistance on data management and risk assessment for research project ● offering back-up and access management and storage facilities ● helping researchers to register their research and questions related to data sharing (stakeholders, licences, etc.)
UCPH SCIENCE AI Centre

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● data process and analysis (including resources and infrastructure for performing AI)
UCPH SCIENCE HPC Centre
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● providing supercomputers and data analysis (DAG, HEL, MODI, customised HPC setup) ● offering repository and assistance for research data storage (ERDA, SIF) and archiving ● providing repository with covering DOI, useful for internal project collaboration
UCPH Technology Transfer Office
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● consultation and assistance on agreements, patents, IP rights, etc.
UCPH Library Research Support
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● organising orientation and training sessions on information/datasets seeking ● offering training sessions on DMP and reviewing DMP on request ● assistance in archiving research data ● supporting research data publication

Heidelberg University (HU)

Table 3. RDM units at Heidelberg University

HU Competence Centre for Research Data (KFD)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● guiding researchers to access relevant datasets ● organising training sessions on DMP and reviewing DMP on request ● offering a variety of software tools and services to support with data processing and data management, e.g. a electronic lab notebook ● assisting with organisation and description of research data: file formats, relevant metadata, metadata schemes and vocabularies, conversion, etc. and advising on data analysis ● advice on storing and archiving research data ● assistance & solutions to archive research data: heiDATA and heidICON; a new long-term preservation infrastructure heiARCHIVE is under construction ● helping research data publication by offering two institutional repositories (heiDATA & heidICON) and offering guidance on external, subject-specific repositories; advice on legal issues of data sharing (copyright, licences, etc.)
HU Data Protection Officer
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● consultation and assistance on legal constraints for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ data storage ○ data sharing ○ personal & sensitive data protection and its processing

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● monitoring compliance with data protection standards
HU Ethics Commission
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● assistance for covering ethical aspects to consider during the data lifecycle
HU Heidelberg Forum Digital Humanities (HFDH)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● support on accessing data related to DH ● assisting DH project planning from the beginning ● methods and technologies (e.g. text & data mining) to collect information for projects related to DH
HU Law and Committees Division
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● providing legal assistance for research projects as well as contracts: publishing data, licence agreement, etc.
HU Research Division - Heidelberg Research Service – Advisory Service and Project Administration
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● counselling services for funded projects and guidance on DMP and research data management
HU Scientific Software Centre (SSC)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● helping research groups to set up practices: version control systems, continuous integration tools, automatic code analysis, code review, etc. ● teaching and consultation for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ research software use and their development ○ programming and computing
HU Tech Transfer Office
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● assisting on questions related to inventions, patents, etc.
HU University Computing Centre (URZ)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● assistance in accessing various databases ● support to cover costs & technical aspects (equipment, storage, servers, data security, etc.) of DMP writing ● IT services for data collection and support and advice: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ installation and training on software & applications, facilities to collect a large amount of data ● IT services for data analysis and support and advice: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ HPC, data analysis and visualisation, etc. ● offering data storage for servers and workstation computers (SharePoint, heiBox, heiCLOUD, SDS@hd, etc.), cloud-based IT resources and consultancy on data security

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● providing service for archiving data for a longer period of time
HU University Library
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● organising training on looking for information related to databases/datasets and individual appointment with an information expert ● assistance on data and metadata standards in heidICON, easyDB, WissKI, and heiEDITIONS ● counselling on data management planning with a special focus on digital humanities project and use of the libraries research infrastructure heiRIS: https://www.ub.uni-heidelberg.de/Englisch/service/openaccess/heiris.html ● data collection with platforms provided by the library is supported (heidICON, easyDB, WissKI, digital editions/TEI)
<u>ZENDAS</u>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● covering questions related to data protection (ZENDAS is a central counselling centre for data protection issues in the federal state Baden-Württemberg)

The University of Milan (UM)

Table 4. RDM units at the University of Milan

UM Data Protection Officer
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● consultation and assistance on legal constraints for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ data storage ○ data sharing ○ personal & sensitive data protection and its processing
UM <u>DPAQVPOS</u> – Dataverse team
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● giving assistance on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ archiving research data securely ○ sharing research data on Dataverse
UM <u>DPAQVPOS</u> – Open Science Support Team
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● assisting for organisation and description of research data: file formats, relevant metadata, metadata schemes and vocabularies, conversion, etc. ● helping research data publication (repositories, data paper, etc.) ● organising workshops and providing supports on search/reuse data and accessing databases ● supporting FAIR data management and DMP drafting
UM Ethics Committee

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● assistance on covering ethical aspects to consider during the data lifecycle ● consultation on ethical issues relevant to data sharing
UM ICT Department
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● data extraction & analysis ● providing cloud-based storing service (Unicloud and Unimibox) and computer security & personal data protection (ICT Security Staff Office) ● consultancy of technical aspects of DMP (costs, servers, etc.) and data security ● software & applications installation, assistance and configuration of management applications etc.
UM Technology Transfer Sector
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● reviewing patent applications and expressing opinion on patents and industrial property clauses and assisting with questions related to inventions, patents, etc.
UM DPAQVPOS Support Unit
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● organising orientation and training sessions on information/datasets seeking
UM UNIGEST
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● consultancy and monitoring funded research projects; assistance in contracts ● legal assistance for research projects as well as a contract: publishing data, licence agreement, etc.
UM UNITECH
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● offering data storage facility: indaco@unimi.it ● providing high-level multidisciplinary technical assistance and services: HPC, mass spectrometry, big data analysis, etc.

Sorbonne University (SU)

Table 5. RDM units at Sorbonne University

SU Centre d'expérimentation en méthodes numériques pour les recherches en Sciences Humaines et Sociales (CERES)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● assisting researchers to search/reuse information and accessing various databases ● technical and methodological assistance on data process & analysis ● training and consultation on Digital Humanities methods to collect information (text mining, web scraping, etc.)
SU Computing and Data Assistance Service (SACADO)

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● advising and engineering services, access to its technological platform MeSU (HPC), and technical assistance. ● consultation and training about data collection/creation methods ● offering larger data storage options for the projects
SU Data Protection Office
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● consultation and assistance on legal constraints for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ data storage ○ data sharing ○ personal & sensitive data protection and its processing
French National Repository (Recherche Data Gouv)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● national generic data repository
SU Institute of Computing and Data Sciences (ISCD)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● offering scientific computing and data analysis
SU IT Department
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● offering cloud data storage (DropSU + SharePoint) ● providing services like software & applications installation, assistance and configuration of management applications, training and consultation, etc.
SU Research and Development Division (DRV [Faculty Level] and DR&I)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● consultation on questions related to DMP (intellectual property, stakeholders, patents, etc.) ● providing legal assistance on data publishing (licence agreement, inventions, and patents related to data & software, etc.)
SU Research Data Information desk (in construction)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Working group on DMP - connecting different actors (library, science department, IT, technology transfer, etc.)
SU Research Ethics Committee
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● consultation on DMP covering ethical issues relevant to data sharing ● covering questions associated with ethical aspects of DMP
SU SARA Archives Department
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Training & consultation on data archiving; offering long-term preservation solutions (arrangement, sorting rules, conservation time, required metadata, etc.); authorization management to access archived data
SU Sorbonne Center for Artificial Intelligence (SCAI)

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● assisting researcher to search/reuse information and accessing various databases ● training on data manipulation and processing (e.g., data visualisation & manipulation via Python, OCR methods, etc.) ● training on methods to collect information (text mining via Python, web scraping, etc.)
<p>SU Library - Research Data Digital Humanities Team</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● assisting with organisation and description of research data: file formats, relevant metadata, metadata schemes and vocabularies, conversion, etc. ● helping research data publication (repositories, data paper, etc.) ● in person meetings on DMP writing and DMP training

The University of Warsaw (UW)

Table 6. RDM units at the University of Warsaw

<p>UW Data Protection Officer</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● consultation and assistance on legal constraints for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ data storage ○ data sharing ○ personal & sensitive data protection and its processing
<p><u>ICM UW</u> Support Staff</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● assistance and training on software and applications ● Disciplinary Open Research Data Repositories by making research data available and improving the quality of shared (meta)data ● Data Centre: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ providing IT services: big data analysis, HPC, modelling of complex processes and data visualisation ● archiving research data archived on the repository level ● offering data storage for extended periods of time. See Terms of use (https://kdm.icm.edu.pl/Formalnosci/zasady_dostepu.en/)
<p>ICM UW – <u>Open Science Platform</u> Team</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● answering questions related to Open Science and providing recommendation of tools & best practices, providing support in RDM ● operating RepOD (reprod.icm.edu.pl/) repository for opening & sharing research data ● organising workshops and providing supports on search/reuse data and accessing databases
<p>UW IT Department</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● offering storage facility ● assistance on installation of applications, software, etc.
UW Rector’s Committee for the Ethics of Research Involving Human Participant
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● assistance and consultation to cover ethical aspects to consider during the data lifecycle
UW Research Administration Office
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● legal assistance for research projects as well as a contract: publishing data, licence agreement, etc. ● support researchers in the preparation of grant applications (intellectual property, stakeholders, etc.) and DMP writing by providing examples
UW Tech Transfer Office
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● assisting on questions related to inventions, patents, etc.
UW Library Science Support Team
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● assistance & training courses on archiving research data ● helping research data publication (repositories, data paper, etc.) ● organising workshops and providing support on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ DMP and FAIR data ○ search/reuse data and accessing databases

2.3.1.4. RDM and 4EU+

From interviews with each university, we noticed that the organisation around RDM is in the process of development in each institution. Positioning and complementarity between the different services are issues common to all institutions. All these services already work together on a daily basis.

Since RDM is a relatively new subject for universities and is evolving very quickly, the need to work on the organisation between the different services remains subject to offer the best service to users. It seems to us that this is a specific characteristic of RDM, whose methods and tools are constantly evolving, and which requires a permanent reactivity of the support services.

2.3.1.5. Stages of the data lifecycle

2.3.1.5.1. Plan

The Plan step covers all other phases of the data lifecycle. Here, the researcher should outline the processes and resources related to every stage of the data lifecycle. In this case, the DMP appears as a useful solution that explains how datasets from a project will be managed, from their creation or collection to their sharing and archiving. In the context of making research data FAIR, DMP serves as a deliverable that details how you obtain, document, analyse, and (re)use your data both during your research and once the project is complete.

Because of this transversal characteristic, we can remark that different actors can more likely integrate into this stage by providing support related to different tasks of DMP. Being the result of collective work, DMP therefore involves a collective reflection on legal, ethical, technical, and administrative aspects of research data.

Figure 3. Data lifecycle: Plan

As we can see in Figure 3, the dispersion of RDM units has been carried out in an equitable way on the scale of the 4EU+ Alliance. This can be explained by the fact that DMP must arise from collaborative work due to its omnipresent feature in the data lifecycle. RDM Units, either library-based or mixed service, accompany researchers to DMP writing and its proofreading. They also organise training and workshops on DMP. The Research Administration Office provides counselling and monitoring services about the preparation of grant applications (stakeholders, intellectual property, etc.), risk assessment, and DMP. The IT Department might cover technical aspects (equipment, storage, server, etc.) and their cost calculation. The Data Protection Office, in turn, gives consultation on personal & sensitive data protection and its processing just as the Ethics Committee which assists researchers to cover ethical aspects of research data.

2.3.1.5.2. Collect / Create

The Collect/Create step concerns the processes of how to acquire and create datasets. Depending on the research discipline, data acquisition methods can be varied. Thus, one should carry out data collection with suitable documentation to make data reusable by other researchers. Likewise, it is crucial to rely on standardised protocols in the studied domain to make data interoperable to illustrate raw data and their collection tools. Since the

reproducibility crisis is very widespread nowadays, research data should be collected in a way that explains the data obtaining process to be able to reproduce datasets.

As mentioned above, the data acquisition step is a very domain-specific area and RDM support units may have difficulties following up all the normalised practices and methods to provide a corresponding accompaniment. Considering that such support might be realised on a laboratory-scale between the lab members. Except, in the Social Sciences & Humanities, we can see that new methods have gained importance with the widening of Digital Humanities practices. Therefore, we can witness the creation of research structures with the aim of giving training and consultancy about these technologies.

Figure 4. Data lifecycle: Collect/Create

From Figure 4, we can see that the Collect/Create step is mainly composed of two units: IT Department, Research Infrastructures. The IT Department supplies software & application installation, assistance, and configuration of management applications. Research Infrastructures in the 4EU+ Alliance offer consultation and training about data collection/creation methods and technologies (e.g., text & data mining, web scraping, programming, and computing). We can also notice that, within the 4EU+ Alliance, some library units might provide such support activities by assisting researchers with a variety of tools and services to harvest data.

2.3.1.5.3. Describe / Process / Analyze

Once the data are obtained, it is indispensable to describe them with their associated metadata to make them FAIR. The description of these datasets should conform to the controlled vocabularies defined in a specific domain. Management of datasets description can be ensured by databases and repositories which require implementation of a certain metadata during its submission.

Then, these acquired datasets should be processed in a standardised way. This step concerns the processes related to raw data (grouping, cleaning, qualifying, etc.) to prepare them for further analysis according to FAIR principles.

Once the raw data is processed, we can then start extracting useful information from them to be able to make an analysis of it. The more data are structured, the more they are usable. Thus, they are more compatible with the analysis, even with computational methods. The Describe/Process/Analyze step covers different techniques (machine learning, data visualisation, high-performance computing, etc.) and associated platforms to realise such manipulation.

Figure 5. Data lifecycle: Describe/Process/Analyze

We can notice that Library RDM Support Units assist researchers in the dataset description and their organisation, such as file formats, relevant metadata, metadata schemes and vocabularies, conversion, etc. In some Library RDM units, tools and training for analysing data are also proposed to researchers. As we can see from the illustration, this step is mostly covered by Research Infrastructures in the 4EU+ Alliance. These computing centres offer data processing and analysis services (HPC, data visualisation, etc.) as well as advising on topics relevant to data processing and analysis. In addition to these research infrastructures, the IT Department in the 4EU+ universities, depending on their faculty, might provide such support for consultation on data processing and extraction.

2.3.1.5.4. Store

The Store step begins with depositing produced files in a place (personal computer, USB, shared drive, etc.) to make them accessible when needed. Then, it should be followed up by backups to duplicate stored data in a place different from where they are stocked. If data contains personal or sensitive information, security procedures and access rights must also be indicated and applied to prevent any risk that may occur.

Backups should be realised in an automatic way with specialised software that allows defining of what is saved and its frequency. These software programs also help to restore data from a specific backup. As they require certain technical skills, they should be implemented by network and system administrators.

In the data life cycle, backup policies (e.g., data volume, financial costs) must be already outlined in the Plan step to facilitate choosing data storage procedures. These policies should also be compatible with data collection methods in the Collect/Create step. Moreover, one should consider the cost of archiving data and make a selection of them based on some criteria.

Figure 6. Data lifecycle: Store

Figure 6 illustrates that the Store steps are mostly covered by technical staff in the 4EU+ universities. As we can see from the collected results, IT departments offer consultancy services for researchers to determine customised solutions for data storage, access, and backup. They also provide data storage services, cloud-based or not, for servers or working stations. For the questions related to sensitive and personal data, DPO intervenes to cover legal constraints to be taken into account for data storage. In addition to these two main services, in some universities, research infrastructures offer some supplementary support for data storage. For storing research data, specialised RDM units may appear in this stage to organise training sessions and to offer advice.

2.3.1.5.5. Archive

The Archive step consists of storing the data in a place where it will be kept for, at least, a long period. By associating the necessary means to be able to make data reusable, data should be preserved in the same state and permanently in time. Therefore, sustainable archiving should be used to ensure the long-term preservation of data and its accessibility.

Research data are fully within the scope of the archives and researchers should make some decisions about what to archive and what will be destroyed at the end of the project. The choice is often made by considering data characteristics and their future reuse through some concerns like sustainability, confidentiality, and security. If the data can be easily re-created, they are more likely to be destroyed than those with unique features.

Figure 7. Data lifecycle: Archive

As stated in Figure 7, specialised RDM support units provide most support services in this step on the scale of the 4EU+ Alliance. They offer not only assistance and general training but also solutions to archive research data. Additionally, the IT departments of some universities provide a service for archiving data for a longer period. In some universities, one can see that institutional repositories, with the help of a team around them, constitute one of these bigger solutions to sustain long-term preservation. Otherwise, national and international repositories cover these tasks with the accompaniment of RDM support units and research infrastructures.

2.3.1.5.6. Share

In the context of Open Science, the last step represents the goal of research data management since it aims at data publishing and dissemination according to FAIR principles to make them findable, accessible, and reusable in interoperable formats and processes. The Share step describes, on the one hand, how data will be exchanged during the project, including between partners. On the other hand, it determines how data will be accessed, disseminated, and shared during and after the project.

The term ‘sharing’, in this phase of the lifecycle, is often referred to as ‘publishing’. It consists of making data available to third-parties via trustworthy repositories, discipline-based or not, according to rich descriptive metadata standards accepted by a research community. This step should also be accompanied by persistent identifiers to ensure data search and reusability.

Figure 8. Data lifecycle: Share

Similarly to the Plan step, Figure 8 demonstrates that different RDM structures interfere equally with this step on the scale of the 4EU+ Alliance. This can be explained by the fact that they represent the beginning and the end of research data management, which requires crucial points to be determined. Therefore, it is inevitable that different organisms be present in this step rather than the collaboration between these structures.

RDM support units help research data publication by the manner of repositories, data papers, etc. TTO reviews patent applications, expresses opinions on patents and industrial property clauses, and assists questions related to these issues. The Research Administration Office, in turn, helps researchers register their research and provides legal assistance for research projects and contracts. The Data Protection Office gives consultation on legal constraints of personal data sharing, just as the Ethics Committee does on ethical issues.

2.3.1.5.7. Search / Reuse

The Search/Reuse step of the research data lifecycle consists of searching and/or reusing datasets that help researchers validate their hypothesis for their research assessments. Normally, these datasets should be deposited in a certified or trustworthy repository accompanied by metadata standards to conform to FAIR principles. However, not all repositories are curated in a reproducible way. Therefore, researchers should be able to evaluate databases and other information resources for their research assessments. At the same time, it needs to be stressed that datasets searching practices are often transmitted between colleagues without having completed a specific training session. Nevertheless, one may need such training not only for reusing the datasets but also for making their datasets reusable.

Figure 9. Data lifecycle: Search/Reuse

In the Search/Reuse step, one can see that most of the support activities are gathered around specific RDM support units created in the university to accompany researchers. In some universities, one can notice that the University Library also assists in this support by providing specific courses on information seeking. Research infrastructures at universities and IT departments can also provide this kind of assistance if researchers require it.

2.3.1.6. Limitations of Milestone 1

Our study focused on university-level services. We sometimes chose to include services at the faculty level when they were essential, but this was not done systematically because they can be very numerous. Additionally, we did not identify services within laboratories, as our time was limited.

2.3.1.7. Conclusions

As a first approach, this analysis allowed us to identify the main services within our six universities to better understand the organisation around research data management in each of them. We were able to observe a distribution of services around RDM at the university level and local disciplinary support within the faculties and laboratories.

Opportunities: this analysis shows relatively consistent RDM services across the six 4EU+ Alliance universities. Collaborations between the Alliance partners could be developed to share practices and work more closely together.

Table 7. Summary table of services by the stage of the data lifecycle

1 - Search/Reuse	
CU	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CU Central Library – Open Science Support Centre ● CU Central Library Support
UCPH	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● UCPH Library Datalab (KUB) ● UCPH Library Research Support
HU	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Competence Centre for Research Data (KFD) ● Heidelberg Forum Digital Humanities (HFDH) ● HU Libraries Support Team ● University Computing Centre (URZ)
UM	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DPAQVPOS – Open Science Support Team ● UM Library Support Unit
SU	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Centre d’expérimentation en méthodes numériques pour les recherches en Sciences Humaines et Sociales (CERES) ● Sorbonne Center for Artificial Intelligence (SCAI)
UW	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ICM UW – Open Science Platform Team ● UW Library Science Support Team

2 - Plan	
CU	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CU Central Library – Open Science Support Centre ● Ethics Commission ● Grant Agency (GA UK) ● Faculty IT Departments ● Open Science Support Centre – Copyright & Open Science Lawyer

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Special working group ● University Data Protection Officer
UCPH
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data Protection Officer ● Ethics Committee ● IT department ● Office of Research Services (F&I Research Services, RDM and Information Security) ● Technology Transfer Office ● UCPH Library Research Support
HU
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Competence Centre for Research Data (KFD) ● Data Protection Officer ● Ethics Commission ● Heidelberg Forum Digital Humanities (HFDH) ● Research Division – Heidelberg Research Service – Advisory Service and Project Administration ● University Computing Centre (URZ) ● University Library ● ZENDAS <p>covering questions related to data protection</p>
UM
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data Protection Officer ● DPAQVPOS – Open Science Support Team ● Ethics Committee ● ICT Department ● UNIGEST
SU
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data Protection Office ● Research and Development Division (DRV [Faculty Level] and DR&I) ● Research Data Information desk (in construction) ● Research Ethics Committee ● SU Library – Research Data Digital Humanities Team
UW
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data Protection Officer ● ICM UW – Open Science Platform Team ● Rector’s Committee for the Ethics of Research Involving Human Participant ● Research Administration Office

- UW Library Science Support Team

3 - Collect/Create

CU

- Computer Science Center
- Faculty IT Departments

UCPH

- Datalabs
- Library Datalab (KUB)
- IT Department

HU

- Competence Centre for Research Data (KFD)
- Heidelberg Forum Digital Humanities (HFDH)
- Scientific Software Centre (SSC)
- University Computing Centre (URZ)
- University Library

UM

- ICT Department

SU

- CERES
- Computing and Data Assistance Service (SACADO)
- IT Department
- Sorbonne Center for Artificial Intelligence (SCAI)

UW

- ICM UW
- IT Department

4 - Describe/Process/Analyze	
CU	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Computer Science Center ● CU Central Library – Open Science Support Team ● Faculty IT Departments
UCPH	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Datalabs ● Library Datalab (KUB) ● Competence Centre for Research Data (KFD) ● SCIENCE AI Centre ● SCIENCE HPC Centre
HU	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Scientific Software Centre (SSC) ● University Computing Centre (URZ) ● University Library
UM	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DPAQVPOS – Open Science Support Team ● ICT Department ● Unitech
SU	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CERES ● Computing and Data Assistance Service (SACADO) ● Institute of Computing and Data Sciences (ISCD) ● Sorbonne Center for Artificial Intelligence (SCAI) ● SU Library – Research Data Digital Humanities Team
UW	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ICM UW – Data Centre

5 - Store	
CU	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Computer Science Center ● CU Central Library – Open Science Support Team ● Faculty IT Departments ● University Data Protection Officer
UCPH	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data Protection Officer ● IT department ● Office of Research Services (F&I Information Security) ● SCIENCE HPC Centre
HU	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Competence Centre for Research Data (KFD) ● Data Protection Officer ● University Computing Centre (URZ)
UM	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data Protection Officer ● ICT Department ● Unitech
SU	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Computing and Data Assistance Service (SACADO) ● Data Protection Office ● IT Department
UW	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data Protection Officer ● ICM UW Support Staff ● IT Department

6 - Archive	
CU	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CU Central Library – Open Science Support Team ● Faculty IT Departments
UCPH	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SCIENCE HPC Centre ● UCPH Library Research Support
HU	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Competence Centre for Research Data (KFD) ● University Computing Centre (URZ)
UM	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DPAQVPOS – Dataverse team
SU	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SARA – Archives Department
UW	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ICM UW Support Staff ● UW Library Science Support Team

7 - Share	
CU	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Centre for Knowledge and Technology Transfer ● CU Central Library – Open Science Support Centre ● Ethics Commission ● Open Science Support Centre – Copyright & Open Science Lawyer ● University Data Protection Officer
UCPH	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data Protection Officer ● Ethics Committee ● Office of Research Services (F&I Research Services)

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SCIENCE HPC Centre ● Technology Transfer Office ● UCPH Library Research Support
HU
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Competence Centre for Research Data (KFD) ● Ethics Commission ● Law and Committees Division ● Tech Transfer Office ● Data Protection Officer
UM
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data Protection Officer ● DPAQVPOS – Dataverse team ● DPAQVPOS – Open Science Support Team ● UNIGEST ● Ethics Committee ● Technology Transfer Sector
SU
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data Protection Office ● French National Repository (Recherche Data Gouv) ● Research and Development Division (DRV [Faculty Level] and DR&I) ● Research Ethics Committee ● SU Library – Research Data Digital Humanities Team
UW
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data Protection Officer ● ICM UW ● ICM UW – Open Science Platform Team ● Rector’s Committee for the Ethics of Research Involving Human Participant ● Research Administration Office ● Tech Transfer Office ● UW Library Science Support Team

2.3.2. Academic libraries supporting RDM and FAIR data – A set of RDM services for academic libraries and a job profile for data stewards (Milestone 2)

Based on the results of Milestone 1 where the RDM support units have been identified in the 4EU+ Alliance institutions, it was possible to create job profiles that could highlight the skills

and competencies for RDM. Our objective was to find a bridge between what we already have as a profession in our institutions and new emerging data roles (data steward, data engineer, data scientist, and data librarian). A workshop on these data roles was also conducted among the 4EU+ members to discuss their perceptions.

2.3.2.1. Methodology

As a methodology, we reanalyzed the benchmark that we have created for Step 1. First, for each stage of the data lifecycle, we emphasised the keywords that illustrate the support services provided. We realised that these keywords correspond to the skills and competencies that might be classed into two groups – Hard skills, which require an expertise; and Soft skills, which are matched with personality traits. As shown in Figure 10, we classified, in another document, the skills and knowledge involved in each stage according to Soft and Hard skills.

Figure 10. Reanalysing the benchmark

Then, we created another benchmark to associate these skills and competencies with each RDM unit. However, as seen in Figure 11 some RDM units (e.g., Data & Computing Centers) provided similar support services but in different scientific domains.

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RDM service					
University	Data Lifecycle	Support Unit	Description	Soft Skills	Hard Skills
SU	Collect/Create	IT Department	providing services like software & applications installation, assistance and configuration of management applications, trainings and consultation, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Communication skills: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o consultancy, consultation o assistance, assisting Didactic and pedagogical skills: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o advises, courses o trainings, teaching o support User and domain analysis: 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Software & application expertise <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o software & application installation o software & application configuration o software & application management o research software use o customized research application
SU	Collect/Create	Centre d'expérimentation en méthodes numériques pour les recherches en Sciences Humaines et Sociales (CERES)	trainings and consultation on Digital Humanities methods to collect information (text mining, web scraping, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Communication skills Didactic and pedagogical skills User and domain analysis: 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o software & application installation o software & application configuration o software & application management o research software use o customized research application
SU	Collect/Create	Computing and Data Assistance Service (SACADO)	consultation and trainings about data collection/creation methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Communication skills Didactic and pedagogical skills User and domain analysis: 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Programming languages (Data collection methods and technologies): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Using APIs to collect data automatized way o data collection with platforms o harvesting data o development and programming o computing
SU	Collect/Create	Sorbonne Center for Artificial Intelligence (SCAI)	trainings on methods to collect information (text mining via Python, web scraping, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Communication skills Didactic and pedagogical skills User and domain analysis: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o customized, configuration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o software & application installation o software & application configuration o software & application management o research software use o customized research application

Figure 11. Creating a different benchmark

In this case, the information we assigned was repetitive for some RDM units. Due to this repetition phenomenon, we changed our approach and grouped our RDM units into general ideal types. These ideal types allowed us to develop job profile templates for RDM units.

Among these RDM units, we realised that some RDM units (Library, RDM helpdesk, Data & Computer Centre) were providing customised support services depending on the institution context. Therefore, it was more complex to develop job profiles for the units due to their interrelated characteristics.

Focusing on these interlinked RDM units, we finally organised a workshop to discuss new emerging data roles and their understanding among the 4EU+ institutions.

2.3.2.2. Job Descriptions for RDM Support Units (Ideal Types)

According to ideal types, we have created a job description template based on Hard and Soft skills (see [5.2. Appendix 2. Task 5.3, Case #1 Research Data Management and FAIR Data. List of the skills of each profession](#)).

The general job description for each RDM unit can be found below.

2.3.2.2.1. Research Administration Office

The Research Administration Officers ensure compliance with regulations relating to external funding and support research project management. They coordinate proposal activities according to institutional, (inter)national, and agency requirements and monitor contracts and grant administrations.

2.3.2.2.2. Tech Transfer Office

Technology Transfer Officers are in charge of commercialising and [transferring research results and findings to the industry](#). To merge the impact of research with the financial benefit, they carry out various commercial activities to introduce research developments to industry, often serving as a connection between university and enterprise.

2.3.2.2.3. Data Protection Office

In compliance with the regulations, Data Protection Officers ensure the securing of personal data by identifying risks and implementing procedures during operations and processing. They also organise consulting sessions to raise awareness of these data protection issues.

2.3.2.2.4. Ethics Committee

The Ethics Committee Administrators evaluate the ethical issues of the research protocol regarding the protection of research participants and data. They review and give ethical opinions on these protocols to ensure compliance with laws and recommendations.

2.3.2.2.5. IT Department

IT Officers coordinate the administration of information technology (IT) services of the University by providing technical services on issues related to infrastructure, software, and applications.

2.3.2.2.6. Library / RDM Helpdesk / Computing & Data Centre

Although we have created ideal types for RDM units, we realised that the job description of certain units (e.g., Computing & Data Centre, Library and RDM helpdesk) could not be defined as easily as other units did. Actually, we have already remarked in Step 1 that there were different tendencies around the similar RDM support services in the 4EU+ institutions.

2.3.2.2.6.1. Library / RDM Helpdesk

At some universities (e.g., SU, CU, UW), libraries have an OS Center to provide RDM support. However, these support services are mainly focused on the Plan, Describe, Share stage of the data lifecycle. To fulfil technical and computational needs, thus covering more stages in the data lifecycle, the library itself can offer such assistance (e.g., Library datalab at the UCPH). Similarly, we can see the presence of an RDM unit which was created as a joint facility between a library and a computing centre (e.g., the Competence Centre for Research Data at the HU).

As the proposed RDM support expands, we tend to see the creation of a structure, the so-called RDM helpdesk, with the aim of covering all stages of the data lifecycle. This structure establishes a single point of reference by embodying different RDM units such as a library, a technology transfer office, a data protection office, etc. (e.g., the Performance, Quality Assurance, Assessment, and Open Science Policy Division (DPAQVPOS) at the UM).

2.3.2.2.6.2. Computing & Data Centre

Within the 4EU+ universities, it can also be seen that Data & Computing Centers provide, apart from libraries, RDM support that promotes OS and FAIR Data movement (e.g., Interdisciplinary Centre for Mathematical and Computational Modelling at the UW, University Computing Centre at HU).

Yet, we are more common to meet these centres at Create, Describe/Process/Analyze, Store, Share, Create stages of data lifecycle (e.g., SCIENCE AI Centre at UCPH, Computing and Data Assistance Service (SACADO) at SU).

This difference between the 4EU+ Alliance members shows us a diverse ecosystem in our universities. Therefore, defining the general description of the job for these RDM units was complicated, as each structure implements them divergently.

To be able to adjust these variations, we adapted a diagram from the OECD acting as a medium for defining these RDM units. Figure 12 illustrates the principal topics to be addressed for data intensive science, which is defined by the OECD report, [Building digital workforce capacity and skills for data-intensive science](#) (2020), as a “data-driven, exploration-centred style of science, where IT infrastructures and software tools are heavily used to help scientists manage, analyse, and share data”⁵. The report aims to determine skills and competences for science established around data handling and defines to build such qualified personnel. As stated in the report, “a digitally skilled workforce is required to complement investments in data-intensive scientific infrastructure. An inclusive workforce needs to reflect the diversity of society to not only improve science but to ensure it is more responsive to societal needs”⁶.

Figure 12. Venn diagram of responsibilities for RDM units (adapted from OECD)

Unlike other RDM support units, as shown in Figure 12, those who are placed in the middle of the schema tend to cover multiple data lifecycle stages, thus providing more interconnected RDM support. In a data intensive science, this support should be compatible with new technical and computing methods to be able to handle data curation, manipulation, processing, etc., for creating FAIR data. Therefore, they should be aligned with new emerging data roles.

On the one hand, individuals working in Computing and Data Centers are involved in the technical and computational aspects of data management and analysis, making them suitable for roles that require skills in data science and engineering. On the other hand, Library and RDM Helpdesk positions are seen as having responsibilities related to organising and curating

⁵ OECD (2020), « Building digital workforce capacity and skills for data-intensive science », OECD Science, Technology and Industry Policy Papers, n° 90, Éditions OCDE, Paris, p. 62 <https://doi.org/10.1787/e08aa3bb-en>

⁶ Ibid.

data, making them well suited to roles that involve managing data assets and ensuring data quality and compliance.

While these comparisons have been made, it's important to note that the alignment of roles may vary depending on the specific functions and responsibilities of individuals within these structures. The roles mentioned are common in the context of data management and research support, but actual job titles and responsibilities may differ between organisations and institutions.

In the next section, we will focus on these data roles by trying to expand their perception in the 4EU+ institutions.

2.3.2.3. Data roles

To ensure the transition to FAIR data and open science practices, new data roles need to be implemented to fulfil the requirements of data issues. In the last several years, some European initiatives (e.g., H2020, Edison, EOSCpilot FAIR4S, DigCurV) have already defined frameworks to professionalise roles and pedagogy for emerging professions. Among those, we focused on 4 types which are data scientist, data steward, data librarian, and data engineer.

To provide recognition for professionals with FAIR and open science skills, the EOSC report, [*Digital skills for FAIR and open science*](#) (2021), defined the frames for these emerging data roles:

- “A Data Scientist or Data Analyst is an expert on data processing, not necessarily from a specific discipline, who is capable of evaluating data quality, extracting relevant knowledge from data and representing such knowledge”⁷. (p.19)
- “A Research Software Engineer (Data Engineer) is an ICT expert who designs, implements, maintains and/or integrates services and software in the EOSC ecosystem to enable FAIR and open science, ensuring the fulfilment of software quality, reproducibility and sustainability”⁸. (p.19)
- “A Data Steward is an expert on the preparation and treatment of data including data selection, storage, preservation, annotation provenance and other metadata maintenance, and dissemination”⁹. (p.21)
- “Data librarians are professional library staff who are experts on RDM, using research data as a resource or supporting researchers dealing with data (description, archiving and dissemination)”¹⁰. (p.21)

However, it is hard to set a clear definition for these professions. Depending on their implementation context, the roles and required competencies vary a lot. For example, “FAIR4S

⁷ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Manola, N., Lazzeri, E., Barker, M., et al., Digital skills for FAIR and Open Science : report from the EOSC Executive Board Skills and Training Working Group, Manola, N. (editor), Lazzeri, E. (editor), Barker, M. (editor), Kuchma, I. (editor), Gaillard, V. (editor), Stoy, L. (editor), Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/59065>

⁸ Ibid.

⁹ Ibid.

¹⁰ Ibid.

sees the data steward role as combining a data management/curation function with at least one other role, (i.e. research, data science, or engineering)”¹¹. Similar to FAIR4S, Wildgaard et al. (2020)¹² showed that the main functions of a data steward can be analysed from four different roles such as administrator, analyst, developer, and agent of change.

During the workshop organised in Week 6, we observed that, without a provided definition, we might give a diverse definition for these roles. Data librarian could appear as an administrator of digital libraries by organising the catalogues. Likewise, a data scientist might be perceived as a broader term to represent a researcher or a doctoral student.

How these roles are called often depends on the place of employment of such employees, e.g. in the library, research support unit, faculty, research project, etc. Data steward is often based on faculty level, in the consulting position where data engineers are more attached to specific tools, and infrastructures like HPC facilities.

2.3.2.3.1. Data roles in the 4EU+ universities

Recognizing emerging data roles in our institutions was challenging as job titles do not exactly correspond to job profiles, thus they are not officially employed in research structures as titles. However, we can see that people involved in RDM give such support, without being considered as one of these data roles.

In all the 4EU+ Alliance members, we can see that data scientists are considered as a generic term for referring to researchers and/or doctoral students with the technical skills to handle the data of their discipline. Therefore, we cannot see a specific recruitment for this position. The main difference is related to the choice between data steward and data librarian and their implementation context.

Charles University (CU)

CU has the Open Science Center located in the library. However, instead of creating library-based data librarian profiles, we can see the choice of implementing data steward roles to faculties that will be the bridge between the main subjects illustrated in Figure 12.

CU is planning to implement data steward courses around the two ideas. The first is to create courses at the library level where they can explore the needs of these new professions. The second one is more focused on the disciplinary level, particularly at the Faculty of Science. This training is considered for doctoral students to improve their knowledge about data issues (manage, analyse, visualise, etc.). There is not yet full recognition of specific needs in this area, but they are expecting to develop skills and knowledge to fill the gap considering that the EOOSC projects will foresee such integration.

At the Faculty of Arts, they are currently preparing a course for Data Stewards where they want to focus on the practical needs of the emerging community of Data Stewards in the Czech Republic. The main target group for this course will be staff members in SSH (researchers, research support staff such as library, IT, etc.), but it will also be open to anyone who wishes

¹¹ https://www.eoscpilot.eu/sites/default/files/fair4s_eoscpilot_skills_framework.pdf

¹² Wildgaard, L., Vlachos, E., Nondal, L., Larsen, A.V., Svendsen, M.: National coordination of data steward education in Denmark: Final report to the National Forum for Research Data Management (DM Forum). DM Forum (2020). doi: <https://doi.org/10.5282/zenodo.3609516>

to improve their competences and skills in research data management. It will be a one semester e-learning course that will also require 20 hours of work experience in institutions focused on data management. It will be divided into theoretical and practical lectures where it will show how to work with some of the data management tools. A pilot run of the course will be available in February 2024. If all parts of the course are completed, a certificate of completion will be issued.

The University of Copenhagen (UCPH)

At the present time, UCPH has data scientist profiles, having a scientific background to support infrastructure and facilities. Staff members who do stewardship at UCPH are also seen as data/project managers. For other profiles, we can see that there are no clear definitions. Therefore, these new emerging data roles are not officially hired in the current job positions with their titles.

Consequently, UCPH is planning to implement a Data Steward Master Program in which two types of data stewards are envisaged. The first type, it will be an opportunity for doctoral students. They will be expected to manage the research data as part of a research team after having completed an appropriate training. The second type of a Data Steward position is offered to candidates without doctoral degree, but those who have completed a master or professional program in RDM or data stewardship.

This new program aims to support research data at a practical level. The role and profile of the Data Steward will be different for each faculty. There is no overall coordination at each faculty or between faculties.

Heidelberg University (HU)

Of all four profiles, HU has data stewards in Heidelberg's RDM infrastructure. There are no librarians who can be specifically described as data librarians. They also do not have data engineers in the sense of specific data expertise, but rather regular roles such as computer scientists, software developers, system administrators, etc. There are data scientists, but they are in the domain of research.

The University of Milan (UM)

Unlike the precedents, the RDM at UM is not placed at the library. In their unit DPAQVPOS we can see an ICT engineer-oriented profile who works on developing software and infrastructures (e.g., Dataverse) that might seem like a data engineer. There are already job positions for transmitting skills and tools to researchers and doctoral students that might look like data stewards as providing full-cycle data support.

However, these roles are not recruited according to their titles. UM has a data engineer (data developer), but the same person also provides support for data management. Its role can not be described only in data engineering because the same person fulfils different roles. For skills and tools related to these data roles, they have profiles, but they have not recruited these roles for now as an official title.

UM has also implemented an action for data steward recruitment but there were no candidates. For now, there are programs for data scientists (researchers), but not for data stewards. There

are special courses for postdoctoral academics and for those who are specialising (e.g., medical specialisation). Data stewardship training is planned for future specialists in medicine.

Sorbonne University (SU)

Because the SU library has been working on OS for many years, data librarian jobs are implemented instead of data stewards. In data centres at SU, we can also see the data engineer roles that provide advising and engineering services. Data scientists are considered researchers with dedicated competencies and knowledge. Currently, there is no training for these roles.

The University of Warsaw (UW)

At the UW, these roles are often project-based; there are no permanent jobs for these specialists. Data librarians are more likely to be identified as metadata specialists while those in charge of data management would be more likely to be data stewards. The UW is not planning to employ data librarians and data stewards because on the labour market there are no exact profiles that can be matched with the needs of the University in this regard. Instead, it is planned to educate librarians to be able to fulfil the requirements for such job profiles. Currently, the UW does not teach students in the area of RDM, nor, how to become a data librarian. Research data management courses have recently been prepared by ICM UW and launched in October 2023. They are designed for people who are to perform the role of data stewards and for researchers. The courses are offered free of charge online in beginner and intermediate levels. An important fact is that the courses have been made available on a freely accessible educational platform NAVOICA which is a Polish educational platform with MOOC-type courses, owned by the Ministry of Education and Science and developed by the Information Processing Centre – State Research Institute (Ośrodek Przetwarzania Informacji – Państwowy Instytut Badawczy). The courses are in Polish:

- [Research data management for data stewards - basic course](#). A course in data stewardship introducing the tasks of a data steward and their role in scientific research units and research projects (Pol. Zarządzanie danymi badawczymi dla data stewardów - kurs podstawowy. Kurs z zakresu data stewardship przybliżający zadania data stewarda i jego rolę w jednostkach naukowo-badawczych i projektach badawczych).
- [Research data management for data stewards - intermediate course](#). A continuation of the course on data management for data stewards [data stewardship] (Pol. Zarządzanie danymi badawczymi dla data stewardów - kurs średnio zaawansowany. Kontynuacja kursu na temat zarządzania danymi dla data stewardów (data stewardship)).
- [Research data management for researchers - basic course](#). A course in research data management and open access in line with good practice and guidelines from research funding bodies (Pol. Zarządzanie danymi badawczymi dla naukowców - kurs podstawowy. Kurs z zakresu zarządzania danymi badawczymi i ich otwartego udostępniania zgodnie z dobrymi praktykami i wytycznymi instytucji finansujących badania).
- [Research data management for researchers - intermediate course](#). A continuation of the course in research data management for researchers (Pol. Zarządzanie danymi badawczymi dla naukowców - kurs średnio zaawansowany. Kontynuacja kursu z zarządzania danymi badawczymi dla naukowców).

Besides RDM units at the UW have some competencies to create educational programs within their teams (self-education, sharing ideas and resources between colleagues, etc.).

2.3.2.3.2. Competencies and capabilities for data roles (EOSC: FAIR4S table)

Considering that these roles evolve quickly based on implementation context, there is a lack of consensus on how these professions are standardised as career development. In the attempt to find a method to explain the theoretical situation of these roles, we used the table adapted from the EOSCpilot FAIR4S¹³ project, about key skills to address for selected job profiles. The choice of this table was based on its structure, which follows a data lifecycle, like what we have done in Step 1.

From the results of each institution, we summarised the degree given to competences and capabilities to highlight the most important skills for data steward, data librarian, data engineer, and data scientist.

The Plan and design stage refers to planning research outputs, monitoring them, and indicating funding requirements. In this phase, we can see that the ‘data steward’ was more credited than others. For Specifying metadata and PID standards and selecting FAIR repositories, along with ‘data steward’, the ‘data librarian’ also plays an important role. ‘Data engineer’ appears only in modelling data structures and defining database needs.

The Capture and process stage consists of creating research outputs to be further analysed, including storage, access, and workflows. The profiles of ‘Data engineer’ and ‘data scientist’ were more present in this phase, as they are interested in data cleaning, processing, software versioning, and prototyping. Apart from ‘data scientist’, ‘data engineer’ also handles the management of databases. To set up and document workflows, a ‘data steward’ came onto the scene. The tasks related to file naming and organising were also shared between these three roles.

The Integrate and analyse stage is dedicated to techniques, methods, and procedures to analyse data. In this phase, the ‘data scientist’ is more dominant than other roles because of the closeness with the research domain. For data transformation, mining, and interpretation, the ‘data engineer’ also offers some support.

The Appraise and preserve stage deals with reproducibility of the research outputs and their long-term preservation. The ‘data steward’ role is ubiquitous for related key skills in this stage. The ‘data librarian’ was associated with transferring data and ensuring its long-term storage. For migrating data and issues related to their format, the ‘data engineer’ was more represented. The ‘data scientist’ also took part in data quality assurance using open standards.

The Publish and release stage concerns access to research outputs and the requirement of share and access. On the basis of the results, the ‘data librarian’ has a more important role in this phase. The ‘data scientist’ was also present, especially, for engaging in open innovation beyond academia. The role of the ‘data steward’ was shown in the skills related to the ethical application of patents, licences.

The Expose and discover stage ensures access to research outputs and their further developments regarding the standards of the community. ‘Data scientist’, ‘data steward’, and ‘data librarian’ have almost the same influences in this phase. The evaluation of the repository and publishing platforms were assigned to the ‘data librarian’ and ‘data steward’ where the

¹³ The file named: TRAIN4EU_WP5_Task_5.3_Case_1_SU_Data-roles-table (deposited with other files in the repository indicated in the project).

application of vocabulary/ontology was considered as a task of the ‘data steward’ and ‘data scientist’. For all three of them, searching repositories and scientific databases was selected. As a ‘data scientist’ is closer to understanding the data, the visualisation and presentation of results are considered as one of her/his tasks.

The Scope and resource stage identifies the extent of research data services, business cases, and governance processes. In this phase, the dispersion between the roles was more equal. Data management costs and their preservation were attached mostly to the ‘data steward’. The creation workflow and the management of provenance information were considered as ‘data scientist’ tasks.

The Advise and enable stage includes the communication between different services to create liaisons. The role of ‘data steward’ was totally present for every skill found in this phase.

Graphs

From the importance attributed to competences and to each data lifecycle stage, we have generated graphs for each data role that can be found below. These graphs were generated from a spreadsheet provided to participants during the workshop. For each job, tasks were listed, and participants were asked to indicate which tasks were most or least important to them. The following graphs reflect the participants' views of the different jobs in their local context and cannot be interpreted more broadly. We note that these graphs are consistent with the general definitions worked on prior to the workshop.

Figure 13. Data roles — data lifecycle stages

This project has received funding from The European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016674

Figure 14. Data roles — plan and design

Figure 15. Data roles — capture and process

This project has received funding from The European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016674

Figure 16. Data roles — integrate and analyse

Figure 17. Data roles — appraise and preserve

This project has received funding from The European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016674

Figure 18. Data roles — publish and release

Figure 19. Data roles — expose and discover

This project has received funding from The European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016674

Figure 20. Data roles — scope and resource

Figure 21. Data roles — advise and enable

2.3.2.4. Limitations of Milestone 2

Several limitations had occurred in Milestone 2. First, the scope of the analysis was reduced to the 4EU+ universities, excluding more profound analysis (interviews, LinkedIn and market analysis, etc.) that might influence the general representation of new emerging data roles. Moreover, by their nature and evolution, these professions had ambiguities to establish a clear

framework. Depending on their implementation context (faculty, project, library, etc.), different employment may occur.

In addition, during the workshop, because the data roles were not concretely defined and not to interfere with their perception, the participants had difficulties in performing the exercises. Therefore, the EOSC FAIR4S table had some loops for some universities that create biases, particularly for data engineers.

We have also remarked that, in the context of the 4EU+ Alliance, these data roles had not been employed yet as official titles. However, the tasks and competences related to these jobs could have been found in different positions. Hence, a further analysis had to be conducted to clarify the actual structure.

2.3.2.5. Conclusions

We can understand from the previous work that professions like data stewards, data librarians, data engineer, etc., appear because of societal needs. Supported by new funding requirements to open up research data, support services for research data management are in full development. The various professions, although theoretically defined, are in the phase of adaptation in the field, where services are not yet homogeneous across institutions. Far from being an obstacle, this is a sign of the great diversity of research data that needs to be managed by adapting the professions to each structure or unit.

The profile of data champions has not been studied in this step, as it is more responsibility than a profession. However, it complements all the professions mentioned in this work. Due to their experience with research data, data champions finally have a key role in spreading the culture of research data management in institutions.

At the end of this second step, it can be said that the research data management is a subject of reflection in all the institutions of the 4EU+ Alliance, which have already set up support services and are constantly considering the best job profiles for such tasks.

2.3.3. Open data support training for staff and doctoral students. Toolkit with a catalogue of existing RDM training offer at the 4EU+ universities and RDM lesson plans to create new training (Milestone 3)

Task 5.3 Case #1 aimed to identify RDM training to create a catalogue of existing training offer at the 4EU+ universities, as well as RDM lesson plans to fill in the identified gaps.

Milestone 3 is a toolkit with a catalogue of existing RDM training for staff and doctoral students at the 4EU+ universities. The catalogue of proposed training topics can serve as an example for further use at other universities.

2.3.3.1. The catalogue of existing RDM training offer

Charles University (CU)

The **CU Central Library** offers RDM training in the form of project-based consultations that correspond to the needs of different CU faculties. These sessions are typically based on requests received from the participants and cover topics like Open Access, RDM, DMP, Legal Support, Ethics, and IT Support. Consultations are also influenced by the involvement of various research infrastructures such as ELIXIR and CLARIN, which provide insight and knowledge about related subjects.

The consultation sessions are primarily focused on issues related to Open Access rather than RDM. The Open Access Moodle lacks specific mentions of Open Data and related concepts, as it is more geared towards publishing. However, another module called Research Data Management¹⁴ covers data-related issues.

During the OAW 2022¹⁵, a workshop titled "*Workshop on Data Steward Wizard*" was organised, and researchers were recommended to use this application as it meets the requirements of some infrastructures like ELIXIR.

Although some DPO sessions (ad-hoc talks and workshops) have been organised several times, the implementation of RDM with other departments at the CU is not yet standardised. Ethics committees are not fully integrated into the RDM process, and the IT department's support for RDM training is not consistent across different faculties.

CU currently does not have doctoral schools as such. It is difficult to identify and contact the studies that need to be supported in RDM. The DocEnhance data stewardship course¹⁶ was planned to fill this gap by enhancing transferable skills, intelligence, and integration into existing doctoral programs. The local version of the course was constructed in two parts: the first part consisted of six online sessions and the second part was composed of in person sessions.

Researchers also often acquire skills necessary in RDM from other sources and research infrastructures such as CESSDA¹⁷, CLARIN¹⁸, and ELIXIR¹⁹ which play a crucial role in providing training in that area.

The University of Copenhagen (UCPH)

The **University of Copenhagen Library** (KUB)²⁰ offers guidance services on complying with the requirements of funding agencies for open and FAIR data, use of data repositories, and

¹⁴ See the course: <https://dlcv.cuni.cz/course/view.php?id=482>

¹⁵ See the program: <https://knihovna.fsv.cuni.cz/aktuality/open-access-week-2022>

¹⁶ See the original course: <https://docenhance.eu/data-stewardship/>

¹⁷ <https://www.cessda.eu/>

¹⁸ <https://www.clarin.eu/>

¹⁹ <https://elixir-europe.org/>

²⁰ The website can be found at <https://kub.kb.dk/datalab>

granting licences and persistent identifiers for research data. They also provide researchers at UCPH with access to DMPonline which contains templates to create a Data Management Plan.

In addition, KUB has an extensive range of instructional resources, offers courses, workshops, and train-the-trainer courses for researchers, students, and UCPH's research supporters.

The **Department for Research and Information Security**, which oversees policy and compliance coordination, is also involved in GDPR and DPO-related issues. Although the Department conducts training sessions, the offer is more limited compared to that of the Library. The Department conducts a local internet portal dedicated to RDM and occasionally collaborates with the Library to host training sessions. However, if in-depth information is needed, stakeholders are advised to consult the Library.

Datalabs provide various RDM frameworks that correspond to the specific needs of each faculty. Researchers from all domains can benefit from the training catalogue, but primarily the training offer is targeted at doctoral students. The content of the catalogue focuses mainly on data science methods, and there is little emphasis on RDM issues. Datalabs do not make a clear distinction between data science methods and RDM, and this can lead to confusion. To bridge this gap, a collaboration between Datalabs and the Library is planned for the future.

The **DPO** offers compulsory courses on GDPR. On the other hand, the Ethics Committee operates in a different way since the review process is based on national standards. Its role at the university is to monitor current events and implement relevant procedures. However, they do not provide ethical approval or any form of training. Similarly, not any other department offers training on RDM.

DEIC²¹ is a national initiative that facilitates collaboration between universities. Currently DEIC is focused on expanding IT/software-based support. It provides various kinds of resources and support, including three online videos on DMP FAIR data, interviews on how to make data FAIR, and webinars on topics such as Horizon Europe.

As stated during the bilateral meeting, having a comprehensive list of RDM courses offered by each faculty is a difficult issue. While some mandatory RDM courses are available to doctoral students to some extent, a complete overview of all RDM training is lacking. Basic RDM education is mandatory at all faculties, and each faculty has its own unique representation, such as summer courses and discipline-based RDM programs. Information on the study boards and research programs of each faculty is not easy to obtain without active solicitation. The RDM training programs of faculties are based on cross-discipline programs and doctoral disciplines.

Heidelberg University (HU)

In HU, the **Competence Centre for Research Data** (KFD) offers regular fixed events such as Data Hour (monthly webinar series) and every semester an interdisciplinary RDM introduction in cooperation with the Graduate Academy.

In addition to these regular courses, they also offer specific courses on RDM. However, these courses are not listed on the KFD website since they are offered by individual agreement, e.g. integrated into individual courses, for specialised graduate schools, or research projects. In

²¹The DEIC website can be found at <https://www.deic.dk/en>

2022 for example, there were five additional courses specific to RDM, plus four courses on Open Science with RDM/FAIR as part of the content.

The **Heidelberg Forum for Digital Humanities** (HFDH) is a joint structure between different units. While the Forum does not focus on RDM training, it offers a Certificate of Advanced Studies for Digital Humanities²² (ECTS-based), which addresses DH as a whole and thus also Data Science and RDM content for this subject area.

The **Scientific Software Centre** (SSC) focuses more on data science methods rather than on RDM only. SSC is specifically focused on research software and software development, so they are not as much into RDM topics.

The **Library** offers training which corresponds mostly to that of KFD. Since the KFD is formed by the library and the **University Computing Center** (URZ), all RDM-specific courses are provided under the joint label of the KFD. Additionally, the library has further courses in related domains such as open access, open science, and copyright. URZ's activities in RDM teaching are also provided via the KFD. Graduate Academy courses on RDM are provided by KFD, while courses on Open Science are provided by the Library.

The **DPO** does not offer regular training on RDM, but events on data protection in research are offered from time to time via the university's internal education program. The **Research Division** offers courses on how to apply for funding and grant management. Finally, the **Tech Transfer Office / Transfer Agency hei_INNOVATION** offers a service portfolio that includes consulting on research collaborations and contracts, IP management, start-up and spin-off formation, and knowledge and technology transfer.

The University of Milan (UM)

RDM training is provided primarily by the **Performance, Quality Assurance, Assessment, and Open Science Policy Division**²³ (DPAQVPOS). The open science support team in DPAQVPOS provides general information courses on Dataverse, DMP, and FAIR data. Additionally, 4-hour courses are available for doctoral students in each discipline such as Medicine, Social and Human Sciences, and Science. UM also has a pilot project for 14 doctoral students, which includes 10 hours of RDM training, individual meetings to develop DMPs for their research projects, and training on the use of Dataverse.

The **Research Services Division** offers training on how to apply for grants and succeed in the European Commission. There is also the collaboration between DPAQVPOS and this department for proposal drafting.

The **Center for Educational Innovation and Multimedia Technologies** (CTU) is focused on e-learning courses, while the **Department of Economics, Management, and Quantitative Methods** offers courses on data science mainly oriented towards economics. Faculty members who offer courses on RDM are mainly statisticians.

The **DPO** provides training on data protection and privacy related to research activities, which is particularly relevant for some disciplines. The **Ethics Committee** offers courses on research

²² See the certificate program: <https://www.uni-heidelberg.de/en/research/research-profile/fields-of-focus/field-of-focus-iii/research-activities/forum-digital-humanities/continuing-education-program-digital-humanities>

²³ Original title: "*Direzione Performance, Assicurazione Qualita, Valutazione e Politiche di Open Science*".

integrity and authorship, but not specifically on RDM. The **TTO** does not offer RDM training but provides a two-part training for doctoral students on reusing third-party data and understanding the conditions of the data's licences. TTO collaborates with DPAQVPOS in providing training for 14 doctoral students on reusing data.

UM participated in the central event for Open Access Week in Italy, OAW22, which was organised by the University of Genoa. The event was attended by most universities in Italy, and UM gave two presentations. One is related to RDM: Experiences on the quality verification of metadata and research data of an institutional archive²⁴.

Sorbonne University (SU)

Research Data & Digital Humanities Team (CDHN), which has officially formed as an RDM support unit within the library, is dedicated to most of the RDM training at SU. The courses offered by this unit can be accessed either from the library training catalogue, which is planned throughout the year or by individual request.

For doctoral students, CDHN organised 10 training sessions on Open Data, its scope, and reutilization practices, which included four general open data-related courses and six discipline-based courses. Doctoral students at SU can also benefit from an online MOOC module called *Open Science*²⁵, which focuses on RDM in one of the sections. In addition to these courses, personalised consultation on DMP writing can be provided if requested by a unit.

At SU, it can be seen that some training programs articulate between events such as OAW and Love Data Week (LDW). During the OAW, CDHN participated in addressing and discussing issues related to research data including their availability, reuse, and closure if necessary.

During LDW, the **Archives and Records Department (SARA)** collaborates with CDHN to provide training on topics related to Digital Humanities (DH) to address data science issues in SSH. The head of the department is interested in this subject and holds necessary competencies to give such training. Specifically, SARA specialises in providing training on Research Data Archiving and tools related to managing perennial archiving.

Additionally, a special training session on Data Storage with **SACADO** was conducted during LDW. SACADO is a unit that was created to meet the growing needs for simulation, data processing, and storage in the research community. Although they do not primarily focus on training, they offer personalised guidance and consultation for projects that require storage options and computing planning.

Moreover, some research units in SU, such as CERES and ObTiC, provide training that can correspond to some stages of the data lifecycle. These units offer courses on data science methods and tools to assist researchers in data collection, analysis, and processing. These service units collaborate with other departments on specific topics. For example, CDHN and SARA were involved in one of CERES's workshops on DMP, GDPR and archiving of personal data in SSH. ObTiC, in turn, provides training activities in DH (scholarly digital publishing, data mining, textual analysis, etc.) for all students and researchers in SSH.

²⁴ Original title: “Esperienze sulla verifica di qualità dei metadati e dei dati della ricerca di un archivio istituzionale”.

²⁵ See the MOOC: <https://www.fun-mooc.fr/fr/cours/la-science-ouverte/>

Research Data Gouv is the ecosystem for sharing and opening research data, and includes a data repository and a suite of services. These services include data management clusters, thematic reference centres, and resource centres. Data management clusters provide researchers with initial expertise in rational research data management where thematic reference centres are dedicated to research infrastructures in each scientific field. Resource centres provide RDM support for other services. The **Repository-Registry Resource Center** ensures the administration of the repository and its future data catalogue. They also provide training on how to deposit data in a repository and how to create and administer institutional data spaces. Other resource centres provide support to users, such as the **DORANUM Resource Center** (self-study), *the Skills Resource Center* (staff training in data management clusters), and the **OPIDoR Resource Center** (provision of DOI, data management plan writing tool).

The University of Warsaw (UW)

At the UW, the **University of Warsaw Library** website provides information about training on various topics such as reference management systems, academic information seeking, and catalogues. However, for RDM training, the Office for Employee Affairs (more specifically: Section for the Development of Competencies of Academic Teachers) and the University Library have recently collaborated to organise open science training sessions (DMP plan, Open Science, publication, etc.). This collaboration between the two services aims to provide comprehensive training sessions on OS and related topics to researchers and students at the university.

The **Interdisciplinary Centre for Mathematical and Computational Modelling (ICM)** offerings in RDM are difficult to characterise due to the organisation's complexity. As seen in the benchmark, their primary focus is on supercomputers and related methods, with a variety of machines and services at their disposal. Although they offer courses and training related to open science, this is not their top priority.

ICM previously offered temporary training through its OpenAIRE project (2021)²⁶. The project included developing a research data repository and training programs. However, the training in this initiative was temporary and is currently inactive. As of now, no training courses are available through this project.

There are some more centres that are not exactly related to RDM, but they still give training which might be helpful during the data lifecycle. The **Digital Competence Center of the University of Warsaw** is dedicated to e-learning and offers a platform, infrastructure, and training to those who want to use e-learning resources. Within the centre, there is a sub-unit called the **Editorial Office of Digital Humanities** at the University of Warsaw. This office deals with issues related to Digital Humanities and aims to collect information on all DH projects being carried out at the university and identify potential areas for collaboration between projects. The **Machine Center Learning Center (Center4ML)**, a recently established unit under the Research University Excellence Initiative at the UW, gives training on machine learning methods.

²⁶ See the project: <https://drodb.icm.edu.pl/szkolenia-przeprowadzone-w-ramach-projektu/>

2.3.3.2. Other RDM training

To expand the scope of our analysis, we conducted additional research on RDM training programs offered by research units beyond the TRAIN4EU members.

What we can see from the results is that these courses tend to group around two main areas: RDM-related issues and data skills training.

Courses related to RDM issues can be further divided into two levels of detail. The first level offers introductory courses, such as *Research Data Management 101*, *Introduction to Research Data*, *Data Management Basics: Introduction to Data Management and Sharing*, and etc.

The second level can be classified as a more advanced version of the first-level courses, with more in-depth courses dedicated to certain aspects of RDM. Ethical and legal issues are the subjects most frequently represented at all the universities. Therefore, we can see courses related to consent issues, research ethics, licences, and copyrights, sensitive and personal data, data anonymization, and protection and sharing of data.

It can be seen that most of the RDM support units propose courses on the use of their own data repositories or other repositories for data sharing and storage. In the subject of data sharing, we can see an emphasis on Data Papers in some structures. Similarly, some units offer training in electronic laboratory notebooks to promote research reproducibility.

At the University of Geneva we also see a different distinction in the length of the courses which are in short and long formats. The *Short formats* (15-minute) courses provide brief introductions to various data management topics. The *Long formats* courses offer more in-depth training on topics that follow stages of the data lifecycle such as data planning, documentation, storage, protection, and sharing research data.

Courses related to data skills include training on different tools and software helpful not only to researchers but also to trainers. Researchers can participate in these courses to learn skills for data collection, analysis, and processing. Trainers, in their turn, can also benefit from these courses, as they need to have the required competencies to be more efficient in their support role.

We observed that in these training sessions there is a special focus on computational methods in social sciences and humanities. This can be explained by the fact that new emerging methods in DH are expanding, and, as a result, we can access more training programs dedicated to data science methods.

Furthermore, some universities, including KUB Datalab, have joined The Carpentries project, and we can see the appearance of their subgroups, such as "Software Carpentry" and "Data Carpentry", in their training. In their workshops, we can find training sessions focused on intermediate coding skills, and one such example is CodeRefinery.

We observed that the RDM courses offered by other institutions were not significantly different from those offered by the 4EU+ universities. These courses covered introductory RDM training topics such as data publishing and repositories.

However, the ethical and legal aspects of RDM were not extensively covered across the 4EU+ Alliance. Only UM and HU had collaborations between DPO and RDM support units that addressed these issues.

Furthermore, we found that research reproducibility was not as emphasised in the 4EU+ Alliance compared to other institutions, which offered training on electronic laboratory notebooks and data papers.

Overall, discipline-specific RDM courses were less common in general RDM support units, as these training courses could be delivered at the faculty or laboratory level.

2.3.3.3. Gaps in training

During bilateral meetings, we asked each participant to highlight the gaps found in their RDM training programs.

CU identified FAIR data, GDPR, and research ethics as the most needed areas for RDM training. However, they also indicated that support units that provide training on legal and ethics issues are difficult to collaborate with and are not particularly interested in RDM. Since there is no framework to determine best practices, there is no formalised RDM support in these domains.

At SU, the gaps in RDM training gather around the ethical and legal issues. The Ethics Committee and DPO do not organise training sessions for researchers and doctoral students. Although the DPO provides consultation services for having information related to personal and sensitive data handling issues, the Ethics Committee reviews only submitted protocols. Another missing area is that the RDM training in SU can be defined as general. More-discipline-based training option is needed to be constructed to cover the specific needs of each discipline.

UCPH addressed some missing aspects of RDM, including lack of legal knowledge about RDM and differences in the handling of personal data and their practices across structures. Furthermore, they noted that people can attend courses, but their level of interest and awareness can be low. UCPH recommended that students should have this awareness before starting the complicated project. Although they organise ad hoc presentations and talks to attract people, the level of awareness is not that high. As a result, different projects can be organised. However, they acknowledged that finding resources to host such events is a challenge.

In the UW's case, a systematic approach to OS is missing. Although every doctoral student has the opportunity to tackle OS issues, there is currently no systematic approach to illustrate OS-related issues in the doctoral program. It is possible to be assigned to a doctoral program and not learn anything about OS, as the courses are not mandatory. It depends on the motivation of the tutor and the student. It would be highly beneficial if every doctoral student could participate in an open science session, along with the creation of a fundamental open science curriculum for all doctoral students.

They also emphasised the importance of the legal aspects of RDM training and pointed out the need for evaluating such training. However, the library currently lacks a dedicated position to handle RDM matters. The library should consider educating someone in this domain or,

alternatively, the university should consider involving a legal expert to provide support in this area.

They also underlined that legal aspects in research are relatively novel and that the connection between the field of law and research data should be established more clearly. Copyright issues are among the main legal challenges, and researchers frequently do not consider legal aspects in their projects due to a lack of awareness about the connections between them.

For UM, the gap in RDM training is about data security, as they currently lack the development of tools and organisational structure in this regard at the university. For example, when they reach this point, also in DMP, they do not know what they have to write.

Although they conduct training sessions in collaboration with the DPO and the Ethics Committee, they also mentioned that organising training sessions with these units is not always a good solution. They mentioned encountering difficulties in collaboration with the DPO, because they use the same words with different meanings. In GDPR, the FAIR principles are present, but the FAIR data differ. It is not easy to communicate with DPO. In some instances, in these courses, they hear things that are not applicable to FAIR data and RDM.

HU stated that the main challenge is not expanding the topics, but rather ensuring that the basic RDM knowledge is provided to all students and researchers on the whole campus. They suggested getting better at individual subjects and developing in-depth courses on specific topics rather than offering fairly general overview courses. This requires developing expertise on our side and interlinking with departments to meet specific subject requirements and methods.

As a consequence, we have observed that in most universities there is a lack of ethical and legal guidelines regarding RDM. The main problem lies in finding personnel to provide training on the related subject or collaborate with experts in this domain.

Moreover, RDM support units and DPOs can have different perceptions of RDM practices and their best practices might differ. As UM mentioned during the meeting, it can be challenging to organise training sessions between these structures due to the fact that DPO's practices may be far from best practices, particularly for handling research data in compliance with FAIR principles.

We should also consider that ethical and legal issues are constantly changing nowadays as new technologies and methods arrive. This situation might be difficult for personnel to cope with and even more complicated for researchers and students.

In some universities, we observed the need for a systematic approach. RDM units propose some options, but they remain optional. Additionally, we can see a need to develop tools, software, and infrastructure to assist researchers. Even though we ensure the necessary training and knowledge systematically, all the learning can remain theoretical if we can't give them relevant concrete cases and examples in practice.

Similarly to tools and infrastructure inside the university, the motivation of researchers and doctoral students also needs to be addressed. Raising awareness should be assured by RDM units. It is true that in all universities, we can find different types of RDM courses with different levels and granularity. However, the problem lies in evaluating the impact of these courses. The main question is, how do we make sure that basic RDM knowledge is provided to all

students and researchers? In addition to the different courses and training, we should also find a medium to motivate the participants.

2.3.3.4. Lesson plans

Based on the gaps identified in the previous section, we have developed lesson plans to address the areas that were lacking. Enclosed are four such plans: *Legal Issues: Intellectual Property*, *GDPR, Personal Data and Anonymization*, *Data Security*, and *Ethics*.

2.3.3.4.1. Legal issues: intellectual property

Name of the course	Legal issues: intellectual property
Training audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Doctoral students ● Researchers ● Staff
Previous knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● None required
Aims of the training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Understand the legal framework of intellectual property ● Understand the rights that apply to research data: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Open data: public sector data, geographical data, environmental data ○ Protected data: database rights, patents, health data, privacy, trade secrets, state secrets, etc. ● Distinguish reusable data from protected data ● Know the different types of open/free licences: public domain licences, permissive licence, copyleft ● Know the different types of content to which these licences apply: research data, databases, open-source software, etc.
Plan and activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Intellectual property rights <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Copyright <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ artistic ■ musical ■ dramatic ■ for texts, images, videos, music, etc. ○ Industrial property <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ trademark ■ Patent ■ Design ■ Database ■ Trade secret ● Open or protected data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Open data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Public sector data: PSI Directive

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Geographical data: INSPIRE Directive (INfrastructure for SPatial InfoRmation in the European community) ■ Environmental data: Aarhus Convention (Convention on Access to Information, Public Participation in Decision-making and Access to Justice in Environmental Matters) ○ Protected data, use cases <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ database rights ■ patents: use case on a research project with a company that wants to file a patent ■ health data: use case on a research project with a clinical trial ■ privacy: sociological research project with a survey ■ trade secrets: example of a grant agreement with a confidentiality clause between the research team and the partner company ■ state secrets: dual use technologies, etc. ● Reusable or protected data? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Identify the legal notices and terms of use on the datasets. ● Open/free licences: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ public domain licences <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Creative Commons: CC0 ■ Public Domain Dedication and License ○ permissive licence <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Apache License ■ BSD License ■ MIT License ■ Creative Commons Attribution: CC-BY ○ Copyleft <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ GNU GPO ■ Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike: CC-BY-SA ● Examples according to the type of content <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Research data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Creative Commons ○ Databases <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ PDDL ■ ODC By ■ ODC ODbL ○ open-source software <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ GNU Licence ● Exercise: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Find your open licence https://ufal.github.io/public-license-selector/
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2.3.3.4.2. Personal data, GDPR and anonymization

Name of the course	Personal data, GDPR and anonymization
Training audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Doctoral students • Researchers • Staff
Previous knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None required
Aims of the training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Know legal framework for personal data: GDPR • Know what is personal data • Differentiate between personal and sensitive data • Understand the data protection principles of GDPR • Understand legal bases for processing personal data • Know your obligations for a research project • Discover anonymization tools
Plan and activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GDPR <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ What is it, who is affected? ◦ Obligations of a research project ◦ Discussion: do you collect personal data? Do you think you are in compliance with GDPR? • Personal data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ an identifiable person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, ▪ examples: a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier, etc. ◦ Example: personal data collected for this training ◦ Discussion: could I collect your date of birth and your personal contact details for this training? • Sensitive data (special categories of personal data in the GDPR) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs ◦ trade-union membership ◦ genetic data, biometric data processed solely to identify a human being ◦ health-related data

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ data concerning a person's sex life or sexual orientation. ● Data protection principles of GDPR <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Lawfulness, fairness and transparency ○ Purpose limitation ○ Data minimization ○ Accuracy ○ Storage limitation ○ Integrity and confidentiality ○ Accountability ● Legal bases for processing personal data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Consent ○ Contract ○ Legal obligation ○ Vital interests of the data subject ○ Public interest ○ Legitimate interests ● GDPR and your research project <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Before the project <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Contact your DPO ■ Writing information for the records of processing activities ■ Writing information for the records of processing activities ■ Write information sheets about the project for people to be interviewed and prepare consent forms ○ During the project <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Regularly check access to the database or files containing personal data, and delete access for people who have left the project ○ After the project <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Verify the retention period of personal data ■ Delete data after the specified retention period ● Anonymization tools <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Amnesia (OpenAire) ○ K-anonymity principles ○ Exercise: test the online version of Amnesia <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Materials to be provided to participants: personal data sheets with false information about imaginary people
References	<p>Engelhardt, Claudia, et al. D7.4 How to Be FAIR with Your Data. A Teaching and Training Handbook for Higher Education Institutions. Zenodo, 2022, https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5837500.</p> <p>European Commission. What personal data is considered sensitive? https://commission.europa.eu/law/law-topic/data-protection/reform/rules-business-and-organisations/legal-grounds-</p>

	<p>processing-data/sensitive-data/what-personal-data-considered-sensitive_en</p> <p>GDPR.eu. Complete guide to GDPR compliance. https://gdpr.eu/</p> <p>OpenAIRE. A complete k-anonymity scenario. https://amnesia.openaire.eu/Scenarios/AmnesiaTutorialKAnon.pdf</p> <p>OpenAIRE. Amnesia. https://amnesia.openaire.eu/</p>
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2.3.3.4.3. Introduction to data security

Name of the course	Introduction to data security
Training audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Doctoral students
Previous knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None required
Aims of the training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the different levels of data security • Be aware of the risks associated with research data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Understand the causes of data loss • Discover methods for protecting research data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Know methods for protecting data on a computer or hard drive ◦ Know methods to protect data during transmission or sharing • Discover methods for backing up data
Plan and activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information classification types example <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Open access: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ no particular risk in case of data loss ▪ e.g. course notes, downloading of a completely open dataset ◦ Restricted access: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ data that require special monitoring ▪ who can access it, for how long? ▪ should they be subject to special security measures (encryption, offline storage) ◦ Embargo: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ data that can be opened at the end of a period to be defined ▪ for example, at the end of a project, after the publication of an article, etc. ◦ Closed access: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ sensitive data whose consultation and analysis is strictly controlled ▪ accesses are verified and login information is kept ▪ these data cannot be downloaded or transmitted under any circumstances • Risks <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Data loss

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ save your thesis drafts and manuscripts! ▪ avoid USB keys for essential data ○ Data theft <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ difficult to predict ▪ solution: backup your data! ○ Security breach (intrusion) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ complicated to detect ▪ check with your IT department ○ Discussion: have you ever had any of these problems? Were you able to identify the causes? ● Causes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Lack of maintenance of the computer or the USB key <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Importance of updates ▪ Regular scanning with an antivirus ○ Lack of data security during transmission <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Transfer by email ▪ Transfer via a private cloud that does not comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) ● Data protection methods <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ On a computer or hard drive <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Create strong passwords to access the computer ▪ Check the access rights of each user if the computer is shared between several people ▪ Protect sensitive data in specific folders, with controlled access and, if necessary, encryption ▪ Reserve USB storage for temporary data, back it up as soon as possible ○ During transmission <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Recommendation: do not send sensitive data by email ▪ Use your university's secure clouds (explain the risks of clouds like Dropbox or Google Drive) ● Back up methods <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 3-2-1 rule <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ There should be 3 copies of data ▪ On 2 different media ▪ With 1 copy being off-site ▪ Discussion: How do you back up your data? Did you know the “3-2-1” rule? ○ If backups are automated, check the data retention period to make sure you can recover it in case of an incident
References	<p>Montclair State University. Data Security in Research. https://www.montclair.edu/institutional-review-board/data-security-in-research/</p>

2.3.3.4.4. The basics of ethics in research

Name of the course	The basics of ethics in research
Training audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Doctoral students • Staff
Previous knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None required
Aims of the training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Be aware of the ethics principles • Know the European framework for research involving the human subjects • Example of the Horizon Europe self-assessment form • Know the ethics committees and the institutional review boards
Plan and activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research fields concerned (selected examples of the Horizon Europe self-assessment form) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Human embryonic stem cells and human embryos ○ Humans ○ Human cells or tissues ○ Personal data ○ Animals ○ Artificial intelligence • Main ethics issues (selected examples of the Horizon Europe self-assessment form) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ the respect for persons and for human dignity ○ fair distribution of benefits and burden ○ the rights and interests of the participants ○ participants' free informed consent (with particular attention to vulnerable categories of individuals such as children, patients, discriminated people, minorities, persons unable to give consent, etc.) • How to address the issues <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Participants are volunteers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ ethics approvals ■ information sheets and consent forms ○ Children: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ justification for involving them ■ parent consents ○ Vulnerable individuals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Ensure that participants are not coerced or induced in any way ○ Clinical trials: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ European and national procedures ○ Human cells or tissues: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ EU regulations and national laws ○ Personal data:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ see the dedicated training ○ Animals <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ EU and national animal testing regulations ▪ Protected species procedures ○ National funders' requirements ● The ethics committee of the university (if applicable) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Role ○ Submitting a protocol ● The institutional review board of the university (if applicable) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Role ○ Contact procedure
References	<p>European Commission. How to complete your ethics self-assessment, 2021. https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/how-to-complete-your-ethics-self-assessment_en.pdf</p>

During bilateral meetings, we were able to observe that RDM training issues were clearly identified at all universities. Sometimes a lack of resources or staff trained in these new topics makes it difficult to create more training sessions.

During bilateral meetings, all members discussed the issue of faculties, where it is particularly challenging to track all RDM training and their specific details. It is complicated for generalist services, whose provision is open to an entire university community, to be aware of the variety of courses and training organised in each faculty. All interviewees identified the problem that some courses offered in one faculty or another may be of interest to a wider audience. In addition, a better understanding of what is offered in each faculty would help to avoid creating an almost identical offer of courses.

However, even if one looks only at university-wide training, its offer is extensive and diversified. The shortcomings identified relate only to emerging topics, since the questions are asked by researchers and doctoral students involved in a research project. It might be interesting to share some sessions to benefit from the specialisation of each member of the Alliance. A joint program or a summer school could be considered for the future.

2.3.3.5. Limitations of Milestone 3

In this step, it is important to note that the RDM training list that we identified is far from representing the real situation at all 4EU+ universities. Due to the limited time we had, we could not take a deeper insight into the RDM training programs, particularly those given separately by each faculty or research unit. Our aim was to focus on RDM support units dedicated to Open Science.

We also focused on the RDM training programs inside the 4EU+ universities. The research we conducted beyond the 4EU+ was limited.

Also, due to the limitation of time, we could not analyse the content of each course related to RDM in depth. The analysis was more oriented towards their titles, which could create biases.

In any case, this work can be defined as exploratory, and there needs to be further analysis to illustrate the real situation.

2.3.3.6. Conclusions

The third phase of Task 5.3 Case #1 aimed to identify RDM trainings to create a catalogue of existing training offer at the 4EU+ universities as well as RDM lessons plans to address the identified gaps. We had originally planned to carry out a survey to gather information about education at the six Alliance universities. However, the bilateral meetings held during Step 1 of this use case allowed us to gather a great deal of information. After asking the members of WP5 for their opinion, we decided to abandon the survey method in favour of interviews with each university.

During the bilateral meetings, we were able to observe that RDM training issues were clearly identified in all universities. Sometimes a lack of resources or staff trained in these new topics makes it difficult to create more training sessions.

All members addressed the issue of faculties during the bilateral meetings. It is complicated for generalist services, whose provision is open to an entire university community, to be aware of the variety of courses and training organised in each faculty. All interviewees identified the same problem that some courses offered in one faculty or another may be of interest to a wider audience. In addition, a better understanding of what is offered in each faculty would help to avoid the creation of almost identical courses.

However, when focusing solely on the training opportunities available across the university, it is broad and varied. The shortcomings identified relate only to emerging topics, as inquiries from researchers and doctoral students involved in a research project come. It might be interesting to share some sessions in order to benefit from the expertise of each member of the Alliance. Looking ahead, a collaborative program or a summer school might be worth considering.

2.3.4. Data repositories – A list of data repositories and funding solutions (Milestone 4)

Milestone 4 of Case #1 involves listing existing research data repositories utilised by the 4EU+ universities. This includes describing their key characteristics to identify common desirable traits. Additionally, an analysis of current repositories funding solutions and a long-term preservation plan have been formulated.

2.3.4.1. Methodology

As a methodology, we created a benchmark to list existing data repositories in the 4EU+ universities. To describe their characteristics, we chose several parameters similar to the work

conducted on listing repositories²⁷. Therefore, one can find the following columns in the benchmark: Discipline/Institutional, Name, URL, Host Institution, Moderation/Curation, Perennial Identifier, Repository Type, Embargo, Supporter Users, Term of Use, and Statistics. We aimed to analyse the data repository at each institution and exchange information on their structure.

Once the information was collected, we organised bilateral meetings with each university. During these meetings, several additional columns were suggested to be added to the benchmark. The first column was 'Certification', which aimed to check if a repository has a standardised certification. The second column was 'Indexation', to determine if the repository is indexed on platforms such as re3data, OpenAIRE, or EOSC marketplace. Lastly, we included, if possible, the 'Download rates' parameter in Statistics for datasets to track the frequency of dataset downloads.

We also discussed the financial solutions used by each data repository to understand how financial options were found to create such repositories. Then, we addressed the long-term preservation options for the data repositories. We explored whether each repository had considered this aspect and how they planned to sustain long-term preservation.

2.3.4.2. Data Repositories

Data repositories play a crucial role in facilitating effective research data management. They provide structured and organised services for storing, sharing, and preserving research data, enabling collaboration and ensuring data accessibility for future (re)use. As part of this phase, a research investigation was conducted to explore the implementation of data repositories in various universities.

Charles University (CU)

Currently, there are not many institutions in the Czech Republic that have data repositories. However, National Czech programme for EOSC implementation²⁸, is being developed to address this issue. The initiative aims to establish the “National Data Infrastructure (NDI) – a common platform for sharing, managing and accessing data and computing resources for research purposes”²⁹. NDI includes various components such as the National Metadata Directory (NMD), the National Repository Platform (NRP), thematic repositories, and education/training initiatives.

NRP serves as the primary solution to address fragmented storage capacity problems. The concept involves creating a shared synchronised storage pool based on an object storage system. Different repository platforms can be built on top of this shared infrastructure, also enabling establishing of new repositories. Rather than creating something entirely new, the focus is on integrating existing data repositories into the NDI, recognizing their value and interoperability.

²⁷ For example: <https://www.dataacc.org/en/warehouses/zenodo/>

²⁸ The website can be found at <https://www.eosc.cz/en>

²⁹ Cited from <https://www.eosc.cz/en/about-eosc-cz>

This NRP will incorporate several data repository solutions, such as DSpace³⁰ and InvenioRDM³¹, but inclusion of Dataverse is at current stage unlikely. The intention behind this choice is to use the existing expertise within Czech institutions, particularly in InvenioRDM and DSpace, although the final decision has not yet been made. To build the NRP, a call will open in November 2023, coordinated by the mandated organisation of the EOSC association (CESNET). The goal is to develop tools, provide training and educational activities, and construct the NRP itself.

For CU, the expectation is to choose the DSpace data repository solution. This decision is based on the strong team and expertise already present at the Institute of Formal and Applied Linguistics, which operates the existing LINDAT/CLARIAH-CZ³² infrastructure. The existing LINDAT/CLARIAH-CZ repository³³ is willing to provide its services to the national platform, serving as the basis for other repositories. This solution is anticipated in the future.

However, implementing the NDI will take considerable time, probably around five years, with the expected completion in 2028. The initial phase has been slow due to the complex nature of the project, involving multiple stakeholders.

Consequently, the university's options for creating a data repository are limited, as the funding will primarily support the larger project. Fortunately, CU has the advantage of a dedicated DSpace team closely aligned with the university's needs, facilitating collaboration on the chosen solution. Choosing an alternative solution like Dataverse would require starting from scratch and competing with two different data repository options. It is more advantageous for the university to utilise the existing system, as the DSpace team is closely connected and offers advanced functionalities.

Currently, there is no explicit structure planned for the data repository. However, a flatter structure can be adopted, considering that DSpace typically employs collections by default, similar to dataverses. However, there is not much enthusiasm within the infrastructure to utilise collections. Therefore, the need for such a structure will be adopted based on its necessity. Considering the small number of repositories present, it is anticipated that filtering through metadata or other means may be employed, rather than creating collections. While collections are a feature in DSpace, it has not yet been decided whether they will be utilised in this context. The final decision will depend on the specific needs and requirements of the repository.

Although there will be more repositories to be built as part of NDI and hosted by national infrastructures, it is expected that the institutional repository of the CU will be relatively independent of others, serving users of the CU or people with some relation to the CU. It will have moderation and curation processes to ensure data quality and reliability and to utilise DOIs as perennial identifiers. Embargo/option to limit access to the data will be implemented.

The exact number of personnel dedicated to the administration and curation of the data repository is yet to be determined. This will depend on the national project and it may happen that the individuals responsible for data curation may not be part of it. Based on current

³⁰ See more: <https://dspace.lyrasis.org/about/>

³¹ See more: <https://inveniosoftware.org/products/rdm/>

³² LINDAT/CLARIAH-CZ is a consolidation of two research infrastructures, LINDAT/CLARIN and DARIAH-CZ.

³³ See the interface of the repository at <https://lindat.mff.cuni.cz/repository/xmlui/discover#>

estimates, 3-4 individuals might be working for administration and development due to project requirements that extend beyond a single institution. Additionally, one person is expected to be dedicated to data curation specifically for the CU.

The national repository platform is currently being financed through the project. However, there is uncertainty about its sustainability after the project is completed on December 31, 2028. Regarding the long-term preservation plan, there has been limited discussion within the national project. As of now, details on maintaining long-term preservation have not been thoroughly addressed.

The University of Copenhagen (UCPH)

Two platforms were identified at the UCPH that can be seen within the archive and data repository. The first, known as the Electronic Research Data Archive (ERDA)³⁴, is an institutional platform hosted by the UCPH's Faculty of Sciences. ERDA functions as a storage service and integrates with HPC and various analysis tools. It also provides an archiving feature where data can be frozen and assigned a DOI to make it publicly accessible. This DOI issuance process represents a relatively straightforward approach employed by the repository.

To ensure the quality and integrity of the stored data, ERDA implements moderation and curation procedures. Researchers using the repository have the option to obtain a DOI for their data, although public access to the data is not granted by default. The platform is primarily dedicated to users who are affiliated with or working for the UCPH. Detailed terms of use for the repository can be found on its website³⁵, and no statistical data on repository usage is available because it requires institutional access to the platform.

The second, called the Sensitive Information Facility (SIF)³⁶, focuses on handling sensitive and personal data. Unlike the ERDA, SIF does not assign DOIs to its data, as nothing from the platform is intended to be made public. Consequently, SIF is highly restricted, requiring individuals to apply and obtain approval from a university-affiliated lawyer.

By default, access is only allowed if the project has received approval from a faculty lawyer in accordance with GDPR regulations and risk assessment. Once approved, an administrator will create a dedicated folder for the project within SIF, granting access to authorised individuals. Any additional individuals who need access must also need approval from the faculty lawyer. Authorization is given by following a project-based approach rather than granting access on an individual basis.

Similarly to ERDA, SIF is hosted by the UCPH's Faculty of Sciences and follows moderation and curation processes. Access to SIF is exclusively offered to users affiliated with or working for the dedicated institution. Detailed terms of use for the repository can be found on its website³⁷, and no statistical data on repository usage is available.

Both of these platforms can be viewed as similar in structure, resembling a file system. Each user has a personal home folder, as well as the ability to create folders for projects and invite others to collaborate. Researchers have the flexibility to use the platforms according to their

³⁴ Website can be accessed at <https://www.erda.dk/>

³⁵ Terms of use: <https://www.erda.dk/public/terms.html>

³⁶ Website can be accessed at <https://sif.ku.dk/>

³⁷ Terms of use is accessible at <https://sif.ku.dk/public/terms.html>

specific needs and use cases, resulting in different structures for each use case. These platforms function as storage spaces, similar to a network drive.

The initial motivation behind the creation of these platforms was to provide a large storage capacity to accommodate the large volume of data generated by researchers at the Faculty of Sciences, particularly in fields such as image processing where data sizes can be substantial. The primary objective was to address the need for efficient storage. Subsequently, the inclusion of a DOI was introduced in response to user requests. Researchers found it beneficial to associate a DOI with their data, especially when combining it with a publication.

However, a limitation of these platforms is that they do not function as repositories in the true sense. Users cannot perform searches within the platforms, making them less compliant with the FAIR principles. Although a DOI and some limited metadata are provided, the platforms lack comprehensive search functionality and advanced features commonly found in repositories.

To address these limitations, some initiatives have been started by the Danish e-Infrastructure Consortium (DeiC)³⁸, a national collaboration, for building a national infrastructure for the eight universities in Denmark. The main objective is to create a national Dataverse (DeiC Dataverse³⁹) that will be made available to all universities, with UCPH hosting the repository. Furthermore, an additional national service called DeiC Storage⁴⁰ will be established, offering researchers in Denmark a secure data storage solution.

The UCPH is in the process of developing these services. Although the installation is not complete for DeiC Dataverse, the company anticipates launching the services sometime this year. The UCPH is actively preparing various aspects, including technical partnerships, governance structure, and support systems, to ensure their operation.

Within the service, each university will have its administrators and curators who will be responsible for managing their users and data. Additionally, there will be an overall record service management structure that will bring together all universities, creating a national database.

In parallel to this, UCPH is expanding the ERDA and SIF platforms to cover the entire country, establishing DeiC Storage service. While DeiC Dataverse will be dedicated to publishing data, this national storage service will serve as active data storage and will also include archiving and security measures, as well as other supplementary functionalities, such as storage for sensitive data.

The UCPH also has plans to integrate the DeiC Dataverse with the national storage infrastructure. While the exact integration method has not yet been determined, the goal is to create two interconnected systems that allow researchers to access and work with their data, without the need for data migration.

³⁸ Website can be found at <https://www.deic.dk/en>

³⁹ More information can be found at <https://www.deic.dk/en/data-management/data-management-services/DeiC-Dataverse>

⁴⁰ More information can be found at <https://www.deic.dk/en/data-management/data-management-services/DeiC-Storage-and-DeiC-Sensitive-Storage>

ERDA and SIF services are financed by the Faculty of Sciences. However, when national services are implemented, the Ministry will initially finance the storage and Dataverse services for three years as a project. After that, there will be a payment model for universities on the storage part. At the same time, there is also an initiative to see if external storage can be used as each institution was requesting to use their storage and connect it to the Dataverse. Otherwise, these institutions have to pay larger amounts of data.

On the SIF and ERDA platforms, three or four people work almost full time on both systems. These individuals are responsible for the maintenance and management of both platforms.

Currently, there is no suitable long-term preservation strategy in place for national services. Therefore, it is crucial to consider this aspect, particularly for the certification process, which requires long-term preservation plans such as CoreTrustSeal.

Heidelberg University (HU)

“heiDATA is a platform for publishing Open Research Data and enables data to be made available in accordance with the FAIR Data Principles. It publishes data from Heidelberg University research projects as well as research data on publications in Heidelberg University Publishing (heiUP) and on Heidelberg University's other open access platforms. In addition, research data on publications from the subject information services arthistoricum.net, Propylaeum, and FID4SA are published. The heiDATA functions here as a subject repository in the fields of art history, photography and design, ancient studies, and South Asian studies”⁴¹.

heiData utilises the Dataverse software as a repository solution which includes DOI as a perennial identifier, embargo option, and datasets reviews. It is hosted by the Competence Centre for Research Data. A user guide can be found on the website⁴².

First, it operates as an institutional data repository for researchers affiliated with HU. Second, it is also a data repository for authors at open access platforms maintained by Heidelberg University Library, e.g. the university press Heidelberg University Publishing (heiUP), in case they want to publish the underlying research data along with their open access publication. The authors on these platforms can also be external. Third, heiData also offers a national service in the fields of art history, archaeology, and South Asian Studies, having specific domain-based dataverses within the repositories which allows external researchers to join and publish their datasets. Only for these three humanities fields, HU offers a data repository solution as a nationwide service because of German Research Foundation (DFG) funding programs, where the task is to offer services in these disciplines.⁴³ As a service for the aforementioned research communities, heiDATA is integrated into the large-scale German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) initiative via the NFDI4Culture consortium.⁴⁴ For other disciplines, different institutions in Germany could also have this job, depending on the funding programs. Other dataverses in heiData are typically for research groups, projects from the university, or the publication platforms, such as Open Access Publishing.

⁴¹ Cited from <https://www.data.uni-heidelberg.de/en/rdm-services/publish-archive/heidata>

⁴² heiData user guide: <https://www.data.uni-heidelberg.de/en/rdm-services/publish-archive/heidata/user-guide>

⁴³

https://www.dfg.de/en/research_funding/programmes/infrastructure/lis/funding_opportunities/specialised_info_services/index.html

⁴⁴ <https://nfdi4culture.de/index.html> and <https://www.nfdi.de/>

Within the repository, there are 477 datasets with a total of 142,358 downloads⁴⁵. The repository hosts 130 dataverses (collections)⁴⁶, which are categorised as follows:

- *Research Group*: 61 dataverses
- *Research Projects*: 18 dataverses
- *Organisation or Institution*: 16 dataverses
- *Departments*: 14 dataverse
- *Journal*: 6 dataverses

arthistoricum@heiData has 35 datasets and hosts 10 dataverses⁴⁷, which are categorised as follows:

- *Research Project*: 4 dataverses
- *Journal*: 1 dataverse
- *Organisation or Institution*: 2 dataverses

propylaeum@heiData has 48 datasets and hosts 7 dataverses⁴⁸, categorised as follows:

- *Journal*: 4 dataverses

FID4SA@heiData has 4 datasets and hosts 1 dataverse⁴⁹.

The decision to choose the Dataverse solution for the institutional data repository was not straightforward. At the time of implementation in 2014, Dataverse was a relatively new platform with only around 15 installations worldwide. Additionally, the HU already had existing repositories such as heiDOK, which served as an e-prints repository for text and other materials. The choice had to be made between improving heiDOK to accommodate research data or implementing a new service altogether.

After careful consideration, it was determined that implementing a new repository would involve less effort from an administrative perspective. While the administration workload would be reduced, adapting heiDOK/EPrints for research data was complex and costly to meet the requirements. Consequently, Dataverse emerged as a suitable solution as it met the conditions for supporting metadata standards, DOIs, and other essential features at a lower cost and with available expertise. Another advantage of Dataverse was its capability to export data and metadata in a structured manner, facilitating potential future transfers to other systems if required.

Furthermore, in 2014, the landscape of institutional data repositories was uncertain and it was unclear how it would evolve by 2023. There was the possibility of implementing national or

⁴⁵ As of 8 November 2023 <https://heidata.uni-heidelberg.de/>

⁴⁶ In Datavers software 'dataverses' are referred to as collections.

⁴⁷ As of 8 November 2023 <https://heidata.uni-heidelberg.de/dataverse/arthistoricum>

⁴⁸ As of 8 November 2023 <https://heidata.uni-heidelberg.de/dataverse/propylaeum>

⁴⁹ As of 8 November 2023 <https://heidata.uni-heidelberg.de/dataverse/FID4SA>

disciplinary databases, among other options. HU became the first German institution to adopt Dataverse as a comprehensive institutional repository for the entire university.

The heiDATA repository does not have a strict policy regarding its structure. Instead, it utilises the taxonomy provided by Dataverse, where dataverse categories are assigned based on the specific needs of users. For instance, if a researcher intends to publish their data, they explore existing corresponding dataverses for groups or projects. If none are available, they engage in discussions to create a separate dataverse for their group. As the installation of heiData expands, it may become necessary to organise all the dataverses into a proper hierarchy, establishing structured dataverse categories for faculties and sub-dataverses for institutes or research projects.

The moderation and curation process within heiDATA operates in two ways. While the repository does not specialise in a specific discipline, it does not provide subject-specific curation of the content of the data. However, it offers guidance on metadata and how to enrich them with detailed descriptions using README files and keywords. Additionally, it provides technical curation by examining the data files and their formats, discussing the feasibility of export and long-term preservation, and recommending open, non-proprietary formats whenever possible. The repository also gathers information on the use of proprietary formats for documentation purposes and maintains an internal knowledge base about these file formats. Furthermore, by using various tools, the validity of data files is checked.

At HU, the heidICON also serves as a data repository for museum objects, multimedia, and 3D data, primarily in the field of humanities, within the HU. Positioned between a digital library and a data repository, it plays a vital role in the digital representation of artworks. Specifically, it offers a metadata schema dedicated to documenting art objects, including photographs. The heidICON is built using Fylr (formerly: easyDB), a commercial software that collaborates with HU. It supports multiple APIs and serves as a backend for various publication services.

An example of its integration is observed in e-books published by the University Press, where videos associated with the publication are stored in heidIcon and directly embedded into the HTML of the e-book. The heidIcon, hosted by the HU Library, has been in operation since 2005, initially as an image database. Depending on the object type, some objects receive DOIs as persistent identifiers. However, not all objects are publicly accessible.

The repository structure consists of open and closed pools, allowing objects to be embargoed based on authorship and copyright concerns. Statistics collected pertain only to objects in the open pools, but it is important to note that numerous objects are stored in closed pools as well. These closed pools are managed by their respective owners, who can grant access to users when necessary.

The funding for repositories comes from the regular budget of the Computing Center and the University Library. Therefore, the maintenance of heiData, system administration, data creation, and researcher communication are handled by the Competence Center with its regular staff. This funding primarily comes from internal sources or the HU Library's budget. Additionally, the storage infrastructure, which serves as the central infrastructure of the university, is financed by both third-party funding, such as the DFG, and the federal state. Funding schemes exist for hardware and storage systems, among other resources. The HU Computing Center applies for and utilises these funding opportunities, allowing heiData to

utilise the same storage infrastructure. However, heiData has not received any specific third-party funding of its own.

Regarding long-term preservation, HU has implemented two different solutions. Currently, preservation measures are already in place, including dedicated storage systems where data is mirrored and backed up nightly.

Then, there is an ongoing large-scale project called heiARCHIVE, aimed at developing new services to serve as a long-term preservation infrastructure for the university. The primary purpose of the heiARCHIVE is to provide researchers with a platform to archive data that they do not intend to publish. On the contrary, heiData is designed for data publication.

Additionally, the heiARCHIVE is intended to serve as the preservation infrastructure for all publication systems within the university, including the University Press, heiData, and heidIcon. It is essential that all data published in the HU will be archived in heiArchive.

The heiARCHIVE system is being developed in-house and is currently in a pilot operational phase. Initially, it offers bitstream preservation capabilities, but efforts are underway to enhance the service by providing additional functionalities for comprehensive content preservation. The existing secure IT infrastructure at HU will be supplemented by the heiArchive service, ensuring that all data, including that in heiData and other repositories, is preserved. Furthermore, HU is actively pursuing CoreTrustSeal certification for heiData. This certification will establish a preservation policy for heiData, enhancing the security and preservation measures implemented.

The University of Milan (UM)

The data repository at the UM, known as Dataverse UNIMI, is an institutional multidisciplinary repository⁵⁰. The repository is hosted by third parties who handle its technical management, including maintenance and updates. Utilise DOIs as perennial identifiers and datasets can be embargoed if necessary. Dataverse UNIMI is not only used by users working with or affiliated with the dedicated institution but also hosts international projects. For example, the repository accommodates doctoral programs with international and European projects, allowing external members to use the Dataverse. The terms of use⁵¹ for Dataverse UNIMI provides users with guidelines and regulations regarding data access and usage within the repository.

The decision to implement Dataverse as a repository solution was made after considering various tools. Dataverse was chosen because it is suitable for a multidisciplinary institution. It is also non-proprietary software that relies on an international community of developers. Since there were no existing projects in Italy for data repositories, the UM became the first university to implement Dataverse. Subsequently, other institutions have started creating their Dataverses. There is no repository at the national level.

The repository hosts a total of 150 dataverses (collections)⁵², which are categorised as follows:

- *Research Projects*: 54 dataverses

⁵⁰ It is accessible at <https://dataverse.unimi.it/>

⁵¹ It can be found at <https://rdm.unimi.it/dataverse-terms-of-use/>

⁵² As of 8 November 2023 <https://dataverse.unimi.it/>

- *Researchers*: 28 dataverses
- *Departments*: 22 dataverses
- *Laboratories*: 16 dataverses
- *Journals*: 16 dataverses

This taxonomy was offered by Dataverse, but it is important for UM because they have different users and stages of users. This taxonomy covers the needs of their researchers and departments.

Currently, there are no strict curation processes for datasets. Researchers will contact UM to create a Dataverse collection based on their needs, and then receive dedicated training to use the Dataverse repository. Then, they are free to upload their datasets. Once deposited, UM will review the metadata and documentation of the datasets to identify any potential issues and then contact the researchers to resolve these problems. In the future, these processes will be planned before publication to ensure better curation and data quality.

In addition, the repository itself is indexed in the re3data platform⁵³. Within the repository, there are 263 datasets, and these datasets have been downloaded widely, accumulating a total of 48,289 downloads⁵⁴. In the OpenAIRE EXPLORE portal, there are 212 research data provided by the Dataverse UNIMI⁵⁵.

The financing of the Dataverse UNIMI came from internal funds. Although developing competencies in the ICT department to manage Dataverse was tried, there was not enough staff to curate and dedicate Dataverse. So, it was chosen to work with a third party. The University authorities decided to fund this part of the research data. In the beginning, this was not with lots of enthusiasm because there was no real awareness about the importance of managing data in a certain way. And now, after four years, this awareness has been reached.

For long-term preservation, UM has developed a project based on the ICT department. This project will be the university data centre that will encompass preserving not only research data, but also various types of data, including those from the library, archives, Health Minister, and administration, among others.

Although specific structural details are not yet available, the HU has been consulted to implement a similar structure. Currently, the project is in the implementation phase and is expected to begin in winter 2024. As part of this project, all data stored in Dataverse will be preserved in the designated data centre for long-term preservation.

Sorbonne University (SU)

The data repository used by SU is a national infrastructure known as Recherche Data Gouv⁵⁶. It consists of creating a national federated research data platform composed of five modules aimed at providing researchers with support services. These modules include a deposit and

⁵³ It can be found at <https://www.re3data.org/repository/r3d100012994>

⁵⁴ As of 8 November 2023 <https://dataverse.unimi.it/>

⁵⁵ Selected parameters: Type (Research data), Source (Dataverse UNIMI). The query can be found at <https://explore.openaire.eu/search/find?type=datasets&resulthostingdatasource=%22re3data%253A%253A45dc559a66c1941d662254de24ec711a%257C%257CDataverse%2520UNIMI%22&page=1>

⁵⁶ The website can be seen at <https://recherche.data.gouv.fr/en>

dissemination service (repository), a catalogue of French research data, and data support services such as data workshops, thematic reference centres, and resource centres attached to Recherche Data Gouv. The goal of RDG is to become an EOSC service that offers access to open and shared research data to support reuse.

Inaugurated in July 2022, the data repository solution is based on Dataverse, which is hosted by the National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment (INRAE). The objective was to offer a sovereign multidisciplinary repository that allows the publication of datasets in an environment ensuring the needs of communities that are not yet equipped with a recognized thematic repository. Instead of creating a completely new solution, this infrastructure recognizes existing solutions used by different disciplines and also proposes an alternative solution for institutions that have not yet implemented their own data repository. Consequently, institutions in France can request the creation of an institutional dataverse space after signing a contract. SU now has its own space on this platform since February 2023⁵⁷.

Although general administration is handled by INRAE, SU's Dataverse space also undergoes its own moderation and curation processes to ensure data quality. Depending on the needs, researchers can get in contact with the Research Data and Digital Humanities Team at the Library before or during the publication of their datasets. A review process is performed after datasets are submitted.

The repository can assign DOIs as perennial identifiers for datasets. While the motivation consists of extending open research data to reuse, an embargo option can be applied to datasets, when necessary. SU's Dataverse space primarily serves users working with or affiliated with SU. Detailed terms of use for the repository can be found on its website⁵⁸.

As of now, the repository contains 10 datasets and there is no subcollection created⁵⁹. Although Dataverse provides a taxonomy for its categories, there is no strict hierarchy implemented in the structure of the repository. It is more flat and subcollections will be created based on the needs of researchers.

Although the process to obtain a trustworthy certification, such as CoreTrustSeal, is in process, RDG does not have a certification right now. However, the repository can be found on the re3data platform⁶⁰ and the national platform itself is indexed on OpenAIRE EXPLORE⁶¹.

To determine the national generic data repository service that would best respond to researchers' requirements, a group of specialists from different disciplinary backgrounds carried out 3 studies in the framework of the Committee for Open Science: [Feasibility study for a generic repository: user requirements](#), [Comparative study of national data services in 6 countries: Australia, Norway, Netherlands, Canada, United Kingdom, Germany](#) and [The ambitions of the service and implementation scenarios](#).⁶²

⁵⁷ It can be accessed through the URL: <https://entrepot.recherche.data.gouv.fr/dataverse/sorbonne-univ>

⁵⁸ Terms of use: <https://recherche.data.gouv.fr/en/page/general-terms-and-conditions>

⁵⁹ As of 8 November 2023 <https://entrepot.recherche.data.gouv.fr/dataverse/sorbonne-univ>

⁶⁰ <https://www.re3data.org/repository/r3d100013931>

⁶¹

<https://explore.openaire.eu/search/dataprovider?datasourceId=re3data::e4cfb545b08f53431fcf0938c7de184b>

⁶² Cited from <https://recherche.data.gouv.fr/en/page/why-recherche-data-gouv>

This RDG project is led by the Ministry of Higher Education and Research for the first three years. It was funded during this same period by the National Fund for Open Science⁶³ with a budget of 7 million euros allocated to the development of the data repository and catalogue, as well as the establishment of data workshops for researchers throughout the country.

Although a long-term preservation plan for research data has not been defined, Recherche Data Gouv's ambition is to become a service of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), thus requiring CoreTrustSeal certification to ensure sustainability for research data archiving and preservation.

The University of Warsaw (UW)

The UW hosts several data repositories within the ICM UW⁶⁴. These repositories include the Institutional Repository for Open Data (RepOD)⁶⁵, the Social Data Repository (RDS)⁶⁶, and the Macromolecular Xtallography Raw Data Repository (MX-RDR)⁶⁷. All of these repositories operate on the Dataverse platform and utilise DOIs as perennial identifiers. While these lack a standardised certification, they are listed on the re3data platform and have data sources available on the OpenAIRE Explore platform⁶⁸. These repositories are open to all interested individuals from all over the world, although in practice most of the clients are researchers from Polish institutions. Data upload by individual researchers does not require signing a contract. Only if an institution is interested in having its institutional collection in the RepOD repository, it is necessary to sign a short agreement. To date, all such agreements have been made with institutions from Poland, but there are no restrictions on concluding such an agreement also with foreign institutions. Therefore, the RepOD can be seen as a national repository solution, as it allows other institutions to create their own Dataverse within.

While the RepOD serves as an interdisciplinary platform for data sharing, offering moderated and curated content, two other repositories are conceived as disciplinary data repositories. Detailed terms of use for the repository can be found on its website⁶⁹. Within the RepOD, 769 datasets can be found; they have reached 130,305 downloads⁷⁰. The RepOD hosts a total of 150 dataverses (collections), which are categorised as follows:

- *Uncategorized*: 79 dataverses
- *Organisation or Institution*: 61 dataverses
- *Research Project*: 5 dataverses
- *Department*: 4 dataverses

⁶³ See more at <https://www.ouvrirlascience.fr/recherche-data-gouv-4/>

⁶⁴ Interdisciplinary Centre for Mathematical and Computational Modelling at University of Warsaw

⁶⁵ The website can be seen at <https://repod.icm.edu.pl/>

⁶⁶ The website can be seen at <https://rds.icm.edu.pl/>

⁶⁷ The website can be seen at <https://mxrdr.icm.edu.pl/>

⁶⁸ The data sources can be consulted successively from OpenAIRE EXPLORE: [RepOD](#), [RDS](#), [MX-RDR](#).

⁶⁹ Terms of use: <https://repod.icm.edu.pl/terms-of-use-page.xhtml>

⁷⁰ As of 8 November 2023 <https://repod.icm.edu.pl/metrics.xhtml>

- *Laboratory*: 1 dataverse

The RDS focuses specifically on the Social Sciences and Humanities discipline. Detailed terms of use for the repository can be found on its website⁷¹. Within the repository, there are 425 datasets, and these datasets have been downloaded widely, accumulating a total of 303,870 downloads⁷². The repository hosts a total of 6 dataverses (collections), which are categorised as follows:

- *Research Projects*: 4 dataverses
- *Organisation or Institution*: 2 dataverses

The MX-RDR repository is specialised in macromolecular crystallography data. It offers researchers a platform to deposit and access raw data. Detailed terms of use for the repository can be found on its website⁷³. Within the repository, there are 414 datasets with a total of 223,365 downloads⁷⁴. The repository hosts 17 dataverses (collections), which are categorised as follows:

- *Researcher*: 8 dataverses
- *Organisation or Institution*: 6 dataverses
- *Departments*: 1 dataverse
- *Laboratories*: 1 dataverse
- *Research Projects*: 1 dataverse

For administration, ICM takes on the role itself for individual researchers. However, they also allow other institutions to create collections within the repository. These institutions can have their own Dataverse collection but do not have administrative access. They can only view records and submit data to the repository. They can create a collection for their home university and advise their researchers about the existence of this collection under RepOD. They inform researchers that they can upload their data to this specific repository collection.

For universities that have not signed a contract with ICM, they can still deposit their data, but it will not be part of a collection. ICM will review the submissions and contact the university if any issues arise. The initial step is to allow researchers from specific domains to publish their data in a dedicated repository rather than a general one. Similarly to the first case, these researchers need to sign an agreement to have space in the repository, with ICM acting as the main administrator.

ICM chose to implement the data repository solution using Dataverse and they have stuck with it. Since Dataverse is an open-source platform, they have the flexibility to customise it according to their needs. The structure of the collection (dataverses) requires approval at the faculty level, as they are responsible for signing any agreements related to the repository. Therefore, faculty would need to request approval and higher management would likely be

⁷¹ Terms of use: <https://rds.icm.edu.pl/terms-of-use-page.xhtml>

⁷² As of 8 November 2023 <https://rds.icm.edu.pl/metrics.xhtml>

⁷³ Terms of use: <https://mxrdr.icm.edu.pl/terms-of-use-page.xhtml>

⁷⁴ As of 8 November 2023 <https://mxrdr.icm.edu.pl/metrics.xhtml>

involved in the signing process. In many cases, it may not be the laboratory that is signing up with ICM directly. Instead, a researcher working in the laboratory would need to discuss the data upload and publication process with his supervisor, who would then sign up for the repository space on behalf of the laboratory.

The financing solution for the data repository at ICM comes from the European Union's Operational Program Digital Poland, which was active from 2014 to 2020. As beneficiaries of this program, the digital library in the UW was also built within the same framework. The current maintenance costs are likely also included in the ICM budget.

Regarding long-term preservation, ICM has planned five years since the completion of the system updates to the latest version. After this timeframe, they may need to seek additional funding. The source of this funding is uncertain, as it could potentially come from the government or programs such as Horizon Europe.

2.3.4.3. Financing Solutions

The financing options for data repositories in the universities examined demonstrate several general approaches to funding such repositories. These approaches can provide insights and options for other institutions looking to finance their data repositories:

1. **Internal Budget Allocation:** HU, UM, and UCPH allocate funds from their internal budgets to support the development and maintenance of their data repositories. This funding might come either directly from the faculty or from the library itself. This approach relies on the university's resources and demonstrates the institution's commitment to research data management.
2. **National Funding:** In the case of national repositories (SU, UCPH, CU), the funding for data repositories is provided by the Ministry and government bodies. Third-party sources and the federal state might allocate some funds for creating discipline-based repositories nationwide (HU). These initiatives demonstrate the recognition of the importance of open science and research data management at the national level, with dedicated funds allocated to support repository infrastructure and related initiatives. This funding constitutes a pioneering movement for institutions to create such a repository. Institutions must eventually develop and adapt these structures to meet their needs and financing.
3. **European Union Funding:** European Union programs and some initiatives between the EU, such as Horizon Europe, can make a call for projects to support the development and improvement of FAIR data repositories (CU, UW) in relation to EOSC. As an option, institutions can leverage EU programs to obtain financial support for building and maintaining data repositories. For example, the HORIZON-INFRA-2024-EOSC-01-03⁷⁵ call which consists of enabling a network of EOSC federated and trustworthy repositories and enhancing the framework of generic and discipline-specific services for data and other research digital objects.

⁷⁵ The call can be seen at <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/horizon-infra-2024-eosc-01-03> .

Institutions need to explore a combination of these funding options, adapt them to their specific contexts, and seek long-term sustainability beyond the initial funding sources. Additionally, collaboration with other stakeholders, such as research funders and international organisations, can also provide additional financial support for data repository initiatives.

2.3.4.4. Long-term preservation Plan

The long-term preservation of research data is a crucial aspect of ensuring its accessibility, usability, and authenticity for the future. While some universities have implemented preservation solutions, explicit plans are not always in place to ensure these solutions. In many cases, repositories are financed through short-term projects, which may not include provisions for long-term preservation lasting beyond a decade.

UCPH already has two archival solutions at the institute level. The Electronic Research Data Archive (ERDA) and the Sensitive Information Facility (SIF) serve as a storage service and also offer an archiving feature, allowing data freezing for long-term preservation. At HU, in addition to the existence of various preservations, heiARCHIVE will function as a preservation infrastructure for the university. Collaborating with the HU, the UM is working on an ongoing project to create a robust archiving infrastructure. These initiatives reflect the dedication of the universities to establish effective long-term preservation solutions for their valuable research data.

Although explicit long-term preservation plans may not be in place for some national data repositories, they recognize its importance and are actively seeking solutions. Many repositories have pursued CoreTrustSeal certification, a community-accepted trust indicator that requires a clear and effective long-term preservation strategy⁷⁶. National services often aim to merge with EOSC services, emphasising the need to secure long-term preservation for data integration and sustainability.

However, universities and national infrastructures must prioritise the formulation and implementation of explicit and robust long-term preservation strategies. By doing so, they can protect research data for generations to come. The CoreTrustSeal, as an example of a widely recognized certification, sets a standard for repositories to follow in terms of data management and preservation. By aligning with these practices, universities and national data repositories can ensure that their data are managed, preserved, and made accessible in a sustainable and reliable manner.

2.3.4.5. Limitations of Milestone 4

The analysis was limited to the 4EU+ university level, which restricts the comparison of data repositories at the European level. Additionally, the limited time available for this examination resulted in a constrained and generalised approach.

⁷⁶ CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board. (2022). CoreTrustSeal Requirements 2023-2025 (V01.00). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7051012>

2.3.4.6. Conclusions

In this research on data repositories implemented in each 4EU+ university, we conducted a comprehensive analysis of the available repositories and their key characteristics.

Similarities:

- The majority of the universities utilise the Dataverse platform for their data repositories, allowing DOI assignment and supporting various types of datasets.
- All universities indicated that their repositories underwent some form of moderation or curation process to ensure the quality and reliability of the data.
- While there is an emphasis on open data for its (re)use, the embargo option can be applied to datasets, when needed, in most of the repositories.
- All repositories have defined terms of use and access policies, ensuring that data usage adheres to established guidelines.
- The Re3data platform serves as a common indexing platform for most of the repositories, facilitating findability and visibility.

Differences:

- Although most of the data repositories are institutional-based, discipline-based repositories can be found at some universities.
- The repositories were primarily offered to users affiliated with the respective universities, although some repositories extended access to external members or individuals involved in international projects.
- The host institution for data repositories varies depending on the university structure.
- The number of Dataverse collections and datasets in each repository varies significantly, with some universities offering a wide range of Dataverse collections and datasets, while others have fewer collections.
- The certification status varies among the repositories.
- The availability of data on OpenAIRE EXPLORE also differs, with some repositories having datasets indexed, while others are yet to be registered.

Furthermore, we observed that financial solutions for establishing and maintaining these repositories differed between universities, ranging from support through national infrastructures to self-funded initiatives. Additionally, long-term preservation plans varied in their consideration and implementation. While some repositories have detailed financial solutions and long-term preservation plans, others may still be in the process of developing or considering these aspects. Additionally, the number of people involved in the maintenance and sustainability of the platforms varies between universities.

In conclusion, the research demonstrates the diverse landscape of data repositories within the 4EU+ universities, highlighting both common practices and unique approaches. These findings provide valuable insights for enhancing research data management and the FAIR data principles within the 4EU+ Alliance.

2.3.5. Good practices

In the course of the work on Case #1, a selection and description of the best or most inspiring practices in RDM and FAIR data in terms of services, infrastructure, and training has been carried out (full description in tables below).

Good practices in services:

- CU: The Open Science Support Centre
- UCPH: Data Labs
- HU: Competence Centre for Research Data
- UM: Single point of reference for data management plan support
- SU: SACADO Service Unit (Service d'Aide au Calcul et à l'Analyse de Données / Computing and Data Analysis Support Service).

Good practices in training:

- UCPH: DMP workshop for Horizon fellows
- UCPH: Data Carpentries
- UCPH: Research data management course for Bachelor and Master Students
- SU: Training for doctoral candidates and scientists – MOOC Open Science / La Science Ouverte
- UW: Training sessions for doctoral candidates and scientists and general university courses for students developing their knowledge on open science issues.

Good practices in infrastructure:

- HU: heiDATA
- SU: Recherche Data Gouv (RDG), an ecosystem for sharing and opening research data
- UW: Project 'Disciplinary Open Research Data Repositories' (DRODB).

Charles University (CU)

This project has received funding from
The European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme
under grant agreement No 101016674

Name of the initiative	The Open Science Support Centre
Use case	Specialised unit for support of Open Access/Research Data Management/Open Science on a central university level.
Type of initiative	Organisational; Research Support
Organiser of the initiative	Central Library of Charles University
Scope and objectives	<p>The Open Science Support Centre was created in 2020 as part of CU's initiative to improve its research environment. Activities were initially divided into two main parts, open access (OA) and open data. Open access activities were related mainly to APC monitoring and distribution of OA tokens. Both are connected to OA transformation agreements that are being negotiated by the Czech national centre for access to electronic information resources, CzechELib.</p> <p>The goal of the Open Data part of the project was to map existing/potential research data in the University and to create the environment for the successful implementation of the institutional data repository. Over time the focus shifted from Open Data to more general Research Data Management, which should in the end help to create FAIR Data.</p> <p>Both parts are also involved in Open Science evangelization, which includes providing educational materials, training, and consultations.</p>
Implementation	<p>The work of the Centre can be divided into three main areas of activities: analysis, providing support, and communication. The Centre analyses requirements regarding Open Science policies & requirements (e.g., funder requirements), existing solutions, and tools. The goal is not to create everything from scratch but rather to identify and reuse existing best practices.</p> <p>Then it provides support, mostly in the form of information materials, training, and consultations. Materials are available online and freely. The Centre is also involved in the further development of university policies, infrastructure, and the definition of recommended best practices.</p> <p>As Open Science is not yet well established in Czechia, communication and advocating for it is also a very important task of the Centre. It includes communication within the university (e.g. researchers, project teams, etc.) but also with partners, both national and international. These activities include strong participation in Czech EOSC initiatives.</p>
Capacity	The Centre was established as a brand new unit, with most of the staff being hired at the beginning of the project. Library background was not necessary, which allowed to hire more people with some hands-on research experience (e.g. doctoral candidates). As the agenda of the

	<p>Centre widened over time, a lawyer with specialisation in copyright was also added to the team. Currently, three members of the Centre work on the research data-related agenda, two work on Open Access topics on the central level. There are also several part-time Open Access coordinators working at the faculties. The role of the Centre is growing, as faculties cannot create their specialised units.</p> <p>Activities of the Centre shift over time from analyses to providing direct support, ranging from Open Access, Data Management Plan and Open Science consultations provided to researchers to training and preparation of supporting materials for other University units (e.g., project departments).</p>
<p>Impact</p>	<p>As Open Science increases in importance and value in Europe, the Open Science Support Centre provides services that would otherwise be missing. Creating the Centre gave the CU a head start (in comparison to most of other Czech institutions) and allowed it to be better prepared for new requirements, which are slowly being implemented even in the Czech Republic.</p> <p>The Centre was also able to establish a new role for the Central Library inside the University, e.g., in providing Research Data Management training and support. The Library is now also involved in discussions about the University’s research data infrastructure and the participation of CU in EOSC activities.</p> <p>Establishing the Centre on the level of rectorate allows all faculties to use its services, though it may result in capacity shortages over time. The Centre can also facilitate communication between groups that are from different domains/faculties but are similarly interested in Open Science practices. On the other hand, the central unit is to some extent more limited in direct access to researchers and students.</p> <p>We expect that the role of the Open Science Support Centre will become more established over time, with clearer responsibilities in the areas of Open Access, Research Data Management, and finally Open Science in a broad sense. The potential for providing more domain-specific services will likely grow over time and there should be some research support structure accommodating them. One of the examples may be the establishment of a new profession – Data Steward – within research teams, which will be a topic in the coming months and in which the Centre is involved.</p>

The University of Copenhagen (UCPH)

<p>Name of the initiative</p>	<p>University of Copenhagen (UCPH) Data Labs</p>
<p>Use case</p>	<p>A network of faculty support centres to support data science across the university.</p>
<p>Type of initiative</p>	<p>Faculty support centres</p>

This project has received funding from The European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016674

Organiser of the initiative	University of Copenhagen																								
Links	https://research.ku.dk/facilities/datalabs/																								
Scope and objectives	<p>At the University of Copenhagen five Data Labs have been established: four at various faculties and one at the central IT department. The overarching aim of the UCPH Data Labs is to support and strengthen the data science capacity at UCPH, with respect for professional diversity and the various technological needs and starting points found in the faculties. The UCPH Data Labs have employed a minimum of 2 FTE of data scientists and data stewards per lab, whose role it is to offer assistance to researchers in data science projects in the research discipline carried out at the faculty: Science, Health, Social Sciences, as well as Humanities, Law and Theology (the latter three combined in one Lab, Figure 1).</p> <div data-bbox="507 779 1342 1238" data-label="Figure"> <table border="1"> <caption>Total number of requests in 2021</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Request Topic</th> <th>Number of Requests</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Data Analysis</td> <td>20</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Data Collection</td> <td>11</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Database</td> <td>8</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Project Application</td> <td>8</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Website</td> <td>6</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Python</td> <td>6</td> </tr> <tr> <td>R</td> <td>3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Computing power</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Data Visualization</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Info</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Licenses</td> <td>1</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> </div> <p><i>Figure 1. Total number of requests to the South Campus Data Lab for Theology, Humanities & Law in 2021, divided by request topic</i></p> <p>The fifth data lab in the IT department offers support in accessing and using data infrastructure including local, national, and international HPC facilities. In the future, it is the expectation that the data science support given will be expanded with support in data management, as is already the case in some of the Data Labs. In addition to supporting the Data Labs, they also provide training and workshops for researchers and doctoral students on topics such as statistics, R programming, Python, and more (Table 1).</p>	Request Topic	Number of Requests	Data Analysis	20	Data Collection	11	Database	8	Project Application	8	Website	6	Python	6	R	3	Computing power	2	Data Visualization	1	Info	1	Licenses	1
Request Topic	Number of Requests																								
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Info	1																								
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WORKSHOPS AND EVENTS IN THE FIRST HALF OF 2021

EVENT	Serge Belongi presents AI pioneer centre
LONG COURSE	Python café
WORKSHOP	Introduction to statistics course
WORKSHOP	Python programming introductory course
WORKSHOP	Web scraping in Python
WORKSHOP	Data Analysis with R
WORKSHOP	Social Media Data Collection
WORKSHOP	Database design principles & implementation
WORKSHOP	Data Visualization

Table 1. The events programme by the South Campus Data Lab for Theology, Humanities & Law in the first half of 2021

The Data Labs were established as a direct result of UCPH’s Strategy 2023 ‘Talent and Collaboration’, which expresses a desire to strengthen positive development within the research based on data science methods. The establishment and operation of the Data Labs is financed by the university's strategic funds in its first four years, 2020-2024. At the beginning of 2024, faculties are expected to take over financing of the Data Labs. Some faculties have already invested in the data labs by hiring additional staff beyond the 2 FTE originally allocated to them.

Implementation

Steps:

Two of the labs were already existing to some extent when the data lab programme kicked-off, and therefore only needed to adjust their scope to fit the programme. The other two labs and the IT lab had to be established from scratch.

Reference groups with researchers were established at the faculties to examine local needs for data science support and to determine the main focus of the data lab in question. The profiles of the data scientists to be hired in the labs were determined in part based on the input of the reference group. It has been valuable to have a reference group, not only in the start-up phase but also during the first two years of running the lab. They work as both a sounding board for the lab staff for new ideas and to help prioritise support request types (and which tasks cannot be supported). Furthermore, the reference group at the South Campus Data Lab determined that resources should be used predominantly to support researchers who are ‘beginners’ in data science, although there are collaborations with experienced colleagues as well.

Strong support from faculty leadership is important not just to raise awareness of the data lab but also to guarantee some continuity of services in the long run. At least two Deans have already committed to

	<p>continue funding their local data lab after the central funding runs out in 2024.</p> <p><i>Challenge:</i></p> <p>Getting known is a continuous challenge for the datalab: It is a challenge to raise awareness of the existence of laboratories. It is hard to reach researchers with information about the lab as a support point for consultations, help with research design, workshops, and programming help because communication channels are limited. Due to a strong communication policy at UCPH, most labs can only use the email list they have themselves built up from people who have contacted them earlier, in addition to the occasional news item on the intranet pages and the newsletter. The labs, therefore, see many of the same researchers, using their services over and over, instead of new people. Therefore, it also becomes relevant to discuss whether there should be a limit to the amount of resources used to support individual researchers.</p>
<p>Capacity</p>	<p>Each lab has been given funding for 2 FTE to hire data scientists, as well as funds for the running of the lab and equipment. These funds can be used in different ways, e.g. by hiring full-time data scientists, or part-time researchers, and/or possibly supplemented with student assistants. Additionally, at some faculties, the faculty leadership decided to provide additional funding and hire additional staff.</p>
<p>Impact</p>	<p>Feedback from the South Campus data lab:</p> <p>All contact with researchers is registered and tagged, so it is clear which departments we support, with how many resources, and what the typical needs are for these departments. When we run workshops, they usually have a small number of participants. Having groups of 3-6 researchers sit together and discuss gives good dynamics during workshops and opens up for tailoring of the workshop content to the level of expertise of the researchers and, to some extent, also to their type of data.</p> <p>The awareness of our lab consultations about data management, GDPR compliance, and safe storage of data is gradually increasing, aided by an increased international focus in these areas with increasing demands.</p> <p><i>Next steps</i></p> <p>The lab plans to extend their support to also cover Master students so that they can help supervisors with the data management support part of MA projects.</p> <p><i>Lessons learned</i></p> <p>The most important lesson learned is that the lab must be visible both digitally and physically. Having a physical spot where people can show up, centrally and visually located on campus is very important. Visibility/information about the lab that reaches the researchers is very important.</p>

Name of the initiative	Research data management course for Bachelor and Master Students
Use case	An online course on research data management for students in preparation for their Bachelor and Master project.
Type of initiative	Educational Programme
Organiser of the initiative	The University of Copenhagen
Scope and objectives	<p>The University of Copenhagen Strategy 2023, Talent and Cooperation, prioritises the education of students in digital skills. All BA students across the University of Copenhagen must obtain a broad basic knowledge of key concepts within digitalisation. They must be able to relate to digitization reflectively and use the digital tools and methods that they encounter in their studies. The students must build on the basic digital competences through their master's programmes, so that strong UCPH graduates can fit into a digitised labour market.</p> <p>As a result of the priorities set out in the strategy, UCPH initiated a large project for education in digital skills. One of the main aims of the project is to set up an online course room for course materials related to five main topics that were deemed relevant to all students regardless of their discipline:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Data management 2. Scientific digital information retrieval 3. Technological understanding 4. Digital reflection 5. Digital research methods. <p>For each topic, various materials will be made available online, at the latest in the summer of 2023. This material can be in the form of very short single modules on a specific topic or a larger course. The material can be used standalone by the students themselves or can be incorporated by teachers in their teaching material, supplemented with discipline-specific content.</p> <p>As part of Topic #1 on data management, two larger courses have already been developed:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) for students 2. Research data management for students. <p>The latter course is specifically intended for Bachelor and Master students who are about to start their projects. The course is aligned with UCPH's new data management policy (University of Copenhagen, Policy for Research Data Management)⁷⁷, which also applies to students. The course includes modules on data management plans, rights to data, ethical and legal approvals, data documentation,</p>

⁷⁷ https://research.ku.dk/integrity/documents/UCPH_Policy_for_Research_Data_Management_2022.pdf

	<p>storage and security, data sharing, and data preservation. A data management plan (DMP) template was developed for students (it is a shorter version of the UCPH DMP template for employees). After each module, students are asked to fill in the part of the DMP template that corresponds to that module, to have a complete DMP to discuss with their supervisors by the time they complete the course. In addition, the course contains animations and video interviews with students across the university, as well as their supervisors. Also, quizzes in each module as well as practical tips on where to find resources at the university have been applied.</p>
<p>Implementation</p>	<p>The course is about to be finalised and has already been deposited on UCPH's online learning platform. The next step is implementation. It will be up to the individual faculties and study programmes to determine how the course is implemented. They will have to determine whether the course will be mandatory locally, and if so, how and for whom. They also need to develop local communication strategies to raise awareness about the course among students. It is also very important to include activities targeted at supervisors, to ensure that supervisors know what their responsibilities are in supervising students in data management (as described in our policy) and to make sure that they have access to support and further guidance when needed. Finally, supervisors should be encouraged to recommend the course to students when conducting a research project in their research group.</p>
<p>Capacity</p>	<p>The course content was developed in a collaboration between the university's departments for education, research and innovation and the university library. UCPH's centre for online and blended learning was responsible for the course platform and all visual material. As mentioned above, the course was financed using strategic funds from the university, as part of a larger project aimed at education in digital skills.</p> <p>All employees, as well as Bachelor students (21,000+) and Master students (15,000+), will be able to access the course material.</p>
<p>Impact</p>	<p>The course in research data management will be evaluated after 8 months, in summer 2023. For this purpose, we conducted interviews with existing student and supervisor focus groups. Based on their feedback, we edited and updated the course and added information where necessary. Accordingly, we were able to update information about a new T-drive for students to store data that was implemented by UCPH's IT department over the summer. A review of the course material is planned yearly.</p> <p>It is too early to measure the success and impact of the implementation of the course, as the course has just been finalised and is yet to be officially implemented.</p>

Name of the initiative	Data Carpentries
Use case	Educational framework to train staff, students, and researchers in foundational coding and data science skills
Type of initiative	Framework for workshops and pedagogy.
Organiser of the initiative	Copenhagen University Library, collaboration between the library Data Lab and Researcher Support.
Relevant links	The Carpentries project main website: https://carpentries.org/ Data carpentry website: https://datacarpentry.org/ Example of material used in teaching session: https://kubdatalab.github.io/2022-04-26-DC-HUM/
Scope and objectives	<p>The Carpentries project is an international project that offers training and curricula in foundational data science skills in three programmes: Library Carpentry which is tailored to working with bibliographic data; Data Carpentry which provides fundamental data skills needed to conduct research. The mission is to provide high-quality, domain-specific training for researchers covering the full lifecycle of data-driven research. Finally, there is Software Carpentry for research computing and software development. At the UCPH the library cooperates with Library Carpentry and Data Carpentry.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The aim is to support digital skills primarily of students of research staff. • The level in data cleaning and analysis is introductory; the software OpenRefine, GitBash; Unix Shell, Python, and R Studio are used. • We link to and coordinate with other digital skills initiatives at the library, the development of eLearning modules, and the development of the competences of the library staff. <p>The following is offered:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carpentry workshops over 2 full days, • Single lessons focused on cross-disciplinary application, • Participation in the teaching network based at the library data lab, • Participation in regional carpentry meetings, • Participation in external carpentry workshops, • Further development of carpentry teaching materials and training instructors (train the trainers) are being prepared.
Capacity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UCPH has funded Silver membership in the Carpentry consortia. Silver membership gives us the possibility to educate five staff members as instructors per year, hold two workshops organised

centrally by the Carpentries, as many self-organised workshops as we like, and have membership on the board, with voting rights.

- The library has allocated a budget of DKK 30,000 (4,000 euros) to fund workshops for students, including refreshments, materials, hotel, and travel for external instructors.
- Currently, there are eight instructors, two from the library’s research support, three from the library’s data lab (representing the Sciences, Humanities and Social Sciences), one from the sister organisation, Roskilde University, one from the library of the Social Sciences and one from the library of the Health Sciences.
- When a carpentry workshop is run, it is advertised through the central carpentry community channels, and a call for instructors is sent out. Accordingly, any instructor from around the world can volunteer to teach at the workshop (particularly if the event is online). Also, a budget to pay an instructor from the Nordic Countries or European countries that are close by, to fly in and teach at the workshop if the staff of the UCPH is missing the skills within their department, has been negotiated.
- UCPH has reached out to the Technical University of Denmark (DTU). A librarian at DTU has completed the instructor training in her own time. UCPH wishes to establish a solid collaboration practice, to support each other’s teaching skills and learn together. A nationwide workshop on data science skills has been applied to hold.
- UCPH is a member of the Nordic Carpentry node, the members meet monthly and discuss teaching methods, workshops to be carried out, and skills to be learned.

Implementation

Challenges and opportunities

Timing:

Carpentries are designed as a workshop over two consecutive days, where the trainees take a generic data set through its cleaning and analysis process. The main challenge for a learner (a student, a researcher, or a colleague) is to take two whole days out of his calendar to participate in the workshop.

Generic vs. relevance:

The Carpentries have been conducted for two years. Initially, it only recognised workshops that followed the rigid two-day structure using carpentry data. Through meetings with Carpentries central administration and talking about experiences gathered, the Carpentries are opening up to break the workshops into single lessons offered over different days and tailored to the disciplinary interests of the learners.

- As the confidence of the staff in the teaching materials has increased, it was possible to adapt and use their own materials and data sets. The curricula are open and available in GitHub repositories.
- Future ambition is to develop complete course material in the **Carpentry Incubator**. The incubator is a GitHub repository where new materials can be peer-reviewed, adapted, and developed before becoming part of the core Carpentry curricula.

	<p><i>Budget</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The budget, while welcome at the beginning of the project, is not necessary. • The two-day workshop format did not appear to be a good fit for the users. Rather, single lessons with data tailored to their disciplines are far more attractive. <p><i>Organisational challenges</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The learning curve was steep and a lot of time and energy had to be invested in learning the software necessary to teach, maintain, and develop new skills as well as learning new teaching pedagogies by the teaching staff. Being able to devote time to the learning process and develop a culture around teaching, required written agreement and understanding from the line managers. In a pilot in 2019, the amount of time staff used on developing their digital competencies and implementing the Carpentry didactic approach of teaching in teams was criticised. More recently, however, the need to be able to maintain skills and to have the time to develop such practices is being verbalised more and more by leadership, so the library can support users' digital skills. • Another challenge is a cultural change within our organisation. We have introduced our colleagues to data science skills and relevant software for their everyday work. However, the feedback UCPH most commonly receives is that the software is really useful and that users can see its potential. However, they do not have time to learn new software or workflow, so they stick to the (unreliable) software with which they already work.
<p>Impact</p>	<p>Lessons learned:</p> <p><i>From project to operation</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By holding workshops, we have become more visible in the university landscape. Teachers have started to recommend to their students to participate and the workshops have been embedded into curricula, where the librarians perform as Teaching Assistants (TAs). Being embedded allows librarians to use their skills and knowledge rather than carpentry material. • Carpentries has provided librarians with a useful teaching pedagogy that has helped to come in closer contact with researchers and students. The librarians are outgrowing the core carpentry material and need to rethink their membership in the Carpentry community. • Getting colleagues to take the instructor's education is a challenge. Commitment to the learning process is still an issue, as in practice there is little time on the day to nurture digital skills and learn. • The carpentry project is now in operation, where the librarians have to reach countable KPIs and work with strategies. KPIs from the leadership include a certain number of workshops and a certain number of trained trainers per year. The challenge is to make visible the impact of the teaching that typically comes a long time after the

workshop. The learners take part in a workshop or lesson, but first at a later date start using their skills in a project. The future points to tailor-made lessons held over a shorter period, focus on the development of Open Educational resources in GitHub and increased collaboration on a national level. Furthermore, we wish to improve in digital skills in the Humanities and Social Sciences, such as image analysis and webscraping.

Name of the initiative	DMP workshop for Horizon fellows
Use case	Support Horizon fellows with the drafting of their data management plan, to be submitted as a deliverable.
Type of initiative	Workshop
Organiser of the initiative	University of Copenhagen
Scope and objectives	<p>As of 31 December 2021, UCPH had more than 500 projects funded under Horizon 2020 or ERC. This means that many UCPH researchers must address requirements for data management and Open Science imposed by the European Commission, including the requirement to make data management plans, share data openly at the end of the project, and produce data according to the FAIR principles. As these concepts are relatively new to most researchers, data management plan workshops are given twice a year. The target audience is Horizon and ERC fellows as well as coordinators and research support staff.</p> <p>In about 5 hours, the workshop covers the following topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Open Science, Open Access, and Open Research Data ● The FAIR principles for research data ● Requirements in Horizon Europe and ERC ● Data Management Plans (DMPs): the Horizon Europe template questions explained ● What to include in your own data management plan ● Who to contact at your faculty for help and guidance ● Data management support and tools are available at UCPH <p>The workshop consists of presentations mixed with exercises and discussions aimed at helping researchers understand central concepts and relate them to their own research. We have formulated a mix of fictional and real answers to the questions to give researchers some examples and help them understand how to address the questions. At</p>

	<p>the end of the workshop, researchers should be able to draft their own DMP.</p> <p>This workshop is a collaboration between the University of Copenhagen and the Copenhagen University Library (a separate organisation). A funding support expert at the University of Copenhagen coordinates and arranges the course and contacts the network of funding support staff throughout the university. Experts in research data management run the workshop, present the topics, and guide the exercises. After the workshop these experts read through and give feedback to the finalised data management plans.</p>
<p>Implementation</p>	<p>The workshop has been run since 2018 and the content has been gradually adjusted over time to become increasingly interactive. It is clear that researchers find the questions in the Horizon DMP template hard to answer. It was therefore crucial to explain the underlying concepts (e.g. FAIR principles) thoroughly and provide examples taken from different disciplines on how the questions can be addressed.</p> <p>Two years ago, an employee of the research executive agency (REA – they evaluate Horizon DMPs) was interviewed to learn about the underlying ideas for the requirements of the European Commission for DMPs and to learn about the procedures REA uses to evaluate the DMP. This has provided further insight into how to draft a DMP, and these insights were presented to researchers.</p> <p><i>Challenges</i></p> <p>A recurring challenge is always to raise enough awareness for the workshop. The university library staff member contacts the funding support network across UCPH far in advance and asks them to tell researchers who have just started new EU funding about our workshop. But in addition to this, and occasionally posting a news item on our intranet pages and in our course catalogue, we do not have many tools to raise awareness.</p> <p>A second challenge is the diversity in the baseline data management expertise of our workshop attendees. Some are Marie Curie fellows just out of their doctoral studies, others are professors on an ERC grant. Some researchers do not recognize their research output as ‘data’ (e.g., our postdocs in law) and attend the course first to find out what data management is. There are also some support staff who do not actually do any research themselves but are there because they do the reporting on the project. This heterogeneity means that we cannot be too detailed or discipline-specific with our explanations or examples, even though this is what attendees like to see. We need to find a balance between being too specific and not being specific enough.</p>
<p>Capacity</p>	<p>The workshop is run twice per year, with a maximum capacity of about 30 attendees. One-third of the attendees typically are either data</p>

	management or research support staff, or coordinators for a large network programme funded through Horizon.
Impact	<p>Surveys are sent to examine satisfaction after each workshop. The respondents indicated that they were very satisfied with the content. They indicated that they especially appreciated all the examples given and the explanation of key concepts. They continue to ask for more discipline-specific examples. In response to this demand, an annotated Horizon Europe template with discipline-specific examples of answers is planned to be prepared. A guide for each of the Horizon Europe DMP questions has been developed, which is available to researchers via DMPonline.</p> <p>The impact of the workshop has not been systematically examined, but the workshop has had a positive effect on the quality of the DMPs produced by the UCPH researchers. This conclusion follows from the comparison of the data management plans sent to the library for feedback from researchers who have attended the workshop vs. researchers who have not attended it. Researchers who have attended the workshop usually provide good DMPs that do not require a lot of feedback. Researchers who do not attend the workshop typically struggle with some of the questions in the DMP, in particular, concerning the FAIR principles.</p>

Heidelberg University (HU)

Name of the initiative	Heidelberg University - Competence Centre for Research Data
Use case	Institutionalisation of RDM support in the university by installing a single point of contact for counselling services and relevant technical infrastructures (e.g., a data repositories).
Type of initiative	Service unit
Organiser of the initiative	University Library & University Computing Centre
Scope and objectives	The Competence Centre for Research Data, a joint service facility of the University Library and the University Computing Centre, provides support for a comprehensive and coherent management of research data. Its services cover the whole research data lifecycle, including software tools for data processing, cloud-based services for file sharing, facilities for large scale data storage as well as options for data publication and long-term preservation. In addition, the University's Scientific Software Centre provides support for the sustainable development of research software.
Implementation	The Competence Centre was established in 2014, and has since continuously expanded its range of services and campus coverage.

This project has received funding from The European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016674

	<p>Central challenges (which have only been partially solved so far) are the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • to make the services offered and the relevance of RDM widely known in a large campus, • to scale up both capacity and expertise as demand grows, • to provide appropriate advice as a generic service centre in each case without being specialised in the respective research field, • to acquire the necessary funds.
Capacity	<p>The University Library and the University Computing Centre allocated six employees to the Competence Centre for Research Data, though not full-time, with expertise in data management, publication, services of the Library and Computing Centre as well as legal issues and grant applications.</p> <p>Additional staff is involved in projects, especially in the context of the National Research Data Infrastructure, the national specialised information services, and a coordination project of the Federal State.</p> <p>At the policymaking level of the university, a Planning Group for Research Data Management has been installed to develop an implementation plan for comprehensive research data management, with basic services that are compatible with discipline-specific requirements and needs.</p>
Impact	<p>The creation of the Competence Centre has helped to structure and systematise research data management on campus. There is now a central point of contact for projects and researchers that provides generic support services. In this regard, the university has been a forerunner in various respects, e.g., in setting up institutional data repositories.</p> <p>The current development is driven by two aspects: First, the interlinking of the institutional offerings with the subject consortia of the National Research Data Infrastructure, and second, the well-planned further evolution of the structures on campus based on the results of the Research Data Management Planning Group.</p> <p>On the technical side, in turn, one focus of the work is on implementing a more comprehensive structure for long-term digital preservation.</p>

Name of the initiative	Infrastructure - Heidelberg University - heiDATA
Use case	Institutional research data repository that also serves as a subject repository for certain humanities disciplines.
Type of initiative	Repository
Organiser of the initiative	University Library & University Computing Centre

This project has received funding from The European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016674

<p>Scope and objectives</p>	<p>The heiDATA is the Heidelberg University research data repository. It is managed by the Competence Centre for Research Data (KFD), a joint research data service infrastructure of the Heidelberg University Library and the University Computing Centre.</p> <p>The heiDATA offers a publication venue for open research data to the following communities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • researchers from Heidelberg University, • researchers from the fields of art history, classical studies and South Asian studies who cooperate with the Specialized Information Services for Art-Photography-Design (arthistoricum.net), Classical Studies (Propylaeum) and South Asian Studies (FID4SA) funded by the DFG, • researchers publishing with Heidelberg University Publishing (heiUP) and other open access platforms maintained by Heidelberg University Library, who want to make research data underlying their publications publicly available.
<p>Implementation</p>	<p>The heiDATA was established in 2014. The service enjoys increasing demand and publishes more and more datasets every year. The service is based on the open-source repository software Dataverse.</p> <p>An essential characteristic of the approach to institutional data publication pursued in Heidelberg is the taking over of data curation activities by the Competence Centre. The aim here is to prepare the datasets during the ingest process in such a way that they are available in a form that allows long-term preservation of the data. This includes e.g. checking and validating file formats. In some cases, datasets are converted to archival formats prior to publication. Support is also provided for improving the subject-specific documentation of the dataset through appropriate metadata and controlled vocabularies, in close consultation with researchers.</p>
<p>Capacity</p>	<p>The heiDATA offers the following features:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • persistent and citable addressing of data via DOI's, • individual authorization and licence models for data access, • linking between research data and related publications, • archiving of various file formats, • flexible and configurable metadata schema with controlled vocabularies, • provision of metadata for external catalogues and databases, • based on the Open Source Software Dataverse, • indexing of all data sets and respective data citations in the Data Citation Index (part of Clarivate Analytics' Web of Science) and Google Dataset Search, as well as in further national and international databases. <p>There was no additional funding to build the service, but the library and the computer centre shifted resources to create it.</p>

Impact	<p>In the first years, one of the main tasks was to acquire customers and raise awareness among researchers about Open Science and research data management. This has become less necessary in the meantime.</p> <p>Currently, the requirements are increasing with regard to the growing number of datasets and the growing volume of data. In addition, the expansion of heiDATA as a subject-specific data publication platform for NFDI4Culture and the subject information services also brings new challenges (e.g., with regard to implementing better support for controlled vocabularies).</p> <p>Currently, certification with the Core Trust Seal is intended to further advance professionalisation.</p>
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The University of Milan

Name of the initiative	Service - Single point of reference for data management plan support
Use case	Create and provide support to researchers on all dimensions covered by Data management plans
Type of initiative	Definition of a working group in which specific skills are involved according to the needs of the Research Project Leader who is to write the DMP (ethics, IP, bibliographic metadata, privacy, data security).
Organiser of the initiative	The University of Milan, in particular, Open Science Support Office, DPO Support Office, Research Integrity Support Office, Technology Transfer Office (TTO).
Scope and objectives	The topic of data management is relatively new in Italy and there are still no specific policies and no specific figures at the national level or at the level of individual institutions for data management and RDM support. The University of Milan has understood the need for the support of its researchers on hitherto unfamiliar issues and has moved on several fronts: policies, training, tools, and advice. In order to offer effective support for researchers who have to comply with requirements of the funding agencies, the University of Milan thought of pooling the expertise present in different fields and creating one flexible group. The ultimate goal is to be able to assist researchers at all stages and in all areas covered by the DMP, offering them a single interface.
Implementation	The interviews were conducted in the 33 departments of the university. From the analysis of the responses, a list of skills needed was created, and these skills have been identified within the university staff. The experts were identified and contacted, and the rationale of the project was shared with them along with the most important documents and guidelines (EC documents and UM policies). A website was created containing basic information on RDM and DMP

	<p>https://rdm.unimi.it/dmp/, an email box was created where the working group can be reached and can decide which expert should answer. When a researcher is asked to produce a DMP, the research unit contacts the single point of reference. A quick analysis of the project and the data part is done, and the skills needed to best support the writing of the DMP are identified. As needed, the experts of the working group respond by email or in one-to-one meetings. As needed, experts from the working group respond by email or in individual meetings and accompany the PI in drafting the DMP. When the DMP is ready, it is read again by the working group for a final check.</p> <p>The project that is dedicated to doctoral students and their mentors deserves specific mention.</p> <p>The Single Point of Reference supported the drafting of 10 DMPs of doctoral students in 2021 and 2022. In addition, the tutors were involved in creating specific expertise within departments. A joint training course was organised on RDM and FAIR data and the use of dataverse (the repository for UM data). Joint training was followed by one-to-one meetings where different staff members (from the Single Point of Reference) were involved according to the type of data to be handled. Version 0 of the DMP was finally produced for each doctoral student. This version will be modified as needed and will be part of the doctoral thesis.</p>
<p>Capacity</p>	<p>Six units were contacted and eight staff members were involved in the project. A certain level of expertise is involved only when it is required, which means the composition of the support group may vary in terms of the number of individuals involved on each occasion.</p> <p>Some members of the working group participated and are still participating in keeping the group updated. For the moment, the staff is able to respond to requests from research groups, but it is expected that there will be an increase in requests from researchers so a facility with dedicated staff will have to be considered in the future.</p>
<p>Impact</p>	<p>30 DMPs have been supported during the 2021/2022 period. The workflow is clear for researchers and team members, and each team member distinguishes well which boundaries to move within, deferring to colleagues for information in which they are competent. All DMPs delivered within European projects were accepted and approved without comment.</p>

Sorbonne University (SU)

Name of the initiative	Training for doctoral candidates and scientists – MOOC Open Science / La Science Ouverte
Use case	#1 raising awareness and training doctoral students and scientists on the issues of Open Science; #2 contributing to the transformation of scientific practices by focusing on doctoral students.
Type of initiative	Creating a training programme, which is freely accessible, about the topics related to Open Science.
Organiser of the initiative	Sorbonne University Alliance ⁷⁸ Team: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sorbonne University Library⁷⁹ • National Museum of Natural History⁸⁰
Scope and objectives	<p>Sorbonne University Library and the Doctoral Institute are committed to implementing the systematic training of doctoral students and scientific staff in Open Science.</p> <p>Launched on March 2022, the MOOC <i>Open Science</i>⁸¹ led by a joint team from Sorbonne University Library and the French National Museum of Natural History aims to fulfil one of the commitments of Sorbonne University from its Strategic Plan 2019 – 2023⁸² to the <i>Charter for open access publications (2019)</i>⁸³: to train all doctoral candidates and scientists for open science.</p> <p>This MOOC constitutes an immense resource for not only researchers and doctoral students, but also those who wish to have a wider perspective about Open Science while:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • providing at once the main keys to understanding issues related to Open Science (e.g. open access to publications, open data, research evaluation, citizen science, etc.), • witnessing some interesting testimonies of participants (e.g. researchers, doctoral students, scientific information and communication professionals, Open Science experts, etc.). <p>To emphasise the importance of reusability in research, all the MOOC contents are deposited in the Zenodo repository⁸⁴ under a CC-BY licence and, therefore, can be freely reused, in particular by other higher education and research institutions.</p>

⁷⁸ See Sorbonne University Alliance page: <https://www.sorbonne-universite.fr/en/research-and-innovation/research-partners/sorbonne-university-alliance>

⁷⁹ See SU Library page: <https://www.sorbonne-universite.fr/en/education/sorbonne-university-library>

⁸⁰ See museum webpage: <https://www.mnhn.fr/en>

⁸¹ See the MOOC: <https://www.fun-mooc.fr/en/courses/open-science/>

⁸² See the Strategic Plan: <https://www.sorbonne-universite.fr/en/university/about-us/strategic-plan>

⁸³ See the charter: <https://www.sorbonne-universite.fr/en/research-and-innovation/research-strategy/commitment-open-science>

⁸⁴ See the repository (in French): <https://zenodo.org/record/6333674>.

Implementation

The MOOC project was launched in November 2019, a few months before the COVID-19 pandemic. The first challenge was to be able to work in an environment where physical contact was restrained. To overcome this situation, the project team relied on digital communication technologies.

All the content (videos, texts, and infographics) of MOOC was decided to be created internally, by Sorbonne University Alliance. This choice led the project team to learn the required skills to manipulate and create the content, especially video recording and editing.

After all, it was a long process to interview all participants during the COVID-19 crisis, which delayed the project's progress. Eventually, the project team interviewed 36 specialists and six doctoral candidates who shared their vision and questions about Open Science in front of the camera.

The MOOC structure is designed to be composed of seven thematic modules that can be taken in any order: *Introduction* module, *Publication* module, *Research Data* module, *Research Evaluation* module⁸⁵, *Citizen Science* module, *Sciences and Society* module, *Perspectives* module.

The *Research Data* module contains:

- an Introduction and four Sequences : *Definitions and challenges*, *The legal side of opening data*, *Manage and open your data*, *Challenges and obstacles*
- 11 videos (including eight videos compulsory to complete the course) and seven interviewers

Completing the MOOC will require approximately eight hours of work. However, depending on the interests and availability of users, different options are possible: following only the essential parts (around five hours) or the optional course materials (up to ten hours of effort total).

The MOOC is bilingual in French/English. While most of the audio is only available in French, English transcripts and subtitles are provided for all videos. All texts are also translated into English.

Quizzes and exercises were implemented at the end of several modules to test the knowledge and skills of the participants. For doctoral candidates, MOOC validation can be integrated into the doctoral training program and lead to a certificate of completion.

Capacity

The MOOC project is carried out by teams:

- at Sorbonne University: three librarians and one learning designer
- at the National Museum of Natural History: one librarian

A monitoring committee (member of the Sorbonne University Alliance) followed the project and validated some decisions of the project team at different steps of the MOOC development.

⁸⁵ The Research Evaluation module has been developed with additional resources on research integrity since September 2023. It has become *Research Evaluation and Scientific Integrity* module

	<p>The funding of the MOOC project comes from IDEX⁸⁶ funds attributed by the Minister of Higher Education and Research to Sorbonne University.</p> <p>With the IDEX funding, a contractual colleague was also hired to help the team with its usual training missions, which allowed the project team to better focus on the MOOC project.</p>
<p>Impact</p>	<p>The results of the first session of the MOOC, which took place in March 2022 for four weeks, are as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2845 registered users (20% of registered not from France, half of registered are older than 35) • 461 participants (one who started at least one exercise) <p>The MOOC project has a completely correct participation rate (16%) compared to the classical participation rate for a MOOC. Generally, it must be understood that a significant number of people register for a MOOC without even starting it.</p> <p>The number of people eligible for certification (more than 50% correct answers) divided by the number of participants gives a satisfactory success rate (70%).</p> <p>Finally, the completion rate (10%), one who completes the MOOC, also remains on the MOOC average.</p> <p>As feedback to improve the MOOC, an optional form available inside the MOOC was answered by 170 registered users, and a survey was sent to all doctoral students at Sorbonne University.</p> <p>In addition, the question of scientific integrity could be a lever to better integrate the MOOC in the career of doctoral students, as there is a training obligation and a specific decree (<i>Decree No. 2021-1572⁸⁷</i>), which defines scientific integrity as “<i>a set of rules and values that must govern research in order to guarantee its honest and scientifically rigorous nature</i>”.</p> <p>In addition, the communication of a new session to the public will be developed to attract a wider audience.</p>

<p>Name of the initiative</p>	<p>Infrastructure – Recherche Data Gouv⁸⁸ (RDG), an ecosystem for sharing and opening research data.</p>
<p>Use case</p>	<p>1) providing a national and multidisciplinary data repository for French researchers;</p> <p>2) propose a sovereign solution for sharing and opening research data produced by communities that do not have a recognized disciplinary repository;</p>

⁸⁶ The IDEX are funds allocated by the French Ministry of Higher Education and Research to research-intensive universities.

⁸⁷ See the Decree no. 2021-1572 of 3 December 2021 (in French): <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/jorf/id/JORFTEXT000044411360>.

⁸⁸ Recherche Data Gouv website : <https://recherche.data.gouv.fr/en>.

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	3) supporting research teams on all data issues, grouped into three modules, to make data more FAIR.
Type of initiative	Creating a national and multidisciplinary data repository.
Organiser of the initiative	French Ministry of Higher Education and Research, Grenoble-Alpes University, Lille University, Lorraine University, Paris Cité University, Paris-Nanterre University, Strasbourg University, CNRS, INRAE.
Scope and objectives	<p>The goal of Research Data Gouv is to preserve, share, and open up research data.</p> <p>After a pre-figuration study⁸⁹, in which Sorbonne University participated, which helped to collect users' needs and to draw scenarios for the future tool, the deployment of the RDG repository has been delegated to INRAE⁹⁰ for its expertise on Dataverse.</p> <p>The platform was launched on 8 July 2022.</p> <p>Recherche Data Gouv aims to become a European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) service, offering access to shared and open research data to support reuse.</p>
Implementation	<p>RDG is designed as an ecosystem with five modules for researchers. Two modules are dedicated to depositing, publishing, and disseminating data – we find the repository⁹¹ to deposit and disseminate data and a registry to search for data published in the repository itself or other external repositories.</p> <p><i>Repository</i>⁹²: Dataverse is chosen as a multi-disciplinary repository solution to ensure the needs of communities that are not yet equipped with a recognized thematic repository and allow French institutions to create their own space within. The solution chosen for the repository is Dataverse. This repository displays the datasets of many French Dataverse, disciplinary, or university repositories. Relying on Dataverse software, the RDG repository proposes a space assigned to an institution based on one of its data contributors. Otherwise, if institutions do not possess such a space, the data produced can be deposited in a generic space.</p> <p>SU also has made a demand to create its institutional repository.</p> <p>The other three modules are dedicated to supporting research teams on all issues related to data: Data management clusters; Thematic reference centres; Resources centres.</p>

⁸⁹ Étude de faisabilité d'un service générique d'accueil et de diffusion des données simples : ambitions du service et scénarios de mise en œuvre : <https://hal-lara.archives-ouvertes.fr/OUVRIR-LA-SCIENCE/hal-03594196> (in French).

⁹⁰ Research Data Gouv and INRAE : <https://www.inrae.fr/actualites/recherche-data-gouv-donnees-commun> (in French).

⁹¹ Repository: <https://recherche.data.gouv.fr/en/page/a-multidisciplinary-repository> .

⁹² <https://entrepot.recherche.data.gouv.fr/>.

	<p><i>Data management clusters</i>⁹³: each data management cluster aims to support researchers on issues related to research data, algorithms, and codes. Research teams can not only be accompanied in writing their data management plan, but also be advised on technical solutions, computing, and storage. In addition, researchers may address their questions related to personal data and the RGPD.</p> <p><i>Thematic reference centres</i>⁹⁴: each thematic reference centre is both national and disciplinary. It supports the work of data management and dissemination in a scientific-thematic area. It helps define the appropriate data standard in their thematic field by providing best practices for data collection, documentation, processing, and dissemination. For now, there are five active centres: Astronomy and Astrophysics; Earth System and Environment; Humanities and Social Sciences; Biology-Health.</p> <p><i>Resources centres</i>⁹⁵: different types of national resource centres provide support for data management clusters and thematic reference centres. Recherche Data Gouv federates existing resources and services to capitalise on these for the benefit of all concerned throughout France. There are three Resources centres: the Recherche Data Gouv repository-registry resource centre; The Recherche Data Gouv DORANum resource centre; The Recherche Data Gouv skills resource centre.</p>
<p>Capacity</p>	<p>The RDG is structured by a steering committee composed of members of the Ministry and members of the seven partner institutions (universities and research organisations mentioned above) of the project. They define the strategy and different actions of the project. A team from INRAE, ensured the deployment of the multidisciplinary repository in association with seven other institutions.</p> <p>Data management clusters are made up of a team from partner institutions. A data management cluster is often organised at the level of a region or several institutions. In general, the teams consist of a minimum of three people, often more.</p> <p>For the first three years, the Ministry of Higher Education and Research will lead the RDG project, and €7 million of funding from the French National Fund for Open Science will be distributed to the project. This investment will be shared between the development of the data repository and the registry and the establishment of data management clusters, as close as possible to researchers around France.</p>
<p>Impact</p>	<p>RDG is currently being developed and will deploy new modules and services in the coming years.</p>

⁹³ Data management clusters: <https://recherche.data.gouv.fr/en/page/data-management-clusters>.

⁹⁴ Thematic reference centres: <https://recherche.data.gouv.fr/en/page/thematic-reference-centers-providing-expertise-for-individual-scientific-fields>.

⁹⁵ Resource centres: <https://recherche.data.gouv.fr/en/page/resource-centres>.

The Data management clusters are still being deployed. After a first call for expressions of interest, which led to the accreditation of eight centres, a second call for expressions of interest⁹⁶ is underway to strengthen the network.

Since the RDG was launched in July 2022, it is difficult to assess its use at this time. Considering that some institutions already have a Dataverse space (mainly INRAE, but some others also), we can access the statistics⁹⁷. According to the RDG portal, 659 dataverses (collections) have already been harvested with 3 469 datasets, 43 814 files, and 675 807 total file downloads⁹⁸.

The project is exemplary in that it was prepared on a national scale to meet a need shared by a large number of French researchers. As a national multidisciplinary repository, RDG allows French research teams and resource centres to focus on developing disciplinary repositories for their communities and enhancing research by sharing and opening their data.

In 2023, the RDG is planned to be completed with a data catalogue that allows users to identify and report data sets from external national or international repositories.

Name of the initiative	Service – SACADO Service Unit (Service d’Aide au Calcul et à l’Analyse de Données / Computing and Data Analysis Support Service)⁹⁹
Use case	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1) making accessible and increasing the availability of computing and data-processing resources and expertise; 2) promoting good practices in the use of computing and data-processing resources; 3) linking and enhancing research communities within Sorbonne University and building relationships with other communities networks.
Type of initiative	Creating a service unit to support researchers for data simulation, data processing, and data storage.
Organiser of the initiative	<p>Sorbonne University</p> <p>Created in 2021, the SACADO service unit follows up the computing platform effort previously led by the IT service and ISCD (Institut des Sciences du Calcul et des Données / Institute of Computing and Data Sciences). Its creation has been motivated by the massive growth of</p>

⁹⁶ Research Data Gouv launches its second call for expressions of interest "Data management cluster", present your projects! <https://recherche.data.gouv.fr/en/actuality/research-data-gouv-launches-its-second-call-for-expressions-of-interest-data-management-cluster-present-your-projects> (in French).

⁹⁷ See more <https://entrepot.recherche.data.gouv.fr/stats>.

⁹⁸ As of 8 November.2023 <https://entrepot.recherche.data.gouv.fr/dataverse/>.

⁹⁹ SACADO Website : <https://sacado.sorbonne-universite.fr/welcome/> .

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	<p>simulation, data processing & storage needs within the research community.</p> <p>To achieve these missions, the service unit works with the IT service and the library. It also interacts directly with researchers and students, and works jointly with other service units working in data science.</p>
<p>Scope and objectives</p>	<p>The SACADO service unit provides support to researchers and students to respond to their needs for simulation, data processing, and storage. Researchers can use the SACADO service unit at any stage of their project.</p> <p>Furthermore, the SACADO services are offered to all staff of the Sorbonne University Alliance (Sorbonne University, National Museum of Natural History, University of Technology of Compiègne, etc.).</p> <p>The SACADO's offer is mainly divided into three areas: consulting and engineering services, access to the MeSU computing platform, and technical support.</p> <p><i>Consulting and engineering:</i> the SACADO supports research teams with questions about the architecture of computing and data processing systems. The SACADO also provides performance analysis, optimization, and development. It can provide assistance not only in deploying applications and its integration but also in managing and archiving research data. The SACADO also provides project management assistance to researchers if desired.</p> <p><i>Access to the MeSU technology platform:</i> access to the supercomputer is offered to users after an evaluation of their needs. Hosting an application or a scientific web portal is possible. The SACADO currently offers three types of data storage facilities: a fast scratch storage for computation, storage for home directories and software repositories, and storage dedicated to the virtualization environment. Also, a display panel connected to a workstation can realise hosting for a visualisation session. Due to this environment, researchers can collect, analyse, and visualise the data sets obtained from numerical simulation.</p> <p><i>Technical support:</i> the SACADO can help set up a computational campaign and provide assistance for the submission of works. It also offers application compilation/installation/integration to researchers during their projects.</p> <p>The SACADO works with the library on research data issues and supports the university's open research data policy¹⁰⁰ by encouraging its users to adopt a FAIR approach to managing their data.</p>

¹⁰⁰ Open research data policy within the Sorbonne University Alliance : https://www.sorbonne-universite.fr/sites/default/files/media/2021-08/03Politique%20douverture%20des%20donnes_EN_VD.pdf .

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	<p>Finally, the SACADO has a bridging role to help researchers find the infrastructures adapted to their projects. It works with other French computing centres¹⁰¹, such as those of the CNRS¹⁰².</p>
<p>Implementation</p>	<p>After only one year of existence, the SACADO supports the projects of several research teams from the faculties of Medicine, Humanities, Sciences, and Engineering.</p> <p>The main steps in implementing the SACADO were as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Designing a scientific computing workspace where both legacy and state-of-the-art scientific applications are supported; • Attracting users coming from scientific communities that were not used to supercomputing or cloud environments; • Adapting communication, training, and support so that users from different backgrounds and with different usage levels (beginners, advanced, experts) get their requests addressed in a reactive and timely manner; • Training users in best practices for data management and pushing for open science awareness.
<p>Capacity</p>	<p>Two engineers are currently working in the unit: its manager, and one person dedicated to high-performance computing (HPC) activities.</p> <p>The unit is partly financed by Sorbonne University. It charges its users for the services. The costs of using the SACADO services are eligible for project funding by French and European agencies.</p>
<p>Impact</p>	<p>Created in 2021 during the COVID-19 crisis, the unit is still in the process of making itself known within the university and its partners in the Sorbonne University Alliance. When the unit is presented to the researchers, they are very satisfied with this service offered to them within the institution.</p> <p>The SACADO already answers many requests from research teams with a high level of satisfaction from users with its customised services.</p> <p>The SACADO supercomputer counts about 140 active users every year, originating from 35 different research units. SACADO cloud hosts 10 active projects.</p> <p>In 2021, SACADO organised 14 short training sessions for new users. Furthermore, by September 2022, 13 short training sessions had already taken place.</p> <p>Although not all scientific publications are reported to SACADO, the service unit is regularly credited for its support by researchers. The most recent publication is, for instance “The streaming of plastic in the</p>

¹⁰¹ Computing centres in France, network of « mésocentres » : https://calcul.math.cnrs.fr/pages/mesocentres_en_france.html (in French).

¹⁰² High Performance Computing CNRS : <https://science-ouverte.cnrs.fr/calcul-intensif/#:~:text=Les%20centres%20de%20calcul%20nationaux,de%20donn%C3%A9es%203B%20le%20%C3%A9veloppement%20et> (in French).

Mediterranean Sea”¹⁰³, by Alberto Baudena, Enrico Ser-Giacomi, Isabel Jalón-Rojas, François Galgani, Maria Luiza Pedrotti, published in Nature Communications, 2022.

The University of Warsaw (UW)

Name of the initiative	Infrastructure — Project ‘Disciplinary Open Research Data Repositories’ (DRODB)
Use case	1) creating and providing a sustainable generalist and domain-specific open data repository infrastructure for research data sharing; 2) building academic and administration staff capacity and creating new training activities as support actions for the implementation of Research Data Management and the FAIR data sharing in Poland.
Type of initiative	Creating research data repositories with user training courses.
Organiser of the initiative	<p>The University of Warsaw (Interdisciplinary Center for Mathematical and Computational Modeling UW and Robert Zajonc Institute for Social Studies UW) in partnership with the Polish Academy of Sciences (Institute of Philosophy and Sociology Polish Academy of Sciences) and Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań (Faculty of Chemistry)¹⁰⁴.</p> <p>The Interdisciplinary Centre for Mathematical and Computational Modeling of the University of Warsaw (ICM) has been actively involved in Open Science for many years, with its activities in areas such as developing open infrastructure for dissemination of scholarly outputs, providing training and consultancy for researchers and research institutions, and promoting open science among Polish citizens. Open science initiatives at ICM date back to the end of the 20th century, with the first deployments in the area of mathematics and natural sciences. Now ICM runs the Open Science Platform that is active not only in the area of open access to scientific articles in all disciplines, but also provides services for data sharing, organising workshops, and functions as the National Open Access Desk for Poland (OpenAIRE). One of its main goals is to enhance access to academic resources and support researchers and academic institutions in implementing open science. In recent years, ICM has been involved in projects that aim to develop open scientific resources in Poland and provide services to safeguard the availability of scientific publications and other research results.</p>
Scope and objectives	The project <i>Disciplinary Open Research Data Repositories</i> ¹⁰⁵ which began in August 2018 and ended in October 2021 aimed to improve access to academic resources by making them available in open

¹⁰³ See the article : <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-022-30572-5>.

¹⁰⁴ Source: <https://drodb.icm.edu.pl/english/>.

¹⁰⁵ Ibid.

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research data repositories, improve the quality of shared data and metadata and facilitate their better use. This was possible by further development of the existing general-purpose Repository for Open Data RepOD and the development of two domain-specific repositories: Social Data Repository (RDS) and crystallographic Macromolecular Xtallography Raw Data Repository (MX-RDR).

- The Open Data Repository [RepOD](#) has been operating since 2015. It is the first Polish repository for open research data, created for all scientists and institutions interested in sharing their resources. It is open and free for everyone to use. Each set of deposited data receives a DOI number. It is run by the Open Science Platform team at the Interdisciplinary Center for Mathematical and Computational Modelling of the University of Warsaw. Thanks to the DRODB project, it could be further developed and adapted to international standards. The new service has replaced RepOD's previous version.
- The RDS Social Data Repository¹⁰⁶ (<https://rds.icm.edu.pl/>) is a domain-specific digital repository of social data. It is open to everyone to use. The purpose of the repository is to make social content consisting of data sets and accompanying technical or methodological documentation available on the Internet¹⁰⁷. The repository hosts collections from the Qualitative Data Archive and the Polish Social Data Archive.
- Macromolecular Xtallography Raw Data Repository [MX-RDR](#) is a domain-specific digital repository of raw diffraction data collected for macromolecular crystals, open to everyone to use. It includes tools that simplify the creation of metadata descriptions by combining information extracted directly from diffraction images, obtained from the PDB database, and/or user input¹⁰⁸.

Each data set is characterised by rich metadata, both to facilitate its management and long-term curation and to allow effective scientific reuse. The resource can be searched using various criteria and all data are available for unrestricted access and download¹⁰⁹.

Implementation

The software development necessary to adapt Dataverse, an open-source research data repository software, was conducted at the Interdisciplinary Center for Mathematical and Computational Modeling, University of Warsaw. It involved a considerable degree of code refactoring.

Repository for Open Data RepOD – Main changes (also available in disciplinary repositories):

- Polish translation of the interface,
- licences assigned to individual files,

¹⁰⁶ Source: <https://rds.icm.edu.pl/terms-of-use-page.xhtml>.

¹⁰⁷ Source: <https://drodb.icm.edu.pl/english/>.

¹⁰⁸ Ibid.

¹⁰⁹ Source: <https://info.mxrdm.icm.edu.pl/index.php/about/few-words-about-mx-rdr/>.

- WCAG improvements.

Social Data Repository RDS – main changes:

- changes in social science metadata,
- implemented selected CESSDA vocabularies.

Macromolecular Xtallography Raw Data Repository MX-RDR – Main changes:

- macromolecular crystallography metadata schema,
- tools for creating crystallographic metadata by combining information extracted directly from diffraction images and obtained from a PDB deposit and/or user input,
- automatic analysis of the data deposited with the XDS software.

Researchers can deposit, share, and publish their datasets openly, in accordance with the FAIR principles. It is possible to describe datasets with metadata, include structured funding information, provide a link to relevant publications and/or datasets, select one of the Creative Commons licences, and attribute it to an individual file. Thanks to the OAI-PMH server and numerous APIs, the repository allows for the automation of extensive exchange of its resources with external services.

All repositories will serve as content providers for OpenAIRE – metadata will be harvested and shown in OpenAIRE Explore. Moreover, repositories are registered in OpenDOAR and in the re3data Registry of Research Data Repositories where important characteristics of the services are provided:

- Repository for Open Data RepOD:
<https://www.re3data.org/repository/r3d100011903>
- Macromolecular Xtallography Raw Data Repository MX-RDR:
<https://www.re3data.org/repository/r3d100013569>
- Social Data Repository RDS:
<https://www.re3data.org/repository/r3d100013574>¹¹⁰

The processing and preparation of social data is provided by the Institute of Philosophy and Sociology, Polish Academy of Sciences; Robert Zajonc Institute for Social Studies, University of Warsaw. The processing and preparation of macromolecular data is provided by the Faculty of Chemistry of Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań. Research data management training, educational materials, outreach, and promotion are provided by the Interdisciplinary Center for Mathematical and Computational Modeling, University of Warsaw.

A series of research data management workshops were conducted as part of the project. The training programme consisted of two parts. The first covered practical aspects of the research data management such as the preparation of data for sharing in accordance with the requirements of research funding organisations, the FAIR principles, and good practices. The second part, devoted to legal aspects of research data management, covers research data as the subject of legal regulations, including intellectual property law, General Data Protection

¹¹⁰ Source: <https://www.openaire.eu/blogs/the-development-of-open-research-data-repositories-in-poland>

	<p>Regulation, and commercialisation of research results, as well as the use of free and open licences (Creative Commons and Open Data Commons).</p> <p>Other promotional and educational activities carried out within the project included the preparation of educational materials on various aspects of research data (available in Polish¹¹¹): legal aspects of the sharing of research data, the selection and preparation of research data for the sharing and the use of scientific resources in data repositories¹¹².</p>
<p>Capacity</p>	<p>The work in the project ‘Disciplinary Open Research Data Repositories’ was carried out by project teams at the Interdisciplinary Center for Mathematical and Computational Modeling (ICM UW), the Institute of Philosophy and Sociology of the Polish Academy of Sciences, the Institute of Social Studies of the UW (ISS UW), and the University of Adam Mickiewicz in Poznań (AMU), led by ICM UW. The funding for the development of the DRODB project repositories came from the Digital Poland Project Centre (Centrum Projektów Polska Cyfrowa) subsidy of PLN 4 998 889 (including funds from European funds in the amount of PLN 4 230 559,76 and from the state budget in the amount of PLN 768 329,24).</p>
<p>Impact</p>	<p>As a result, over 1600 datasets are made available (Nov. 2023), almost all of them using open licences. In the future, it will also be much easier to create new domain repositories based on the software developed as part of the project, which is available on GitHub (https://github.com/CeON/dataverse).</p> <p>New datasets are deposited by individual users and researchers affiliated with institutions that have agreed to cooperate with the University of Warsaw to set up an institutional collection in the Repository for Open Data. Currently, more than 15 institutions have chosen this solution to share the data collected during research and make them FAIR¹¹³.</p> <p>During the implementation of the project, 22 research data management training courses were conducted, in which 1,411 people from various scientific institutions from all over Poland participated. Two stationary training courses were held in November and December 2019, the remaining ones, due to restrictions during the pandemic, were organised online from March 2020 to October 2021.</p> <p>In addition, in 2021, user training on the repositories created under the project was started: 6 training courses on the Data Repository RepOD were organised (in total 388 people participated); 2 training courses on social data and the RDS Social Data Repository (204 participants) and</p>

¹¹¹ Source: <https://drodb.icm.edu.pl/materialy-2/>

¹¹² Source: <https://drodb.icm.edu.pl/english/>

¹¹³ Source: <https://www.openaire.eu/blogs/the-development-of-open-research-data-repositories-in-poland> (in English).

	2 training courses on the Macromolecular Xtallography Raw Data Repository MX-RDR (25 participants). In total, more than 2,000 people participated in all training courses ¹¹⁴ .
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Name of the initiative	Training sessions for doctoral candidates and scientists and general university courses for students developing their knowledge on open science issues.
Use case	<p>The primary objectives of the training were, on the one hand, to actively engage the University of Warsaw Library in the University's efforts to mainstream open science as the global approach to disseminating scientific knowledge. Increased awareness among scientists and doctoral students regarding open science and more encouragement in the scientific community to take steps in this direction are still required. The library's training program was designed to bridge the training gap and bring attention to open science issues, offer possible solutions and enhance the skills and qualifications of doctoral students and researchers.</p> <p>Although the main focus was on doctoral students and researchers, the University of Warsaw Library also took the initiative to educate students about open science. Part of this initiative was a university-wide course on <i>Open Science and the Foundations of Research Data Management</i>.</p> <p>To meet the needs of the University of Warsaw community (researchers, doctoral students) to implement the guidelines and recommendations for the dissemination of open science at the institutional, national, and international levels, the structural transformation of the Information Services and Training Department at the University of Warsaw Library was necessary with the aim of establishing a team of experts in the field of open science, scientific communication, and assessment of scientific results.</p>
Type of initiative	Training courses organised by the Information Services and Training Department at the University of Warsaw Library
Organiser of the initiative	University of Warsaw Library, Information Services and Training Department, Science Support Team.
Scope and objectives	The concept of open science training courses has been developed in the University of Warsaw Library since 2018, particularly in the context of the new science communication model based on the opening up of knowledge resources and supported by the Polish Ministerial recommendations outlining directions for the development of open

¹¹⁴ Source: <https://drodb.icm.edu.pl/szkolenia-przeprowadzone-w-ramach-projektu/> (in Polish).

access¹¹⁵. Furthermore, the Excellence Initiative Research University program¹¹⁶ aims to develop, adopt, and implement an open science policy at the University of Warsaw and requires librarians to change and adapt to new tasks. Initially, it was training in scientific publishing with elements of open access. Since 2020 consideration has been given in particular to intensifying training activities and targeting different audiences to maximise the impact of research in the future. In addition, the creation of hybrid forms of training is pondered, where partially recorded material and real-time commentary from the librarian are available. Enabling interpersonal communication is essential for specific needs.

1. Training for doctoral candidates and scientists

Open Means Show Off! How to promote your scientific output through open science (editions 2020 and 2021).

In June/July 2020, two staff members created a concept for the development of open science training for researchers and doctoral students at the University of Warsaw. The purpose of the initiative was to broaden the knowledge of researchers on various aspects of open science, which was linked to the intensification activities of the European Union under the Horizon Europe programme and the implementation of the open science policy by the Polish National Science Centre (Narodowe Centrum Nauki – NCN)¹¹⁷, which is the main grant-giver in Poland.

Thematic course topics:

- What is open science and how is it used to promote scientific production/results?
- Where and how to publish in open access models?
- What is research data management?
- Where and how to publish research data in open access models?
- How to prepare a research data management plan?
- The licence to publish scientific publications and research data.

2. Training during Open Access Week 2021

In 2021 the University of Warsaw Library joined an Open Access Week – a worldwide initiative held in October, which can be considered beneficial in promoting the very idea of openness in science at the university, as well as globally, as an opportunity to mainstream the principles and encourage the practice of open science activities.

Thematic course topics:

- Publishing in the open access model
- Research Data Management Plan in scientific work

¹¹⁵ In Poland in 2015 the Ministry of Science and Higher Education published recommendations on open access. <https://www.gov.pl/web/edukacja-i-nauka/dokumenty-na-temat-otwartego-dostepu> (in Polish).

¹¹⁶ The Excellence Research University program - Inicjatywa Doskonałości Uczelnia Badawcza <https://inicjatywadokonalosci.uw.edu.pl/en/>

¹¹⁷ https://www.ncn.gov.pl/sites/default/files/pliki/2021_10_instrukcja_open_access_NCN_ang.pdf

- Open access and research funding.
2. General university course for students
 1. *Open Science and the Foundations of Research Data Management* (since 2021)

To extend open science education and introduce students to open science already at the undergraduate level, a general university course for students on open science and research data management was created in the academic year 2021/2022. The scope and objectives of the university course were to familiarise students with issues related to Open Science and Research Data Management (RDM). The class provided an introduction to theory and practice. It showed the impact of a properly drafted data management plan on workflow. The objectives of the course are that the knowledge gained during the classes is useful not only in the course of studies but also in everyday professional or scientific life – students should be able to independently prepare a plan and manage research data for their own work and know how to transfer the acquired skills to the professional environment, e.g., preparing project proposals.

Thematic course topics:

- Organization of the research process.
- What are the research data?
- Creating a research data management plan for the student's own work.
- Tools and skills needed to manage research data.
- Promoting research data management.
- Open Science, Open Access, FAIR principles, and Research Data Management.

Implementation

Expert librarians supported researchers in research data management and other issues related to open science even before the structural reform of the Information Services and Training Department. In 2020, information on research data management, data repositories, and training was published on the library website and a research data guide (in Polish “Dane Badawcze”¹¹⁸) tailored to the needs of Polish researchers was produced.

The research environment of the university has changed due to the dissemination and implementation of scientific openness. Furthermore, the functions and working methods of the Information Services and Training Department in the Library required changes, especially in view of the challenges brought about by the SARS-Cov-2 pandemic in 2020 and 2021. In July 2021, a plan was presented to reform the department. The approved proposal was implemented in October 2021. However, the team-building process was not yet complete, as it was assumed that a copyright specialist and more repository editors were needed.

¹¹⁸ <http://www.buw.uw.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/DANE-BADAWCZE-1.pdf> (in Polish).

1. Training for doctoral candidates and scientists

1. *Open Means Show Off! How to promote your scientific output through open science* (editions 2020 and 2021)

The first edition of the course, entitled *Open Means Show Off! How to promote your scientific output through open science* ran from mid-November to mid-December 2020. For the course, 57 people registered, with an average of 25 people attending each meeting¹¹⁹.

In April 2021, the second edition of the course was held by the University of Warsaw Library. Both courses were conducted online by two members of the staff, consisting of four 1.5-hour meetings each (in total, six hours). There were 213 participants in 2021.

The courses took into account the guidelines of the Polish National Science Centre, the guidelines of Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe, as well as the 2.0 Act (a Polish law on higher education and science)¹²⁰.

2. *Training during Open Access Week 2021*

A member of the Science Support Team of the Information Services and Training Department developed a series of three training sessions for doctoral candidates and researchers, which took place on 25, 27, and 29 October 2021.

Each meeting lasted 1.5 hours and was attended by a total of 45 people. The scope of the training was in accordance with the requirements of the Polish National Science Centre for project funding. Among the Centre's policy requirements is that the DMP must be attached to the funding application. Introducing open access to scientific data produced as part of projects funded by the Centre, and in the near future also to scientific publications is the first stage of open science in Poland. The course is in line with the policy.

2. General university course for students

1. *Open Science and the Foundations of Research Data Management* (since 2021)

The general university course for students was given by two members of the staff. One of the staff members, who is also a lecturer at the Faculty of Journalism, Information and Bibliology at the University of Warsaw, together with a librarian from the Information Services and Training Department, ran a regular university course on open science and research data management. Five students from various departments participated in the first edition. The course will be continued in the next semesters. It is open to all students at the University of Warsaw and may be included in curricula of different disciplines. It takes 15 hours and is scored with 2 ECTS.

¹¹⁹ More information on the description, recommendations, and evaluation of the course can be found in the article by Ph.D. Anna Kamińska, Jak biblioteki akademickie szkolą badaczy w zakresie otwartej nauki – na przykładzie kursu oferowanego przez Bibliotekę Uniwersytecką w Warszawie (How academic libraries teach researchers on open science. The case of a course offered by the University of Warsaw Library), EBIB Bulletin, no. 198, <http://ebibojs.pl/index.php/ebib/article/view/739>

¹²⁰ <https://www.gov.pl/web/edukacja-i-nauka/konstytucja-dla-nauki-2> (in Polish).

	<p>The challenges that appeared in organising the training course can be listed as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • substantive – 1) library staff skills and knowledge development; 2) selection of the scope and topics of the training most suitable for the university environment; 3) tailoring the content of courses to diverse audiences, taking into account their progress in subject matter; • organisational – 1) the heavy burden on the small number of staff preparing and conducting the training and reaching the right focus group. Therefore, it is recommended that this training course be organised by a larger group (team). 2) Attention should also be paid to the difficulty in promoting courses in the context of the absence of a national¹²¹ and institutional open access policy.
<p>Capacity</p>	<p>The Science Support Team is part of the Information Services and Training Department at the University of Warsaw Library and, in 2022 consisted of five librarians:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • one editor/publisher of the institution repository, • two staff members involved in open science, open access publishing, and bibliometrics, • one person working with electronic resources (EDS) and repository, • one employee who is involved in the integration of open science through training courses and collaboration with doctoral schools. <p>The tasks of the Science Support Team include: 1) providing training in open science for groups or as individual consultation on research data management planning issues, 2) providing consultations in the field of the analysis of research results, 3) the dissemination of knowledge on research data management at the University of Warsaw, 4) providing expertise in publishing in open access models as required by grant funding programmes.</p> <p>Three members of the Science Support Team of the Information Services and Training Department of the University of Warsaw Library were involved in the preparation of the training course in terms of content and organisation. Cooperation took place at the institutional level between the library and other units of the University of Warsaw: the doctoral schools, the Faculty of Journalism, Information and Book Studies and Research Services Office.</p> <p>The open science institutional policy is expected to be adopted by the University of Warsaw in 2023, and the UW institutional repository will be upgraded to the latest version (7.x) of the DSpace system. The repository's collection will be supplemented with articles, books, and other types of scientific publications produced at the University of Warsaw. The implementation of institutional OS policy and the</p>

¹²¹ In Poland in 2015 the Ministry of Science and Higher Education published recommendations on open access. <https://www.gov.pl/web/edukacja-i-nauka/dokumenty-na-temat-otwartego-dostepu> (in Polish).

	<p>development of the repository will require the expansion of the Science Support Team.</p> <p>The team's efforts are also focused on developing a new open learning training offer. An e-learning course has been developed and online and on-site training is planned¹²².</p>
Impact	<p>The learning outcomes were the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge <p>Participants: 1) acquired a broad knowledge of research data management and open science; 2) gained in-depth reflection on the impact of research data management on the process of planning, conducting, and communicating results in research, especially in the context of open science; 3) gained knowledge of research data management tools.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Skills <p>Participants: 1) were able to identify and analyse different types of research data, depending on the scientific discipline and the stage of the research conducted; 2) learned how to make a research data management plan; 3) prepared their own research data so that it is suitable for reuse and available in dedicated repositories.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competencies <p>Participants: 1) were able to engage in advocacy for research data management and open science and know what the benefits are; 2) were able to identify the most appropriate tools and the best repositories for managing and depositing research data, depending on the scientific discipline.</p>

¹²² Among the regularly offered thematic training courses, three are specifically focused on open science <https://www.buw.uw.edu.pl/szkolenia/szkolenia-tematyczne/> (in Polish).

3. Part 2 – Case #2 Responsible Publishing

3.1. Introduction and objectives

3.1.1. What is Responsible Publishing?

In Task 5.3, Case #2, our main focus was on the critical aspects of tools and methods of support for scholarly publishing. In this context, we emphasised the term ‘**responsible publishing**’. This concept embodies the commitment to open access to scholarly outputs, making them available to broad and diverse audiences. Responsible publishing takes into account also the financial aspects of publication. Often it is funded from public money. Responsible publishing places a strong emphasis on the protection of authors' rights through the principle of copyright retention, too. The most important characteristics of responsible open access scholarly publishing are the following:

- **Transparency** – Responsible Open Access publishing requires clear and transparent communication about the publishing process, peer review, author fees (where applicable), and copyright and licensing terms.
- **Peer review** – Maintaining rigorous peer review processes to ensure the quality, validity, and integrity of published research. Peer review helps maintain scientific standards and academic credibility.
- **Ethical standards** – Adherence to ethical standards, including proper attribution, avoidance of plagiarism, and adherence to academic and research integrity guidelines.
- **Avoidance of predatory practices** – Responsible open access publishing avoids predatory practices and publishers who engage in deceptive, unethical, or poor-quality publishing. These practices can exploit authors for profit and provide minimal or no peer review.
- **Accessibility** – A commitment to make research results openly available to a global audience, free of charge or with reasonable access fees, without unnecessary barriers to access.
- **Licensing** – Clear use of open licences, such as Creative Commons licences, that allow readers and users to understand how they can use, share and build upon the content.
- **Financial transparency** – Transparent disclosure of publication fees or charges and fair pricing models. Authors and institutions should have a clear understanding of the costs associated with open access publishing.
- **Long-term preservation** – Ensuring the long-term preservation and accessibility of research outputs to prevent the loss of valuable scholarly work.
- **Quality control** – Maintaining high editorial and production standards, including proper formatting, citation guidelines, and the use of professional editorial and publishing services.
- **Inclusivity** – Efforts to ensure inclusivity, diversity, and equal opportunity in publishing, with no bias against authors from underrepresented groups or regions.

- **Authors' rights** – Promoting the rights of authors and ensuring that they retain control over their research output and have the freedom to share their work in accordance with open access principles.
- **Respect for academic values** – Compliance with the values and norms of the academic community, including a commitment to the pursuit of knowledge, honest and ethical conduct, and the dissemination of research for the public good.

3.1.2. Objectives

In Case #2 our primary objective was to undertake a comprehensive assessment of the scientific and responsible (open) publishing support provided by each of the six universities in the 4EU+ Alliance in terms of:

- **Infrastructure:** We aimed to investigate the availability and functionality of institutional repositories and publishing platforms within each university. This included an assessment of the capacity to archive and disseminate research outputs, thereby improving their accessibility.
- **Legal support for publication agreements:** We looked at the extent to which the Alliance universities provide legal support and advice to researchers on entering into publishing agreements, ensuring that these agreements are in line with responsible publishing principles.
- **Selection of journals to avoid predatory publishers:** An important aspect of our review was to assess the mechanisms and criteria used by these universities to help researchers with the selection of journals. Particular emphasis was placed on strategies on how to avoid predatory publishers and journals, thereby safeguarding the quality and integrity of scholarly publications.
- **Support for publication charges (APCs/BPCs — Article/Book Processing Charges):** We examined the extent to which these universities provide financial support, including coverage of article and book processing charges (APCs/BPCs). This support helps to ensure that researchers are able to publish their work openly and ethically, particularly where such charges are applicable.

By examining these four key dimensions, our aim was to gain a comprehensive understanding of the policies and resources used by the 4EU+ universities to facilitate scholarly publishing and contribute to the promotion of open and responsible scholarly communication within the Alliance.

3.2. Methodology and Data Collection

In Case #2, existing tools and solutions for support in publishing at each of the six Alliance universities, were investigated and listed, that is repositories and publishing platforms. As complementary undertakings, we also took into account: education (training courses offered by the libraries/units) as well as open and responsible publishing advocacy, e.g., online guides on OA publishing for authors (the findings are presented in section 3.2.3. in the tables),

commitment to Open Access Week at each university (as a part of TRAIN4EU Deliverable 5.2 Report on best practices on Open Science publication and Open Research Data, mainstreaming Open Science¹²³).

We asked the members of WP 5 to fill in a table containing the fields for the courses provided at their universities: name of training, scope, form, duration, link to webpage (if available, e.g. e-learning course), provider, availability, language, comments/remarks. We wanted to share best practice in this area, and see how the support provided was reflected in the number of open publications. We have been able to identify which channels for disseminating knowledge about open publishing are the most fruitful and which should be strengthened across all partners.

In order to assess forms of support for responsible publishing and to identify good practices that might be useful for other universities, we decided to map the landscape of scholarly publishing within the 4EU+ Alliance. To achieve it, we conducted a comprehensive bibliometric analysis of the publications for the 2021-2022 period from the six 4EU+ universities. This analysis placed a particular emphasis on open access publishing and served as the fundamental source for drawing conclusions and shaping recommendations for support centres. The bibliometric report *Open Access Publishing in the 4EU+ Alliance in 2021-2022* provides the background to the description of the current situation of open access publishing at the 4EU+ Alliance universities. The report is in [5.3. Appendix 3. Task 5.3, Case #2 Responsible publishing. Open access publishing in the 4EU+ Alliance in 2021-2022. Bibliometric report on Scopus, Web of Science, OpenAlex, COKI Open Access Database, and Open APC.](#)

3.2.1. Findings from the bibliometric analysis

The scope of the bibliometric analysis was the following: the number of OA documents (peer-reviewed publications), type of OA (publication routes), research fields, publishers, funding sponsors, co-publishing practices, and article publication charges (APCs). Statistics and data have been downloaded from the following databases: Scopus™, the Web of Science™, OpenAlex, the COKI Open Access Dataset, and the OpenAPC. The data were analysed using bibliometric methods.

General findings:

1. There are large differences between universities in the number of publications indexed in the databases studied. The number of publications indexed can vary up to four times.
3. Only 50 percent of publications in Scopus™ have a DOI number, in contrast to over 93 percent in the Web of Science and OpenAlex.
4. More than 60 percent of the 4EU+ Alliance scientific publications in 2021-2022 were openly accessible to the public.
5. According to the data from the OpenAlex database, the golden route of publishing dominates in the 4EU+ Alliance, while the data from the Scopus™ and the Web of

¹²³ See <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101016674/>

Science™ databases indicate a predominance of the green route of scientific publishing (repositories).

7. Around 30 percent of publications (according to the COKI database) are still closed. This means that researchers and other stakeholders do not have access to the results of research paid by taxpayers.
8. According to Scopus™ and the Web of Science™, in the 4EU+ Alliance the most popular subject areas in open access publishing are medicine, biochemistry, genetics, molecular biology, physics, astronomy, and agricultural and biological sciences.
9. Analysis of publisher data showed that the 4EU+ Alliance authors were most likely to publish with Elsevier™, Springer™, and Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI).
10. Sorbonne University, Heidelberg University, and the University of Copenhagen collaborate most strongly, which results in the highest percent of co-authored publications within the Alliance.
11. Analysis of the results shows that co-authored papers in our Alliance are dominated by articles with more than 100 authors. The dominant research fields are physics, astronomy, and medicine.
12. In most cases, the largest funders of grants for research and scientific publications are specially designated government agencies. The situation is different in Denmark, where the largest funder is the private foundation Novo Nordisk. In addition, all the 4EU+ Alliance universities benefit from European funding for publications.

The analysis of researchers' publication practices will provide the background for further research and indicate the possibilities for developing cooperation between our universities. The conclusions of the analysis can also be used to develop support services for scientists at the Alliance universities.

The bibliometric analysis of the 2021-2022 publications allowed us to identify the strong and weak points of each partner institution in terms of open access publications.

Charles University (CU)

According to the study, the university's **strengths in open publishing** are:

- More than 60 percent of publications (according to Scopus™, Web of Science™, and OpenAlex) are open access. According to Scopus™ and the Web of Science™, the green route is dominating.
- Researchers from Charles University published first of all in cooperation with researchers from the University of Copenhagen and Sorbonne University.
- Provision of data to the OpenAPC database, increasing transparency of publication fee expenditure.

The **weak points** are:

- According to the COKI database, 37 percent of publications from 2022 were closed.

- The worrying phenomenon is MDPI's first position among the most popular publishers (according to the Web of Science™ database). Publishing in journals of dubious reputation can lead to the reduction of citation rates and loss of scientific credibility.

The University of Copenhagen (UCPH)

According to the study, the university's **strengths in open publishing** are:

- A tool for monitoring open access publications: [Danish Open Access Indicator](#).
- High (ranked 2nd) number of OA publications in the database analysis.
- Gold and hybrid publishing models dominate at the UCPH.
- Strong network with Sorbonne and Heidelberg universities, evidenced by many joint publications (506 and 505 in 2021-2022).

Heidelberg University (HU)

According to the study, the university's **strengths in open publishing** are:

- The highest percentage of publications with DOI number — 99 percent. Publications with DOI are more visible and accessible on the Internet and, hence more frequently cited.
- As much as 75-77 percent of the university's scholarly publications are open access.
- The highest number of joint publications in the 4EU+ Alliance with Sorbonne University — 608 (in 2021-2022) which demonstrates strong collaboration between these universities.

The University of Milan (UM)

According to the study, the university's **strengths in open publishing** are:

- The online platform for monitoring Open Access publications [Indicatore RIC-5 DIP percentuale di pubblicazioni sul totale annuale, open access gold e green](#).
- The highest percentage of publications with DOI number — 99 percent.
- According to the COKI database, 50 percent of publications are available from both publishers' and other open platforms.
- Provision of data to the OpenAPC database, increasing transparency of publication fee expenditure.

The **weak points** are:

- MDPI's first position among the most popular publishers (according to the Web of Science™ and the OpenAPC).

Sorbonne University (SU)

According to the study, the university's **strengths in open publishing** are:

- A webpage for monitoring Open Access publications ([Baromètre Science Ouverte de Sorbonne Université – Publications](#)¹²⁴):

¹²⁴ English version can be found at <https://www.sorbonne-universite.fr/en/research-and-innovation/research-strategy/commitments-open-science>.

- [Publications](#)¹²⁵
- [Doctoral theses](#)¹²⁶
- [Codes & software](#)¹²⁷
- [Research data](#)¹²⁸
- The highest number of publications in the databases analysed (between 24,000 and 28,000). In addition, the highest number of OA publications are indexed in Scopus™, the Web of Science™, and the OpenAlex databases.
- Predominance of the green route of open publishing (HAL repository).
- Considering all databases, more than 70 percent of publications are OA.
- The highest number of joint publications in the 4EU+ Alliance with Heidelberg University — 608 (in 2021-22). This demonstrates the strong collaboration between these universities. In addition, a strong research cooperation with the University of Copenhagen and the University of Milan is evident.
- Provision of data to the OpenAPC database, increasing transparency of publication fee expenditure.

The University of Warsaw (UW)

According to the study, the university's **strengths in open publishing** are:

- Considering all databases, more than 60 percent of publications indexed in the databases analysed are open, although the University of Warsaw has not yet adopted an open science policy.
- An analysis of the databases shows that the gold and green publishing routes dominate, although the University of Warsaw does not yet have an institutional repository.
- Lack of medical faculty limited the UW's publishing capacity in 2021-2022. However, a new Faculty of Medicine was inaugurated in October 2023. This creates fresh prospects for collaboration within the Alliance in the years to come.
- The University of Warsaw collaborates most strongly with Charles University (227 papers).

The **weak points** are:

- According to the COKI database, 29 percent of publications are available from both publishers' and other open platforms.
- MDPI's first position among the most popular publishers (according to the Web of Science database).
- Low number of joint publications with other universities: UM (39), HE (57), UCPH (60).

¹²⁵ English version can be found at <https://www.sorbonne-universite.fr/en/research-and-innovation/research-strategy/sorbonne-universitys-open-science-monitor-publications>

¹²⁶ English version can be found at <https://www.sorbonne-universite.fr/en/research-and-innovation/research-strategy/sorbonne-universitys-open-science-monitor-ph-d-theses>

¹²⁷ English version can be found at <https://www.sorbonne-universite.fr/en/research-and-innovation/research-strategy/sorbonne-universitys-open-science-monitor-codes-sofware>

¹²⁸ English version can be found at <https://www.sorbonne-universite.fr/research-and-innovation/research-strategy/sorbonne-universitys-open-science-monitor-research-data>

3.2.2. Findings of the study on forms of support for responsible publishing

Within the 4EU+ Alliance, the landscape of existing solutions designed to promote responsible publishing is notably multifaceted. Each member institution has developed its own set of strategies and resources to address the challenges and opportunities associated with responsible publishing. The varying approaches within the Alliance illustrate the broad range of experiences, requirements, and preferences present in the member institutions.

The differences we observe can be attributed to several factors. First, they are influenced by the varying stages of development and maturity of the infrastructure that supports responsible publishing across the member institutions. Some universities may have well-established systems and practices, while others may be in the process of building and refining their infrastructure. Second, these disparities are shaped by the complex interplay of regulations and publication requirements. Each institution operates within its national context, which may have distinct regulations and expectations for responsible publishing. These regulations can significantly impact the strategies and approaches adopted by universities in their efforts to support responsible publishing. Thus, the combination of infrastructure development and regulatory environments contributes to the diversity of approaches within the Alliance.

The 4EU+ Alliance universities, and libraries in particular, can continue to foster collaboration in responsible publishing by:

- **Co-creating Guidelines:** Collaboratively developing comprehensive guidelines on publishing issues that draw from best practices within their institutions and the broader national context. These guidelines can serve as valuable resources for researchers and authors. With a particular focus on sharing knowledge about copyright, free licensing, and the retention of authors' rights.
- **Building Infrastructures for Strengthening National Initiatives:** Improving national infrastructures will simplify the research process by providing core platforms for accessing and disseminating scientific publications, fostering a culture of shared knowledge and mutual support in research activities. In parallel, monitoring the progress of open publications becomes more efficient, enabling universities to track and assess the impact of their research initiatives. In the context of 4EU+ Alliance they can indeed serve as valuable platforms for networking, knowledge exchange, and the sharing of technology related to Open Science infrastructures.
- **Promoting University Press Cooperation:** Encouraging collaboration among university presses to explore innovative publishing models for books. This cooperation can lead to the development of sustainable and open access publishing practices.
- **Increasing Research Publication:** Advocating for the growth of the Alliance's collaborative network by stimulating research publication across a broad spectrum of disciplines. This includes not only fields within science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) but also the social sciences and humanities (SSH).

- **Integrating Open Science in Education:** Promoting the integration of Open Science practices into academic curricula and fostering a culture of open research. Additionally, advocacy for the regular evaluation of researchers to assess their engagement with Open Science practices and their contributions to the open scholarly ecosystem.

3.3. Good practices

In the course of the work on Case #2, a selection and description of the best or most inspiring practices in terms of dedicated responsible open publishing support has been carried out.

Figure 22. Tools and solutions to support publishing analysed in Case #2

We have categorised information on open access publishing as presented below, with a focus on website-based content, publishing infrastructures and training courses (in person/online). A full description with reference to the materials is provided in the tables, with a breakdown by each university (Sections 3.3.1. – 3.3.5.).

Good practices in methodological support for authors on open publishing (overall courses):

- CU: Open Access at CU – How to publish Open Access?; Open Science: Open Access & Research Data Management; Open science for researchers and staff; Open science for doctoral students; MOOC Open Science (for doctoral students and open to everyone).
- SU: Open Science MOOC; How to recognise a predatory journal? Open Access publishing thanks to the right retention strategy; Open access and HAL: what are my rights?; Workshop deposit in HAL; Markdown text editors and bibliographic tools; ORCID and idHAL digital identifiers: how to improve your online presence?; Preparing

for funders' requirements; Open science for PhD students : Open access to scientific publications; Open Science, the exception that is becoming the rule; ORCID and idHAL digital identifiers; Scientific posters; Academic publication circuit. Some training sessions for Masters students: introduction to open science, digital humanities and identifiers.

- HU: Open Access & Open Science; Research Data Management; Good Scientific Practice; Proper citation and avoidance of plagiarism; Successfully publish your dissertation in the social sciences and humanities; Writing scientific papers in English for doctoral students.
- UCPH: Open up your Academic Publishing Toolbox; A basic introduction to Open Access; Open Access and funding compliance; Responsible Conduct of Research 2: Getting Ready for Submission of Manuscripts and Thesis.
- UM: Open Science for doctoral students; Open Science in the project [ENABLECARES](#); Research Data Management RDM; Open Badge for students of Master and single-cycle degree programmes.
- UW: Open science infrastructure: publication paths, open journals, repositories, publishing policy; Open Mandate and Grant Programs. Plan S. Open Publishing Programs; What journal to publish in?; The course on the University's e-learning platform is currently under review (only in Polish). Planned release date early 2024.
- 4EU + Alliance : “Open for you!” cycle.

The overall training reported by the partners were predominantly delivered by university libraries, often by library staff, as part of university-wide courses (e.g., HU). They cover a variety of target groups, all interested, students, doctoral students, researchers. At one university (UM) the courses are run by an autonomous unit (not part of the library) dedicated to open science. Additionally, two universities (CU, SU) organised content on open science (including publishing) using a MOOC platform. The UW has developed its course on an e-learning platform and aims to make it available in early 2024. During general training sessions, topics on open publishing are regularly presented together with information on open research data (case #1). We have not separated this information to reflect the actual syllabus structure of the training.

Good practices in evaluating journals (How to find a suitable OA journal to publish in? Journal finder. How to avoid predatory journals? White lists of journals):

- CU: Webpage – Description How to Find an Appropriate Open Access Journal for Publication; Information about DOAJ and predatory publishers.
- SU: Webpage – List of more than 3,300 presumed non-predatory journals in medical fields.
- HU: Linking to Whitelist OA Journals (DOAJ).
- UCPH: Webpage – ChronosHub Journal Finder.
- UM: Webpage – Linking to Think.Check.Submit and Compass to Publish.
- UW: Webpage – The Ministry list of punctuated journals; Link to specific tools; A warning against predatory publishers.

Each university has provided guidance on its website and links to the most popular tools, mainly international ones. Despite this, the discussion surrounding predatory journal lists remains a contentious issue within the academic community (most recently the subject of the MDPI publisher, i.a.).

Good practices in information on APC/BPC fees (prices, rules, discounts, list of editors, etc.):

- CU: Webpage – CzechELib consortium lists; data on open publication fees (APC) paid by the Charles University in a given year, breakdown by publisher and journal title.
- SU: Webpage – Information on consortia and agreements with publishers, APC and discounts.
- HU: Webpage – Overview discounts Open Access publications (APC) in Germany-wide consortia; Data on open publication fees (APC) paid by the Heidelberg University; Description of the Open Access Monograph Fund, Open Access Publishing Fund.
- UCPH: Webpage (UCPH Intranet) + leaflet, infographic, and video – Discounts and waivers on Open Access publishing; Guidelines for Open Access publishing in licence agreements between The Royal Danish Library and publishing houses; The Danish Open Access Indicator; Open Access in CURIS; Open Access Submission Form.
- UM: Webpage – Open publication funding form; Reports on the open publication fees (APC); Data on open publication fees (APC) paid by the University of Milan; Overview discounts Open Access publications (APC) and agreements.
- UW: Webpage – Description of open publishing programs; Overview discounts Open Access publications (APC) and publishing agreements; Overview of and linking to Open Access Publishing Fund (articles and monographs).

Each partner of the 4EU+ Alliance ensures that its employees have access to information about existing open publishing agreements and possible APC/BPC subsidies. If there is any funding available for open publishing, the relevant information material and funding application forms provide details.

Good practices in legal support for open publishing, copyrights (legal aspects):

- SU: Webpage – Description of the Creative Commons Licence (in French); Webpage and PDF leaflet – *I publish, what rights do I have?* (in French, national level).
- HU: Course – An introduction to copyright law for doctoral students.
- UCPH: Webpage (UCPH Intranet) – Copyright in relation to open access publishing; *Forskerportalen* (The Researcher Portal) – Open Access and Copyright Law.
- UW in cooperation with other Polish institutions: Online course and textbook in PDF (in Polish) – *Intellectual Property* at Polish universities; Publication (monograph) – “Otwarty dostęp do publikacji naukowych. Kwestie prawne.” (English: *Open access to scientific publications. Legal issues*).

Responsible publishing recognises that authors retain rights through the principle of copyright retention and ensures that authors retain control over the use and dissemination of their work. As a result, authors retain the right to decide how their research is shared, reused and distributed, contributing to a more equitable and author-friendly scholarly publishing landscape. The retention of copyright is in line with the broader goals of open access and transparency in the dissemination of research. It enables authors to make knowledgeable decisions about the accessibility and licensing of their scholarly output. It is apparent that not all universities within the alliance provide courses to aid authors in managing their copyright. This ultimately impacts the effectiveness of their negotiation with publishers in terms of publishing contracts. Each partner should take the time to assess what this support should look like and which experts should be involved in preparing this type of training. This is an essential issue, so it is worth developing it further to ensure that it is not just mentioned in general training on open science.

Good practices in providing the infrastructure, i.e. repositories and open publishing platforms:

- CU: CU Digital Repository for theses and dissertations defended at the Charles University; CU's repository of publishing activities (various types of publication); Publishing – Karolinum Press (since 2015 in open access).
- SU: Repository – Sorbonne University HAL repository.
- HU: Repository – heiDOK – The Heidelberg Document Repository; Publishing – Heidelberg University Publishing (heiUP); heiJOURNALS; heiBOOKS; Subject-specific information services with open access publishing venues.
- UCPH: Repository – CURIS (Copenhagen University Research Information System); Publishing – Tidsskrift.dk.
- UM: Repository – AIR - Institutional Research Repository; IRIS - Research Information System; Publishing – Milano University Press (UNIMI Journals and UNIMI Books).
- UW: Repository – University of Warsaw Repository (collects doctoral dissertations; an updated version available in early 2024 will also include additional scientific contributions beyond current scope); Publishing Press – University of Warsaw Press.

At each university, there exists repository infrastructure, currently undergoing optimisation. For a detailed overview, refer to Case #1 in Part 2. Regarding this infrastructure, each partner has developed their own materials for the purpose of dissemination and training. In terms of publishing platforms offering software dedicated to managing the publication process (without open peer review, but with final open publication), the partners are at different stages of development. University publishing houses mainly provide support for these tools. The HU is most advanced in terms of tools and software, with the IT department working with the publishing house and the library. The UM is also implementing infrastructure for open books and journals on a larger scale (both OJS and OMP – PKP systems).

3.3.1. Examples of information and support activities (training, websites) on open publishing

CHARLES UNIVERSITY (CU)	
Name of the course	Open Access at CU – How to publish Open Access?
Scope	Open Access – basic principles, green, gold route, how to publish Open Access, predatory journals, what is open access?, OA at Charles University
Form, duration	MOOC : 5 modules with an introduction, Online course, Free – can log in as a quest
Link to webpage (if exists, e.g. e-learning course)	Czech: https://dlcv.cuni.cz/course/view.php?id=381#section-0 English: https://dlcv.cuni.cz/course/view.php?id=490
Provider	Central Library of Charles University
Availability	Since 2020
Language	Czech, English
Note	Without ECTS credits

Name of the course	Open Science: Open Access & Research Data Management
Scope	Open Access – basic principles, OA routes, CU’s OA repository – how to use, Research data management (RDM), FAIR Data Principles, DMP, Data sharing
Form, duration	30-90 minutes, Ad hoc courses (available on demand), Online or in person
Link to webpage (if exists, e.g. e-learning course)	not applicable
Provider	Central Library of Charles University
Availability	2021/2022, 2022/2023
Language	Czech
Note	Without ECTS credits

THE UNIVERSITY OF COPENHAGEN (UCPH)	
Name of the course	Open up your Academic Publishing Toolbox
Scope	Copyright in publishing, Creative Commons licences, open access publishing, responsible metrics and responsible evaluation of researchers, management and optimization of researcher profiles, data management and the FAIR principles
Form, duration	8-hour workshop, In person
Link to webpage (if exists, e.g. e-learning course)	https://kubkalender.kb.dk/event/3990611
Provider	University of Copenhagen Library
Availability	Spring 2023
Language	English
Note	<p>For doctoral students with the division into three groups:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Natural and Health Sciences ● Humanities and Social Sciences (SSH) ● All faculties <p>Additional materials on the Absalon platform (it is the University of Copenhagen's digital learning platform) 1 ECTS credit</p>

Name of the course	A basic introduction to Open Access
Scope	The different Open Access routes, archiving accepted manuscripts in CURIS, publishing with a reduced or waived publishing fee, how Copenhagen University Library supports researchers in publishing Open Access
Form, duration	1-hour webinar, Online
Link to webpage (if exists, e.g. e-learning course)	https://kubkalender.kb.dk/event/3975902
Provider	University of Copenhagen Library
Availability	Spring 2023
Language	English
Note	Without ECTS credits

Name of the course	Open Access and funding compliance
Scope	The Danish public funds' Open Access conditions, Open Access conditions from the EU framework programme Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe, how to determine the journals' Open Access policies, how Copenhagen University Library supports researchers in complying with Open Access requirements
Form, duration	1-hour webinar, Online
Link to webpage (if exists, e.g. e-learning course)	https://kubkalender.kb.dk/event/3975904
Provider	University of Copenhagen Library
Availability	Spring 2023
Language	English
Note	Without ECTS credits

Name of the course	Responsible Conduct of Research 2: Getting Ready for Submission of Manuscripts and Thesis
Scope	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • open access requirements • data management • authorship issues • duplicate text • documentation of ethical and legal permissions • declaring your conflicts of interest
Form, duration	4-hour course, Online or in person
Link to webpage (if exists, e.g. e-learning course)	https://healthsciences.ku.dk/phd/phd-courses/obligatoryintroductioncourse/responsible-conduct-of-research-2-getting-ready-for-submission-of-manuscripts-and-thesis/
Provider	UCPH Graduate Schools at the Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences / Faculty of Science
Availability	Spring 2023
Language	English
Note	Mandatory for doctoral students 1-1.5 ECTS credits

HEIDELBERG UNIVERSITY (HU)	
Name of the course	Open Access & Open Science
Scope	<p>The course would like to invite you to participate in the current discussion about open science in its different facets. The workshop focus on the following topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Open access for text publications and research data ● Current developments on the publication market ● Open licences and copyright issues ● Open peer review and alternative metrics. <p>In addition, various open science services available on campus will be presented.</p>
Form, duration	3-hour workshop, In person
Link to webpage (if exists, e.g. e-learning course)	https://www.graduateacademy.uni-heidelberg.de/karriere/workshops_en.html
Provider	Instructor from University Library, organisation via Graduate Academy (additionally equivalent courses are offered as “free” courses independent of the Graduate Academy’s program ¹²⁹)
Availability	2021/2022, 2022/2023
Language	German
Note	Without ECTS credits

Name of the course	Research Data Management
Scope	<p>Topics like data sharing and data publication are becoming increasingly important. This course is meant to give a general, discipline-independent introduction to various topics essential to the efficient management of research data with a special focus on questions related to data archiving and Open Research Data.</p>
Form, duration	4-hour, Workshop, In person
Link to webpage (if exists, e.g. e-learning course)	https://www.graduateacademy.uni-heidelberg.de/karriere/workshops_en.html

¹²⁹ https://www.graduateacademy.uni-heidelberg.de/karriere/workshops/kursarchiv_en.html

Provider	Instructors from Competence Centre for Research Data, organisation via Graduate Academy (additionally equivalent courses are offered as “free” courses independent of the Graduate Academy’s program ¹³⁰)
Availability	2021/2022, 2022/2023
Language	English
Note	Without ECTS credits

Name of the course	Good Scientific Practice
Scope	<p>Participants will explore the differences and grey areas between good scientific practice, questionable research practice, and scientific misconduct. They will learn how misconduct can be recognized and prevented, and how it should be addressed and dealt with in case it occurs, and what damage it can cause if handled improperly. The content of the course follows the curriculum “Good Scientific Practice” which was commissioned by and developed in cooperation with the Research Ombudsman (DFG):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definitions of good scientific practice and scientific misconduct • Degrees and extent of scientific misconduct • Examples of responsible and irresponsible conduct of research data management • Authorship and the process of publication • Mentoring and supervision • Conflict management: how to deal with scientific misconduct • Local, national and international guidelines
Form, duration	8-hour, Workshop, Online
Link to webpage (if exists, e.g. e-learning course)	https://www.graduateacademy.uni-heidelberg.de/karriere/workshops_en.html
Provider	Graduate Academy
Availability	2021/2022, 2022/2023
Language	English
Note	Without ECTS credits

¹³⁰ Ibid.

Name of the course	Proper citation and avoidance of plagiarism
Scope	<p>The course provides an overview of the correct citation and the avoidance of plagiarism. The focus is on the following questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What do I have to cite and how much? • How do I deal with illustrations? • How can plagiarism be avoided? • How can I detect plagiarism with and without software?
Form, duration	3-hour, Workshop, In person
Link to webpage (if exists, e.g. e-learning course)	https://www.graduateacademy.uni-heidelberg.de/karriere/workshops_en.html
Provider	Instructor from University Library, organisation via Graduate Academy (additionally equivalent courses are offered as “free” courses independent of the Graduate Academy’s program ¹³¹).
Availability	2021/2022, 2022/2023
Language	German
Note	<p>SEMINAR – PROGRAMM 2023 – II: https://www.graduateacademy.uni-heidelberg.de/md/gradakad/workshops/ga/seminarprogramm_2023_i_i_web.pdf Without ECTS credits</p>

Name of the course	Successfully publish your dissertation in the social sciences and humanities
Scope	<p>The course offers comprehensive information on the topics of publication strategies for doctoral students in the humanities and social sciences:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • publication forms and strategies, • financing possibilities, • selection, cooperation and negotiation with publishers.
Form, duration	3-hour, Workshop, In person
Link to webpage (if exists, e.g. e-learning course)	https://www.graduateacademy.uni-heidelberg.de/karriere/workshops_en.html

¹³¹ https://www.graduateacademy.uni-heidelberg.de/karriere/workshops/kursarchiv_en.html

Provider	Instructor from University Library, organisation via Graduate Academy (additionally equivalent courses are offered as “free” courses independent of the Graduate Academy’s program ¹³²).
Availability	2021/2022, 2022/2023
Language	German
Note	SEMINAR – PROGRAMM 2023 – I: https://www.graduateacademy.uni-heidelberg.de/md/gradakad/workshops/ga/seminarprogramm_2023_1_web.pdf Without ECTS credits

Name of the course	Writing scientific papers in English for doctoral students
Scope	In the academic world clear, concise, and well-written texts play an important role in convincing journal editors and conference organisers to accept a paper for review and publication, or to invite a researcher to present at a conference. This workshop provides doctoral students with strategies to write short texts efficiently and effectively. It enables participants to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● organise ideas and structure texts effectively, ● present their own and other researchers’ findings and opinions appropriately, ● use correct terminology and vocabulary
Form, duration	14-hour (2 days), Workshop, Online
Link to webpage (if exists, e.g. e-learning course)	https://www.graduateacademy.uni-heidelberg.de/karriere/workshops_en.html
Provider	External trainer, organised by Graduate Academy
Availability	2021/2022, 2022/2023
Language	English
Note	Without ECTS credits

Name of the course	An introduction to copyright law for doctoral students
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¹³² Ibid.

Description	<p>When preparing a dissertation, numerous copyright issues are of concern, e.g., How are one's research results protected? Under what conditions may third-party images and graphics be used in a publication? What are the limits of permissible quotations? What should be considered when concluding a publishing agreement for the publication of the dissertation? The course introduces copyright regulations relevant to doctoral students and imparts basic knowledge by means of concrete application examples.</p> <p>Main focus:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • basics of copyright law (What exactly does copyright protect (work in the sense of the UrhG)?, What rights do authors have?, etc.), • dealing with other people's intellectual property in the context of one's own research and teaching (legally permitted uses for teaching and science, in particular, §§ 60 c and d UrhG) • publication, duplication, and utilisation of own research results (§§ 31 ff. UrhG, publishing law, OA licences).
Form of the training	1.5-hour, Workshop, Online or in person
Link to webpage (if exists, e.g. e-learning course)	https://www.ub.uni-heidelberg.de/Englisch/schulung/Welcome.html
Provider	University Library
Academic year	2021/2022, 2022/2023
Language	German
Note	<p>For advanced students and doctoral candidates with the division into two groups:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Humanities and Social Sciences, • Medicine and Natural Sciences <p>Without ECTS credits</p>

THE UNIVERSITY OF MILAN (UM)

Name of the course	Open science for doctoral students
Scope	Open Science policies and tools (e.g. Research Institutional Archive), Open Access, FAIR data, preprint, and open peer review , research integrity and research evaluation, rights management, predatory publishers , reproducibility of research
Form, duration	12-hour course (12 hours for each area: science, medicine and HSS), Online

This project has received funding from The European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016674

Link to webpage (if exists, e.g. e-learning course)	https://www.unimi.it/en/study/postgraduate-study/doctoral-research-phd-programmes/following-your-plan-study/soft-skills
Provider	Open science Unit
Availability	Since 2017
Language	Italian, English
Note	Without ECTS credits

Name of the course	Open science in the project ENABLECARES
Scope	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Open access ● FAIR data ● Data management and DMP ● Data storage ● Predatory journals ● Ethics aspects ● Evaluation ● Management of rights and licences, ● Research ethics and data protection ● Funders' requirement ● Tools: Sherpa; DOAJ, CORE; Unpaywall etc.
Form, duration	16-hour course, Ad hoc course, Plenary sessions, hands-on sessions in presence, the completion of assignments and complementary e-learning materials
Link to webpage (if exists, e.g. e-learning course)	https://www.semm.it/education/courses
Provider	Open science Unit (part on FAIR data in cooperation with Istituto Europeo di Oncologia - IEO)
Availability	Academic year: 2021/2022, 2022/2023
Language	Italian, English
Note	Without ECTS credits

Name of the course	Research Data Management RDM
Scope	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data management plan (RDM) ● FAIR data

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Use of dataverse
Form, duration	1-hour course (on RDM or dataverse or DMP) the last Friday of each month
Link to webpage (if exists, e.g. e-learning course)	https://rdm.unimi.it/training
Provider	Open science Unit
Availability	Academic year: 2022/2023
Language	Italian, English
Note	Without ECTS credits

Name of the course	Open Badge for students of Master's and single-cycle degree programmes
Scope	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Open science principles ● Data management and DMP ● Open access ● European Commission guidelines and Open Science policies
Form, duration	10-hour course, Online and in person
Link to webpage (if exists, e.g. e-learning course)	https://best.it/badge/show/2386
Provider	Open science Unit
Availability	Academic year: 2021/2022, 2022/2023
Language	Italian, English
Note	Without ECTS credits

SORBONNE UNIVERSITY (SU)

Name of the course	Open science for researchers and staff
Scope	Fundamentals of open science: open access, open data, digital humanities, research dissemination
Form of the training	58-hour course, Online and in presence

This project has received funding from The European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016674

Link to webpage (if exists, e.g. e-learning course)	https://www.sorbonne-universite.fr/sites/default/files/media/2023-08/Catalogue-interactif-2023-2024%20_%20site%20web%20V1.pdf (Section I.)
Provider	SU Library
Academic year	2021/2022, 2022/2023, 2023/2024
Language	French, English
Note	Without ECTS credits, Including OAW and love data week

Name of the course	Open science for doctoral students
Scope	Wikipedia, publications and research integrity, bibliometrics, open access, open data
Form of the training	49-hour course, Online and in presence
Link to webpage (if exists, e.g. e-learning course)	https://www.sorbonne-universite.fr/sites/default/files/media/2023-08/Catalogue-interactif-2023-2024%20_%20site%20web%20V1.pdf (Section IV.)
Provider	SU Library
Academic year	2021/2022, 2022/2023, 2023/2024
Language	French, English
Note	Can be included in the PhD portfolio (individual course plan) required to validate the PhD.

Name of the course	MOOC open science (for doctoral students and open to everyone)
Scope	Fundamentals of open science
Form of the training	8 hours minimum to get the certificate, and complementary material (additional videos), Online course
Link to webpage (if exists, e.g. e-learning course)	https://www.fun-mooc.fr/fr/cours/la-science-ouverte/ (in French) https://www.fun-mooc.fr/en/courses/open-science/ (in English)
Provider	SU Library
Academic year	2021/2022, 2022/2023, 2023/2024

Language	French, English
Note	Suggested as a baseline before starting a course for researchers and doctoral students. Can be included in the PhD portfolio (individual course plan) required to validate the PhD

THE UNIVERSITY OF WARSAW (UW)

Name of the course	Open science infrastructure: publication paths, open journals, repositories, publishing policy
Scope	<p>The topics of the course:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • principles and spectrum of open publishing practices, • policy of openness of leading Polish and foreign publishers, • publishing strategies and forms of journals distribution, • how to make our publications available in accordance with the requirements of copyright law and scientific ethics, and how to read publishing contracts.
Form of the training	1.5-hour online course with presentation and discussion
Link to webpage (if exists, e.g. e-learning course)	not applicable
Provider	University of Warsaw Library
Academic year	2022/2023, 2023/2024
Language	Polish
Note	Without ECTS credits

Name of the course	Open Mandate and Grant Programs. Plan S. Open Publishing Programs
Scope	<p>The topics of the course:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • requirements of institutions financing science in the context of open science, • open science policy of the National Science Centre, European Commission regulations in this regard and the assumptions of Plan S, • university and national programs supporting open publishing at the university and in Poland.
Form of the training	1.5-hour online course with presentation and discussion

Link to webpage (if exists, e.g. e-learning course)	not applicable
Provider	University of Warsaw Library
Academic year	2022/2023, 2023/2024
Language	Polish
Note	Without ECTS credits

Name of the course	What journal to publish in?
Scope	<p>Training for authors of scientific articles. The topics of the course:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● journal selection criteria, ● tools that can be helpful in finding the right title for publication, ● most popular forms of publishing contracts, ● how a copyright transfer agreement works, ● what provisions are worth paying attention to protect author's copyrights.
Form of the training	1.5-hour online course with presentation and discussion
Link to webpage (if exists, e.g. e-learning course)	not applicable
Provider	University of Warsaw Library
Academic year	2022/2023, 2023/2024
Language	Polish
Note	Without ECTS credits

Name of the course	Open for you! An introduction series to open science
Scope	<p>The topics of the course:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Research integrity and open science ● Open access (journals, monographs for Humanities) ● Open licences ● Right retention strategy ● Open peer review ● Predatory publishers

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Searching for open access works ● Data Management and FAIR Data (Humanities, Science, technology and engineering) ● Researcher ID ● Open research software ● Citizen science
Form of the training	15-hour online course with presentation, flash-interviews and discussion
Link to webpage (if exists, e.g. e-learning course)	https://4euplus.eu/4EU-273.html https://4euplus.eu/4EU-688.html
Provider	4EU+ Alliance
Academic year	2021/2022, 2022/2023, 2023/2024 (online soon)
Language	English
Note	Without ECTS credits. Two editions organised, third under preparation.

3.3.2. Examples of information and support activities (training, websites) on evaluating of journals, predatory journals, white lists

CHARLES UNIVERSITY (CU)	
Scope	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Description How to Find an Appropriate Open Access Journal for Publication ● About the practices of predatory publishers and how to avoid them ● Information about DOAJ
Form	Webpage
Provider	Open Science Support Centre in Charles University Central Library
Link to webpage	https://openscience.cuni.cz/OSCIEN-39.html https://openscience.cuni.cz/OSCIEN-27.html https://openscience.cuni.cz/OSCIEN-36.html

SORBONNE UNIVERSITY (SU)	
Scope	Alphabetical list of more than 3,300 presumed non-predatory journals in medical fields prepared between October 2020 and May 2021 by the Faculty of Medicine of Sorbonne University
Form	Webpage (only in French)

Provider	Faculty of Medicine of Sorbonne University
Link to webpage	https://sante.sorbonne-universite.fr/recherche-0/liste-des-revues-non-predatrices

THE UNIVERSITY OF COPENHAGEN (UCPH)

Scope	ChronosHub Journal Finder is a database where you can search for journals that meet specific requirements from funders. The database contains more than 26,000 journals. After choosing a grant provider, you can further sort the journals by discipline, etc.
Form	Webpage
Provider	A joint initiative of several universities (including the Royal Library of Denmark and the University of Copenhagen) and publishers. ChronosHub was built in 2016 to encourage the adoption of the policy, reduce complexity, and minimise manual work. While initially built for the Gates Foundation, ChronosHub was re-designed to scale to the broader research community to simplify the implementation of publishing policies for research and address the grantees' concerns about additional workload. ChronosHub takes a collaborative approach to support all scholarly communication stakeholders throughout the publishing process. Since its launch in 2017, ChronosHub has managed over 20 thousand grants and ten thousand OA articles with over \$22 million in article processing charges (APCs).
Link to webpage	https://ku.chronoshub.io/?jf https://chronoshub.io/

THE UNIVERSITY OF MILAN (UM)

Scope	Presents basic information on predatory publishers and gives tools on how to avoid them e.g., link to Think.Check.Submit ¹³³ , Compass to Publish ¹³⁴ and search engines for open access materials
Form	Webpage
Provider	Open Science Policy Support Office

¹³³ <https://thinkchecksubmit.org/>

¹³⁴ <https://app.lib.uliege.be/compass-to-publish/>

Link to webpage	https://www.unimi.it/it/ricerca/dati-e-prodotti-della-ricerca/scienza-aperta/scienza-aperta-materiali-e-strumenti
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THE UNIVERSITY OF WARSAW (UW)

Scope	The Polish Ministry of Education and Science List of Journals (assigning specific scores to individual titles and publishers)
Form	Webpage
Provider	The Polish Ministry of Education and Science
Link to webpage	https://www.gov.pl/web/edukacja-i-nauka/nowy-rozszerzony-wykaz-czasopism-naukowych-i-recenzowanych-materialow-z-konferencji-miedzynarodowych

Scope	Link to specific tools to help verify the title of the journal: Think. Check. Submit. and DOAJ
Form	Webpage
Provider	The University of Warsaw
Link to webpage	https://www.buw.uw.edu.pl/dla-nauki/otwarta-nauka/otwarte-publicacje-naukowe/

Scope	A warning against predatory publishers and a reference to a letter from the Director of the National Science Center (NCN)
Form	Webpage
Provider	The University of Warsaw Research Administration Office
Link to webpage	http://bob.uw.edu.pl/list-dyrektora-ncn-ws-drapieznym-czasopism-predatory-journals/

3.3.3. Examples of information and support activities (training, websites) on APC/BPC, prices, discounts, rules, list of editors

CHARLES UNIVERSITY (CU)	
Scope	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Open Access Publishing ● Open Access types ● Research Funders' Policies ● Discounts and waivers on Open Access publishing (APC): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ American Chemical Society (ACS) ○ American Institute of Physics (AIP) ○ Association for Computing Machinery (ACM) ○ Cambridge University Press (CUP) ○ IOPscience ○ Karger Publishers ○ Lippincott Williams & Wilkins (LWW) ○ Oxford University Press (OUP) ○ Royal Society of Chemistry (RSC) ○ SAGE ○ SCOAP3 ○ Springer Nature ○ Taylor & Francis ○ Wiley
Form	Webpage
Provider	Open Science Support Centre in Charles University Central Library & CzechELib
Link to webpage	https://openscience.cuni.cz/OSCIEN-10.html & https://www.czechelib.cz/en/442-instructions-for-authors
Scope	Data on open publication fees (APC) paid by Charles University in a given year, breakdown by publisher and journal title
Form	Webpage – data visualisation
Provider	The OpenAPC initiative – Charles University uploads its APC fee data to this webpage
Link to webpage	https://treemaps.openapc.net/apcdata/charles-u/

SORBONNE UNIVERSITY (SU)

Scope	Information on consortia and agreements with publishers, APC and discounts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cambridge University Press (CUP) ● EDP Sciences ● Elsevier ● Thieme ● Wiley ● Wolters Kluwer (Ovid)
Form	University main webpage (only in French)
Provider	Content prepared by Sorbonne University Library
Link to webpage	https://www.sorbonne-universite.fr/remises-sur-les-frais-de-publication-en-open-access

Scope	Data on open publication fees (APC) paid by Sorbonne University in a given year, breakdown by publisher and journal title
Form	Webpage – data visualisation
Provider	The OpenAPC initiative – Sorbonne University uploads its APC fee data to this webpage
Link to webpage	https://treemaps.openapc.net/apcdata/sorbonne-u/#publisher/

HEIDELBERG UNIVERSITY (HU)

Scope	Overview discounts Open Access publications (APC) in Germany-wide consortia: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● BMJ – British Medical Journals ● Cambridge University Press ● Frontiers ● De Gruyter ● Hogrefe ● MDPI ● PNAS – Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences ● RSC – Royal Society of Chemistry ● Sage ● American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS): Science Advances ● SCOAP3
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Springer Nature (inclusive Springer Open & BMC Central) ● Wiley <p>Linking to Whitelist OA Journals (DOAJ), Referenced materials on the linked page https://open-access.network/en</p>
Form	Webpage
Provider	The Heidelberg University Library
Link to webpage	https://www.ub.uni-heidelberg.de/Englisch/service/openaccess/monographienfonds.html

Scope	<p>Open Access Monograph Fund:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Requirements for funding ● Eligible publications – these are in particular, but not exclusively, publishers that are members of the Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association (OASPA) or listed in the Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB). In particular, these include university open access publishers such as Heidelberg University Publishing (heiUP) ● Procedure for assumption of costs and application
Form	Webpage
Provider	The Heidelberg University Library
Link to webpage	https://www.ub.uni-heidelberg.de/Englisch/service/openaccess/monographienfonds.html

Scope	<p>Open Access Publishing Fund:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Funding conditions ● How to receive funding? ● Internal settlement of the remaining costs ● Discounts on open access publications (link to information resources mentioned earlier) ● Fund for Open Access Monographs (link to information resources mentioned earlier) <p>Application form for funding by the publishing fund of Heidelberg University, On the page provided links to records from the repository for works that have been funded by the OA fund</p>
Form	Webpage
Provider	The Heidelberg University Library

Link to webpage	https://www.ub.uni-heidelberg.de/Englisch/service/openaccess/publikationsfonds.html https://www.ub.uni-heidelberg.de/Englisch/service/openaccess/antrag.html
Scope	Data on open publication fees (APC) paid by the Heidelberg University in a given year, breakdown by publisher and journal title
Form	Webpage – data visualisation
Provider	The OpenAPC initiative – The Heidelberg University uploads its APC fee data to this webpage
Link to webpage	https://treemaps.openapc.net/apcdata/heidelberg-u/

THE UNIVERSITY OF COPENHAGEN (UCPH)

Scope	<p>The service guides in the following fields:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Open Access Publishing: What is Open Access and what are the benefits of Open Access? ● Open Access types: Green Open Access – Gold Open Access – Hybrid Open Access – Diamond Open Access ● Embargo periods: The publishers' embargo periods – Licences when depositing post-prints ● Open Access in CURIS: See how to handle Open Access in CURIS ● Open Access requirements from the EU and Danish funders: Horizon 2020 – Horizon Europe – Requirements on embargo periods – ChronosHub ● Discounts and waivers on Open Access publishing (APC): APC discounts — Free publishing options ● Open Access Submission Form: Make your post- or pre-print available as Open Access in CURIS ● Predatory Journals <p>Other resources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● “Open Access: You share, we take care” leaflet ● “OA Routes” infographic ● “What is a post-print” video¹³⁵
Form	Webpage – Research Portal KUnet / UCPH Intranet
Provider	Department for Research Support, University of Copenhagen Library

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https://api.kultura.nordu.net/index.php/extwidget/preview/partner_id/343/uiconf_id/23451035/entry_id/0_cudqk_cm2/embed/dynamic

This project has received funding from The European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016674

THE UNIVERSITY OF COPENHAGEN (UCPH)

Scope	<p>The service guides in the following fields:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Open Access Publishing: What is Open Access and what are the benefits of Open Access? ● Open Access types: Green Open Access – Gold Open Access – Hybrid Open Access – Diamond Open Access ● Embargo periods: The publishers' embargo periods – Licences when depositing post-prints ● Open Access in CURIS: See how to handle Open Access in CURIS ● Open Access requirements from the EU and Danish funders: Horizon 2020 – Horizon Europe – Requirements on embargo periods – ChronosHub ● Discounts and waivers on Open Access publishing (APC): APC discounts — Free publishing options ● Open Access Submission Form: Make your post- or pre-print available as Open Access in CURIS ● Predatory Journals <p>Other resources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● “Open Access: You share, we take care” leaflet ● “OA Routes” infographic ● “What is a post-print” video¹³⁵
Link to webpage	<p>https://kub.ku.dk/english/usethe/library/researchers/open-access/</p>
Note	<p>Eight Danish universities (with UCPH) submit data every year to the Danish Open Access Indicator¹³⁶. The Danish Open Access Indicator is produced and released annually by the Danish Agency for Higher Education and Science, part of the Ministry of Higher Education and Science. The Indicator monitors the implementation of the Danish Open Access Strategy 2018-2025¹³⁷ by collecting and analysing publication data from Danish universities. The intention is to support the implementation of the national Open Access strategy.</p>

Scope	<p>National Licensing Consortium: UCPH users receive APC waivers and discounts for a number of publishers under the agreements negotiated by the National Licensing Consortium / The Royal Danish Library, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Wiley Agreement 2022-25 ● Elsevier Agreement 2021-24 ● Springer Compact Agreement 2023-26 ● Cambridge University Press 2023-25
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¹³⁶ <https://www.oaindikator.dk/en/>

¹³⁷ <https://ufm.dk/en/research-and-innovation/cooperation-between-research-and-innovation/open-access/Publications/denmarks-national-strategy-for-open-access>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IOP Publishing Agreement 2023-25 • ACS, PNAS, MDPI, and others <p>On the webpage can be found guidelines for Open Access publishing in licence agreements between The Royal Danish Library and publishing houses.</p>
Form	Webpage
Provider	The Royal Danish Library
Link to webpage	https://pro.kb.dk/en/licensing/wiley-agreement-2022-25 https://pro.kb.dk/en/licensing/elsevier https://pro.kb.dk/en/licensing/springer-compact https://pro.kb.dk/en/licensing/cambridge-university-press https://pro.kb.dk/en/licensing/iop-publishing https://pro.kb.dk/en/licensing/oa-publication-guidelines

THE UNIVERSITY OF MILAN (UM)

Scope	Publication funding form, Rules of participation
Form	University webpage for employees (only in Italian)
Provider	Open Science Policy Support Office
Link to webpage	https://work.unimi.it/servizi_ricerca/127897.htm https://unimibox.unimi.it/index.php/s/GjTkFoiHdcDkdzs https://unimibox.unimi.it/index.php/s/39BX2pxen4BWBjD

Scope	General information and linking to materials on the gold, green and diamond publishing route available at the university
Form	Webpage
Provider	Open Science Policy Support Office
Link to webpage	https://www.unimi.it/en/research/research-data-and-outputs/open-science/open-access-university-milan

Scope	Reports on the open publication fees (APC), e.g. Reports Transformative agreements – Open Science Commission, Annual Reports Open Science Commission
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Form	Webpage (Reports only in Italian)
Provider	Open Science Policy Support Office
Link to webpage	https://www.unimi.it/en/research/research-data-and-outputs/open-science https://unimibox.unimi.it/index.php/s/9nXPfZNSE3ncQqs https://unimibox.unimi.it/index.php/s/9WsbKCCEzm7trri

Scope	<p>Overview discounts Open Access publications (APC) and agreements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Elsevier ● AAAS (Science) ● ACM American for Computing Machinery 2022 - 2025 ● ACS ● BioMed Central and Springer Open Journal ● BMJ British Medical Journal ● BMJ Case Reports ● Cambridge University Press 2023 - 2025 ● Cogitatio Press (2023 - 2025) ● De Gruyter ● Elsevier ● IEEE 2022-2024 ● Institute of Physics ● Kluwer Law International ● Lippincott ● MDPI ● Il Mulino ● Oxford University Press ● RSC 2022 - 2024 ● SCOAP3 ● Springer Nature ● Verduci Editore - European Review for Medical and Pharmacological Sciences ● Wiley
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Form	Webpage
Provider	The University of Milan Library System
Link to webpage	https://www.sba.unimi.it/en/digital-library/13719.html

Scope	Data on open publication fees (APC) paid by the University of Milan in a given year, breakdown by publisher and journal title
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Form	Webpage – data visualisation
Provider	The OpenAPC initiative – The University of Milan uploads its APC fee data to this webpage
Link to webpage	https://treemaps.openapc.net/apcdata/milano-u/

THE UNIVERSITY OF WARSAW (UW)

Scope	Description of open publishing programs available to the university community, Rules for getting funding from UW's IDUB program for open publication of articles (APC) and monographs (BPC).
Form	Webpage (only in Polish)
Provider	The University of Warsaw Library
Link to webpage	https://www.buw.uw.edu.pl/dla-nauki/programy-publicowania-otwartego/

Scope	<p>Overview discounts Open Access publications (APC) and agreements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Elsevier 2022-2024 ● ACS 2023-2025 ● American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS): Science Advances 2022-2024 ● IEEE 2023 ● IOP 2023-2025 ● Wolters Kluwer ● Oxford University Press ● SCOAP3 ● Springer Nature 2022-2024 ● Taylor&Francis
Form	Webpage (national level, only in Polish)
Provider	The Interdisciplinary Centre for Mathematical and Computational Modelling UW (ICM UW)
Link to webpage	https://wbn.icm.edu.pl/publikowanie-otwarte/

Scope	Open Access Publishing Fund (articles and monographs):
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding conditions • How to receive funding? • Application form
Form	Webpage
Provider	The University of Warsaw Research Administration Office
Link to webpage	https://inicjatywadoskonalosci.uw.edu.pl/en/actions/microgrants/

3.3.4. Examples of information and support activities (training, websites) on legal aspects of publication, copyrights

SORBONNE UNIVERSITY (SU)	
Scope	Creative commons (in French)
Form	Webpage
Provider	Sorbonne University Library
Link to webpage	https://hal.sorbonne-universite.fr/public/Fiche_HAL_Creative_Commons_OAW_2021.pdf

SORBONNE UNIVERSITY (SU)	
Scope	French Digital Republic Law (in French)
Form	Webpage
Provider	Sorbonne University Library
Link to webpage	https://hal.sorbonne-universite.fr/public/Loi_pour_une_Republique_numerique.pdf

Scope	Implementing the rights retention strategy for scientific publications (in French, national level)
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Form	Webpage and PDF leaflet
Provider	The Committee for Open Science, French Ministry of Higher Education and Research
Link to webpage	https://www.ouvrirlascience.fr/je-publie-quels-sont-mes-droits/ https://www.ouvrirlascience.fr/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/JepublieQuelssontmesdroits-Vdef.pdf

Scope	I publish, what rights do I have ? (in French, national level)
Form	Webpage and PDF leaflet
Provider	The Committee for Open Science, French Ministry of Higher Education and Research
Link to webpage	https://www.ouvrirlascience.fr/implementing-the-rights-retention-strategy-for-scientific-publications/

THE UNIVERSITY OF COPENHAGEN (UCPH)

Scope	<p>The service guides in the following fields:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Assignment of copyright to publisher (Copyright Transfer Agreements) ● Copyright in relation to open access publishing ● Use of copyrighted works and resources ● Use and application of Creative Commons licenses in publishing ● Use of Copydan's licenses in connection with research and teaching <p>(detailed guidelines on Research Portal KUNET / UCPH Intranet)</p>
Form	Webpage – Research Portal KUnet / UCPH Intranet
Provider	Department for Research Support, University of Copenhagen Library
Link to webpage	https://kub.ku.dk/english/usethelibrary/researchers/copyright/

Scope	<p>Releases about:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● General information about publication ● Authorship ● Publishing agreements
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open Science • Open Access and Copyright Law
Form	Webpage
Provider	<i>Forskerportalen</i> (The Researcher Portal) is developed by the Committee for Protection of Scientific Work (UBVA), which is a standing committee under the Danish Confederation of Professional Associations (Akademikerne) which represents the interests of academics related to copyright and patent law issues.
Link to webpage	https://forskerportalen.dk/en/

THE UNIVERSITY OF WARSAW (UW)

Scope	<p>“Otwarty dostęp do publikacji naukowych. Kwestie prawne.” (English: <i>Open access to scientific publications. Legal issues</i>) DOI: https://doi.org/10.31338/uw.9788323509677 The book contains basic information about copyright law instruments relevant to the introduction of open access to scientific publications. It presents definitions of key concepts functioning in the area of open access and explains basic legal issues from the point of view of: authors of scientific publications, scientific journals, scientific units planning to introduce an open mandate or operating an open institutional repository of scientific publications, as well as research funding institutions planning to introduce open access in the projects they fund.</p>
Form	Publication (monograph), Print and online version (in Polish)
Provider	Interdisciplinary Centre for Mathematical and Computational Modelling UW (ICM UW), was published by University of Warsaw Press (WUW)
Link to webpage	https://www.wuw.pl/product-pol-6731-Otwarty-dostep-do-publikacji-naukowych-Kwestie-prawne-PDF.html

Scope	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Guide about Creative Commons Licenses, Free licenses, Public domain 2) Labeling Open Educational Resources (OER) with Creative Commons licenses
Form	Webpage (in Polish)
Provider	University of Warsaw Library
Link to webpage	1) https://www.buw.uw.edu.pl/dla-nauki/otwarta-nauka/licencje-creative-commons/

2) <https://www.buw.uw.edu.pl/dla-nauki/otwarta-nauka/otwarte-zasoby-edukacyjne/>

Scope	The course is prepared in such a way that on its basis in 15 hours (6 lectures and a test at the end of the class) it is possible to implement the primary themes included in the curricula of the subject "Intellectual Property" at Polish universities. General issues concerning the subject and object scope of copyright law which are applicable to scientific publications.
Form	Online course and textbook in PDF (in Polish)
Provider	Fundacja Nowoczesna Polska, Koalicja Otwartej Nauki, patronage and co-authorship: Interdisciplinary Centre for Mathematical and Computational Modelling UW (ICM UW)
Link to webpage	https://prawokultury.pl/kurs/ https://prawokultury.pl/kurs/media/krotki-kurs-wlasnosci-intelektualnej-podrecznik.pdf

3.3.5. Information about available repositories and publishing platforms

CHARLES UNIVERSITY (CU)	
Repository	<p>The CU Digital Repository provides access to theses and dissertations defended at Charles University since 2006, habilitations defended after 1.3. 2017, articles from journals Faculty of Arts Press published in open access mode, monographs published by Karolinum Press in open access mode, monographs published by the Faculty of Law at Charles University in open access mode, digitised study materials for students with special needs and digitised theses defended before 2006.</p> <p>https://dspace.cuni.cz/?locale-attribute=en</p> <p>The CU repository of publishing activities („Repozitář publikační činnosti UK”) is a place to store and make available the full texts of the results of scientific studies and research of authors at Charles University. Employees and students of Charles University can store their results in the repository. Storing and making the result available (auto-archiving) in the CU Repository of Publishing Activities is voluntary. Auto-archiving of the results in the repository takes place via CU’s CRIS system where they are originally stored. Results are then automatically transferred to the repository after being checked by the faculty open access coordinators.</p>

Publishing

<https://publications.cuni.cz/?locale-attribute=en>

Karolinum Press <https://karolinum.cz/en/information-and-services/about-us/karolinum-press>

Karolinum Press supports research and education in all of the disciplines taught at the 17 faculties at Charles University. The books published reflect a wide scope spanning from humanities to natural sciences and medicine. Karolinum Press publishes scientific monographs, journals, and textbooks, ranging from specialised exercise books to general textbooks; independent series present prestigious publications on the history of Charles University, titles in art history, language textbooks, and many disciplinary and interdisciplinary series, including translations of renowned foreign publishers focusing on literary science, history of culture, linguistics, and philosophy. Karolinum Press cooperates with leading scholars to ensure a high quality of text preparation, follow contemporary trends in international editing standards, and focus on first-rate graphical layout and print. Since 2005, Karolinum Press has been gradually working on incorporating Charles University's publications, including monographs, journals, and ebooks into international distribution and library networks.

Several faculties of Charles University also operate their own publishers:

- Faculty of Mathematics and Physics (MatfyzPress, <https://matfyzpress.cz/cz/o-nas> [only Czech version])
- Faculty of Arts (Faculty of Arts Press, <https://books.ff.cuni.cz/en/about-fa-press/about-us/>)
- Faculty of Education (Publishing Centre of Faculty of Education, <https://vydavatelstvi.pedf.cuni.cz/> [only Czech version]).

Karolinum Press has been publishing all journals as open journals since 2015. In addition, it publishes high-quality open-access books, ensuring their maximum accessibility and world-wide distribution.

<https://karolinum.cz/en/information-and-services/open-access>

THE UNIVERSITY OF COPENHAGEN (UCPH)

Repository

CURIS (Copenhagen University Research Information System)

The main purpose of CURIS is the registration of research and communication at the University of Copenhagen.

It also allows upload and dissemination of Open Access publications, e.g., compliance with funder requirements.

When uploading an article, CURIS is cross-checking with the SHERPA/RoMEO database to see what OA permissions apply.

CLARIN-DK-UCPH Repository

The CLARIN Centre at the University of Copenhagen

CLARIN-DK Datacenter

<https://repository.clarin.dk/repository/xmlui/>

The CLARIN Centre at the University of Copenhagen, Denmark, hosts and manages a data repository (CLARIN-DK-UCPH Repository), which is part of the research infrastructure for humanities and social sciences financed by the University of Copenhagen. The CLARIN-DK-UCPH Repository provides easy and sustainable access for scholars in the humanities and social sciences to digital language data (in written, spoken, video, or multimodal forms) and provides advanced tools for discovering, exploring, exploiting, annotating, and analysing data. CLARIN-DK also shares knowledge on Danish language technology and resources and is the Danish node in the European Research Infrastructure Consortium, CLARIN ERIC.

Researchers have access to five types of national HPC installations. One of which is suitable for the processing of sensitive data. This nationally coordinated approach is managed by the Danish e-infrastructure Cooperation **DeiC** (<https://www.deic.dk/en/supercomputing/national-hpc-facilities>)

UCPHs Electronic Research Data Archive allows sharing and archiving of non-sensitive data across institutions (<https://www.erda.ku.dk/>)

UCPHs Sensitive Information Facility allows sharing of sensitive data across institutions (<https://sif.ku.dk/>)

DeiC Dataverse

In 2023, UCPH will launch a national trusted data repository for research data called “DeiC Dataverse”. It will be available to all researchers at the eight Danish universities through the Danish e-infrastructure Cooperation (DeiC).

Publishing

Tidsskrift.dk

[Tidsskrift.dk](https://tidsskrift.dk) is the Royal Danish Library’s portal for the publication of professional, scientific, and cultural journals in digital full text. Tidsskrift.dk is also part of the National Strategy for Open Access, which is supported by the Ministry of Education and Research.

HEIDELBERG UNIVERSITY (HU)

Repository

heiDOK – The Heidelberg Document Repository

heiDOK is the Heidelberg University's institutional open access repository. It provides members of the university with the opportunity to publish their primary and secondary publications open access. Currently, it contains over 27,000 publications with free access to the electronic full text.

<https://archiv.ub.uni-heidelberg.de/volltextserver/>

heiDATA – The Heidelberg Open Research Data Repository

heiDATA is an institutional repository for Open Research Data from Heidelberg University. It is managed by the Competence Centre for Research Data, a joint institution of the University Library and the Computing Centre.

<https://heidata.uni-heidelberg.de/>

heidICON – The Heidelberg Digital Image Repository

heidICON is the image and multimedia archive of the university and is suited for the requirements of the corresponding file formats.

<https://heidicon.ub.uni-heidelberg.de/search>

Heidelberg University Publishing (heiUP)

The mission of Heidelberg University Publishing is to provide open access to outstanding academic publications. We see the opportunities afforded by digital publishing as a way to advance the visibility of research output beyond the confines of academic disciplines. For us, this means that we publish open access, follow a consistent e-strategy, use innovative digital publication formats, and ensure quality through a peer review process (usually double-blind). In addition to electronic formats, we offer high-quality printed versions of all our titles. Our decision to accept a submission does not depend on its provenance but on its quality.

In keeping with our role as a Comprehensive University, we facilitate forms of interdisciplinary exchange that grow from the strengths of our academic disciplines. Our portfolio includes primarily monographs, edited volumes/proceedings, and textbooks.

The heiUP is an Open Access publisher, works published by heiUP fall under a Creative Commons licence (preferably CC-BY or CC-BY-SA). The copyright of the work shall remain with you as the author, with the publisher retaining only a simple right of use.

To ensure maximum visibility of all publications and to allow convenient access to both our digital and printed media, we provide each format (PDF, HTML, and print-on-demand books) with a unique ISBN. Each book series will also be assigned an ISSN and online publications will receive a DOI (Digital Object Identifier). Bibliographic information and content descriptors (keywords, subjects, etc.) both for the individual book and book chapters or essays within edited volumes will be catalogued to ensure optimum visibility in databases, search engines, and both national and international library catalogues (such as HEIDI/HeiBIB, SWB, KVK, Google Scholar, DOAB, Open Library, Worldcat). Our books are also listed in national and international trade directories (e.g. Amazon, VLB, KNOE, and Buchhandel.de) and can be ordered online or through retailers. Additionally, we support authors with proof for the payout of royalties from copyright collectives such as VG Wort.

Hei JOURNALS

The heiJOURNALS infrastructure provides researchers with the opportunity to publish open access e-journals. Based on an open source software for the management of peer-reviewed scientific publications, the library has been hosting e-journals already since 2008, and renowned scientists act as journal editors. Currently, roughly 150 journals are hosted at the platforms for the university and the subject-specific information services.

<https://journals.ub.uni-heidelberg.de/>

heiBOOKS

The service heiBOOKS provides researchers at Heidelberg University with the opportunity to publish e-books in open access. The University Library hosts an open source software suitable for publishing scholarly books, provides support with the production of the e-book, guarantees long-term availability, and ensures the greatest possible visibility. In total, the library has published ~750 open access e-books.

<https://books.ub.uni-heidelberg.de/heibooks>

Subject-specific information services

Heidelberg University Library operates three DFG funded ‘Specialised information services for Researchers’: arthistoricum.net (Art, Photography, Design), Propylaeum (Classical Studies) and FID4SA (South Asian studies). These provide researchers with the following community-specific services:

- needs-based acquisition of scholarly resources
- field-specific information infrastructure platforms
- **open access publishing venues**
- digitization and subject-cataloguing of resources
- linked Open Data Services
- science communication/PR/marketing
- consulting for Digital Humanities projects

<https://www.arthistoricum.net/en/publishing>

<https://www.propylaeum.de/en/publishing>

<https://www.fid4sa.de/en/publishing>

SORBONNE UNIVERSITY (SU)

Repository

DMP OPIDoR (<https://dmp.opidor.fr/>): French equivalent to DMP online. The library is the administrator for the university.

Data storage: each member of the university has access to the institutional cloud, [DROPSU](#), and has 100GB of storage.

SACADO has storage infrastructures for large volumes of data: servers and virtual machines. <https://sacado.sorbonne-universite.fr/welcome/>

Data sharing **Research Data Gouv**, a national data repository based on Dataverse, was launched in July 2022: <https://recherche.data.gouv.fr/en>
(Project presentation:

<https://www.rdalliance.org/sites/default/files/2021.05.11%20Recherche%20Data%20Gouv-webinaireRDA.pdf>)

	<p>Sorbonne University has made a request for operating its own Dataverse space on Research Data Gov.</p>
	<p>Sorbonne University HAL repository: Sorbonne University HAL: https://hal.sorbonneuniversite.fr</p>
<p>Publishing</p>	<p>The Sorbonne University Press https://www.sorbonne-universite.fr/en/culture-and-outreach/bookshop/sorbonne-university-press https://sup.sorbonne-universite.fr/ With a catalogue of over 900 titles, and the publication of some 50 new books per year, the Sorbonne University Press highlights current research in the human and social sciences, engineering and medicine.</p>

THE UNIVERSITY OF MILAN (UM)

<p>Repository</p>	<p>AIR - Institutional Research Repository IRIS - Research Information System https://www.unimi.it/en/research/research-data-and-outputs/air/iris-institutional-repository</p> <p>AIR is the University's repository of scientific publications. It collects articles, monographs, essays, edited books, conference speeches, and working papers since 2004, as well as all doctoral theses since 2010.</p> <p>According to the university policy, the full text of research works is associated with bibliographic data to enhance its significance and increase its web visibility.</p> <p>AIR is also the University research registry: the data is sent daily to the MIUR, used for the evaluation of doctoral schools and research facilities, for departmental annual reports, for authors' CVs, and for internal evaluation campaigns.</p> <p>Dataverse – Fair Data repository - https://dataverse.unimi.it/ The FAIR data repository of the University of Milan. It is managed by the unit on Open Science.</p>
<p>Publishing</p>	<p>Milano University Press Milano University Press was conceived as an open-access publishing house to ensure the broadest possible dissemination of scientific findings, as well as to provide visibility to the work of a pool of internal and external researchers.</p> <p>In keeping with the principles of open science, Milano UP has positioned itself as a publishing channel granting access to scientific literature and the dissemination of research findings to both the academic community and the broader audience.</p>

It covers two publishing areas:

- UNIMI Journals <https://riviste.unimi.it/>

The University online journals, the starting block of Milano University Press,

- UNIMI Books <https://libri.unimi.it/>

Scientific and educational series and single volume works, textbooks.

Books and journals are published under the Diamond Open Access model, with no fees for authors or readers.

THE UNIVERSITY OF WARSAW (UW)

Repository

University of Warsaw Repository

The UW Repository collects doctoral dissertations defended at the University of Warsaw after October 1, 2012.

Doctoral dissertations are retrieved from the UW Dissertation Archive. By the end of 2023, the doctoral collection will be transferred to the new institutional repository at the University of Warsaw. An updated version of the repository will be available in early 2024 that also includes additional scientific contributions beyond the current scope.

RepOD Repository for Open Data

The project „Disciplinary Open Research Data Repositories” (drodb.icm.edu.pl/english/). It aims to enhance access to academic resources by making them available in open research data repositories, as well as to improve the quality of shared data and metadata and to facilitate their better use. This is possible by developing two domain-specific repositories for social data RDS (rds.icm.edu.pl) and crystallographic data MX-RDR (mxrdr.icm.edu.pl/). The project is run by two units of the University of Warsaw (Interdisciplinary Centre for Mathematical and Computational Modelling and Robert Zajonc Institute for Social Studies) in partnership with the Institute of Philosophy and Sociology, Polish Academy of Sciences and Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań.

Repository for Open Data (repod.icm.edu.pl/), Repository of Open Research Data RepOD has been operating since 2015. It is run by the team of the Open Science Platform of the Interdisciplinary Center for Mathematical and Computational Modeling of the University of Warsaw. RepOD is the first Polish repository of open research data, created for all scientists and institutions interested in sharing their resources. The repository is free, and each set of deposited data is given a DOI number.

	<p>Disciplinary Open Research Data Repositories Repository for Open Data RepOD — repod.icm.edu.pl — is a general-purpose repository for open research data, offering scholars the possibility to deposit their datasets. The purpose of the repository is to make available on the Internet research data, such as tables, photographs, audiovisual material, and any other types of data created, collected, or annotated for academic research. The Repository is open for everyone to use.</p> <p>Social Data Repository RDS - rds.icm.edu.pl — is a domain-specific digital repository of social data. The purpose of the repository is to make available on the Internet social data, consisting of data sets and accompanying technical or methodological documentation. The Repository is open for everyone to use.</p> <p>Macromolecular Xtallography Raw Data Repository MX-RDR — mxrdr.icm.edu.pl — is a domain-specific digital repository of raw diffraction data collected for macromolecular crystals. It includes tools simplifying metadata descriptions by combining information extracted directly from diffraction images, obtained from the PDB database and/or user input. The Repository is open for everyone to use.</p>
<p>Publishing</p>	<p>The University of Warsaw Press (Wydawnictwa Uniwersytetu Warszawskiego) https://www.wuw.pl/main-eng.html publishes journals, monographs,, scholarly and educational books authored by the researchers from both the University of Warsaw and other scientific centres. It also offers translations of the foreign titles that contribute to the development of science. Nowadays more and more publications are available as e-books (including open access).</p> <p>Publishers operate at most of the faculties, e.g. at the Faculty of Management, the Faculty of Archaeology; the Faculty of Geographics and Regional Studies; and the Centre for East European Studies. They publish mostly journals.</p> <p>Some University faculties cooperate with external publishing houses.</p>

3.4. Lesson plans

Open access should not be equated with subpar-quality journals or monographs, nor should it place an undue financial burden on authors. We acknowledge the potential for our Alliance members to strengthen the diamond open access model, widely considered to be the most sustainable approach. Our aim is to reconnect scholarly publishing with its roots – placing scientists at the heart of the publishing process to ensure high publication standards. Specifically, we aspire to provide support for scientists struggling with the complexities of launching their own diamond open access journals and embarking on open access monograph

projects. To this end, we have developed two distinct lesson plans, which we have listed below: 'Creating a Diamond (Platinum) Open Access Journal: A Guide' and 'Open Access Monograph Publishing: A Guide'.

3.4.1. Creating a Diamond (Platinum) Open Access Journal: A guide

Name of the course	Creating a Diamond (Platinum) Open Access Journal: A guide
Training audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Doctoral students ● Researchers ● Staff
Previous knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Basic knowledge of the journal publishing process (with emphasis on electronic journals), editorial integrity, publishing standard ● Prior review of the 4EU+ webinar material: STRATEGIES FOR PUBLISHING IN OPEN ACCESS JOURNALS Open for you! https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TIZO1Zq-oMg
Aims of the training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Understand the differences among various types of Open Access ● Understand No-fee OA publishing options with emphasis on what is a diamond open journal ● Understand the rights that apply to open access publishing: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Copyright transfer agreement ○ Rights retention mechanisms (Plan S, Funder requirements) ○ Self-archiving policies + embargo (repositories) ○ Publication version (VoR, AAM, postprint, preprint) ● Learn what funding models are available for running a diamond open access journal ● Learn to acquire and manage financial resources ● Know indexing databases and directories, such as DOAJ and DOAB ● Know examples of innovative platforms (e.g. ResearchEquals, Octopus) ● Know examples of open peer review practices (e.g. Open Research Europe – F1000Research publishing platform)
Plan and activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Planning a new Diamond Open Access Journal <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Choose the name and define a scope ○ Plan the organisational and governance structure ○ Form an editorial board ○ Decide on the structure, content and layout ○ Choose the hosting and data systems <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Web hosting ▪ Domains and Uniform Resource Locator (URL)

- Backup
 - Archiving
 - Journal management software
- Prepare instructions for authors
- Prepare policies state practices, procedures and expectations for authors and readers as recommended by the Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE)
 - Peer-review policy
 - Publication policy / Publisher-Author agreement – authors agree to the publisher licensing the content to appropriate search engines and database providers to ensure maximum exposure of the content to the intended audiences, on the understanding that any income received by the journal is used only to support its development and publication
 - Authorship – retain copyright to the material
 - Creative Commons licences
 - Appropriate review of human subject research policy
 - Disclosure of conflicts of interest
 - Complaints policy

Examples

- Documentation prepared by other diamond journals searched e.g. at DOAJ
- CC licence types and their meaning
- Platforms with open peer-reviews
- Sample contracts with provisions on rights retention and self-archiving
- Cooperation with libraries: <https://librarypublishing.org/>

Exercise

- check what submission requirements are in the DOAJ <https://doaj.org/apply/guide/>
 - search available materials on the COPE platform <https://publicationethics.org/management>
 - Find diamond journal initiatives in your country/Europe, e.g. <https://www.diamondopen.com/>
- Resource and Financing models
 - Generating incomes
 - Volunteer effort
 - Internship
 - Personal/Institutional membership fees
 - Sponsorship from commercial publishers, information providers and universities/libraries funds

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Donations from readers ▪ The sale of added-value products (e.g. PDF format, Kindle/epub formats, print on demand paperback) ▪ Obtaining grants ▪ Inter-institutional cooperation / Collectively-organised funding (e.g. Open Edition Journals, Diamond Open) ▪ Shared infrastructure ▪ Advertisements ○ Expected costs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Professional copy-editing ▪ Translation ▪ Conversion of articles to XML/XHTML format ▪ Reference checking ▪ Indexing and archiving (e.g. LOCKSS system, WebCite consortium – https://webcitation.org/ which supports permanent archiving of web material cited by authors) ▪ Web development / OJS PKP development – customised version ▪ Screening software to check for plagiarism ▪ Assigning PID to publication like DOI number ● Disseminating the Content of the Journal <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ISSN Portal ○ CrossRef (DOI) ○ Indexes (professional) ○ Directories (e.g. DOAJ) ○ Content Aggregators (e.g. EBSCOhost) ○ Metadata harvesters ○ Search engine (e.g. Google, Yahoo!) ○ Server log analyzers or services such as Google Analytics ● Partnership and utilisation of modern technology <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ResearchEquals ○ Octopus ○ Open Research Europe
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Bosman, Jeroen, Frantsvåg, Jan Erik, Kramer, Bianca, Langlais, Pierre-Carl, & Proudman, Vanessa. (2021). OA Diamond Journals Study. Part 1: Findings. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4558704 ● Becerril, Arianna, Bosman, Jeroen, Bjørnshauge, Lars, Frantsvåg, Jan Erik, Kramer, Bianca, Langlais, Pierre-Carl, Mounier, Pierre, Proudman, Vanessa, Redhead, Claire, & Torny, Didier. (2021). OA Diamond Journals Study. Part 2: Recommendations. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4562790 ● Solomon, D. Developing Open Access Journal : A Practical Guide, Chandos Publishing Limited, Oxford, 2008. Version 1.02 2008-06-19:

	<p>https://www.uib.no/sites/w3.uib.no/files/attachments/guide_to_developing_oa_journals.pdf</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ševkušić, Milica, Nježić, Irena. Open access publishing: training approaches : The EIFL open science train-the-trainer bootcamp, 2023, https://europa.eu/youreurope/business/running-business/intellectual-property/rights/index_pl.htm
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3.4.2. Open Access monograph publishing: A guide

Name of the course	Open Access monograph publishing: A guide
Training audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Doctoral students • Researchers • Staff
Previous knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic knowledge of the monograph publishing process, editorial integrity, publishing standard, gold and green open access • Prior review of the 4EU+ webinar material: PUBLICATION STRATEGIES FOR MONOGRAPHS IN HUMANITIES AND SOCIAL SCIENCES Open for you! https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5yN5JvTDn0
Aims of the training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic barriers blocking open access for monographs • Benefits of open access monographs publishing • Publisher selection (specifics of the scientific publishing market) • Publication costs • Funding models for open monograph publishing • Selecting the appropriate Creative Commons licence • Finding a trustworthy repository and publisher's policy to self-archive • Available support at the 4EU+ universities (OA publication policies of university publishers and available publication platforms)
Plan and activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Barriers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Unsustainable business models for small and medium-sized publishers ○ Insufficient publication infrastructures ○ Harder to maintain the necessary competencies in the rapidly changing publishing landscape ○ Print editions of books are continuing importance ○ Various forms of books makes it difficult to manage the publishing process ○ Submission, peer-review, and editorial processes are less standardised than in the area of journals

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The costs of publishing open access books depend on the volume/type of the document (is much bigger than publishing an article) ○ The fear that open access leads to serious shortfalls in the sales of print editions ● Benefits <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Visibility (e.g. indexing in DOAB and OAPEN Library) ○ Increased reuse ○ Readership (diverse audiences) ○ Citability (better assessment of the study) ○ Authorship acknowledged/control (against plagiarism) ○ Wider impact and bigger public engagement ○ Complies with the requirements of research funding agencies and the institution's openness policies ● What to look for when selecting a publisher (essentials): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The OA version of the publication is made visibly accessible on the publisher's website, together with the respective paid versions ○ Text and data mining (TDM) are permitted ○ OA publications are recorded in corresponding databases such as OAPEN and DOAB ○ Authors and editors grant the general public extensive rights of use by granting an Open Access-compliant Creative Commons licence (CC BY or CC BY-SA) ○ Rights information is included in text form in the imprint and embedded in the file in a machine-readable form ○ A peer review or review process is used for scientific review that meets the usual standards in the field ○ There is openness to new, innovative forms of quality assurance, e.g., open peer review ○ The publications are published in PDF, XML, HTML formats ○ The metadata are as detailed as possible ○ Each publication receives a DOI as a persistent identifier. Other possible identifiers are URN and Handle, if applicable ○ Provide a list of the publication fee if applicable ○ The publisher provides information on the added value of an OA publication and advises on legal issues and CC licences ○ Usage statistics are presented on the page ● Costs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Staff costs (Staff time for those working in the following departments: Acquisitions, Manuscript Editorial, Design, and Production) ○ Title-specific direct costs (any outsourced work or services directly related to the creation of a monographs)
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- Press-level overhead (General and Administrative expenses and Departmental overheads)
- In-kind contributions (these include the many contributions the press may benefit from, but are not paid for, like generating an index)

Examples of the distribution of publication costs

- F1000 <https://blog.f1000.com/2020/08/19/price-transparency-on-f1000research/>
 - Community development
 - Submission to prepublication checks
 - Peer review management
 - Prepublication checks to publication
 - Services after publication
 - Platform development
 - Marketing and business development
 - Author and user support
- Ubiquity <https://ubiquity.pub/book-publishing/charges/>
 - Full-text peer review
 - Providing editorial support (e.g. advice on copyright clearance, ethics matters etc)
 - Crossref Similarity Check service
 - Cover design
 - Metadata, DOI and ISBN registration
 - Publication in downloadable PDF, EPUB, MOBI (Kindle) formats as well as in-browser online reading
 - Chapter specific landing pages
 - Print-on-Demand (POD) service and listing through book retailer websites and distribution lists
 - Publication of data, software and media files associated with the book
 - Inclusion in search, indexing and aggregation platforms, library catalogues, library suppliers, discovery services, etc.
 - Sending print copies of the published book to authors/editors as well as reviewers
 - Promotion and marketing
 - Full book and chapter specific usage metrics
 - Royalty payments to authors/editors from print sales
 - Archiving into appropriate repositories, legal deposit and preservation services
 - Typesetting and digital file creation
 - English language copyediting (CE) will also be added to our services as standard, however, this may be removed to reduce the BPC if the authors are able to provide high quality texts or arrange the copyediting themselves

■ Rates at commercial publishers

Examples:

- The OpenAPC initiative collects and disseminates datasets on fees paid for open access publishing (also BPC)
 - <https://openapc.net/>
- Publishers of open access books can earn revenue through
 - Publication fees (book processing charges, BPCs) and the sale of the print edition (dual publishing), which is often produced using digital print-on-demand technology.
 - Other publishers finance the basic costs of their open access segment via crowdfunding (e.g., Knowledge Unlatched, transformative agreements negotiated by consortia) or institutional memberships (e.g., Open Book Publishers [OBP], the Open Library of Humanities [OLH], Language Science Press). Crowdfunding and partnerships:
 - [Open Book Publishers](#)
 - [Open Humanities Press](#)
 - [COPIM](#) (Community-led Open Publication Infrastructure for Monographs)
 - [KOALA](#)
 - [Knowledge Unlatched \(books\)](#)
 - [SCOAP3](#)
- Creative Commons licence
 - CC-BY
 - CC-BY-SA
 - CC-BY-ND
 - CC-BY-NC
 - CC-BY-NC-SA
 - CC-BY-NC-ND
- Trustworthy repository
 - Good practice if it is certified and meets the recommendations of the requirements (e.g. CoreTrustSeal)
- Available publishing support at the4EU+ universities

Examples (gold OA):

 - Karolinum Press (CU)
 - Tidsskrift.dk (UCPH)
 - heiUP (HU)
 - heiJOURNALS (HU)
 - heiBOOKS (HU)
 - UNIMI Journals (UM)
 - UNIMI Books (UM)
 - IDUB UW BPC fund (UW)

Examples (green OA, institutional repositories):

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Repozitář publikační činnosti UK (CU) ○ Sorbonne University HAL repository (SU) ○ CURIS (Copenhagen University Research Information System) (UCPH) ○ CLARIN-DK-UCPH Repository (UCPH) ○ heiDOK – The Heidelberg Document Repository (HU) ○ AIR — Institutional Research Repository (UM) ○ University of Warsaw Repository, in the process of upgrade (UW)
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Arbeitsgemeinschaft Universitätsverlage. (2018). Qualitätsstandards für Open-Access-Monografien und -Sammelbände (Version 1). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3562239 ● CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board. (2022). CoreTrustSeal Requirements 2023-2025 (V01.00). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7051012 ● Nordhoff, S. (2018). <i>Cookbook for open access books</i>. Language Science Press. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1286925 ● Open Access Books Toolkit (2020, October 29). <i>The OAPEN Open Access Books Toolkit</i>. https://oabooks-toolkit.org/ ● Open Access Network. (Last updated: 2022, October 21) <i>Business Models for Books</i>. https://open-access.network/en/information/financing/business-models-for-books ● Open Access Network. (Last updated: 2023, February 3) <i>Open Access Books</i>. https://open-access.network/en/information/publishing/open-access-books ● Research Libraries Group & OCLC. (2002). <i>Trusted digital repositories : attributes and responsibilities : an rlg-oclc report</i>. RLG. https://www.oclc.org/content/dam/research/activities/trustedrep/repositories.pdf

4. Part 3 – Case #3 Citizen Science

4.1. Introduction and objectives

What is citizen science? According to the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA), Citizen Science is an ‘umbrella’ term that ‘describes a variety of ways in which the public can participate in science. The main characteristics are that: (1) citizens are actively involved in research, in partnership or collaboration with scientists or professionals; and (2) there is a genuine outcome, such as new scientific knowledge, conservation action, or policy change¹³⁸. Furthermore, characteristics of citizen science can be found in the ECSA report *Characteristics of Citizen Science*¹³⁹ which also builds on the ‘10 principles of citizen science’ developed by ECSA members¹⁴⁰.

CS empowers the role of the public in scientific research and monitoring, as exemplified in the CS projects described WP5: ‘Mainstreaming open science’, Task 5.3, Case #3. CS takes place in many diverse fields of research, including ecology, astronomy, medicine, computer science, history, and many more. A CS project can be implemented at different levels – from local projects to continental and global scales, and from short-term projects to those–run over decades¹⁴¹. Through CS participants can contribute to science with their intellectual effort, with their local knowledge, or with their tools and resources. Therefore, in a CS project, the participant contributes with data sourced from their local communities, with observations submitted for inclusion in the project through online platforms or through mobile applications, or even collaborates in the design and development of the CS research project. This inclusive approach allows a larger number of people to contribute to scientific research, increasing the public trust in science and expanding the reach and capacity of scientific investigations.

4.2. Methodology and Data Collection

CS is a method that is drawing increasing attention from the academic and administrative worlds. Scientific reports show that CS can offer an effective way for citizens to interact with policy¹⁴². CS can contribute to informed decision making resulting in richer and more inclusive policy documents and policy implementation, which can bring long-term societal and economic as well as scientific and political benefits¹⁴³. The method is being applied in multi institutional cooperations, where universities, public libraries, city halls, hospitals, and other authorities work together on CS projects, e.g. federal citizen science projects in the USA investigating

¹³⁸ European Citizen Science Association: <https://www.ecsa.ngo/>

¹³⁹ ECSA's Characteristics of CS: <https://zenodo.org/record/3758668>

¹⁴⁰ Ten Principles of CS: <https://zenodo.org/record/5127534>

¹⁴¹ European Citizen Science Association: <https://www.ecsa.ngo/>

¹⁴² Nascimento, S., Rubio Iglesias, J.M., Owen, R., Schade, S., Shanley, L. (2018) Citizen science for policy formulation and implementation. In: Hecker, S., Haklay, M., Bowser, A., Makuch, Z., Vogel, J., Bonn, A., (eds.) *Citizen Science - Innovation in Open Science, Society and Policy*. (pp. 219-240). UCL Press: London. <https://discovery.ucl.ac.uk/id/eprint/10066313/>

¹⁴³ Hecker, S; Wicke, N; Haklay, M; Bonn, A; (2019) How Does Policy Conceptualise Citizen Science? A Qualitative Content Analysis of International Policy Documents. *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice* , 4 (1) , Article 32: <https://discovery.ucl.ac.uk/id/eprint/10088732/>

climate and the weather¹⁴⁴ and the active living project in Denmark, which is a collaboration between municipalities, universities, and the media¹⁴⁵. Hence, such projects contribute to improving partnerships between government and public institutions¹⁴⁶. Although the positive effects of such collaborations can be significant to society, such as the economic benefits discussed by Hanley¹⁴⁷, many years may pass before the results of the CS projects and the implementation of policies show a visible effect.

CS shows its strengths on the macro level as discussed above and on the micro level where single volunteers contribute to research projects. Through involvement in CS the individuals can acquire the interest, confidence, and knowledge they need to get involved in policy debates, in science, and in skill development¹⁴⁸. As a result, involvement in CS projects can potentially raise the educational level of volunteers^{149,150} and raise awareness of issues in society or the natural environment¹⁵¹. Enthusiasts of citizen science argue that this method of scientific research is more sensitive to challenges in our societies and, as a consequence, a more appropriate method to apply in “societal” investigations. In some countries, social movements, for example, may neglect the importance and achievements of modern science. CS can be applied to create awareness of the results of research and argue evidence-based proofs, such as countering the misinformation distributed by anti-vaccination movements that oppose public vaccination against COVID-19¹⁵². Further examples of CS applied in formal educational processes have been discussed at the European level¹⁵³ and in local contexts e.g., for primary school teachers¹⁵⁴ and as a method to combat misinformation in a post-factual era¹⁵⁵.

¹⁴⁴ STM Weather: <https://www.stmweather.com/blog/personal-perspectives/collaborative-citizen-science>

¹⁴⁵ <https://www.sdu.dk/en/forskning/forskningsformidling/citizenscience/campus-odense-active-living>

¹⁴⁶ Hanley, N., Roberts, M., 2019. The economic benefits of invasive species management. *People Nat.* 1, 124e137. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pan3.31>

¹⁴⁷ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Manola, N., Lazzeri, E., Barker, M., et al., Digital skills for FAIR and Open Science : report from the EOSC Executive Board Skills and Training Working Group, Manola, N. (editor), Lazzeri, E. (editor), Barker, M. (editor), Kuchma, I. (editor), Gaillard, V. (editor), Stoy, L. (editor), Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/59065>

¹⁴⁸ Ponti M. and Craglia M. Citizen-generated data for public policy, European Commission, Ispra, 2020 JRC120231.

¹⁴⁹ Peltoniemi, A. J., Kauppinen, H., Lampi, E., Lämsä, J., Sabel, O., & Hämäläinen, R. (2023). How Citizen Scientists Learn : Exploring Learning Perceptions Through an International Survey. *Citizen Science*, 8(1), Article 18. <https://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.485>

¹⁵⁰ Brandt, M., Groom, Q., Magro, A. M., Misevic, D., Narraway, C. L., Bruckermann, T., Beniermann , A., Børsen, T., González, J., Meeus, S., Roy, H. E., Sá-Pinto, X., Torres, J. R., & Jenkins, T. (2022). Promoting scientific literacy in evolution through citizen science. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 289(1980), [20221077]. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2022.1077>

¹⁵¹ Paul, K., Quinn, M. S., Huijser, M. P., Graham, J., & Broberg, L. (2014). An evaluation of a citizen science data collection program for recording wildlife observations along a highway. *Journal of environmental management*, 139, 180-187: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2014.02.018>

¹⁵² Burki, T. (2019). Vaccine misinformation and social media. *The Lancet Digital Health*, 1(6), e258-e259.

¹⁵³ Roche, J., Bell, L., Galvão, C., Golumbic, Y. N., Kloetzer, L., Knoblen, N., ... & Winter, S. (2020). Citizen science, education, and learning: challenges and opportunities. *Frontiers in Sociology*, 5, 613814.

¹⁵⁴ Aristeidou, M., Lorke, J., & Ismail, N. (2022). Citizen Science: Schoolteachers’ Motivation, Experiences, and Recommendations. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 1-27.

¹⁵⁵ Leguina, Leire, Magalhães, Joana, Tola, Elisabetta, Guasch, Blanca, Elorza, Ana, Lacunza, Izaskun, & Arias, R. (2023). Deliverable 3.7 Citizen Science as a communication tool in the Post-Factual Era. Deliverable report of project H2020 NEWSERA (grant agreement No 873125). (v1.2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7689045>

4.3. Challenges in CS methodology

CS projects are demanding research projects that entail complex, specific challenges and are typically run over a long period of time. Challenges include, among other things, the assurance of data quality, data management and data processing, recruitment and long-term motivation of participating citizens in longer-lasting projects, the creation and maintenance of user-friendly tools, awareness of ethical pitfalls, and solving potential conflicts of interest and ethical considerations¹⁵⁶. These aspects are constantly being addressed in the CS literature¹⁵⁷ and work on improving the implementation and design of CS methodologies is ongoing¹⁵⁸. Such evaluative approaches are conducted, for example, in the field of monitoring birds or amphibians, where volunteer results are compared with the results of professional eco-acoustic recording equipment to assess the quality of the collected data^{159,160}. Similarly, data protection issues are also being assessed¹⁶¹ because CS research activities raise novel ethical and policy issues for human subjects research. In CS there is the unique challenge that an individual can be both researcher and subject, where traditionally individuals occupy the role of researcher or subject, but not both at the same time.

4.4. The approach of Task 5.3, Case 3

The challenges and opportunities that CS brings to research activities need closer consideration. Projects like TRAIN4EU give us the opportunity to learn more about the “needs” that citizen scientists have to be able to provide timely and quality data on pressing social and environmental issues.

Therefore, to gain insight into good practice and requirements for CS support, we interviewed three CS projects. The projects came from Denmark, France, and the Czech Republic and were rooted in different disciplines, respectively species identification and genealogy (the Arter project, Denmark)¹⁶², agriculture and biodiversity (The French Agricultural and Biodiversity Observatory)¹⁶³, and drought and changes in agricultural landscapes (the project *Na Suchu* from the Czech Republic)¹⁶⁴. The aim was to learn more about how CS projects are supported at the universities and which competencies researchers and research support staff should have to carry

¹⁵⁶ Fritz, S., See, L., Grey, F. (2022). The grand challenges facing environmental Citizen Science. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 10, 1019628. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2022.1019628>

¹⁵⁷ Resnik, D. B., Elliott, K. C., Miller, A. K. (2015). A framework for addressing ethical issues in Citizen Science. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 54, 475–481. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2015.05.008>

¹⁵⁸ Leguina, Leire, Magalhães, Joana, Tola, Elisabetta, Guasch, Blanca, Elorza, Ana, Lacunza, Izaskun, & Arias, R. (2023). Deliverable 3.7 Citizen Science as a communication tool in the Post-Factual Era. Deliverable report of project H2020 NEWSERA (grant agreement No 873125). (v1.2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7689045>

¹⁵⁹ Cooper, C., Martin, V., Wilson, O., & Rasmussen, L. (2023). Equitable Data Governance Models for the Participatory Sciences. *Community Science*, 2(2), e2022CSJ000025.

¹⁶⁰ Lee, L., Desroches, M., Mukhi, S., Bancej, Ch. (2021). FluWatchers: Evaluation of a crowdsourced influenza-like illness surveillance application for Canadian influenza seasons 2015–2016 to 2018–2019. *Canada Communicable Disease Report*, 47(09):357–363.

¹⁶¹ Pierce, R., Evram, M., 2022. Getting it right: implementing data protection in citizen science research. *Insights: the UKSG journal*, 35(0), p.2. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.538>

¹⁶² The Danish Citizen Science project “Arter”[Species]: <https://om.arter.dk/>

¹⁶³ The French agricultural biodiversity observatory: <https://www.observatoire-agricole-biodiversite.fr/>

¹⁶⁴ The Czech project “Na Suchu”[On Drought]: <https://eu-citizen.science/project/36>

out and support CS projects. Furthermore, we explored how these three CS projects are funded, and together with the interviewees, we speculated on which funding models they would like to see in the future.

The findings are collected in the three short milestone reports included in this final deliverable. Our qualitative approach enables us to analyse in depth the conditions, circumstances, and requirements that exist when scientists work with CS.

The key takeaways and recommendations for impactful next steps are presented below. The recommendations may contribute to developing a strategy for infrastructures and support models for CS. Each recommendation has the potential to enhance the value of CS research at the individual university and through collaboration inside, across, and outside the universities of the Alliance.

4.5. Description

4.5.1. A qualitative approach to understanding skills and funding in Citizen Science projects – Main findings from the first round of interviews (Milestone 1)

4.5.1.1. Introduction

To keep track of the process in task 5.3, milestone 1: ‘*Main findings from the 1 round of interviews*’ summarises the activities that have been carried out with a focus on the interviews.

4.5.1.2. Methods

Three citizen science projects were selected from the case catalogue prepared by the WP5 partners which made it possible to choose the most relevant CS projects. A qualitative method, in the form of three sequential interviews, was designed to ensure a series of short discussions, where themes and topics relevant to each project could be explored. The benefits of a short succession of interviews are that it encourages the continuous engagement of the interview person and time taken from these busy people is minimal. Furthermore, we can tailor the interviews to build on previous discussion points and take our investigations in new and unexpected directions.

Hence an interview guide was produced and used for the first round of interviews investigating the support that is necessary to run CS projects professionally. Based on the responses, a list of new questions was outlined and asked during the second round of interviews with the same interviewees, where further details regarding competence development and skills in CS projects could be gathered. The final interview addresses financial models and funding for CS projects. The goal was to describe and analyse all crucial facets that are necessary to provide support that make CS projects run in the best possible way. This information was collected and summarised in the present final WP5 deliverable which also contains recommendations.

4.5.1.3. Interview 1: Interview guide

The interview guide consists of two parts. Part 1: ‘*About the project*’ and Part 2: ‘*Experiences running the CS project*’.

Part 1: About the project

In this part the following questions were asked:

- *What is the name of the CS project?*
- *Is there a website or any source material that we can refer to?*
- *Collect URL/DOIs (can be filled in before the interview by the expert)*
- *Who are the citizens in the project, and what data did they need to collect (and how)?*
- *Did you have support from the university administration – in what form/who?*
- *Did the library provide support and in what form?*
- *Did you have help from the university IT?*
- *Did you have help from the university data lab or similar?*

Part 2: Experiences running the CS project the following questions were asked:

- *Which CS activities were/are in your project?*
- *Was the project a negative or positive experience?*
- *What was the greatest success experience you had during the project?*
- *What was the greatest challenge you faced during the project?*
- *What could have gone better in your project?*

4.5.1.4. Findings

4.5.1.4.1. Findings from the CS project ‘Arter’

With the help of the website <https://arter.dk/landing-page> or the app "Arter - reporting" nature enthusiasts can gain knowledge about Denmark's approximately 35,000 species of animals, plants, and fungi. At the same time, one can create a profile on the website and report occurrences of species. These “finds” are identified and validated by experts and the community active in the Arter project. Furthermore, the data are freely available for download. The ambition is to provide a national portal, where all information about Danish biodiversity is collected. At the present time, more than 50,063.091 findings are registered with more than 10,000 unique contributors. The project was launched in May 2021. This is a huge project, and stakeholders in the project, as well as data contributors, have many wishes for the further development of the platform in the future. Denmark is the last land in Scandinavia to make such a species portal, previously data about biodiversity have been collected separately and without coordination by private interest groups.

Arter conducted segment analyses to identify citizen profiles and communication about the project and how to contribute was tailored to these profiles.

Arter did not receive any support from the university (apart from lawyers at the faculty w.r.t. partnership agreements). They did not receive support from the library, and they did not ask for any. Only recently has the connection to the library been made. Neither the university IT department nor the university datalabs provided any help.

The main challenges are the following:

- Facilitating communication and dialogue between contributors and stakeholders in the project. Part of community building and engagement is the ability to have conversations and meet others with shared interests. However, GDPR means that people collecting data cannot direct any messages to each other and neither can experts or the project development team contact them. The project is able to host meetings and events at the Natural History Museum.
- Balancing the data collection process, depth of data, and technical platform to the needs of researchers, scientific integrity, and amateur contributors.
- Maintaining the data. Arter has employed one person, 30 hours a week with the sole responsibility to update and maintain the platform's taxonomy. This is a big resource in the project. If the taxonomy is not up-to-date, users will be dissatisfied and engagement will fizzle out.
- Obtaining funding to continue developing the platform and ensuring long-term access

Further information from the interview about 'Arter is available in [5.8. Appendix 8. Task 5.3, Case #3 Citizen science. Project Arter Interview 1.](#)

4.5.1.4.2. Findings from the CS project 'On drought' (*Na Suchu*)

The Na Suchu (On drought)¹⁶⁵ is a citizen science project started in 2022. It investigates the current state of the agricultural landscape in the Czech Republic. The main goal is to engage farmers, farm landowners, or people walking by farmland in taking photos of agricultural areas and uploading the photo on the iNaturalist app. Six main themes are investigated: 1) solitary trees, 2) crops, 3) biobelts and embankments, 4) restoration of dirt roads, 5) pools and areas to retain water, and 6) fruit trees in agroforestry fields. Therefore, the project addresses which changes are happening in agricultural landscapes and monitors how these changes are taking effect in the landscape. Because the project is for the whole country of the Czech Republic, it is a requirement that a large number of people engage in providing the data.

The aim is to jointly create a database monitoring the impacts of drought in Czech agriculture, to share examples of bad and good practices, and thus contribute to a better future in the field of water retention in the landscape, a better yield of fields, and more ecological management. In this first year of the project, a lot of effort will be used on stakeholder engagement and communication of the project, raising awareness, and running workshops on how to gather the data.

The project was established as part of a grant project from the Technology Agency of the Czech Republic and does not have any designated future development or maintenance funding of the collected data or the project platform. The project does not pay for advertisements on other CS platforms, and is currently investigating how to improve the visibility of the project. Opportunities to participate in conferences, forums, and interaction with the general public will be investigated.

No support is provided by the university, the library, or other organisations. There is a special department in the scientific library at the Tomas Bata University in Zlin, dedicated to open science, but open science is supported on a more general topic level than citizen science. Support is provided by partner organisations in the project and from CS networks, e.g.

¹⁶⁵ [EU-Citizen.Science : On Drought \(Na suchu\)](#)

methodological support from ECSA (European Citizen Science Association) and dedicated working groups in EU Citizen Science.

Challenges are as follows:

- Attracting and motivating people to participate in the project. The interview highlighted the need for skills and support in marketing the project from the beginning. More promotion means more data.
- As no financial support is secured after the project period, the sustainability of the project is thus on a voluntary basis.

Further information from the interview about ‘Na Suchu’ is available in [5.11. Appendix 11. Task 5.3, Case #3 Citizen science. Project Na Suchu. Interview 1](#)

4.5.1.4.3. Findings from the CS project ‘L’Observatoire Agricole de la Biodiversité’ (OAB)

The project is an initiative of the “Ministère en charge de l’Agriculture” and was launched in 2011 to compensate for the lack of surveillance on biodiversity. Its aim is to establish a link between biodiversity research and farmers as well as other stakeholders around agriculture to record relevant biodiversity data. The OAB provides the participants with five different protocols. 1) solitary bee nestboxes, 2) butterfly transects, 3) earthworm plots, 4) terrestrial invertebrate plots, and 5) bat recordings. The protocols address the broader topics and landscape quality, pollination, soil fertility, pest monitoring, and crop auxiliaries.

The participation of stakeholders is essential for a successful project. In this regard, time and effort must be allocated to capacity and awareness building, particularly at the start of the project, to ensure the depth and robustness of the data collected. Build opportunities to meet-up with citizens and representatives of the organisations involved in the project as part of a communication strategy.

Challenges can be the following:

- the applicability of the results. The farmers who took part in the study expected the results to be directly applicable to their daily practices, therefore, alignment of expectations must be clarified and applicable outcomes a priority.
- lack of conversation tools and interaction between citizens (farmers) involved in the project to promote ownership, recognition, and continuous participation.
- the user-friendliness of the platform used to collect the data. The platform has to be appropriate for science, i.e. live up to demands of scientific integrity and responsible data management, but also be usable by citizens.

Further information from the interview about ‘L’Observatoire Agricole de la Biodiversité’ is available in [5.14. Appendix 14. Task 5.3, Case #3 Citizen science. Project ‘L’Observatoire Agricole de la Biodiversité’ \(OAB\) . Interview 1.](#)

4.5.2. A qualitative approach to understanding skills and funding in Citizen Science projects – Main findings from the second round of interviews (Milestone 2)

The main recommendations from the second round of interviews are as follows:

- Recognise that **CS projects are different from other research projects and hence require other forms of support.** University policy papers need to clarify how the university will benefit from the citizen science projects to advocate for citizen science and the necessary investment in resources for citizen science projects. **Support for CS projects could include a single point of contact for citizen science (SPOC)** at the university or national competence centre. Support at the SPOC could be provided in two streams, human infrastructure and technical infrastructure.
- Human infrastructure: a **“hub” (lab or office)** that offers advice on how to design a citizen science project, where to find funding, recruitment and retainment of citizens, communication and promotion strategies, and how citizens and other stakeholders feel validated in their contribution to the project. Furthermore, the hub could provide knowledge of applications and technical solutions for data collection and handling, including expertise in ethical and legal considerations regarding data collected by citizens.
- Technical infrastructure: **provide safe storage for data**, and data collection devices for researchers to use in training and promotion of projects. In particular, guidance on how to build an easy-to-use platform that citizens can use to deliver relevant, quality data and researchers can use to process the data and provide sustainable outcomes.
- **It is a core responsibility of the university to promote research.** A communication channel should be provided by the university or between universities where researchers and citizens are able to exchange knowledge, interests, projects, and recruitment. This could be the face of the university in society and contribute to reducing the distance between research institutions and citizens, increasing trust in science and in the application of results.
- **Invest in the education or up-skilling of communication experts.** Continued communication is essential throughout a citizen science project and requires skills in science communication across diverse groups of stakeholders. The following profiles are identified as key performers in CS projects which require professionalisation and identification of a minimum viable skill set:
 - **A Citizen Science Steward:** the CS steward has an advisory role and provides guidance on how to run the CS project and identify target groups in the community and design the CS project to fit them. The steward would have knowledge about user experience and design of data collection and delivery tools, and act as a facilitator who could create connections between persons who want to contribute to citizen science projects and researchers who have a CS project that needs volunteers.
 - **Citizen Science “champions”.** Students or members of the community (citizens) who help with the face-to-face promotion of the project. The

champion goes from library to library, from museum to museum, and talks about the Citizen Science project to the public.

- A **“Community manager”** (facilitator). A project member (researcher or administrator) with the responsibility and people skills to continuously work with the community, and navigate between stakeholders across the project. They would ensure communication with the community, nurture relationships with stakeholders, gather up and solve issues, collect results and make sure the community is heard and valued in the project.

4.5.2.1. Introduction

To keep track of the progress in task 5.3, Milestone 2: ‘*Main findings from the 2nd round of interviews*’ only sums up the second round of interviews. These findings, together with the findings from Milestone 1: summary of interview 1 and Milestone 3: summary of interview 3, are formulated as recommendations for future support of Citizen Science projects at the universities in the TRAIN4EU partnership

4.5.2.2. Methods

Three citizen science projects were selected from the case catalogue prepared by the WP5 partners which made it possible to choose the most relevant CS projects. A qualitative method, in the form of three sequential interviews, was designed to ensure a series of short discussions, where themes and topics relevant to each project could be explored. The benefits of a short succession of interviews were that they encouraged the continuous engagement of the interviewer, the questions could be tailored to the Citizen Science project and the time taken from these busy people was minimal. Accordingly, the questions in Interview 2 were considered to be prompts and were tailored to fit the maturity of the project and consequently follow the interviewees' story about support. They were regarded as a framework rather than a list. In the interview framework follow-up questions were suggested, but the interviewer was encouraged to allow the interviewees to tell their story and not to restrict to pre-defined questions.

The interview guide for the second round of interviews was hence produced, based on the responses from interview 1. Interview 2 is in two parts. In part one, we investigated the support each of our selected cases received or were receiving during their project. We dug into the interviewees' opinions about the support they considered to be missing and the support they ultimately need. In part 2, we discussed the training and skills different stakeholders need to take part in a citizen science project, and again as each project has a different pallet of stakeholders, the conversation was led by the interviewee.

The interview guide consists of two parts. Part 1: ‘*Support for Citizen Science*’ and part 2: ‘*About skills and training*’.

Part 1: Support for citizen science

In this part the following questions were asked:

- *How is CS promoted/supported at your university? Who promotes it?*
- *If none, use the follow-up question:*
- *How would you like your university to support Citizen Science?*
- *Are there policy papers specifically on CS at your university?*

- *A follow-up question could be to ask if they know of any national CS policy.*
- *Are there CS associations, CS platforms, or other information services on CS at your university? If so, please specify them.*
- *Which support units at the university helped you throughout the project?*
- *Which technical infrastructure(s) provided support in your project?*
- *Which human infrastructure(s)-provided support in your project?*
- *IF no support, what kind of help would you like to have?*
- *What requirements or needs exist for handling, cleaning, storing, and sharing data in CS projects?*
- *Which aspects of support are CS specific and which are “agnostic” support? Where and when in the process around a CS project is the support most needed?*
- *What support did/will you need for reflection?*
- *Which gaps in support do you see?*
- *How are the researchers best supported in connection with CS projects at the moment and how could this be optimised?*

Part 2: Skills and training

In part 2 the asked questions were the following :

- *Which skills do each stakeholder group need (including yourself in running and administering the project)*
- *Does your university run CS courses or training programs (on which level)*
- *Did the [stakeholder group] receive training to take part in your project?*
- *Do you plan training for stakeholders?*
- *What gaps in skills development do you see?*

Full transcripts of interviews are available in:

- [5.9. Appendix 9. Task 5.3, Case #3 Citizen science. Project Arter. Interview 2 \(in-depth on support & training\) – summary.](#)
- [5.12. Appendix 12. Task 5.3, Case #3 Citizen science. Project Na Suchu. Interview 2 \(in-depth on support & training\)](#)
- [5.15. Appendix 15. Task 5.3, Case #3 Citizen science. Project ‘L’Observatoire Agricole de la Biodiversité’ \(OAB\) . Interview 2.](#)

4.5.2.3. Findings

4.5.2.3.1. Findings from the CS project ‘Arter’

Citizen Science at The Natural History Museum Denmark/Copenhagen University

The Arter project¹⁶⁶ is run by members of the Vertebrate Zoology research group based at The Natural History Museum Denmark, which is part of UCPH. They offer an introduction to CS for master and doctoral students, that is run over an 11-day Summer School, which rewards the participants with 7 1/2 ECTS. The course covers hands-on data handling exercises, field work,

¹⁶⁶ <https://arter.dk/landing-page>

excursions as well as workshops focusing on motivation, communication, and evaluation processes. By the end of course, the participants will be able to design their own project determined to answer a specific research question using citizen science.

There are no national CS strategies or CS networks in Denmark. It would be challenging to establish a national CS network. The concerns were raised regarding who would be the primus motor, how it would be funded, and how resources would be shared/provided between many different institutions and stakeholders. Universities Denmark could potentially be the resource to facilitate such a network¹⁶⁷.

UCPH itself does not offer central support for citizen science projects, although CS is named a strategic focus area in the university's "Talent and Collaboration" strategy¹⁶⁸. There have been attempts to legitimise citizen science at UCPH, but recommendations from working groups and position papers have yet to be implemented. The individual project is responsible for sourcing both its own technical support and its own communication support. Arter is included in the Ministry of the Environment¹⁶⁹ who provides the technical support and coders necessary to develop CS solutions. In Arter, and in previous projects, project managers have created their own project websites and brought server space with project money.

Communication in CS projects is a core activity. The project has to communicate with citizens, volunteers, experts who validate the data, other researchers, investors and stakeholders including technical responsables, communicate research outputs, and promote the project. It would be relevant in the university to centrally promote CS projects. Part of this promotion work could be to increase the findability of CS projects. The university could standardise the terminology around CS projects, so they are visible and findable in searches, as at the present time each project seems to use its own terminology to describe "citizen science", e.g. "community science", "crowd sourcing", "volunteer monitoring", "public participation", etc. The university could also provide a communication channel where researchers and citizens can exchange knowledge, interests, news about current projects and recruitment possibilities. This would be something new, as typically such networks or platforms are tailored to researchers or citizens, but not to both. Such an initiative needs to be centrally initiated and supported, as one citizen science project could not lift it.

Training needs in the Citizen Science project "Arter"

Citizens are expected to come to the project with no skills. They receive no training other than the instructions on the website¹⁷⁰. Therefore, rather than training citizens to enable them to contribute to the project, Arter points to the need to train "Gatekeepers". The gatekeeper of the project has the responsibility to communicate across different stakeholders, in different contexts and know how and with whom to communicate with at different strategic stages of the project. A particular communicative skill is to nurture the citizens and volunteers to ensure their long-term investment, as the project wants to keep contributors who deliver quality work. Continuous but relevant communication retains citizens in the project in the long term. The Arter project has, for example, experienced the need for special consideration and recognition

¹⁶⁷ Universities Denmark is the cooperation organisation of the eight Danish universities, which promotes the universities coöeration, visibility and impact: <https://dkuni.dk/>

¹⁶⁸ UCPH Talent and Collaboration Strategy 2023: [strategy_2023_UK_print.pdf \(ku.dk\)](https://ucph.dk/strategy_2023_UK_print.pdf)

¹⁶⁹ Globe Team: [Danmarks Miljøportal tager et stort skridt ind i fremtiden \(globeteam.com\)](https://globe.team/danmarks-miljoportal-tager-et-stort-skridt-ind-i-fremtiden)

¹⁷⁰ <https://om.arter.dk/videnbase/arters-webside-vejledninger/>

of the experts who volunteer their time and knowledge in data validation. This is referred to as “nursing”. These experts know that they have a powerful position. Being co-creators of quality data gives them this power. The project would lose its value without them. As a Gatekeeper, one has to navigate this power balance and ensure that the experts are satisfied. In the Arter project, they have established a ”Species Council” [Arts Råd], which represents the 12 natural history associations in Denmark that provide the expert validation of the data. Further, Arter has ensured that the Species Council has representatives in the Steering Committee, so they have a voice in the project (see diagram in 5.8. Appendix 8. Task 5.3, Case #3 Citizen science. Project Arter Interview 1).

Engagement is another area in which CS researchers need to be trained. CS has the possibility of engaging interested citizens in research and bringing them closer to universities. To engage citizens, the project needs to be designed in such a way that it makes sense for the target group. Also as it was in the case of the Arter project, it must be easy and intuitive as far as possible, so data can be delivered correctly and completely into the system, displayed with attribution to the contributor in the system, and easily extracted out of the system for analysis. Everything in Arter is Open Source – everyone (citizens and researchers) can download the data as it is uploaded to GBIF¹⁷¹.

In the future, Arter would like to see the participation of citizens in more stages of the project than data collection only. Perhaps in the design of the project and in interpreting the data as well as in publishing the results. Such opportunities would engage and retain the citizens even longer in the project. Particularly if the results are to be applied in society, this could expand the citizen science agenda and increase trust in research and research institutions.

The main requirements for support and skills are:

- for the university to establish a single point of contact and collate CS resources. Generic support could be in two streams:
 - a hub/lab that offers help and advice on how to design a citizen science project, recruit and retain volunteers, communication strategies, and how to engage citizens (communication and feedback on their work). The lab could be for all faculties and subjects, preferably a virtual and physical service.
 - data management: advice and support in data collection of CS data which has a very special character, GDPR, preservation, data stewardship (bias in data, mistakes in the data, messy data, etc.).
- to establish a network for researchers to share experiences and create awareness of CS projects. This could be a communication channel where researchers and citizens can exchange knowledge, interests, projects, and recruitment. This would also be the face of the university in society.
- to nurture recruitment, communication, engagement, and retainment of citizens and experts.

¹⁷¹ <https://www.gbif.org/using-gbif-data>

- to educate Citizen Science Stewards:
 - A Citizen Science Steward has experience with communication, recruitment, how to engage and retain volunteers and encourage them to do more in the project! In the lab-setting the Citizen Science Steward could have an advisory role and provide guidance on how to identify target groups in society and design the CS project to fit them. The steward would have knowledge about user experience and design of data collection and delivery tools, and act as a facilitator who could create connections between persons who want to contribute to citizen science projects and researchers who have a CS project that needs volunteers. Therefore the stewards need to be good communicators and design research projects with a high level of “oplevelse”¹⁷² for the participant.
- knowledge and competencies in thinking of user solutions in the project design from day one.

See Appendix 5.5-5.7 for the full interview transcript.

4.5.2.3.2. Findings of the CS project ‘On drought’ (*Na Suchu*)

Na Suchu¹⁷³ (On drought) is a citizen science project started in 2022. It investigates the current state of the agricultural landscape in the Czech Republic. The main 4 Oplevelse = experience, immersion, value, enjoyment. Goal is to engage farmers, farm landowners, or people walking by farmland in taking photos of agricultural areas and uploading the photo on the iNaturalist app, <https://www.inaturalist.org/projects/na-suchu>.

Na Suchu is a joint project of several institutions that are part of the Czech Academy of Sciences (CAS)¹⁷⁴, led by Tomas Bata University in Zlin¹⁷⁵. None of the institutions support and promote the project directly, but use the portal¹⁷⁶ as the main communication channel. There are, however, no funds to maintain the portal in the long term. External funds are required to support the portal after the project ends in 2023. Currently, project members and involved citizens are attempting ad hoc promotion of the project across a variety of platforms, and the project-lead publishes a monthly newsletter. The project members are also part of ECSA¹⁷⁷, which describes itself as a hub for CS initiatives and networks, through which the project members can present and discuss their topics and issues of citizen science with their project with an international group of researchers and stakeholders. Further, ECSA has working groups that inform on and advocate for the value of CS for achieving policy goals, provide a source of open-access tools and training materials, and set standards for high-quality citizen science practices.

¹⁷² Oplevelse = experience, immersion, value, enjoyment.

¹⁷³ <https://eu-citizen.science/project/361>

¹⁷⁴ Czech Academy of Sciences is a complex of 54 public research institutions: <https://www.avcr.cz/en/aboutus/mission-of-the-cas/>

¹⁷⁵ Research institutions in Na Suchu are : Institute of Geonics (Academy of Sciences of the Czech Republic), Research Institute of Geodesy, Tomáš Bata University in Zlín, Masaryk University and Mendel University.

¹⁷⁶ <https://www.citizenscience.cz/>

¹⁷⁷ European Citizen Science Association: <https://www.ecsa.ngo/>

In the future, the Na Suchu would like to see a grant scheme for CS projects at Czech universities and some university policy or strategy clarifying how to promote CS projects. Without such a strategy, it is challenging to design an effective communication strategy and garner long-term support for the project. Hence, at the present time, systematic promotional support is missing, particularly digital promotion of the project.

Aside from support in promoting the project, there is also a need for other forms of technical and human support. Human support could be an “Open Science Office”, which provides support and advice on practising OS in general, part of which would be expertise in how to run a CS project. Needs expressed in the interview are advice on applying for funding, promotion, and community management in CS projects, and technical knowledge of applications and tools that can be used to collect and analyse CS data. An important profile in CS support is a “Community manager”. In a CS project, one must continuously work with the community, with the public who is collecting the data, and participate in the project in other ways. The community manager would be the person who is the link between the project, researchers, developers, funders, and the public. They would ensure communication with the community, gather up and solve issues, collect results, and make sure the community is heard and valued in the project.

Regarding requirements for technical support, the interview dug into generic and discipline-specific needs, finding that generic needs in data management, and the provision of hardware infrastructure to store data and manage the data in a secure way were the most acute. Currently, the project data is stored on servers like iNaturalist, Microsoft Cloud, Google Drive, Google Cloud, and on the researchers' own private drives. This means that the data can be stored “somewhere” outside of the European Union. Similarly, project members are using their own devices, tablets, and mobile phones to show citizens how to collect the data. Researchers need “project” tablets or mobile phones they can use in demonstrations and training. Particularly for *Na Suchu*, there is a need for a spatial framework, and a specific server to run mapping applications particular to a project dealing with agriculture and the environment.

Training needs in the CS project Na Suchu (On Drought)

Researchers affiliated with the *Na Suchu* project need training in handling, cleaning, storing, and sharing data in a CS project. They need skills in project management and information technology (IT) knowledge because there is no IT expert or support service attached to the project.

The community and stakeholders involved in the project, such as agricultural experts, members of the Chambers of Commerce, and farmers need basic IT skills. These skills were trained using free courses on the European Citizen Good Science platform¹⁷⁸. In the Na Suchu project data collection is very simple. The public collects data with their own mobile phone by taking a photo and uploading it to the project website. They are only trained by text instruction. What to observe? What does it look like, what they are observing and what should they focus on? The instructions are intentionally simple, so anyone can join the project (see the instructions “How to take part”¹⁷⁹).

¹⁷⁸ EU Citizen Good Science platform is an online platform for sharing knowledge, tools, training and resources for citizen science – by the community, for the community <https://eu-citizen.science/>

¹⁷⁹ <https://eu-citizen.science/project/361>

The main requirements for skills and support are:

- For the university or Academy of Sciences to establish a dedicated Open Science office, which should, among other services supporting Open Science, provide expertise on how to run citizen science projects, from fundraising to the promotion, and identification of tools and technical solutions. Furthermore, the office needs to provide support in the technical, ethical, and legal aspects of how to store and share data collected by the citizens.
 - The university or the EU (if the project is funded by the EU) provides safe storage for data and devices for researchers to use in training and promotion of the project,
- The recognition at the university level that CS projects are different from other research projects and hence require other forms of support. University policy papers need to clarify, for example, how the university will benefit from CS projects to advocate for citizen science and invest in citizen science resources.
- Communication and expert facilitators. Continued communication is essential throughout a citizen science project and requires access and skills in science communication to a diverse group of stakeholders.
 - As a minimum, the university should give research projects access to its own communication channels, e.g. Instagram and Facebook channels, amongst others, to promote and brand the project.
 - Establish Citizen Science “champions”. The Academy of Sciences provides one student who helps with the face-to-face promotion of the project. The student goes from library to library, from museum to museum, and delivers lectures about the Citizen Science project to the public and engages people by this face-to-face event.
 - Each project needs a “Community manager” (facilitator). This person has the responsibility and people skills to continuously work with the community, and navigate between stakeholders across the project. They would ensure communication with the community, gather up and solve issues, collect results, and make sure the community is heard and valued in the project.

See Appendix 5.8-5.10 for the full interview transcript.

4.5.2.3.3. Findings from Citizen Science project ‘L’Observatoire Agricole de la Biodiversité’ (OAB)

Citizen Science at the Museum of Natural History, France

The interview focuses on support at the Museum of Natural History, France. The Museum is

the only museum in Europe to offer a master's degree and have a doctoral school¹⁸⁰. There is one course on CS per year, with room for 25 participants/candidates. The course covers different aspects of designing and running a CS project such as approaches to different topics, support, tips, etc. The course is a joint offer by the museum and Sorbonne University. At Sorbonne University, CS is currently a strategy topic on the university level, but there is no explicit support infrastructure or mediation between researchers and university leadership. In this respect, the situation at Sorbonne is similar to the situation at the museum before 2018. Citizen Science showed up for the first time as a topic in a research scheme at the Museum in 1998. In 2005 dedicated CS projects started at the Museum of Natural History and CS was taken up by the head of the museum as a strategic topic. For a long time, there was no organisation between the head of the museum, i.e. the strategic level, and the researchers performing CS-based research. In 2017 a more systematic coordination was started, so that CS became part of the museum's organisational structure, and a CS strategy was proposed in 2018. Since then, Citizen Science has been in the organigram. However, there are still no CS associations, CS platforms or other information services supporting CS at the museum. Optimally universities should have their own services for CS which would create a win-win-effect by internalising facilitation into the university.

There is, though, a strong human infrastructure in the unit MOSAIC at the Museum. The support unit MOSAIC was installed in the museum in 2018¹⁸¹ and the unit is mostly for supporting new projects in CS and advises researchers throughout their projects. The unit offers not only support but also an infrastructure for communication, data storage, and presentation of materials. They guarantee the technical sustainability of the outputs. Researchers need to trust and believe in the CS approach otherwise it will not work. The researchers need to trust the participants in the sense that they trust their capacity to collect and provide meaningful content for the project.

Many CS projects at MOSAIC help rely on the quality of the protocol for the data collection. CS “experiments” are not comparable to the lab environment, because there are no second chances to redo the experiment and adjust the measurement. Because citizens are involved in data collection this has to work right from the beginning. If it does not work right from the beginning, people will not be willing to participate further. We need to be able to improve the user experience to foster participation. Therefore, we use a lot of resources on one-to-one-counselling with different projects where data is gathered by different groups of citizens.

Training needs in the Citizen Science project ‘L’Observatoire Agricole de la Biodiversité (OAB)

In the OAB project, the citizens collecting the data are farmers. There are also “facilitators” whose role is to explain the project, its expectations, workflows, and values, to the farmers, scientists, and to other stakeholders. They recruit farmers to participate and then train them on data collection, etc. The farmers need to be interested and open to committing and contributing

¹⁸⁰ <https://www.mnhn.fr/en/teaching-and-training>

¹⁸¹ <https://mosaic.mnhn.fr/>

to the project, while the facilitators need to create relationships with large numbers of farming organisations (and similar institutions). Both farmers and facility managers need training to be fit for the project; there is one training session in late winter each year for new facility managers; and then another session in autumn for farmers and facilitators about how to gather data – topics covered include basic information about the project and how the data collection works.

Training is specific to each CS project. There are no generic training courses.

The main requirements for support and skills are:

- To offer support in the research design and “co-construction of research questions” (from project design to analysis tools). In particular, guidance on how to build an easy-to-use platform that citizens can use and deliver relevant data. Such support will result in a real engagement of the researchers in CS. It is important to ensure data quality, innovation, sustainability of the outputs, and technical solutions to gather and process the data.
- To establish a support team that includes members with specific skills and knowledge, such as a researcher who brings subject knowledge and knowledge on data collection and research design, etc. Other members could have domain knowledge of user-friendly interfaces and expertise in ethical and legal considerations regarding data.
- To motivate the volunteers: the citizens who provide the data. Support could be the role of facilitators who try to motivate, in this case, farmers, to become and remain involved in the project.
- To nurture and invest in facilitators. In OAB being a facilitator is not a full-time job, but it needs to be done constantly and with high dedication to ensure engagement of the citizens and recognition of their efforts. You need communication skills and skills in making the project attractive for citizens to engage in, by making it fun and rewarding.

See Appendix 5.11-5.13 for the full interview transcript.

4.5.3. A qualitative approach to understanding skills and funding in Citizen Science projects – Main findings from the third round of interviews (Milestone 3)

4.5.3.1. Introduction

To keep track of the progress of task 5.3, Milestone 3: ‘*Main findings from the third round of interviews*’ summarise the third round of interviews. These findings, together with the findings from Milestone 1: summary of interview 1 and Milestone 2: summary of interview 2 are formulated as recommendations for future support of Citizen Science projects at universities in the TRAIN4EU partnership.

4.5.3.2. Methods

Three citizen science projects were selected from the case catalogue prepared by the WP5 partners, which made it possible to choose the most relevant CS projects. A qualitative method, in the form of three sequential interviews, was designed to ensure a series of short discussions, where themes and topics relevant to each project could be explored. The benefits of a short succession of interviews are that they encourage the continuous engagement of the interviewed person, the questions can be tailored to the Citizen Science project and the time taken from these busy people is minimal. Accordingly, the questions in Interview 3 are considered to be prompts and are tailored to fit the maturity of the project and consequently follow the interviewees' stories about funding. They should be regarded as a framework rather than a list. In the interview framework follow-up questions are suggested, but the interviewer is encouraged to allow the interviewee to tell their story and not restrict to pre-defined questions.

The interview guide for the third round of interviews was hence produced, based on the responses from interview 1 and interview 2. Interview 3 investigates how CS projects are and can be funded. We explored the difficulties and opportunities that are in getting funded and discussed which funding models our cases would like to see.

4.5.3.3. Interview 3: Interview guide

The interview guide consists of the following questions:

- *How was the project funded?*
- *What is the name of the funder(s) and are there requirements that the project has to fulfil according to the funder (compliance).*
- *Tell me more about your funder(s), are they national, international, institutional, or a mix?*
- *What are the requirements from your funder(s)?*

- *What does the funding cover/not cover (budget costs)
What does the funding cover or not cover compared to the budget costs that you have?*
- *What are your experiences regarding getting EU funding?*
- *Any particular difficulties or opportunities in getting CS projects funded?*
- *Have you tried to crowdfund your projects? Third-party funding?*
- *Do you know of any other funding possibilities for CS projects? If yes, who funds CS projects in which area?*
- *Which model of investment would you like to see?*
- *Speculative question: What would be your preferable, optimal model of support for your project?*

See Appendixes 5.7, 5.10, 5.13 for the full interview transcripts.

4.5.3.4. Findings

4.5.3.4.1. Findings from CS project ‘Arter’

The Arter project (<https://arter.dk/landing-page>) is run by members of the Vertebrate Zoology research group, who are based at The Natural History Museum Denmark. The museum is part of Copenhagen University (UCPH). The project is funded by Danish funders.

The first funder is the ”15. juni-fonden” (<https://www.15junifonden.dk/>) which supports art and culture, research and education, humanitarian and social commitment, and Danish nature. The second funder is the “Aage V Jensen naturfond” which works for the preservation of nature and the protection of wild animals. The project is also funded with a few resources from the Danish Ministry for the Environment that have to be used on the development and maintenance of the Arter portal. It is through the portal data is collected, validated, communicated, and can be downloaded for analysis.

The project did not apply for EU funding, as it is a Danish project focused on Danish nature. Members of the Vertebrate Zoology research have experience with applying for EU funds. The EU has an increasing focus on citizen science, however, EU money is difficult to get as CS projects are in competition with “traditional” research projects. Further, being part of a European-wide CS project was very complex. Currently, some members of the Vertebrate Zoology research group are in an EU project with 17 partners on the topic of new ontologies and genealogy. They found that trying to agree and attain a joint understanding of the project’s aims and deliverables across so many partners is time-consuming. A lot of time and resources were used on understanding the EU application language and application process and now the project is funded, project time is used on making project aims into actionable work packages and tasks that make sense for the different partners and their very different contexts. The

communication flow throughout the application process and in the CS project is also challenging, as some partners have few resources invested in the project, therefore engagement and commitment are an issue too.

4.5.3.4.1.1. Requirements from the funder

The requirements from the funders were that Arter's objectives, aims, and goals have to be described and operationalized as deliverables. They require that the data collection has to be accurate and easy for citizens. The language on the portal has to be written in layman's terms and in Danish.

All funders have a place on the project's steering committee, so they are in continuous contact with the Arter project group and can contribute with feedback and ask questions throughout the project, eg., about the usability of the portal.

There is no university money invested in the project. The project group has invested many "in kind" hours in the project.

4.5.3.4.1.2. What the funding covers

The funding covers running the project and ensuring progression in the primary activities, which are the development of features on the portal, wages, and IT support. However, CS projects are expensive, there is a lot of communication, and in relation to a typical research project, not that much output. The research councils and funders have not yet opened their eyes to the benefits and potentials there are in including citizens in science and the extra costs that ensues. Private funds have understood the benefits of CS. Yet, their focus is on the teaching, education, and IT parts of CS projects rather than the "research" parts which are not prioritised in funding. Novo Nordisk is one of the few funders that understand CS and they are willing to invest.

4.5.3.4.1.3. Third-Party Funding

Some projects are permitted to share funds with third parties, a project can invite other museums to monitor the biodiversity in for example Denmark. Similarly, governmental agencies could be a source of collaboration but not funding, for example, the research group at the Natural History Museum supplies DNA & Liv¹⁸² with data about ringmarked wildlife and they collect this data using CS methods.

Crowdfunding is an opportunity that could potentially be useful but the Arter project had no experience with this. In the USA, philanthropy is a source of third-party funding, but it is not practised in Denmark.

4.5.3.4.1.4. Future funding models

CS is a method that bridges private and public funders. It does not completely fit the profile of the one or the other. The private funds do not want to invest in the research part of a project and the research funds down prioritise the inclusion of citizens. A future model could be a fund

¹⁸² DNA & Life: <https://snm.ku.dk/skoletjenesten/forloeb/dnaogliv/>

that covers both the research AND the CS part of a project, and hence support the facilitation of citizens and voluntary experts.

The main requirement for funding is:

- To develop funding models that are specifically designed to support CS projects, that is the research, the citizens, and the technical and human infrastructures that are unique to CS projects.

4.5.3.4.2. Findings from CS project 'On drought' (*Na Suchu*)

Na Suchu (On drought) is a part of a larger project investigating broader aspects of climate change and the impact of drought. As such, the CS project received funding from the larger umbrella project, and this was a one-time funding amount that will not be extended or renewed. There is no connection to the European grant schemes or the European Union funding. The funder is the Technology Agency of the Czech Republic. This is a governmental institution that supports applied research projects, where CS projects are one type of methodology they support.

Regarding funding from the EU, the experience is that it is highly competitive, and it is difficult to write all the facts and the information needed to describe a Citizen Science proposal in the limited space in the standardised grant application.

4.5.3.4.2.1. Requirements from the funder

There are no requirements or key performance indicators (KPIs) from the Technology Agency of the Czech Republic. The CS project group simply delivered a timeline and plan for research output. Across Europe, quality criteria for CS projects are being developed, in Austria and Germany for example. However, there are no formal requirements for CS projects in the Czech Republic at all. In the Czech Republic, the development of CS methods and quality assessment has just started. The Czech Citizen Science National Portal (CitizenScience.cz) has for example basic requirements that projects should meet to be published on the site.

4.5.3.4.2.2. What the funding covers

The funding does not cover all expenditures. It was necessary to co-finance the budget. The funding covered about 85% of the whole budget, and the last 15% was paid by institutions involved in the umbrella project. There was money for personal costs, travel expenses, etc., and the project group received some indirect funding that was used to buy a domain for the project website, hosting, and some graphical design/IT help.

The promotion of the project, such as holding roundtable discussions, is seen as part of the “job” of being a researcher at the university and therefore, not covered by the funding. Likewise, time spent on data collection and piloting the methodology and equipment were not part of the funding. The project group is unsure where they can apply for funds for a project that is ongoing.

4.5.3.4.2.3. Third-Party Funding

The project did not apply for third-party funding. However, they are aware of the possibility to apply for EU funds through “Impetus” (www.impetus4cs.eu) which funds selected projects and also offers mentoring or some other kind of support.

4.5.3.4.2.4. Future funding models

The Na Suchu project would like to see funding designated for the continuation or up-keep of citizen science projects as many CS projects have a very long lifespan. Once the major expenses are paid for such as IT and portal development, there are not that many funds left that can be used on promotion, facilitation of citizens, data management, and maintenance. If the institution is big enough, like the university or the Czech Academy of Sciences, they could budget for CS projects in their finances. Second, there is potential for national agencies to run CS projects in partnership with CS research groups. At the moment, there is no national CS funding in the Czech Republic. As with any other research project, the project group expects competition for funding, but at least some sort of CS grant scheme at a national level could contribute to the development of CS. Likewise, at an international level, the project group would like to see a Citizen Science Association established that could invest in international CS projects.

The main requirements for funding are:

- To develop standardised and transparent quality criteria for CS projects to grade CS projects in funding rounds
- To develop templates in EU funders’ grant applications, such as Horizon Europe, that fit the description of and elements in a Citizen Science project.

4.5.3.4.3. Findings from Citizen Science project ‘L’Observatoire Agricole de la Biodiversité’ (OAB)

L’Observatoire Agricole de la Biodiversité¹⁸³ is an initiative of the “Ministère en charge de l’Agriculture” and was launched in 2011 to compensate for the lack of surveillance concerning biodiversity. The Ministry for Agriculture is the only financial funder and as such the project is funded on a national level. Farming organisations support the coordination of the project by providing infrastructure and support for this, but no money. Additionally, the MOSAIC¹⁸⁴ infrastructure offers technical and organisational support.

The funding is not part of a specific funding programme for which there has been an open call for proposals, rather it results from an individual decision by the ministry to set up such a project. The funding must be renewed every year, i.e. there is no long-term guarantee for the funding. As a consequence, there can be only one-year-working contracts. However, cooperation with the ministry is very good and over the last ten years, the project has been very

¹⁸³ <https://www.observatoire-agricole-biodiversite.fr/>

¹⁸⁴ <https://mosaic.mnhn.fr/>

high on the ministry's agenda. There is still motivation and engagement in the project. The budget coming from the ministry is appr. 60,000 € per year.

4.5.3.4.3.1. Requirements from the funder

Since there is no specific funding scheme, there are no specific formal requirements and likewise no requirements to publish in OA. There are legal requirements for data management, i.e. person identifiable data about the individual farmer must not be delivered. The data must be anonymised and delivered as aggregated statistics.

4.5.3.4.3.2. What the funding covers

The funding covers the position of a project coordinator. The ministry also funded the technical infrastructure and the project can use the centrally funded infrastructure provided by MOSAIC. In France, there are many opportunities for funding. Apart from public funders, there are also private funders interested in supporting CS projects. The most important funding agency ANR explicitly dedicates 1% of its budget to funding for projects on “participatory research”, which includes but is not limited to CS.

Community engagement in CS projects is crucial, yet it is difficult to gain funds to fully cover this activity. Community engagement is not the same as outreach or administration and typically, there is no specific funding for that. In the OAB project, the role of the facilitator discussed in Milestone 1 and Milestone 2 is highly relevant to the project's success. This type of community management is typically not a full-time job, rather one person would act as the facilitator for multiple projects. A way forward could be to pool facilitator positions from several projects and compile a full-time position for a CS community manager.

Currently, there is a mismatch between funding schemes and the needs of CS projects. Typically, short-term projects for two or three years can be funded and whether an extension/follow-up project is possible is unclear in funding agreements. As a rule, a CS project needs more time not only because of the type of research question they address and the data they need to answer these questions but also because everything needs to be planned and prepared more carefully before the citizens can be involved e.g. in the data collection. The infrastructure used, e.g., web interfaces for data acquisition, must also be designed and tested and as a result optimised in terms of usability.

4.5.3.4.3.3. Third-Party Funding

Crowdfunding for CS has to be handled very carefully because of engagement and willingness to support a project. No element of force or coercion must be applied.

4.5.3.4.3.4. Future funding models

“L’Observatoire Agricole de la Biodiversité” would like to see conditional financing of long-term projects. There needs to be opportunities to make such long-term funding possible through clearly defined agreements on project aims. Funding should be secured as long as these goals are met. This would both safeguard the funding and give the possibility to stop projects that do not work and continue to evolve projects that do.

The main requirements for funding are:

- To pool positions of project “facilitators” from several projects to then compile a full position CS community manager who could oversee the communication of multiple CS projects. Community management could also be in cooperation with interested partner organisations or NGOs.
- To ensure funding opportunities that support conditional financing of long-term projects. Conditional financing, that is the project continues to reach goals and have momentum, would secure funding and safeguard not only the maintenance but also the evolution of the project.

5. Appendixes

5.1. Appendix 1. Task 5.3, Case #1 Research Data Management and FAIR Data. Visualisations of the universities' RDM units in a data lifecycle

Figure 23. Charles University data lifecycle

This project has received funding from The European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016674

Figure24. Sorbonne University data lifecycle

This project has received funding from The European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016674

Figure 25. Heidelberg University data lifecycle

This project has received funding from The European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016674

Figure 26. University of Milan data lifecycle

This project has received funding from The European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016674

Figure 27. University of Copenhagen data lifecycle

This project has received funding from The European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016674

Figure 28. University of Warsaw data lifecycle

This project has received funding from The European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016674

5.2. Appendix 2. Task 5.3, Case #1 Research Data Management and FAIR Data.
List of the skills of each profession

Name of profession	Data Protection Officer
Soft Skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Communication skills ● Leadership skills ● Project management ● Didactic skills ● User and domain analysis ● Liaison skills
Hard Skills	<p>Project management:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Legal, audit and risk management <p>Project monitoring:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Monitoring and reviewing personal data handling <p>Policy awareness:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EU and global privacy laws, legislation and policies ● Technology provisions ● Outsourcing agreements <p>Data security expertise</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Legal constraints related to data storage ● IT and computer security <p>Legal expertise:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Legal aspects of open data ● Having knowledge of data sharing agreements, privacy, consent and data management ● Interpretation of licence agreements ● Using third-party data regarding data management ● Personal and sensitive data protection and their processing ● Monitoring compliance with data protection standards ● Personal & sensitive data sharing ● EU and global privacy laws, legislation ● Having deep knowledge about General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

Name of profession	Data Scientist / Data Engineer
Soft Skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Communication skills ● User and domain analysis ● Analytical and problem solving skills ● Liaison skills ● Leadership skills ● Project management

<p>Hard Skills</p>	<p>Software & application expertise:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Software & application installation, configuration and management • Customised research application • Troubleshoot system and network problems, diagnosing and solving hardware or software faults <p>Technical equipment expertise:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Having knowledge about HPC, supercomputers, mass spectrometry • Installing, maintaining and upgrading servers • Troubleshoot existing systems (hardware, network, software) • Assists with the installation, configuration and maintenance of computers, workstations and/or other related equipment and devices • Recommendation of solutions relating to hardware and software acquisitions and/or network updates • Perform routine preventive maintenance on systems software, applications, hardware, networking, and communications <p>Data analysis expertise:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data collection methods and technologies • Data preparation, cleaning techniques • Machine learning methods • Programming languages • Data collection methods and technologies • Data mining and harvesting (API, scripts, etc.) • Data visualisation and graph databases <p>Data engineering expertise:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing tools and applications to cover data lifecycle • Designing cloud computing services • Big data techniques for large data processing and data integration • Data modelling of complex systems • Implementing systems for data access and data security • Databases and data warehouses expertise (develop, build, operate)
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<p>Name of profession</p>	<p>Data Steward / Data Librarian</p>
<p>Soft Skills</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication skills • Didactic and pedagogical skills • Leadership • Raising awareness • Liaison skills • Project management • Project planning

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Project monitoring ● Analytical and problem-solving skills
Hard Skills	<p>DMP:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Providing recommendation of tools & best practices ● Familiarisation data life cycle within a field of practice ● Expertise on DMP drafting and its reviewing <p>FAIR data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● FAIR (meta)data management and governance ● Having knowledge about FAIR tools and services <p>Ethical knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Research ethics related to a scientific domain ● Ethical and responsible data use and share <p>Legal knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Legal aspects of open data, data access, reuse and share <p>Data organisation and curation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Expertise on (meta)data standards, schemas, vocabularies and ontologies ● Data documentation ● Metadata conversion ● Improving quality of shared (meta)data <p>Data archiving and preservation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Long-term preservation solutions (arrangement, sorting rules, conservation time, required metadata) ● Authorization management to access archived data <p>Data share</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Expertise on repositories & data catalogues ● Making research data available <p>Policy awareness</p> <p>Technical and computational skills</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Programming languages (use of Python/R) ● Data extraction methods (e.g., via APIs, web scraping) ● Data cleaning, analysis ● Topic modelling and ontologies ● Social network analysis ● Data visualisation

Name of profession	Ethics Committee Administrator
Soft skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Communication skills ● User and domain analysis ● Liaison skills ● Organisation and time management skills ● Maintain high standards of confidentiality ● Project management

Hard skills	<p>Ethical expertise:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Research ethics related to a scientific domain ● Appreciation of ethical issues in relation to research and the requirements of a process to review these issues ● Knowledge about ethical issues about data sharing ● Having experience of handling sensitive personal data, and the associated audit processes” <p>Project management:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Risk assessment ● Compliance assurance <p>Project monitoring:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Having experience of acting as a source of expert advice ● Communicating complex or specialised information ● Operating ethical review process <p>Policy awareness:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Knowledge of current legislation, standards and codes of practice relating to human research ethics ● Capacity to develop further expertise in these fields (ex. relating to animal welfare and biosafety), including their implications for the conduct of research in a university environment
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Name of profession	IT Officer
Soft skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Communication skills ● User and domain analysis ● Didactic and pedagogical skills ● Analytical and problem solving skills ● Liaison skills ● Leadership skills ● Project management
Hard skills	<p>Project management:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Technical assistance and maintenance on projects <p>Technical equipment expertise:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Having knowledge about HPC, supercomputers, mass spectrometry ● Installing, maintaining and upgrading servers ● Troubleshoot existing systems (hardware, network, software) ● Assists with the installation, configuration and maintenance of computers, workstations and/or other related equipment and devices ● Recommendation of solutions relating to hardware and software acquisitions and/or network updates

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perform routine preventive maintenance on systems software, applications, hardware, networking, and communications <p>Software & application expertise:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Software & application installation, configuration and management • Customised research application • Troubleshoot system and network problems, diagnosing and solving hardware or software faults <p>Data storage expertise:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Having experience on data storage management • Having knowledge about data storage options (cloud based, servers, storage facilities) <p>Policy awareness:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of policies and standard <p>Reviews vendor contracts and coordinates IT purchases Assure the implementation of university IT operations, projects, and programs</p>
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Name of profession	Research Administration Officer
Soft skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication skills • Leadership • Raising awareness • Liaison skills • Problem solving skills and applied reasoning • Didactic Skills
Hard skills	<p>DMP:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge about DMP writing in funding proposal <p>Policy awareness:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assure the proper application of policies and regulations • Interpret and communicate applicable policies, procedures, and guidelines to project leaders <p>Project management:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding requirements • Manage multiple projects under tight deadlines • Risk assessment <p>Project planning:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preparation of grant applications • Knowledge and application of standard budgeting procedures • Knowledge of the electronic grants process • Check and verify budget calculations • Analyse the eligibility of matching fund contributions

Name of profession	Tech Transfer Officer
Soft skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Communication skills ● Leadership ● Raising awareness ● Liaison skills ● Project management ● Project planning ● Project monitoring ● Entrepreneurial mindset ● Analytical skills
Hard skills	<p>Project planning:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Planning and coordination for strategic project collaborations and commercialization opportunities <p>Project commercialization:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Having experience working in both sectors (university and industry) to establish industry-academia partnerships ● Commercialization of research data <p>Project valorization:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Communication of project through activities ● Reviewing patent application ● Expressing opinion on patents and industrial clauses <p>Legal knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● General legal aspects of open data ● Research data patenting ● IP, copyrights and licences ● Inventions ● Contract negotiations with companies relating to stakeholders, technology transfer agreements and licences, monitor ● Monitoring of emerging trends, sector analysis and industrial organisation ● Provide market research and analysis on technology commercialization ● Marketing of project through activities ● Manage information systems to ensure underlying support for commercial opportunity disclosures, patent and contract administration processes ● Commercialization of IP through licensing ● Creation of spin-off companies

5.3. Appendix 3. Task 5.3, Case #2 Responsible publishing. Open access publishing in the 4EU+ Alliance in 2021-2022. Bibliometric report on Scopus, Web of Science, OpenAlex, COKI Open Access Database, and Open APC

5.3.1. Executive summary

The aim of Task 5.3, Case #2 Responsible publishing is to investigate open access publishing practices at 4EU+ universities, to draft recommendations for support centres at the universities on how to support open access publishing.

The main objective of the report Open Access publishing in 4EU+ Alliance in 2021-2022 is to examine the publishing practices of researchers from the 4EU+ Alliance universities in terms of responsible publishing. Responsible publishing means providing open access to texts resulting from research funded by taxpayers' money (grants or researchers' salaries). Responsible publishing researchers should also take into account the costs of publication and retain their author's copyright.

5.3.2. Methodology

Bibliometric methods were used to analyse the publication practices of authors affiliated with the 4EU+ Alliance universities. Bibliometric is a multidisciplinary field that uses statistical and quantitative methods to analyse and evaluate scientific publications. Peer-reviewed publications from the years 2021-2022 were taken into account, with a particular focus on open access publications. Statistics and data have been downloaded from the following databases: Scopus™, the Web of Science™, OpenAlex, the COKI Open Access Dataset, and the Open APC. For more information, see the Introduction of the Report.

The subjects of the bibliometric analysis were the following:

1. the number of all publications and publications with a DOI number
2. open access publications
3. open access publication routes (gold, hybrid, green, brown)
4. research fields
5. publishers
6. co-publishing practices
7. funders
8. article publication charges (APCs).

The main findings are:

1. There are large differences in the number of publications indexed in the databases studied. The largest number of publications belongs to authors from Sorbonne University (SU) and the University of Copenhagen, and the smallest to the University of Warsaw.
2. Similarly, Sorbonne University has the highest number of open access (OA) publications, and the University of Warsaw has the lowest (up to 4 times less). The University of Copenhagen and Heidelberg University also have a lot of open access publications.
3. Only 50 percent of publications in Scopus™ have a DOI number, in contrast to over 93 percent in Web of Science™ and OpenAlex.
4. More than 60 percent of the 4EU+ Alliance scientific publications in 2021-2022 were openly accessible to the public. At Heidelberg University, as much as 75-77 percent of scientific publications are available in open access.
5. According to data from the OpenAlex database, the golden route of publishing dominates in the 4EU+ Alliance, while data from the Scopus™ and Web of Science™ databases indicate a predominance of the green route of scientific publishing (repositories).
6. The green route of open publishing (HAL repository) is predominant at Sorbonne University. At the University of Copenhagen, gold and hybrid publishing models dominate.
7. Around 30 percent of publications (according to the COKI database) are still closed. This means that researchers and other stakeholders do not have access to the results of research paid by taxpayers.
8. According to Scopus and the Web of Science™, in the 4EU+ Alliance the most popular subject areas in open access publishing are medicine, biochemistry, genetics, molecular biology, physics, astronomy, and agricultural and biological sciences.
9. Analysis of publisher data showed that the 4EU+ Alliance authors were most likely to publish with Elsevier™, Springer™, and Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI).
10. Sorbonne University, Heidelberg University, and the University of Copenhagen have the strongest collaboration, resulting in the highest number of co-authored publications.
11. Analysis of the results shows that co-authored papers in our Alliance are dominated by articles with more than 100 authors. The dominant research fields are physics, astronomy, and medicine.
12. In most cases, the largest funders of grants for research and scientific publications are specially designated government agencies. The situation is different in Denmark, where the largest funder is the private foundation Novo Nordisk. In addition, all the 4EU+ Alliance universities benefit from European funding for publications.

General conclusions and recommendations for researcher support centres can be found at the end of the report.

5.3.3. Introduction

The report analyses publications from 2021 and 2022. These are the years of the start and duration of the TRAIN4EU project. However, the study did not take into account the year 2023, which is the last year of the project because the data for this year was not complete at the time of preparing the report.

Publications from the following universities (forming the 4EU+ Alliance) were analysed: Charles University (CU), the University of Copenhagen (UCPH), the Heidelberg University (HU), Sorbonne University (SU), the University of Milan (UM), and the University of Warsaw (UW). Universities (Paris-Panthéon-Assas University, and The University of Geneva) that joined the 4EU+ Alliance during the project TRAIN4EU were not included in the analysis.

The number of publications and the share of open access (OA) in total publications, subject areas, types of OA, funding bodies, publishers, and the number of co-authored publications were analysed. Types of publications (mainly peer-reviewed) included in the analysis were: article, review article, proceedings paper, book chapter, letter, and data paper (Web of Science); articles, review, conference paper, book, book chapter, data paper (Scopus).

Statistics and data have been downloaded from the following databases: Scopus™, the Web of Science™, OpenAlex, and the COKI Open Access Dataset because they index the publications of all universities forming the 4EU+ Alliance. We have also decided to add some statistics on article processing charges (APCs) from the Open APC database. However, this data is incomplete as not every the 4EU+ Alliance university has a record in the Open APC database.

While some of the partner universities monitor their authors' publishing activity on an ongoing basis, others do not and this is not a common practice. Among the 4EU+ universities, three good practices are worth mentioning:

- 1) [Baromètre Science Ouverte de Sorbonne Université – Publications](#)¹. A webpage counting OA publications at Sorbonne University. It is based on bibliographic data collected from the Web of Science, PubMed, and HAL (French Open Repository).
- 2) [Indicatore RIC-5 DIP percentuale di pubblicazioni sul totale annuale, open access gold e green](#)² - RIC-5 DIP indicator presents the percentage of publications out of the annual total, open access gold and green. The Microsoft Power BI platform is run by the University of Milan that provides information on OA publications. The online platform allows the number of publications to be tracked in real-time in each faculty of the university.
- 3) [Danish Open Access Indicator](#) monitors the implementation of the [Danish Open Access Strategy 2018-2025](#). The Indicator collects publication data for each of the Danish universities, including the University of Copenhagen. The data comes directly from the universities' CRIS systems and is therefore more accurate than data downloaded from Scopus and Web of Science™.

However, not all Alliance universities have such tools at their disposal, and often their data is scattered. That is why we focused only on the aforementioned databases, being aware that the results are incomplete but comparable.

The analysis of researchers' publication practices will provide the background for further research and indicate the possibilities for developing cooperation between our universities. The conclusions of the analysis can also be used to develop support services for scientists at the Alliance universities.

Data for the report was retrieved from 23 to 29 September and from 2 to 4 October 2023.

5.3.4. Number of publications

The method of data retrieval from the Web of Science Core Collection.

Search by: affiliation, publication years 2021 and 2022, document types (article, review article, proceeding paper, book chapters, letter, data paper), DOI.

The method of data retrieval from Scopus™.

Search by: affiliation, publication years 2021 and 2022, and document types (articles, conference papers, book chapters, review, book, letter, data paper). Search within results: DOI.

The method of data retrieval from OpenAlex.

Filter by fields used to create queries in “works” entities collection: OpenAlex ID, institution.ror nr, publication_year (2021 and 2022); has_doi (true or false).

Publications with a DOI (Digital Object Identifier) number were included in the analysis because they are always accessed online and therefore more visible and accessible on the Internet, hence more frequently cited. „Furthermore, the DOI plays a very important role for databases collecting their information from different sources to avoid unwanted duplicate entries and to enhance the accuracy and quality of the databases.” (Juan Gorraiz, 2016, p. 99). The DOI is also crucial for the application of new metrics.

The table brings together the number of publications from 2021-2022, broken down by all publications, publications with DOIs, and the percentage of publications with DOIs among all publications indexed in Scopus™, Web of Science™, and OpenAlex databases.

Table 8. Scientific publications of the 4EU+ Alliance according to Scopus™, Web of Science™, and OpenAlex, years 2021-2022

Scientific publications in years 2021 and 2022									
University	All publications			Publications with DOI			% of publications with DOI out of total number of publications		
	Scopus	Web of Science	OpenAlex	Scopus	Web of Science	OpenAlex	Scopus	Web of Science	OpenAlex
Charles University (CU)	13658	11330	12207	6783	10846	11961	50%	96%	98%
University of Copenhagen (UCPH)	24404	21778	23087	13287	21287	22402	54%	98%	97%

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University	All publications			Publications with DOI			% of publications with DOI out of total number of publications		
	Scopus	Web of Science	OpenAlex	Scopus	Web of Science	OpenAlex	Scopus	Web of Science	OpenAlex
Heidelberg University (HU)	15898	15127	22375	8830	14819	22136	56%	98%	99%
Sorbonne University (SU)	26326	24112	28560	13257	23489	26675	50%	97%	93%
University of Milan (UM)	17743	15832	19231	6783	15394	18977	38%	97%	99%
University of Warsaw (UW)	6823	5621	7909	3160	5410	7667	46%	96%	97%

Figure 29. Comparison of the number of publications with and without DOI indexed in Web of Science™, y. 2021-2022

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Figure 30. Comparison of the number of publications with and without DOI indexed in Scopus™, y. 2021-2022

Figure 31. Comparison of the number of all publications 2021-2022

The first conclusion on the number of publications of the 4EU+ Alliance universities:

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- The number of peer-reviewed publications of the 4EU+ universities indexed in the Scopus™, Web of Science™, and OpenAlex databases varies greatly, from almost 6 000 to more than 28 000 publications.
- Sorbonne University and the University of Copenhagen have the highest number of indexed publications. The University of Warsaw has the fewest publications.
- The highest percentage of publications with DOI is at Heidelberg University.
- The analysis shows that the vast majority (93-99%) of the 4EU+ Alliance publications from years 2021-22 indexed in OpenAlex have DOI numbers. Similarly, in the Web of Science™ database, 96-98% of publications have DOI identifiers. In contrast, the Scopus database has fewer publications with DOIs, ranging from 38% (UM) to 56% (HU). A study carried out in 2015 on the implementation of the digital object identifier (DOI) in the Web of Science Core Collection and Scopus™ (Juan Gorraiz, 2016), found that the percentage of documents with DOIs in the life and health sciences, and physical sciences is higher than in arts, humanities, and social sciences. "Other disciplines, like the humanities and the social sciences, are less competitive and slower in embracing digital information sources. As a consequence, an identifier such as the DOI is still a minor issue." (Juan Gorraiz, 2016, p. 107)
- There are more of the 4EU+ Alliance publications in the Scopus™ database than in the Web of Science™, probably because Scopus™ covers more journals and records.
- OpenAlex database indexes more publications than Scopus™ and the Web of Science™ for the four universities (HU, SU, UM, UW), but not for UCPH and CU.

5.3.5. Open access publications

Web of Science™

The method of data retrieval from the Web of Science Core Collection.

Search by: affiliation, publication years 2021 and 2022, document types (article, review article, proceeding paper, book chapters, letter, data paper), open access.

Table 9. Comparison of the number of all publications and OA publications indexed in Web of Science™, y. 2021-2022

Web of Science Core Collection, 2021-2022			
4EU+ Alliance University	All publications	All OA	% of OA publications out of total number of publications
Charles University (CU)	11372	7191	63%
University of Copenhagen (UCPH)	21786	15954	73%
Heidelberg University (HU)	15128	11716	77%

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Sorbonne University (SU)	24119	19092	79%
University of Milan (UM)	15832	11577	73%
University of Warsaw (UW)	5625	4034	72%

Table 10. Web of Science™, types of open access publications, y. 2021-2022

Web of Science Core Collection, types of open access publications, 2021-2022						
4EU+ Alliance University	Gold	Gold-Hybrid	Free to Read	Green published	Green Accepted	Green Submitted
Charles University (CU)	3892	1472	555	4524	904	1870
University of Copenhagen (UCPH)	7043	4334	1532	11359	1851	3792
Heidelberg University (HU)	5294	3631	947	8557	1538	3042
Sorbonne University (SU)	6598	4559	1816	10755	2011	9716
University of Milan (UM)	6105	2285	888	9385	847	2689
University of Warsaw (UW)	1929	1089	183	1874	504	1499

It should be noted that the above figures for publication types do not add up. In the Web of Science™ database, a publication may have more than one open access type. This is because (for example) the text may be posted on the publisher's website and deposited in an institutional repository after the embargo period has expired.

It should also be noted that the Web of Science™ database does not use the bronze open access type, which is used for texts posted on publishers' websites without a licence.

Scopus™

The method of data retrieval from Scopus™.

Search by: affiliation, publication years 2021 and 2022, document types (articles, conference papers, book chapters, review, book, letter, data paper), open access.

Table 11. Comparison of the number of all publications and OA publications indexed in Scopus™, y. 2021-2022

Scopus™ 2021-2022			
4EU+ Alliance University	All publications	All OA	% of OA publications out of total number of publications
Charles University (CU)	13658	8186	60%
University of Copenhagen (UCPH)	24404	16905	69%
Heidelberg University (HU)	15898	11860	75%
Sorbonne University (SU)	26326	20059	76%
University of Milan (UM)	17743	12215	69%
University of Warsaw (UW)	6823	4509	66%

Table 12. Scopus™, types of open access publications in 2021-2022

Scopus™, types of open access publications, 2021-2022				
4EU+ Alliance University	Gold	Hybrid Gold	Bronze	Green
Charles University (CU)	4194	1448	1198	6008
University of Copenhagen (UCPH)	7364	4075	2159	14302
Heidelberg University (HU)	5267	3473	1290	10301
Sorbonne University (SU)	6748	2955	3793	18149
University of Milan (UM)	6275	2113	1333	11374
University of Warsaw (UW)	2126	1068	444	3024

It should be noted that the above figures for publication types do not add up. In the Scopus™ database, a publication may have more than one open access type.

OpenAlex

The method of data retrieval from OpenAlex: filter by fields used to create queries in “works” entities collection: OpenAlex ID , institution. ror nr, oa_status (closed, gold, green, hybrid, bronze, unknown), publication_year (2021 and 2022); group by: oa_status (closed, gold, green, hybrid, bronze, unknown), publication_year (all records, various years).

Table 13. Comparison of the number of all publications and OA publications indexed in OpenAlex, y. 2021-2022

OpenAlex, 2021-2022			
4EU+ Alliance University	All publications	All OA	% of OA publications out of the total number of publications
Charles University (CU)	12207	7496	61%
University of Copenhagen (UCPH)	23087	15915	69%
Heidelberg University (HU)	22375	16185	72%
Sorbonne University (SU)	28560	20605	72%
University of Milan (UM)	19231	13440	70%
University of Warsaw (UW)	7909	5411	68%

Table 14. OpenAlex, types of open access publications

OpenAlex, types of open access publications, 2021-2022				
4EU+ Alliance University	gold	green	hybrid	bronze
Charles University (CU)	3 595	1 817	1 288	796
University of Copenhagen (UCPH)	6 499	4 337	3 462	1 617
Heidelberg University (HU)	6 410	3 471	4 501	1 803
Sorbonne University (SU)	6 239	7 913	4 303	2 262
University of Milan (UM)	6 677	3 008	2 261	1 494
University of Warsaw (UW)	2 785	1 118	1 172	336

Figure 31. Comparison of the number of all OA publications 2021-2022

Table 15 summarises all publications (selected types) from the universities in the 4EU+ Alliance indexed in the Web of Science™, Scopus, and OpenAlex databases. The number of all publications has been compared with the number of Open Access publications.

Table 15. Comparison of the number of all publications vs. OA publications indexed in three databases

4EU+ Alliance, publications 2021-2022		
	All publications	OA publications
Web of Science™	93862	69564
Scopus™	104852	73734
OpenAlex	113369	79052

Figure 32. Comparison of the number of all publications vs. the number of OA publications, according to three databases

The analysis confirms that the OpenAlex database indexes the largest number of publications, but for OA publications the difference in the number of documents is smaller.

Figure 33 (below) shows the percentage share of OA publications in the publication output of individual universities. More than 60 percent of the 4EU+ Alliance scientific publications in 2021-2022 were openly accessible to the public.

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Figure 33. Percentage of 2021-2022 open publications indexed in three databases

At this point, it is worth mentioning that a comprehensive study of trends in open access publishing is made possible by integrating the data collected by Unpaywall into the Scopus™ and the Web of Science™ databases. Unpaywall is also one of the data sources for OpenAlex. As we read on the Unpaywall website [<https://unpaywall.org/team>], this is a project of OurResearch, “a nonprofit building tools to help make scholarly research more open, connected, and reusable”.

The COKI Open Access

Another initiative - COKI Open Access Dataset (provided by The Curtin Open Knowledge Initiative) is also worth mentioning. The COKI measures the open access performance of countries and institutions. It fetches data about research publications from multiple sources (Crossref Metadata, Crossref Funder Registry, Crossref Events, OpenAlex, Unpaywall, the Research Organization Registry (ROR) and Open Citations).

Table 16 shows the number of the 4EU+ Alliance universities publications from 2021-2022. Data was obtained from the COKI platform.

The method of data retrieval from the COKI. Searching the institutional profile on the website <https://open.coki.ac/institution/039bjqg32/>, where the last number is the ROR number of the institution (here – the University of Warsaw), chart Volume of open access over time, years 2021-2022, OA and closed publications.

Table 16. Comparison of the number of all publications and OA publications indexed in the COKI

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COKI OA Database, 2021-2022		
4EU+ Alliance University	All publications (OA + closed)	All OA
Charles University (CU)	11943	6135
University of Copenhagen (UCPH)	22122	11188
Heidelberg University (HU)	21986	10914
Sorbonne University (SU)	29574	14869
University of Milan (UM)	18446	9277
University of Warsaw (UW)	7549	3843

Table 17. Comparison of the number of all publications vs. OA publications indexed in four databases, y. 2021-2022

4EU+ Alliance	Web of Science™		Scopus™		OpenAlex		COKI	
	All publications	OA	All	OA	All	OA	All	OA
Charles University (CU)	11372	7191	13658	8186	12207	7496	11943	6135
University of Copenhagen (UCPH)	21786	15954	24404	16905	23087	15915	22122	11188
Heidelberg University (HU)	15128	11716	15898	11860	22375	16185	21986	10914
Sorbonne University (SU)	24119	19092	26326	20059	28560	20605	29574	14869
University of Milan (UM)	15832	11577	17743	12215	19231	13440	18446	9277
University of Warsaw (UW)	5625	4034	6823	4509	7909	5411	7549	3843

The conclusions on open access publications in the 4EU+ Alliance:

- The results of the database analysis show that the largest number of open publications comes from Sorbonne University, with the green OA route dominating. This is not surprising, since in France scholarly publications are deposited in the national open access repository [HAL](#).
- The University of Copenhagen ranks second in terms of the number of open publications. It is also the leader in gold (according to the Web of Science and Scopus) and hybrid publishing (according to the Web of Science).

- In the EUA Open Science Survey 2020-2021, which results were analysed at the beginning of the TRAIN project, both universities rated highly their level of embedding open access in publishing. The results of this bibliometric analysis confirm this assessment.
- The least number of publications indexed in the databases comes from the University of Warsaw, but again, more than 60% of these publications are open.
- The average percentage of open publications is high and reaches 71%. At Heidelberg University, as much as 75-77% of scientific publications are available in open access.
- The COKI Open Access Dataset has fewer OA publications than the other databases analysed, although it does include data from OpenAlex.

Figure 34 illustrates the proportions of open access types (according to Scopus) in the following charts. Charts were created using data from Table 5. Scopus™, types of open access publications in 2021-2022

Figure 34. 4EU+ Universities, proportions of OA types according to Scopus™

Heidelberg University, types of OA in Scopus

Sorbonne University, types of OA in Scopus

University of Milan, types of OA in Scopus

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Figure 35. Proportions of OA types according to OpenAlex

Table 18 presents the percentage of publications by type of access.

The method of data retrieval from the COKI. Searching the institutional profile on the website <https://open.coki.ac/institution/039bjqg32/>, where the last number is the ROR number of the institution (here – the University of Warsaw), chart: Percentage of open access over time, years 2021-2022.

Publisher Open – means that a document is available from the publisher's website or the main hosting platform.

Other Platform Open – a copy of the publication is made available via a platform other than the publisher (mainly repositories, but also pre-print servers, university library platforms, or other sites and blogs).

Both – a publication is available from both Publisher Open and Other Platform Open.

Closed – a publication is inaccessible.

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For more details see also <https://open.coki.ac/open/>.

Table 18. Percentage of publications by type of access according to the COKI OA Database, y. 2021-2022

The COKI OA Database, types of OA in %, 2021-2022					
4EU+ Alliance University	Year	Publisher Open	Other Platform Open	Both	Closed
Charles University (CU)	2021	15%	14%	37%	34%
	2022	16%	13%	34%	37%
University of Copenhagen (UCPH)	2021	12%	17%	43%	28%
	2022	14%	17%	42%	27%
Heidelberg University (HU)	2021	13%	13%	49%	25%
	2022	14%	13%	45%	28%
Sorbonne University (SU)	2021	8%	27%	43%	22%
	2022	14%	24%	38%	27%
University of Milan (UM)	2021	8%	15%	50%	27%
	2022	11%	13%	49%	27%
University of Warsaw (UW)	2021	32%	11%	29%	28%
	2022	30%	13%	29%	28%

The conclusion on open access publication routes:

- At the universities of the 4EU+ Alliance, the primary mode of publishing is through green publishing, as indicated by the Web of Science and Scopus, even despite the lack of an institutional repository at the university (the University of Warsaw will launch the repository in late 2023).

Table 19. List of the 4EU+ Alliance repositories

4EU+ University	Name of the repository	Website
Charles University (CU)	CU Digital Repository	https://dspace.cuni.cz/?locale-attribute=en
University of Copenhagen (UCPH)	Search researchers and publications	https://research.ku.dk/search/
Heidelberg University (HU)	heiDOK – The Heidelberg Document Repository	https://archiv.ub.uni-heidelberg.de/volltextserver/
Sorbonne University (SU)	HAL Sorbonne University	https://hal.sorbonne-universite.fr/
University of Milan (UM)	AIR - Institutional Research Repository	https://air.unimi.it/
University of Warsaw (UW)	University of Warsaw Institutional Repository	https://repozytorium.uw.edu.pl (It will be launched by the end of 2023)

- However, according to OpenAlex, Gold Open Access (papers published in journals that publish exclusively open access) is the predominant mode of publishing at all universities

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of the 4EU+ Alliance. The hybrid-gold³ and bronze⁴ routes are less frequently chosen by the authors of the Alliance.

- According to the data in the COKI database, the difference between the percentage of publications available on publishers' platforms and in repositories is not big. The exceptions are Sorbonne University (where the green route – Other Platform Open – dominates) and the University of Warsaw (where Publisher Open dominates). In most cases, however, the Alliance publications are available on both platforms: publisher, and repository or other platform.
- Around 30% of publications (according to the COKI database) are still closed. This means that researchers and other stakeholders do not have access to the results of research paid by taxpayers.

5.3.6. Research areas

Web of Science™

The method of data retrieval from the Web of Science Core Collection.

Search by: affiliation, publication years 2021 and 2022, document types (article, review article, proceeding paper, book chapters, letter, data paper), open access, and research areas.

Scopus™

The method of data retrieval from Scopus™. Search by: affiliation, publication years 2021 and 2022, document types (articles, conference papers, book chapters, review, book, letter, data paper), open access; Analyse search results – documents by subject area.

Table 20. The most popular subject areas according to Scopus™ and Web of Science™

4EU+ Alliance University	Scopus™	Web of Science™
Charles University (CU)	Medicine Biochemistry, Genetics and Molecular Biology Physics and Astronomy	Physics Chemistry Biochemistry Molecular Biology
University of Copenhagen (UCPH)	Medicine Biochemistry, Genetics and Molecular Biology Agricultural and Biological Sciences	Science Technology Other Topics Environmental Sciences Ecology Biochemistry Molecular Biology
Heidelberg University (HU)	Medicine Biochemistry, Genetics and Molecular Biology Physics and Astronomy	Oncology, Neurosciences Neurology Physics
Sorbonne University (SU)	Medicine Physics and astronomy Biochemistry, Genetics and Molecular Biology	Physics Astronomy, Astrophysics Science Technology Other Topics
University of Milan (UM)	Medicine Biochemistry, Genetics and Molecular Biology Agricultural and Biological Sciences	Chemistry Biochemistry and Molecular Biology Physics
University of Warsaw (UW)	Physics and Astronomy Social Sciences Arts and humanities	Chemistry Multidisciplinary Astronomy, Astrophysics Physics Particles Fields

- According to Scopus™ and the Web of Science™, the most popular subject areas in open access publishing are: medicine, biochemistry, genetics, molecular biology, physics, astronomy, and agricultural and biological sciences. This indicates possible areas for joint

research and co-publishing. The University of Warsaw opened a new Medical Faculty in October 2023; this enables new opportunities to collaborate in the coming years.

- Social sciences and humanities appear among the popular fields of research only at the University of Warsaw.
- The results of the analysis indicate the dominance of the sciences (STEM) or, in other words, confirm the existence of the well-known problem of underrepresentation of the humanities and social sciences (HSS) in both databases.
- Publications in local languages face a similar problem of underrepresentation. This was not explored in detail in this study, but the dominance of English is evident.

5.3.7. Open access publishers

Web of Science™

The method of data retrieval from Web of Science Core Collection. Search by: affiliation, publication years 2021 and 2022, document types (article, review article, proceeding paper, book chapters, letter, data paper), open access, and publishers.

Table 21. The number of open access documents published by the five most popular publishers for each university, according to Web of Science™

Publisher	CU	UHCP	HU	SU	UM	UW	Total
Elsevier	903	2971	1492	3841	1710	494	11411
Springer	887	1880	2222	2095	1681	543	9308
MDPI	1229	1375	1354	1375	2792	651	8776
Wiley	487	1912	1132	1360	954		5845
OUP		1024	698	1021			2743
Frontiers Media SA	403				832		1235
APS						272	272
IOP Publishing						169	169

Figure 36. Top 5 publishers 4EU+ Alliance according to Web of Science™, y. 2021-2022

The Web of Science™ database allows the analysis of search results by one of its categories – publishers.

- According to the Web of Science™, in 2021-2022 researchers from the 4EU+ Alliance universities most often published with the following publishers: Elsevier™, Springer™ Nature™, MDPI, and Wiley™. The first five most popular publishers of scientific literature for each university were taken into account. Elsevier™ published the most authors from Sorbonne University, Springer from the University of Heidelberg, and MDPI from the University of Milan. For Charles University and the University of Warsaw, MDPI is also an important publisher. In Poland, more than 200 titles of MDPI journals are on the governmental white list of recommended journals.

Scopus™

The method of data retrieval from Scopus™. Search by: affiliation, publication years 2021 and 2022, document types (articles, conference papers, book chapters, review, book, letter, data paper), open access; Analyse search results: Documents per year by source – top 5 of source titles.

Table 22 collects the results of the search in Scopus™ for the titles of the five most popular scientific journals, in which in 2021-2022 the most documents of authors affiliated with the 4EU+ Alliance's universities were published. Based on the titles of the journals (i.e., the selection of the “Source title” category in Scopus™’ “Refine results” filters), it was possible to identify the most popular publishers. As of 30 September 2023.

Table 22. Journals indexed in Scopus™ in which 4EU+ Alliance researchers most frequently published articles in 2021-22, ordered by total number of papers

University	Number of articles published in 2021-22	Title	ISSN	CiteScore /SNIP 2022	Publisher

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UCPH	298	Scientific Reports	2045-2322	7.5 / 1.312	Springer Nature
SU	289				
HU	208				
CU	166				
UM	166				
UW	75				
Total: 1202					
SU	564	Astronomy and Astrophysics	0004-6361	9.8 / 1.303	EDP Sciences
HU	214				
UCPH	156				
Total: 934					
SU	250	Nature Communications	2041-1723	24.9 / 3.268	Springer Nature
UCPH	244				
HU	187				
Total: 681					
SU	348	Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society	0035-8711	9.5 / 1.018	Oxford University Press
HU	244				
Total: 592					
UM	275	International Journal of Molecular Sciences	1661-6596	7.8 / 1.263	Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI)
CU	180				
UW	115				
Total: 570					
HU	243	Cancers	2072-6694	7.4/1.086	Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI)
UM	188				
Total: 431					
SU	215	Astrophysical Journal	0004-637x	8.8/1.089	American Astronomical Society
UCPH	159				
Total: 374					
CU	115	Journal of High Energy Physics	1029-8479	10.3 / 1.171	Springer Nature
UW	94				
Total: 209					
UM	222	Journal of Clinical Medicine	2077-0383	5.4 / 1.179	Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI)
Total: 222					
UCPH	219	PLoS ONE	1932-6203	6.0 / 1.253	Public Library of Science
Total: 219					
University	Number of articles published in 2021-22	Title	ISSN	CiteScore /SNIP 2022	Publisher

UM	164	International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health	1666-7827	5.4/1.280	Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI)
Total: 164					
CU	111	Physical Review D	2470-0010	9.2 / 1.185	American Physical Society
UW	95				
Total: 206					
UM	188	Cancers	2072-6694	7.4/1.086	Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI)
HU	243				
Total: 431					
CU	75	Vnitri Lekarstvi	0042-773X	0.5/0.107	Nakladatelske Stredisko CLSJE Purkyne
Total: 75					

Table 23. Top 5 publishers among the 4EU+ Alliance, according to Scopus, y. 2021-2022

	Publisher (Scopus)	Number of OA documents
1.	Springer™	2092
2.	MDPI	1596
3.	EDP Sciences	934
4.	Oxford University Press	592
5.	American Astronomical Society	374

- According to Scopus™, 2092 documents were published in **Springer Nature™** journals: Scientific Reports, Nature Communications, and Journal of High Energy Physics.
- The second publisher is the **Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute**. 1,596 documents were published in MDPI journals: International Journal of Molecular Sciences, Journal of Clinical Medicine, International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, and Cancers.
- The third publisher of the 4EU+ Alliance authors is **EDP Sciences**, with 934 papers published in the journal Astronomy and Astrophysics.
- 592 papers appeared in the Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society published by Oxford University Press. And 374 – in the Astrophysical Journal published by AAS.
- It should be noted that these are not all articles (and other types of papers) published by the listed publishers. Only the five most popular journal titles from publishing houses were taken into account.
- It is also worth noting that Elsevier, which is the most popular publisher according to the Web of Science database, does not appear in the list of the five most popular publishers according to the Scopus database. This is because of the use of a different methodology. In the Web of Science database, a publisher filter can be applied to all search results from

years 2021-2022, whereas in the Scopus database, only the five most popular journal titles (source titles) were taken into account and the most frequently selected publishers were determined on this basis.

5.3.8. Co-publication

The method of data retrieval from SciVal: Collaboration - Search Institutions and Groups; enter the institution; on the chart of institution choose: Find institution and enter the name of the collaborating institution; on the chart Collaboration with [name of institution compared] choose Co-authored publications, then filter the results: years 2021 and 2022 and Open access (all OA, gold, hybrid gold, bronze, green). Check the number of co-authored publications (the results are shown in the table below), publication types, subject areas, and author numbers.

Table 24. The number of co-authored publications, 2021-2022

Years	HU		CU		UCPH		SU		UM		UW		Total
	2021	2022	2021	2022	2021	2022	2021	2022	2021	2022	2021	2022	
HU			198	122	286	219	294	314	201	174	28	29	1865
CU	198	122			209	147	226	132	162	121	121	106	1544
UCPH	286	219	209	147			275	231	193	158	34	26	1778
SU	294	314	226	132	209	147			264	216	75	46	1923
UM	201	174	162	121	193	158	264	216			21	18	1528
UW	28	29	121	106	34	26	75	46	21	18			504

Figure 37. The 4EU+ Alliance, number of OA co-publications in 2021 & 2022, according to SciVal

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Figure 37 shows the co-authorship of open access publications between authors from the 4EU+ Alliance universities. The research outputs were published in 2021 and 2022. The data was obtained from the SciVal database.

- The largest number of co-authored publications was between the following universities: Sorbonne University and the Heidelberg University (608 OA publications); the Heidelberg University and the University of Copenhagen (505) and the University of Copenhagen and Sorbonne University (506).
- Researchers from Charles University published first of all with researchers from the University of Copenhagen and Sorbonne University.
- The University of Warsaw collaborates most strongly with Charles University (227 papers).
- Authors from the University of Milan collaborate most often with researchers from Sorbonne University (480 publications).
- Analysis of the results shows that co-authored papers in our Alliance are dominated by articles with more than 100 authors. The dominant research fields are physics, astronomy, and medicine. It should be noted that multi-author articles are the dominant publication model in these disciplines. This contrasts with other disciplines where single-author publications dominate (e.g. mathematics).

5.3.9. Funding sponsors

Funding sponsors by **Scopus™**

The method of data retrieval in Scopus™.

Search by: affiliation, publication years 2021 and 2022, document types (articles, conference papers, book chapters, review, book, letter, data paper), open access; and funding sponsors (first on the list).

Table 25. Largest funding sponsors for each university in 2021-2022 (1st on Scopus™ list)

University	CU	UCPH	HU	SU	UM	UW
Funders	Grantová Agentura České Republiky	Novo Nordisk Fonden	Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft	Agence Nationale de la Recherche	Ministero della Salute	Narodowe Centrum Nauki
English version of the name	The Czech Science Foundation (GACR)	The Novo Nordisk Foundation	The German Research Foundation (DFG)	The French National Research Agency (ANR)	The Ministry of Health	The National Science Centre (NCN)
Numbers of publications in 2021-2022	1658	1821	3406	2929	974	1576

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Table 26. Major funding sponsors of the 4EU+ publications according to Scopus™

Funding sponsors (Scopus)	University
Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft	CU, HU, SU, UCPH, UW
European Research Council	CU, HU, SU, UCPH, UM, UW
Horizon 2020 Framework Programme	CU, HU, SU, UCPH, UM, UW
European Commission	CU, HU, SU, UCPH, UM, UW
European Regional Development Fund	CU, UW

Funding agencies by the Web of Science™

The method of data retrieval from Web of Science Core Collection. Search by: affiliation, publication years 2021 and 2022, document types (article, review article, proceeding paper, book chapters, letter, data paper), open access, and funding agencies.

Table 27. Largest funding sponsors for each university in 2021-2022 (1st on the Web of Science™ list)

University	CU	UCPH	HU	SU	UM	UW
Funders	Grantová Agentura České Republiky (GACR)	Novo Nordisk Fonden	Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG)	Agence Nationale de la Recherche (ANR)	Ministero della Salute	Narodowe Centrum Nauki (NCN)
English version of the name	The Czech Science Foundation	The Novo Nordisk Foundation	The German Research Foundation	The French National Research Agency	The Ministry of Health	The National Science Centre
Numbers of publications in 2021-2022	1609	1749	3382	4132	800	1187

Conclusions on top funders 2021-2022.

- Most often, the largest funders are specially appointed government agencies, except for UCPH as Novo Nordisk is a private foundation. This is probably related to UCPH's strong focus on health sciences and medicine, which is also the Novo Nordisk Foundation's focus.
- All the 4EU+ Alliance universities benefit from European funding for publications (funds from the European Commission, Horizon 2020 Framework Programme, European Regional Development Fund, and European Research Council).
- It is worth noting that the DFG (German Research Foundation) has been one of the most important funders of all our universities. This is probably due to intensive collaboration between scientists from the 4EU+ Alliance universities and German scientists. The DFG is also the largest funding organisation in Germany.

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Limitations of grantor data analysis:

- Grantor data in Scopus™ and the Web of Science™ databases are difficult to analyse because the names of these institutions come in various variants. For example, Horizon 2020 Framework Programme or Horizon 2020 are listed separately in Scopus™. Therefore, both categories are counted separately. In the Web of Science™, the largest Polish funding agency, the National Science Centre, has more than 300 name variants with the names of individual grants included. To analyse the data on the number of OA publications resulting from research funded by specific institutions accurately, it would be necessary to clean the data (i.e. to unify names of funding institutions) extracted from the Scopus™ and the Web of Science™ databases. Such additional work was beyond the scope of this report.

5.3.10. Article processing charge (APC)

Data for this part of the report was downloaded from the [OpenAPC](#) website, which collects and disseminates datasets of fees paid for open access publishing on GitHub under an open database licence. The initiative aggregates data on open access journal articles (APCs), open access books (BPCs), and data on articles published under transformative agreements (such as Springer™ Compact or Wiley™ DEAL). All data is provided voluntarily by the universities, but not all members of the 4EU+ Alliance provide their data to OpenAPC. In addition, there is no data for 2022. The following summarises the 2021 APC fees for the three 4EU+ Alliance universities.

The method of data retrieval from OpenACP (3 October 2023): affiliation (SU, UM, CU), Filter year: 2021, Hybrid Status: All, Measure: Sum.

Table 28. Comparison of fees paid for OA publications in 2021, according to OpenAPC

	Sum €	Number of articles	Mean value €	Percentage (the 1 st publisher)
Sorbonne University (SU)	263.015	135	1.948	Springer Nature 16.65%
University of Milan (UM)	723.969	427	1.695	MDPI 42.4%
Charles University (CU)	951.495	501	1.899	MDPI 33.91%

Figure 38. Sorbonne University, treemap of APCs paid in 2021

Tables 29-31 show the total APC charges for publications in 2021. Publishers are ranked in descending order of publication costs. Only expenditure above 1% of total costs is shown in the tables. All APC costs, including those below 1%, can be viewed on the OpenAPC website ('view small values').

Table 29. Sorbonne University, list of publishers and total charges (APCs) paid in 2021

Publishers (24 entries)	Sum	Number of Articles	Mean Value	Standard Deviation	Percentage
Springer Nature	€43.800	18	€2.433	€1.054	16.65%
Frontiers Media SA	€38.453	19	€2.024	€685	14.62%
MDPI AG	€36.304	24	€1.513	€384	13.80%
Elsevier BV	€31.593	13	€2.430	€852	12.01%
Copernicus GmbH	€27.403	15	€1.827	€466	10.42%
Public Library of Science (PLoS)	€21.255	12	€1.771	€324	8.08%
Oxford University Press (OUP)	€11.995	4	€2.999	€242	4.56%
Wiley-Blackwell	€9.702	5	€1.940	€519	3.69%
eLife Sciences Publications, Ltd	€6.356	3	€2.119	€0	2.42%
American Geophysical Union (AGU)	€5.246	2	€2.623	€655	1.99%
American Chemical Society (ACS)	€4.783	2	€2.391	€451	1.82%
IOP Publishing	€4.200	3	€1.400	€433	1.60%
American Physiological Society	€3.000	1	€3.000	NA	1.14%
EMBO	€2.925	1	€2.925	NA	1.11%
+ view small values					
Total	€263.015	135	€1.948	€785	100%

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UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI MILANO

Figure 39. The University of Milan, APCs paid in 2021

Table 30. University of Milan, list of publishers and total charges (APCs) paid in 2021

Publishers (41 entries)	Sum	Number of Articles	Mean Value	Standard Deviation	Percentage
MDPI AG	€306.988	209	€1.469	€406	42.40%
Frontiers Media SA	€156.588	65	€2.409	€902	21.63%
Springer Nature	€93.429	47	€1.988	€631	12.91%
Elsevier BV	€38.495	18	€2.139	€701	5.32%
Public Library of Science (PLOS)	€20.622	12	€1.718	€246	2.85%
Informa UK Limited	€19.726	12	€1.644	€1.058	2.72%
Wiley-Blackwell	€18.718	11	€1.702	€1.075	2.59%
Oxford University Press (OUP)	€12.342	4	€3.086	€1.262	1.70%
view small values					
Total	€723.969	427	€1.695	€809	100%

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CHARLES UNIVERSITY

Figure 40. Charles University, APCs paid in 2021

Table 31. Charles University, list of publishers and total charges (APCs) paid in 2021

Publishers (65 entries)	Sum	Number of Articles	Mean Value	Standard Deviation	Percentage
MDPI AG	€322.616	193	€1.672	€529	33.91%
Springer Nature	€169.423	69	€2.455	€821	17.81%
Frontiers Media SA	€110.530	43	€2.570	€651	11.62%
Elsevier BV	€72.290	28	€2.582	€779	7.60%
Wiley-Blackwell	€38.652	13	€2.973	€1.161	4.06%
Oxford University Press (OUP)	€32.757	10	€3.276	€1.057	3.44%
Public Library of Science (PLoS)	€19.818	10	€1.982	€421	2.08%
Academia Scientiarum Bohemoslovaca	€18.936	21	€902	€308	1.99%
Informa UK Limited	€14.447	6	€2.408	€786	1.52%
BMJ	€12.622	5	€2.524	€797	1.33%
SAGE Publications	€11.395	3	€3.798	€1.194	1.20%
view small values					
Total	€951.495	501	€1.899	€961	100%

5.3.11. Overall conclusions and recommendations for centres supporting researchers

- University authorities should encourage researchers to increase the visibility of research outputs, particularly publications, by promoting open access publishing and DOIs. Researchers in the fields of social sciences and humanities should pay greater attention to increasing the visibility of their publications.
- Support centres should promote a shift in publication strategies, encouraging researchers to opt for channels that offer DOI numbers for their publications. It is crucial to provide training for researchers, helping them understand the significance and implications of publishing research results that have received public funding in an open and accessible way.

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- The number of open access publications should also be taken into account in the evaluation of a researcher.
- University authorities should ensure that as many publications as possible are indexed in the most prestigious bibliographic databases. These are used not only for bibliometric analyses, but also for searching for references, co-authors, and collaborators for research, which helps to expand national and international networks.
- An analysis of the number of co-authored publications shows that Sorbonne University, the Heidelberg University, and the University of Copenhagen collaborate most frequently. On the other hand, the number of joint publications of the University of Warsaw with those universities is several times lower. The collaborative network in the Alliance needs to be strengthened by increasing the publication activity of the University of Warsaw with the other Alliance partners.
- Around 70 percent of the 4EU+ Alliance publications are available OA. The remaining 30 percent of it is still inaccessible, meaning that academics and other stakeholders (the general public, business) cannot access the results of taxpayer-funded research. Support centres should emphasise and communicate the benefits of open publishing to researchers, not only in terms of benefits to the authors themselves (increased number of citations) but also in terms of socially responsible publishing. The public must have access to research results.
- According to Scopus™ and the Web of Science™, the most popular subject areas in open access publishing are medicine, biochemistry, genetics, molecular biology, physics, astronomy, and agricultural and biological sciences. In addition, an analysis of the collaboration between the 4EU+ Alliance universities (in SciVal) confirmed that the Alliance researchers publish jointly mainly articles in the fields of physics, astronomy, and medicine. This indicates possible areas for the next joint research and co-publishing. The University of Warsaw launched a new Medical Faculty in October 2023, which enables new opportunities for collaboration in the coming years.
- The results of the analysis indicate the dominance of the sciences (STEM) or, in other words, confirm the existence of the well-known problem of underrepresentation of the humanities and social sciences (HSS) in both databases. Research articles, the main form of communication in the sciences, dominate the analysed databases. In the humanities, monographs and other longer texts dominate. Publishing books in open access requires different business models to those used for scientific journals, as book publishing is more expensive and time-consuming. Some of the recently proposed models consist of freemium, selective open access, and crowdfunding, in addition to established models such as author payment or university presses. (Collins, Ellen, Milloy, Caren and Stone, Graham, 2015, p. 17-19). The support centres should assist in understanding new models of publishing monographs and their impact on the academic market, particularly researchers in art, humanities, and social science.
- Authors from the 4EU+ Alliance universities usually publish in prestigious journals from publishers such as Elsevier™, Springer™, Wiley™, or Oxford University Press. However, according to the data provided to OpenAPC, gold OA publisher MDPI, whose journals editorial policies are often considered controversial in regard with publishing most of the articles after short peer-review time and extensive using of special issues, received largest cut of finances spent on APCs on UM (42%; 209 articles published) and CU (34%, 193 articles).

Support centres should, in the first instance, identify the risks associated with publishing in journals considered to provide lower quality services and raise awareness among researchers on it.

The data from the OpenAPC platforms were collated with the data published on the MDPI publisher's website. Table 32 summarises the search results (accessed on 9 October 2023). In 2021, authors affiliated to 4EU+ universities published 2616 articles in MDPI journals. It can be seen that the data from the publisher's website shows a higher number of articles (for CU, UM and SU) than the data from the OpenAPC website. This suggests that the 4EU+ Alliance universities probably have higher costs for publishing in MDPI than the OpenAPC database shows.

The method of data retrieval from the MDPI website: search for articles, advanced search, affiliation, search filter: years - 2021, article types - article.

Table 32. The 4EU+ Alliance, number of research articles published in MDPI in 2021

4EU+ Alliance University	Number of research articles published in MDPI in 2021
Charles University (CU)	694
University of Copenhagen (UCPH)	514
Heidelberg University (HU)	292
Sorbonne University (SU)	89
University of Milan (UM)	357
University of Warsaw (UW)	670
Total	2616

The high quantity of articles featured in MDPI can be attributed to national evaluation system regulations. For example, MDPI is a recommended publisher on the ministerial list in Poland. Publishing in these journals yields high scores and speedy review processes. In the Czech Republic, article speed of publication, impact factor of the journal, and placement in open access also hold significance. When evaluating research, the focus on publication quantity and bibliometric measures, has resulted in an excessive production of publications.

A broader discourse on qualitative publication assessment and the implementation of the postulates of CoARA (The Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment) is crucial.

- The analysis of research funding data revealed that different notations are used to identify research funding bodies in publications. The inconsistent and non-uniform names of funding bodies and projects cause information about sponsoring entities to scatter across bibliographic databases. It is important that authors provide accurate metadata, including the grant and project name when publishing. Support centres ought to incorporate this area in their training program. More recently, the scientific community has also been considering the use of a unique identifier for funders of research and publications.

5.3.12. References

1. Juan Gorraiz, D. M.-F.-C.-Z. (2016). Availability of digital object identifiers (DOIs) in Web of Science and Scopus. *Journal of Informetrics*, 10(1), pp. 98-109. doi:10.1016/j.joi.2015.11.008
2. Collins, Ellen, Milloy, Caren and Stone, Graham (2015). Guide to open access monograph publishing for arts, humanities and social science researchers. Research Report. AHRC/Jisc Collections, London. <http://eprints.hud.ac.uk/id/eprint/25391/>

5.4. Appendix 4. Task 5.3, Case #3 Citizen science. Interview guide

The following interview guide uses and builds on the following work: Strähle, Michael, Urban, Christine, Anastasakis, Marinos, Lymperopoulou, Smaragda, Kikis-Papadakis, Kathy, Santos, Patricia, Miriam Calvera-Isabal, Ishari Amarasinghe, Ohto Sabel, Aaron Peltoniemi, Emilia Lampi, Joni Lämsä, Raija Hämäläinen, Julia Lorke, Florence Mühlenbein, Marius Oesterheld, Reuma De-Groot, Yaela Golumbic, Raul Drachman, ... Cleo Schulten. (2022). Conceptual Framework for Analytics Tools D1.2. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6045639>

The interview guide templates in the above deliverable are released under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](#) licence.

Interview guide

All experts receive a guideline before an interview takes place combined with the information how detailed we will want them to answer. Some of the questions in the guideline can be filled out by the expert before the interview, such as URL to resources or DOIs to relevant publications/materials.

This is connected to conditions for and length of the interview (duration, max. words for summary). The expert has occasion to reflect on the issues listed there and is not taken by surprise.

Social

setting

Let experts decide on his/her preference online or physical, over coffee or more formal. Any mixture of written and oral communication is possible. Because we do not research the expert, there is no need to standardise the interview settings. If the expert does not utter any preferences, the optimal setting depends on the intuition of those conducting the interview. Most important is that the expert is relaxed and can concentrate on elaborating on the issues of interest.

Documentation

To be sure to get their expertise, and not spontaneous feedback, and to exclude any communication errors, which always occur, experts receive not a transcript but a written summary of what they said to the issues in the interview guideline. The expert concerned can accept it as it is, correct, rewrite or retract parts of the summary.

Consented summaries will be used as an official source

Because experts are officially named as a source, we need written confirmation from them that we can use their summarised expertise in reports and publications. We need a signed agreement that they allow us to do so with the final version. We will confirm that they will indeed be fully named as an expert in all publications, papers, etc. in which we use their input, and if we quote literally from the summary, they will be cited by name.

Interviewer behaviour

All interviewers in Task 5.3 have sufficient expertise to conduct expert interviews. In all communication with the expert interviewers:

- Explain that the restrained communication of the interviewer serves to avoid influence.
- Signal all the time that positive, negative, neutral expert opinions on the discussed CS issues are equally welcome.
- Respect the time and effort of the experts by using it economically.

Procedure for you as an interviewer

- Send out invitation letter, contact by phone, if no answer
- Explain purpose, length, and conditions
- Send guideline together with a signed confirmation how we will use the summary
- Let expert decide on setting
- Get data protection consent Declaration of Consent on data protection from expert
- Conduct interview
- Agree on expert summary and have it signed

Declaration of consent

Declaration of Consent (DoC) to the collection and processing of personal data

If the expert agrees to be interviewed, please also ask her/him to sign a Declaration of Consent (DoC) to the collection and processing of personal data. This is required by the General Data Protection Regulation. If you do not have a DoC at hand, you may use the one below.

Research project:

Train 4EU, Task 5.3: A qualitative approach to understanding skills and funding in Citizen Science projects

Funding: Train 4EU, H2020-IBA-SwafS-Support-1-2020 - Project no.:101016674 - Start date of project: 1 January 2021 - Duration of project: 36 months

Interviewers: <INSERT YOUR NAME(S) AND THE NAME OF YOUR ORGANIZATION>

Pursuant to Article 6 para. 1 GDPR we collect and process the following personal data: Name, affiliation, specialist field, phone number, name of citizen science project, email address.

You agree to participate in three interviews within the framework of the research project mentioned above.

For this purpose, your contact data will remain stored beyond the end of the research project.

Furthermore, you agree that we may transfer the above-mentioned personal data to the

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TRAIN4EU consortium partners and the Project Officer responsible for the Train 4EU+ project at the Research Executive Agency of the European Commission upon their request.

Participation in the interview and online workshop is voluntary. You may at any time cancel an interview, refuse further interviews, and withdraw your consent to a recording or transcript of the interview without incurring any disadvantages.

The interviews are conducted in person, in writing or via online meeting and are recorded as far as possible (transcript and/or recording) and then summarised by the interviewer at <INSERT THE NAME OF YOUR ORGANIZATION>. The summary will be made available to you, the interviewee for review for one week and, if necessary, extensions/modifications. By returning the (edited) document, you confirm that we may use this document officially and publicly under your name and publish it in whole or in part in freely accessible (open access) publications such as papers in scientific journals and research reports. You will be named and seen as an expert by the publication. Personal contact information is stored separately from interview data and inaccessible to third parties (encryption of the file with the contact data, password-protected computer).

Within the framework of the legal requirements, you are entitled to claim from <INSERT THE NAME OF YOUR (THE INTERVIEWERS) ORGANIZATION>

Confirmation whether personal data concerning you are processed by us,

Information on these data and the purposes of the processing

Correction, if these data are incorrect

Deletion, if there is no justification for the processing and no obligation to keep (any longer)

Limitation of processing in special cases determined by law, and

Transmission of your personal data - if you have provided them - to you or a third party in a common and machine-readable format.

Pursuant to Article 77 GDPR, you also have the right to complain to the <INSERT YOUR COUNTRY> data protection authority.

Your Declaration of Consent can be withdrawn by sending a message to <INSERT AN E-MAIL ADDRESS TO WHICH THE MESSAGE CAN BE SENT> with the consequence that, in accordance with your declaration of withdrawal, the processing of your personal data by

<INSERT THE NAME OF YOU'RE THE INTERVIEWERS ORGANIZATION> will become inadmissible for the future.

However, this does not affect the legality of the processing of your data that has taken place based on your consent until the revocation.

Your personal data will not be processed for the purpose of automated decision making (including profiling) pursuant to Article 22 para. 1 and para. 4 GDPR.

This Declaration of Consent will be kept in a separate folder in a place accessible only to authorised researchers part of the Train 4EU+, WP5, Task 5.3 A qualitative approach to understanding skills and funding in Citizen Science projects. This is only to enable them to prove that you consent to the collection and processing of the data.

A written summary of the content of the research project and the research process was handed out before the interview. You confirm this with your signature below.

Name (capital letters):

Affiliation:

Email:

Date, signature:

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5.5. Appendix 5. Task 5.3, Case #3 Citizen science. Project Arter Interview 1

Date of interview: 9th November 2022.

Case: Arter, <https://arter.dk/landing-page>

Current funding: 2020 - 2023

How to cite Arter: <https://om.arter.dk/videnbase/om-arter/citering-af-arter/>

Interviewee: Anders Tøttrup

Interviewer: Uffe Smed

Summary responsible: Lorna Wildgaard

Part one: About Arter

Arter is a collaborative project, in conjunction with Miljøstyrelsen (Ministry of Environment of Denmark, <https://eng.mst.dk/>), Statens Naturhistoriske Museum (Natural History Museum of Denmark, <https://snm.ku.dk/english/>), DanBIF (Danish Biodiversity Information Facility, <https://danbif.dk/om-danbif/>) og Naturhistorisk Museum Aarhus (Natural History Museum Aarhus, <https://www.naturhistoriskmuseum.dk/?AreaID=4>).

Financed by the Aage V. Jensen Naturfond (<https://www.avjf.dk/>), 15. Juni Fonden (<https://www.15junifonden.dk/>), and the Danish State. Arter is financed through 2023, and is in the process of applying for further funding with the aim to continue the project. The Ministry of Environment of Denmark is responsible for the operation and development of the Arter platform (website) and APP (data collection), including data protection and communication. The Natural History Museum of Denmark provides subject expertise.

Figure 41. Organisation of stakeholders

<https://om.arter.dk/videnbase/om-arter/organisationen-bag-arter/>

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Note 1: Artsråd (species advisory board) consists of 2 representatives from 16 societies who advise on platform development, network activity, relevance and experts who can validate data and recommend data quality benchmarks.

Note 2: The Natural History Museum is the project owner and is responsible for project development. The Danish Environmental Portal (<https://miljoportal.dk/english/>) develops the code. Coding is undertaken in both Denmark and Vietnam.

Arter gathers knowledge about Danish species and makes this data available to researchers, nature managers, citizens and all those interested in nature.

With the help of the website arter.dk or the app "Arter - reporting" nature enthusiasts can gain knowledge about Denmark's approximately 35,000 species of animals, plants and fungi. At the same time, you can create a profile on the website and report finds of species as well as contribute to having the finds identified and validated by experts and by the community active in the Arter project. Further, all the data is freely available for download. The ambition to provide a national portal, where all information about Danish biodiversity is collected is a huge project, and stakeholders in the project as well as data contributors have many wishes for development of the platform in the future.

Denmark is the last land in Scandinavia to make such a species portal, previously data about biodiversity has been collected separately and without coordination by private interest groups.

Data collection and validation

Data collectors, be it citizen or expert, take a photo of an insect, bird, plant or animal seen in Denmark. These citizens are anyone with an interest in nature, therefore the platform and App need to be simple enough but at the same time detailed enough that anyone gets started and as a collective we can learn from the data. Using the App, the data collector reports their observations. They upload the photo and provide metadata, describing when and where they found the specimen. The data is then validated by experts and the species confirmed. The community can also provide joint validation. If a species is confirmed by 10 non-experts, the sighting is assumed valid. End-users can extract data, and sort expert-validated observations from community-validated observations. Since the app was launched 1 1/2 years ago, there are over 10,000 users of the Arter app, 140,000 observations of which 70% have been validated (November 2022).

Citizens in the project

A segment analysis was conducted to identify 8 "citizen" profiles. Communication is tailored to these profiles.

Support

Arter did not receive any support from the university (apart from lawyers at the faculty w.r.t. partnership agreements). They did not receive support from the library, and they did not ask for any. Only recently has the connection to the library been made. No help from the university IT department or university datalabs.

Challenges

Arter is attempting to build up a community of people interested in biodiversity. Part of

community building and engagement is the ability to have conversations and meet others with shared interests. However, GDPR means that people collecting data cannot directly message each other, neither can experts or the project development team contact them. The project is able to offer facilities to local (amateur) natural science associations. “Naturen Hus” (<https://snm.ku.dk/det-sker/naturens-hus/>) at the Natural History Museum of Denmark can be rented for meetings, exhibitions and citizen science project meetings/discussions. By offering spaces to discuss biodiversity and citizen science, Arter hopes to create interest, activity and support in citizen science. But, they are lacking funds to make Naturen Hus facilities available to a wider audience.

Another challenge is getting the balance of information on the platform right. The information has to be useful for both experts and citizens, this means the data being collected and variables therein have to be understandable and useful for both user groups.

Tough decisions need to be made regarding investment of project funds in development of the platform and APP. The greatest conflict is the platform having to manage thousands of sightings of common species that can flood the system. Data collectors need to have their observations validated quickly, otherwise they lose interest and engagement in the project. The demand for (voluntary) expert validators is high.

There are over 30,000 species in Denmark, and this is not a static list. Arter has employed one person, 30 hours a week with the sole responsibility to update and maintain the platform’s taxonomy. This is a big resource in the project. If the taxonomy is not up-to-date, users will be dissatisfied and engagement will fizzle out.

Future development and aims in Arter

If the project gets successfully funded, over the next three years the ambition is to develop the platform to better support reporting of botanical and ornithological data. At the present time, the majority of ornithological data is collected by the Danish Ornithological Society at “Birdlife” (<https://www.dof.dk/en>), and information about mushrooms and fungi are collected by the Danish Mycological Society (<http://www.svampe.dk/>). It would be beneficial to have these two societies and their data in Arter. Both the Ornithological and Mycological societies have demands for data and data collection that the Arter platform cannot accommodate at the present time.

5.6. Appendix 6. Task 5.3, Case #3 Citizen science. Project Arter. Interview 2 (in-depth on support & training) – summary.

Date of interview: 15th February 2023

Name of expert: Anders Tøttrup

Name of interviewer: Uffe Smed

Summary responsible: Lorna Wildgaard

Duration: 60 mins

Case: Arter, <https://arter.dk/landing-page>

How to cite Arter: <https://om.arter.dk/videnbase/om-arter/citering-af-arter/>

Part 1: Support for citizen science

We would now like to enquire into the support you received during the project. Then we'll ask about the support that perhaps was missing and you needed (or vice versa, support you received but did not need!). In the second part of the interview we'll talk about the training and skills needed to take part in a citizen science project.

- **How is CS promoted/supported at your university? Who promotes it?**
- Not centrally, it is the individual project that has the responsibility to provide support and promote the projects. It would be relevant in the university to centrally promote CS projects. It is a core responsibility of the university to promote research, particularly regarding the relevance of research for society and promote trust in the research institutions. The ideal is to reduce the distance between universities, the public and government institutions. At certain places in the US, you can see distrust in research, fake news that is flourishing and people who do not understand or trust research institutions. Funding that comes from the EU and other private actors are a component of citizen science, and it is obvious that the university should support and assist researchers. The university could establish a single point of contact, collate CS resources, establish a network for researchers to share experience and create awareness of CS projects.

IF none, a follow-up question:

- **How would you like your university to support Citizen Science?**
- As a minimum, provide a research support infrastructure – this could be an innovation hub or a datalab or the like that have already been established in other contexts at the university over the last few years. Another perspective could be centrally to support a network of citizen scientists.

After one has been involved in a citizen science project, often one would like to continue in the project or try another one. But at the present time there is no unit or person at the university working on retaining talented citizen science contributors. Citizen science projects are typically short lived. Volunteers (citizens and researchers) take part for about two years, for a researcher employed as a project member, and there are no

possibilities or paths to keep these people in the project. There are rarely any funds either.

We need to grab this possibility to engage interested citizens in research and get them closer to universities. One idea the university could provide is a communication channel where researchers and citizens can exchange knowledge, interests, projects and recruitment. This could be the face of the university in society. A network for both researchers and citizens. This could be both a physical and virtual network/platform/website – a Danish network for citizen science where researchers can post their projects, preferably with filtering possibilities to attract target audiences and collaborators within an area of interest. Here the researcher and citizen could read about and find projects they could take part in or learn from. This would be something new, as typically such networks or platforms are tailored researchers OR citizens and not both. Such an initiative needs to be centrally initiated and supported, no one citizen science project can lift it.

- **Are there policy papers specifically on CS at your university?** (*A follow-up question could be asked if they know of any national CS policy*).
- Citizen Science is named as a strategic focus area, but there are no governing policies or strategies at UCPH to support and legitimise citizen science.

In the UCPH strategy “Talent and collaboration 2023”:

https://about.ku.dk/strategy2023/download-pdf/strategy_2023_UK_print.pdf

Citizen Science is identified as an aim: “Increase our contribution to open science, including open access, open data and citizen science, as a focal point for increased global knowledge exchange”.

Further, in 2019 an OS-taskforce with the aim to identify a roadmap for OS at UCPH was established, consisting of directors from the University IT department, Research and Innovation, the university library and included an Open Science ambassador. They built on the work of LERU and eight focus areas, including citizen science, in Open Science work. The work of the taskforce was to drive and coordinate the process and is published on the UCPH internal pages (<https://kUNET.ku.dk/arbejdsomraader/forskning/open-science/Sider/default.aspx>) and their aims regarding citizen science were as follows:

After conducting workshops across the university and interviewing citizen science experts the UCPH task force recommended in 2020 that citizen science:

- Investigating how to build a simple and transparent system to support citizen science at UCPH.
- Citizen science is a priority area that needs to be supported and included (credited) in researcher evaluations.

The main recommendation of the taskforce was to create an Open Science forum at the university, with representatives from each faculty (administration, IT, experts in research evaluation and researchers) that can nurture, engage in and monitor the cultural change and development in the following Strategic areas: Open Access, Open Education, Data Management based on FAIR principles, Citizen Science. The recommendations of the taskforce

have never been implemented. There are no national CS strategies in Denmark. Attempts have been made to develop such a strategy but the Ministry of Science and Education was at the time prioritising EU calls.

It is also challenging to establish a national citizen science network, and sadly it comes down to resources – who would be the primus motor, how would it be funded, how could we share/provide resources across many different institutions and stakeholders. Maybe Universities Denmark could lift the network: <https://dkuni.dk/> (Explanation: Universities Denmark is the cooperation organisation of the eight Danish universities, which promotes the universities' cooperation, visibility and impact).

So, there is no national engagement at the present time. It will most likely be difficult to get-off the group because of the competition element between universities and the rectors have to reach a consensus.

- **Are there CS associations, CS platforms or other information services on CS at your university? If so, please specify them.**

If they name some, we can do research on who operates them and which expectations did they have

- No, not as of yet.

We are holding a workshop to investigate the placement and role of a citizen science lab at the university. The aim is to garner support from each faculty at the university. We are hoping for funding from the university's pool of strategic funds.

- **Which support units at the university helped you throughout the project?** *(suggest the library, central admin, data manager, data steward, EU office or other to get the ball rolling without biassing the expert). We aim to compare the needs formulated by the projects with the available services/infrastructures (on campus, but also at other levels, e.g. within EOSC or similar) in order to answer the question of whether there is a lack of services or whether the existing services are not visible enough or somehow too difficult to use.*

- None.

- **Which technical infrastructure(s) provided support in your project?**

- None from UCPH. The project has its own IT solutions and support. Arter is included in the Ministry of the Environment of Denmark's framework agreement with the IT firm "Globe Team", who provide the technical support and coders necessary to develop solutions.

IF no support

- **What kind of help would you like to have?**

- It would be great if UCPH had an IT department that could establish a server for research data. But we knew from the start of Arter that the university could not provide the IT support/infrastructure we needed, so they have never been included in our considerations as a solution. We have "Globe Team " in Arter and in previous projects we have made our own project websites and brought server space with project money.

- **What requirements or needs exist for handling, cleaning, storing and sharing data in CS projects?**

Encourage the expert to consider requirements from the side of the citizens collecting the data, researchers/technicians handling the data and requirements from the funder.

- Well, in Arter everything is Open Source – everyone (citizens and researchers) can download the data as we upload to GBIF (<https://www.gbif.org/using-gbif-data>). The data is validated by experts in the Arter community. As a researcher, you can easily filter the data that has not been validated out of the data export. We have been careful to design a system that is easy for both citizens and researchers to use.

In other projects, with other types of data and in other types of systems, you need R or Python skills to get the data out of the database, for example in the Ring Marking project, <https://rc.ku.dk/>. You needed programming skills to clean the data, import/export the data but in Arter we thought user solutions from the get-go.

- **Which aspects of support are Citizen Science specific and which are “agnostic” support? Basically, is there a need for Citizen Science support or is general OS support enough (DM, coding, communication etc)?**

- Generic support could be in two streams:
 1. A hub/lab that offers help and advice in how to design a citizen science project, recruit and retain volunteers, communication strategies and how to engage citizens (communication and feedback on their work). We want to ensure we engage these people who are invested in the project and deliver quality data). We have experienced that continuous/frequent feedback retains citizens in the project in the long term. The lab could be for all faculties and subjects, perhaps both a virtual and physical service.
 2. Data management: advice and support in data collection, GDPR, preservation, data stewardship (bias in data, mistakes in the data, messy data – data has a special character in citizen science).

In the Arter project, we have experienced a special collaboration with the experts who volunteer their time and expertise in data validation. It takes time to engage these experts, they need “nursing” to keep them invested in the project. Their contribution needs to be recognised. These experts know they have a powerful position, co-creation of quality data gives them this power. The project would lose its value without them. As a project manager (gatekeeper), I have to accept this power and ensure they are happy. In a citizen science project there are many interests to juggle, but particularly challenging is the power of the species expert. Accordingly, we have established an “Species Council” [Arts Råd], that represents the natural history associations in Denmark (in Danish: <https://om.arter.dk/videnbase/bag-om-arter/organisationen-bag-arter/>). (See Figure 42).

Figure 42. Organisation diagram

- **Where and when in the process around a CS project is the support most needed?**
- See above.
- **What support did/will you need for reflection?**
- See above.
- **Which gaps in support do you see?**
- Inhouse IT support. CS lab at the university (see above).
- **How are the researchers best supported in connection with CS projects at the moment and how could this be optimised?**
- As we have talked about before, a network and a lab. The university could also standardise the terminology around citizen science projects, so they are visible and findable in searches. We tried to do a landscaping study of which citizen science was being produced at UCPH and who was involved in them, but it was impossible to create an informative summary. Each project seems to use its own terminology to describe “citizen science”, e.g. Community science, crowdsourcing, volunteer monitoring, public participation, etc.

Part 2: About skills and training

- *Part of the support infrastructure is ensuring skill development. You mentioned in the first interview that [name the stakeholder groups] were involved in the project. For each stakeholder group please talk about the skills they needed to be part of your*

project. We are looking at skills on a higher level in this interview. To get this conversation started, describe briefly:

Which skills does each stakeholder group need (including yourself in running and administering the project)?

- The Arter project is specifically designed to tune in to and engage different target groups. We expect the citizens to come to the project with no skills. Therefore the project needs to be designed so anyone can take part, and in Arter our aim is to include knowledge from all taxonomies in Denmark, so experts need to be able to easily contribute to.
- **Does your university run CS courses or training programs (on which level)?**
- We have a summer school in citizen science that is open for PhDs. and master students. It gives 7½ ECTS and takes 11 days with a project to complete after the last course day.
- **Did the [stakeholder group] receive training to take part in your project? (Do you plan for stakeholder training?)**
- No, the citizens receive no training. The platform is designed to be easy to use. Instructions on how to use the Arter platform are found here: <https://om.arter.dk/videnbase/arters-webside-vejledninger/>
Experts come to the project with their deep knowledge of species and taxonomy. Some are researchers, some are amateurs with extensive knowledge.
We do not use resources on training, all resources are used on communication and recruitment.
- **Which gaps in skills development do you see?**
- We need Citizen Science Stewards: Citizen Science Stewards has experience with communication, recruitment, how to engage and retain volunteers and encourage them to do more in the project! The Citizen Science Steward could design the project so it makes sense for the target group, in the case of Arter as easy and intuitive as possible so data can be delivered as correct and complete as possible. In the lab-setting the citizen science data steward could identify target groups in society, have knowledge about user-experience and design and act as a facilitator who could create connections between persons who want to contribute more to citizen science projects and researchers. The stewards also needs to be a good communicator and design research projects with a high level of “oplevelse” for the participant.

Oplevelse = experience, immersion, value, enjoyment.

In the future, I would like to see citizen science projects involve citizens in much more of the project, not just data collection. Perhaps in the design and the project to interpreting and publishing the results. Such opportunities would engage and retain the citizens long term in the project, and particularly if the results are to be applied in society, this could expand the citizen science agenda and increase trust in research/institutions.

Signatures

Anders Tøttrup, Uffe Smed

This project has received funding from The European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016674

Appendix 6.1: Call for the kick-off workshop

What is a Citizen Science Lab?

Citizen Science Lab is a cross-faculty initiative that aims to strengthen UCPH's research by increasing and qualifying the use of Citizen Science throughout UCPH. Citizen Science Lab must, among other things, spread knowledge of Citizen Science among UCPH researchers and make it easier for them to get started.

The Citizen Science Lab must be a natural place for researchers to start Citizen Science projects, seek collaborations, advice and match-making with citizens. According to the plan, the Citizen Science Lab will be anchored at the Statens Natural History Museum (SNM) and will possibly could use the Lighthouse or the Fiolbiblioteket for outside activities

Why the kick-off workshop?

The aim of the workshop is to clarify:

- How Citizen Science is relevant for all faculties
- Which services and activate the Citizen Science lab needs to deliver to create the greatest possible value.

On the basis of the workshop, a cross-faculty working group can prepare proposals for a concrete activity plan regarding final approval of the establishment of the Citizen Science Lab at UCPH. **Workshop main discussion topics**

1: How will the Citizen Science lab be visible and relevant for researchers at all faculties?

2: Which services and activities should the Citizen Science Lab deliver to create the greatest possible value?

Appendix 6.2: Summer school

<https://kurser.ku.dk/course/nnmk21000u/2021-2022>

This course offers an introduction to citizen science: the involvement of the public in the scientific process. Members of the general public undertake various tasks often in collaboration with or under the direction of professional scientists and scientific institutions. The development and application of citizen science is increasing around the world as a method to collect large amounts of data and make research relevant for the public by co-creation. Through lectures and discussion seminars, you will be presented for various projects and applications of citizen science. You will get experience with data handling in exercises and during the course there will be field work opportunities as well as workshops focussing on motivation, communication, and evaluation processes. By the end of course you will design your own project determined to answer a specific research question using citizen science.

Competencies

During the course you will obtain the following competencies:

- Evaluate citizen science literature
- Identify research questions relevant for citizen science and reflect on solutions
- Target specific groups of volunteers based on motivation, prerequisites and preferences
- Design a citizen science project including all aspects from idea/question and communication to methods development and data analyses
- Application of co-creation methods

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Skills

During the course you will obtain the following skills:

- Communication of scientific methods and research results to various public target groups
- Design citizen science methods and apply a selection of these methods
- Handle and analyse citizen science data

Knowledge

During the course you will obtain the following knowledge:

- Basic aspects of citizen science such as communication of scientific methods and research results to the public and specific target groups
- Collaboration and co-creation with public target groups
- Various levels of citizen engagement, from contributory to extreme citizen science
- Links of CS research to UN Sustainability Goals
- Design scientific methods to meet the interests and needs of the public

Teaching and learning methods

A mixture of lectures, exercises, workshops, lab activities, fieldwork and excursions. The course will be completed with each student having one week (40 hours) to write a 5-page written assignment (essay).

Workload

Lectures 40 hours

Preparation 60 hours

Theory Exercises 8 hours

Practical Exercises 15 hours

Field work 15 hours

Excursions 4 hours

Laboratory 16 hours

Exam prep 8 hours

Exam 40 hours

Total 206 hours

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5.7. Appendix 7. Task 5.3, Case #3 Citizen science. Project Arter. Interview 3 (in-depth on funding)

Interview date: 26th May 2023.

Duration: 30 mins

Case: Arter, <https://arter.dk/landing-page>

Current funding: 2020 - 2023

How to cite Arter: <https://om.arter.dk/videnbase/om-arter/citering-af-arter/>

Interviewee: Anders Tøttrup

Interviewer: Uffe Smed

Summary responsible: Lorna Wildgaard

- **How was the project funded and what are the names of the funders?**
- The project was funded by Danish funders. The project was funded by the "15. juni-fonden" (<https://www.15junifonden.dk/>) which supports for art and culture, research and education, humanitarian and social commitment and Danish nature, the Aage V Jensen naturfond that works for the preservation of nature and the protection of wild animals, and a few resources from the Danish Ministry for the Environment regarding the portal.
- **What are the requirements that the project has to fulfil according to the funder (compliance)?**
- Typical research funding application, where the objectives and aims and goals have to be described and operationalized as deliverables. The funders have a place on the steering committee, so they are in continuous contact with the project group and can contribute with feedback and ask questions about the usability of the portal. The data collection has to be accurate and easy to collect and record for citizens. The language we use on the portal has to be easily understandable and in Danish. There is no university money invested in the project, so we in turn have invested many "in kind" hours in the project.
- **What does the funding cover or not cover in comparison to the budget costs that you have?**
- The funding covers project management (running the project and ensuring progression in the primary activities), development of features on the portal, wages, and IT support.
- **What are your experiences regarding getting EU funding?**
- A big hassle. Currently, we have an EU project with 17 partners about new ontologies and genealogy. Trying to agree and attain a joint understanding of the project's aims and deliverables is time-consuming. Understanding the EU application language and application process is complex, just as is making project aims into work-packages and tasks. The communication flow throughout the application process and the project is also challenging. And when you think about it, some partners in the project have invested very few resources in such a large project so engagement and commitment are

an issue too. With so many partners, the project has to make sense in many different countries and contexts.

- **Any particular difficulties or opportunities is getting CS projects funded?**
- The EU has an increasing focus on citizen science, however EU money is difficult to get! In Denmark I feel we are in competition with “traditional” research methodologies. Citizen science is expensive, there is a lot of communication and in relation to a typical research project, not that much output. The research council has not yet opened their eyes to the benefits and potentials there are in including citizens in science. Private funds have understood the benefits of CS. Yet, their focus is on the teaching, education and IT parts of CS projects rather than the ”research” parts. Novo Nordisk is one of the few funders that understand CS and they are willing to invest. Of course, I can shop around and apply to multiple funders. But, more applications means more deadlines. In summary, we are missing funders in Denmark willing to invest in CS.
- **Have you tried to crowdfund your projects? Third party funding?**
- Some projects are permitted to share funds with third parties. One of the things you could apply for in an EU project is the opportunity for other museums to monitor the biodiversity in for example Denmark. I have never tried crowdfunding. I have experience of philanthropy from the USA, where like a presidential candidate you travel around on a charm offensive and meet with these people. Projects that I know of that have successfully had third party funding have been run by Finn Danielsen (<https://www.nordeco.dk/finn-danielsen>), who looks into trends in ecological revolution.
- **Do you know of any other funding possibilities for CS projects? If yes, who funds CS projects in which area?**
- Well, maybe governmental agencies. They do not offer funds, but we can help solve concrete problems together. For example DNA & Liv [DNA & Life: <https://snm.ku.dk/skoletjenesten/forloeb/dnaogliv/>] have asked us to deliver data about ring marked wildlife and provide this data using CS methods.
- **Which model of investment would you like to see?**
Speculative question: What would be your preferable, optimal model of support for your project?
- CS is a method that bridges private and public funders. It does not completely fit the profile of the one or the other. The private funds as I said before do not want to invest in the research part, which the research funds down prioritise the inclusion of citizens. What I would like to see is a fund that covers research AND the CS part, the part with the citizens and voluntary experts.

Signatures

Anders Tøttrup

Uffe Smed

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5.8. Appendix 8. Task 5.3, Case #3 Citizen science. Project Na Suchu. Interview 1

- **What is the name of the CS project?**
- The name is ‘On drought’ in English and ‘Na Suchu’ in Czech.
- **Is there a website or source material we can refer to?**
Please collect URL/DOIs (can be filled in before the interview by the expert).
- The information about CS in the Czech Republic is on the website citizenscience.cz We currently stand the project at the main Citizen Science platforms like www.scistarter.com, citsci.com and on EU-citizen.science, citizenscience.cz which is the technical platform of Citizen Science. We are the persons in charge of this platform, we own this technical portal and we are some kind of pioneers of citizen science methodology in the Czech Republic. We are also running the EU Horizon project, which is focused on establishing the Citizen Science association of the Czech Republic. This project “Na Suchu” is some kind of reference project, which can also be taken as an example.
- **Please explain briefly what is the purpose of the project.**
Encourage the expert to explain the research questions, the topic of the project, the dates the project ran or will run to if it is a current project.
- The main goal is to engage people in monitoring the agricultural landscape from the climatological point of view. I mean we are running a project which is dealing with some changes in the agricultural landscape and we need to monitor how the changes are taking effect in the landscape. And because the project is for the whole country of the Czech Republic then we need a large number of people who would like to monitor this kind of landscape. So, the main goal is to monitor the agricultural landscape by the people.
- **Regarding stakeholders**
Find out about all the different groups of people involved in the project and the roles they have/had.
Who are the citizens in the project, and what data did they need to collect (and how)?
- It's important to say that the project has been just released so we don't have many observations. The observations are down through the iNaturalist app. It's all prepared for used applications for citizens like iNaturalist and they are collecting different types of agricultural landscape, the good and best practices. This is how landscape could look like, a selection of examples of good and bad practices and people trying to find these examples in the field. They are for volunteers, people don't have to have any specialist knowledge. It is not intended for farmers because farmers are quite a small group. We want to have it open for everyone so observation on what should be captured by observers, it's very easy to understand for everybody.
- **Did you have support from the university administration – in what form/who?**

- This is a little bit specific because this CS project was established as a part of the grant project of National Science agency 4 '15 but we do not have any special funding for, especially in the future. So, the sustainability of the project will be only on the voluntary basis and we don't have any special support nor from the university or from the other organisations.
- **Did the library provide support and which form?**
- No, no they don't give us any support. There is a special department in our scientific library dedicated to open science but open science is some more general topic than citizen science, so any support we get, we get from the partners organisations we are cooperating with through our citizen science networks. For example, the methodological support we can bring from ECSA (European Citizen Science Association) , from the dedicated working groups, we can get support from the EU Citizen Science, where we can gather the resources for the project but no financial support, no in-house support from our university or library there.
- **Did you have help from the university IT?**
- No, we are doing it by ourselves.
- **Did you have help from the university data lab or similar?**
- No (nodding).
- **Additional question: Do you get any support from the other partners of the project: Tomas Bata University, Masaryk University. Mendel University, Research Institute of Geodesy; Topography and Cartography; v. v. i., Institute of Geonics; CAS, Envipor, Association of Private Agriculture** (according to information from link: [EU-Citizen.Science : On Drought \(Na suchu\)](#)).
- Just a quick explanation to the project which is funded by the technological agency and which is focused on drought in the agricultural landscape. This project (out CS project) is added on to this big project to monitor how successful we are in implementing the agricultural landscape. So basically the partners which are listed, they are the partners of the main projects of climate changes in the agricultural landscape which our CS project is a part of. So we are running this CS project with two institutions: The Czech Academy of Sciences and Tomas Bata University in Zlin and other partners are focused on different topics and fields of specialisation of the general project.

Part 2: Experiences running the CS project

Encourage the expert to explore the successes and challenges they meet during the project.

Provide prompting questions, to ensure we get the information we need.

- **Which CS activities were/are in your project?**
- So far we were just collecting data through the iNaturalist, we are running some workshops where people could gather the data in different way, for example we are talking with our Hungarian partners in organising the open Biomaps as a second platform but it's still some ideas , it's not implemented yet and the project is pretty new so we don't have many experiences except data and observations. All other things will be probably in the future, we need to discuss them, yes.

Raising public knowledge, science education, observing/gathering research data, developing analysis tools, DIY research & development. This question will help us inform policy in the future.

- **Was the project a negative or positive experience?**
- We have just a few experiences and I'm not able to answer this question because our experiences are extremely limited, because the project is running just for a few months. We don't have such experiences. We don't expect so many experiences like in a project like bird watching or collecting information about the plans, and very popular project like that because this topics (e.g. bird watching) is a domain stream for volunteers and citizen scientists. So people who would like to join these projects need to search for specific topics. We (Na Suchu) also don't pay for the advertisements at the CS platforms so it is not visible as other projects. It's still not too many people involved in this project, participants and citizen scientists so we will see how it will develop in a few months or few years. Then we will go back to the beginning and try to spread the word about the project, among a large group of people according to what we would be able to collect.
- **What was the greatest success experience you had during the project?**
- I think so far the greatest success was that we were able, at least, to run this project because it's not so usual to run CS project in the case of agricultural landscape and also one of successes we were able to present the ideas of the project to several conferences and forums, for general public to make it more visible but according to data collected we still don't have any successes in this field.
- **Additional question: but from the perspective of pioneering in the CS field in the Czech Republic, is it a kind of success that you make a partnership?**
- Well, it was more than 1,5 years to prepare a project. We started the preparations 2,5 years ago and launched it a few months ago, so it took a long time to prepare it as an achievable project with achievable goals for the citizens in such a , let's say, hard topic. At least harder than others.
- **What was the greatest challenge you faced during the project?**
- I think that the greatest challenge is to attract people for this kind of topic, because as I said it's not usual and it's also a little bit hard to find the places and the fields where you can get the observations. I like other projects, like bird watching, when you can get observation almost everywhere. In our project it's focused on agricultural landscape so, first of all you need to go to agricultural landscape to collect the observations, so that was the hardest challenge, to attract people to motivate them to participate in this kind of observations.
- **What could have gone better in your project?**
- We still don't have proper feedback for it (our project Na Suchu), so it's hard to answer this question. I appreciate, what I like is we were able to get the project to many CS, global platforms. I appreciate it is not only for Czech citizen science participants. What are the disadvantages and what could we do better? It's probably the marketing from the beginning, I mean to promote it more, to gain more data than we have right now. I

think that time will show us what things could be done better, so far I'm not able to give other examples.

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5.9. Appendix 9. Task 5.3, Case #3 Citizen science. Project Na Suchu. Interview 2 (in-depth on support & training)

Part 1: Support for citizen science

- **How is CS promoted/supported at your university? Who promotes it?**
- Well, till now there is no support and no promotion, not even at the university and not in the Academy of Sciences, because the project, “Na Suchu”, is a joint project of several institutions, not only from the university, but also from the The Academy of sciences. And none of the institutions supports and promotes it directly. We have external funding for the large project, which dealings with drought in the landscape. And this citizen science project is one part of the project. So we have financing for it, but not, let's say, long lasting finance.
- **How would you like your university to support Citizen Science?**
- In general? I would like to have some specific, let's say, grant scheme for citizen science projects at university. And I would like to see some policy or strategy how to promote citizen science projects at universities at all. When there is no such kind of strategy, it's sometimes hard to prepare a good promotion and long term support. In the case of promotion, I would like to see some dedicated office, which should serve to researchers and to academics to promote their project, that would support all the citizen science projects in all the ways from the promotion, for the fundraising, for the communication. That would be nice, but let's say some kind of ideal state, if there would be at least anything from it, it would be nice.
- **Additional question: what about digital or traditional promotion?**
- Exactly. The digital promotion is very important. We try to do it by ourselves by listing the citizen science project in the citizen science platforms. But if the university could use its own communication channels like the Instagram Facebook channels to promote such kind of project. It would be also nice. And the promotion and the dissemination of the project by face to face event is also nice. I can imagine that there would be some paid students who would take lectures at the libraries at the museums to present the project itself. They could have some lectures at the public library's museums to the public to get more engaged participants in the projects. Actually, at the Academy of Science, I have one student who is coming to my office and helping me with the project and she's doing such kind of promotion. She's going from library to library, from museum to museum, and delivering lectures about the Citizen Science project to public and trying to engage people by this face to face event.
- **Are there (or could be) policy papers specifically on CS at your university?**
- I think they should focus on, let's say, institutionalisation of the project. I mean that there would be clearly written of which kind of support you are eligible to get. Who can help you with with the promotion? How the university will benefit from the citizen

science projects? How do you deal with the data collected by the citizens? Because it's also quite a big question how to work with such kind of data. So all the stuff, all the things could be there because the university in general has some papers or measures about the research in general. But the citizen science projects are a little bit different. And I think that there are not so many focus on the specifics of citizen science projects in these measures and papers.

- **Are there CS associations, CS platforms or other information services on CS at your university? If so, please specify them.**
- Not at our university, but our university together is the Academy of Sciences are maintaining the citizen science cs.cz portal to traditional citizen science portal. So yeah, we are maintaining it, but we, the university doesn't fund it. So it means that for maintaining the portal, we need to get external funding. So it's typically maintained by a group of people with the affiliation to university. But the university itself has just the logo of the university and a page. And that's almost all.
- **Which support units at the university helped you (or could help you) throughout the project?**
- I would like to have the options to get some money for maintaining the Citizen Science Project. I mean, to have some approach to grant schemes for citizens science support the university. Secondly, I would also appreciate some systematic promotional support, which is also missing. We talked about it earlier, and maybe in some cases, I would also appreciate support with the data management, with some hardware infrastructure where we can store a data and manage the data in a secure way.
- **Which technical infrastructure(s) provided support in your project?**
- Well, we need some secure data storage. For now, we are well storing the data, the public, the servers like iNaturalist or some under clouds like the Microsoft cloud or the Google Google Drive. Google Cloud. And to have the data at home, let's say, would be nice because we can manage the security of all the data then because our project also has a, let's say, some spatial framework and we need to look for specific server. I would also appreciate some, some better where we can run around our mapping applications. These are the technical things, let's say maybe for the lectures to do public. It would be also nice to have some spare tablets or mobile phones where we can demonstrate how the Citizen Science Project works, how the people can collect the data using these tools. So this would also help. Nowadays we are using our own devices, our own tablets and mobile phones to show people how to collect the data. But it might be better if we have some more from the university that does the hard work. However, some.
- **Additional question: What about data protection of the data stored by Google?**
- It's exactly the problems we are dealing with that you don't have. You don't know where exactly the data is. They can be outside the European Union. They have different legislative strokes. These are all our problems we are dealing with. And the hardware support, if you can store the data inside the European Union would be nice.
- **So now the human infrastructure, what would you like to have in your project?**

- We were talking about some person for the promotion of the project in general, in our specific case, we could also have some, let's say, researchers who would analyse the data. But basically this could be done by us. So it's not needed by the university. So the promotion of some you also mentioned a scientific officer. It's also a nice idea, which would be nice to have at a university.
- **Maybe programmers for backup of the data?**
- Yes, it might be helpful. We would like to say that we don't want to develop new applications, but to use the ones which are on the market. So in our project we are using the naturals, which is widely spread among the population. So to be honest, we don't need exactly a programmer, but I can imagine that in some specific cases and in some other citizens project, the program for us might help a lot. So if some spare capacity of programmers at the University or the IT workers at the universities could be dedicated to the citizen science background or the help of the project, it would be nice.
- **What kind of help would you like to have?**
- Well, I actually don't have any kind of help at my university or the academy, aside from different classes besides the. Yeah, we have aid from different sources. We have it from the external grants scheme for the different projects. We have financial support and we are working with, with the funding to, to, to develop the project. But it's an, let's say, external funding from the university.
- **What requirements or needs exist for handling, cleaning, storing and sharing data in CS projects?**
- Yes, exactly. Yeah. Just our team is doing it and we are still not in the phase that we need to be. We need to take control over a lot of data. It's the project is still in the beginning and we don't have enough observation to do such kind of, let's say, database management under the data. So we still are preparing for it.
- **Which aspects of support are Citizen Science specific and which are support “agnostic” support? Basically, is there a need for Citizen Science support or is general OS support enough (DM, coding, communication etc)?**
- It's a very good question. I think that the support of citizen science could also be done within the framework of open science. There are a lot of similarities. So the basic concepts of open science are very close to the Citizen Science Project itself. So maybe the general approach or the general support for the open science could be enough. But in some aspects it is specific. Well, one of the main specification is that you need to continuously work with the community, with the public, with the people who are participating. A new approach. This is not always the role for open science. So in that case, maybe some specific support might be useful. I mean, some, let's say community manager, some person who will be in touch with the community, who will send regular newsletters, who will get their results, to back to the community, back to the participants who will do the dissemination. So the community manager, in my opinion, it's a good idea.
- **Where and when in the process around a CS project is the support most needed?**

- I think it's very important in the beginning when you need a lot of energy and a lot of time too, to establish and to run the Citizen Science Project. I think that if we did not get the funding from the external grant agency, we wouldn't be able to start a project. So it is time consuming and you need to really look forward to the support. It's very important in that phase. Then I think of another kind of support during the beginning, which is on the promotion, to engage as many people as possible. And in the further phases of the project, you need a community manager who is in touch with the community and getting the results back to the community. But if I should compare this three, let's say three phases I talked about, I think the most important is the initial, the first place.
- **What support did/will you need for reflection? Which gaps in support do you see?**
- Yeah, It's a great association and we get a lot of support from ECSA. Well we don't use all of the support. For example, we are part of some working groups in ECSA where you can present and discuss your particular topics and problems. I should do that as support in a dissemination of results through the monthly newsletters. That's also great and the opportunity to hope on some running European projects led by is also good. So I feel very satisfied with the support from ECSA by the way. I'm in America and I'm also dealing with the CSA Citizens Science Association, the American One. I think the support from ECSA is better and much more sophisticated and the structure of support is better there than in North America.
- **How are the researchers best supported in connection with CS projects at the moment and how could this be optimised?**
- Well, we are quite a small, small team participating or running the Citizen Science Project. So all of us are connected to each part of the Citizen Science Project. So we all have access to the data. We work with them. As I said before, unfortunately, we still don't have enough data to produce some relevant analyses. So there is not such an output. But everyone from our team is connected to the project. We also would like to open all the collected data to the public, to other researchers. But after we will have some, let's say, more than a database, since now there are just a few observations, like hundreds of surveys, which is still not enough.

Part 2: About skills and training

- **Which skills do each stakeholder group need (including yourself in running and administering the project)?**
- Yeah, that's true. That's a really hard question for me. I don't feel qualified to completely utter it, at least to me what I meet or is let's say some managerial skills, how to help to manage the project itself. We all should have some informatics knowledge because we don't have any expert, an external IT person who would take care about the project. We are doing it by ourselves and the stakeholders. You said right that there are not so many stakeholder groups, but still some of them are like the the agricultural experts or the Chamber of Commerce for example, and the people, farmers who can also join a project.

And these people should have, let's say, some basic IT skills. They should know how does it work. All the process from collecting data to work with the data.

- **Does your university run CS courses or training programs (on which level)?**
- Well, we have some basic training in the description of the project. They are only trained by text instruction. What to observe? How does it look like, what they are observing and what they should focus on? But basically anyone can join the project and I believe that the instructions are sufficient. We were limited by the space in the in the project descriptions at all the citizen science platforms where we tried to do our best to explain it as much as is possible. What they really need is to have an approach to the I'm not sure it's the platform we have chosen for our science project, and this goes hand in hand with the mobile phone, which is equipped to do the camera, and the users should be able to take a picture to upload a picture. And yeah, that's just basically that's basically all, all the skills they need.
- **Did the [stakeholder group] receive training to take part in your project?**
- No, no. But we are using free services of citizen science training which are accessible in the new citizen science. And we use this kind of courses from the EU citizen good science platform.
- **Do you plan for stakeholder training?**
- Well, not now. Maybe in a later stage. If we see that the project is not running so smoothly, then we may plan some kind of training. But not now.
- **Which gaps in skills development do you see?**

Well, in the specific case of our project, they could more or they could yet deeply learn the topic of the agricultural drought because it's a main leitmotif of our project. But it's probably not necessary. In some cases it might be hard to classify all types of the agricultural drought, even we tried to describe them briefly in the description in Inaturalist and other platforms that might be difficult. And this could be classified as a skill gap in this specific project like ours.

5.10. Appendix 10. Task 5.3, Case #3 Citizen science. Project Na Suchu. Interview 3 (investment models)

Duration: 30 mins

- **How was the project funded?**
- Szymon Andrzejewski (SzA) – The first question: How was your project funded?
- Jakub Trojan (JT) – This project was part of the broader project, which was focused on climate changes and the impact of droughts and the Citizen Science project was such a side effect of the project. It wasn't the primary outcome. So we've got funding for it from the larger umbrella project, and this is just a one-time funding. We don't have secured the funding for the next few years. We'll manage it by ourselves.

Ask the name of the funder(s) and if there are requirements that the project has to fulfil according to the funder (compliance)

- SzA – If there were any requirements that the project has to fulfil according to the funder? If there were any requirements that the project has to fulfil for the funder?
- JT – Yes. Czech Academy of Sciences, this is the institution, which is the owner of the project, actually. I was enrolled from the beginning, also in the bigger umbrella project focused on climate change. And there were no requirements for it. So we just wrote that one of the outputs will be the Citizen Science Project for the monitoring of climate changes in the agricultural landscape. And that's basically also all other requirements we managed by our service. And actually there are no, no requirements or former requirements for citizen Science Project in the Czech Republic at all. I know that there are some quality criteria in other countries, like in Austria some quality criteria. There are also quality criteria for citizen science projects in Germany, but not in our country. And we are actually in other projects, dealing with the methodologies of citizen science. We are working on such kind of quality criteria to be met by the Citizen Science Projects. Actually, we are also running the Czech Citizen Science National Portal. It's the Citizen Science.cz and there are some requirements for projects which you would like to be listed in the Citizen Science Portal of the Czech Republic. These are, let's say, basic requirements should be met by all projects, including our projects. But there are no formal requirements at all.

What are the requirements from your funder?

- SzA – Additional question: Don't you have to fulfil any indicators at the, at the end in connection with your citizen science activities?
- JT – Well, if we are talking just about the Citizen Science Project, then the answer is no.
- SzA – Can you tell me something more about your funder, their specifics, how they work?

This project has received funding from
The European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme
under grant agreement No 101016674

- JT – Yes, the founder is a technology agency of the Czech Republic. It's a governmental institution with which funds the applied projects or the projects of applied research. The funding doesn't cover all expenditures. So you have to co-finance the budget. So we've got funding for about 85% of the whole budget. And the last 15% is paid by, by the institutions which are involved in the umbrella project. The Technology Agency of the Republic is a big institution which funds a lot of projects, not necessarily the projects with the citizen science attribute, but all projects of applied research. And we've got funding from them.

What does the funding cover/not cover (budget costs)

- SzA – What does the funding cover or not cover compared to the budget costs that you have?
- JT – There was money for the personal costs, so we've got paid for creation of the project. From the, the, the indirect funds we were able to, to buy a domain for the project, website and buy some graphical design. And that's all. So, the personal cost and the IT stuff, including the web design, the domain and the web hosting, that's all markers.
- SzA – Other costs that you are aware of have to cover by yourselves? Or by your work?
- JT – Yes, exactly. Then it's part of our work. So when we do a propagation or the promotion that was funded by ourselves and done as part of our work. We've got some round tables with people who might be interested in the projects. Also part of our work, so not, not covered by the funding. Collecting the data, some pilots, although as part of our work not funded. So all of this wasn't part of the funding.

Have you tried to crowdfund your projects? Third party funding?

- SzA – According to this answer that you just gave, so have you tried to crowdfund your projects? Some third party funding, some people's, let's say crowdfunding or massive or maybe some funding from private sector or other sources?
- JT – No, we haven't tried it at all.

What are your experiences regarding getting EU funding?

- SzA – What are your experiences regarding getting EU funding? When you submitted your proposal, was it big or low?
- JT – Again, if we, if we are talking about the Citizen Science Project only then it was part of the bigger, bigger project. So I think that the scoring of the project or the evolution of the project itself wasn't done only, only about the Citizen Science Project. So, the umbrella project was quite big, so there was quite a big administration behind the project. But, as I said before, the Citizen Science project was just a very small part of it. We didn't spend much time with the proposal of the Citizen Science Project itself, and it was funded by the Technology Agency of the Czech Republic. So, there is no connection to the European grant schemes or the European funding.
- SzA – Imagine that you are submitting your proposal by yourself, for example, for the next stage for your project. It's a question about your experience in submitting European Union funding. Do you have any and how much?

- JT – Well, from my previous experience of submitting EU projects like the Horizon projects, , it was quite difficult to, to write all the facts and the information to the limited space and also the Horizon Programme calls are highly competitive. It was, it was quite, quite hard. Well, but now, I'm not talking about our student science projects, I'm now talking about my experiences from the funding EU project.
- SzA – So, maybe do you know, and do you have any particular difficulties or opportunities in getting, , those, well, your citizen science project fund that, well, you said about some, let's you, that you think about some continuation about projects. So you think about how to find financing for this continuation, for example.
- JT – Yes, we will definitely continue with the project. We still don't have many observations in the project. We'll run it as part of our work because all, all of the major expenses are already done. I mean, the expenses in the domain and hosting the graphics are done. The promotion is running somehow. So, now we are not planning to ask for other funding after, after the funding from a bigger project. We'll finish with our current project, which is actually at the end of the year. If the project will be successful and will be a long lasting project with many observations. And we need to further manage the data and deal with the target group much more. Beyond our current situation we will need to find some, other, fundings., but still, we are not sure where we can apply for the funding.

Do you know of any other funding possibilities for CS projects? If yes, who funds CS projects in which area ?

- SzA – Don't you know any other funding possibilities for citizen science projects in your country and at the European Union level?
- JT – Well, I don't know. There is some project called Impetus in the European Union where they can fund some selected projects, which can help them to empower them by financial support or by mentoring or some other kind of support. But that's, I think, the only way I can remember right now. There's definitely no funding, at the national level, so we don't have any possibilities. And within Europe, I can remember just the impetus project.

Which model of investment would you like to see?

- SzA – Last question will be more speculative. What model of investment would you like to see? So let's say what model of support you would like to have. If you have any possibilities that you would like to have for the support of your citizen project, what would be your preferable, optimal model of support for your project?
- JT – I can view two ways. The first one could be the support of your institution. If the institution is big enough, like the university or the Czech Academy of Sciences, it is also a big institution. There could be some, some budget for the Citizen Science project and the budget could compete between themselves for the limited money. That's okay. The second, second way are some calls for funding skills and science projects run by some national agency or national grant agency, which would be willing to support citizen science projects.

There could be a competition. So it's absolutely okay that the best citizen science projects will get the funding, but at least some grant scheme could exist at the national level. So I think the baseline is at the institutions. The second line could be in the international level, and it's done through the, let's say some, some citizen science association or grant agency of the country. It doesn't matter. But on a national level, some kind of funding could be also helpful.

- SzA – You mentioned, you know, institutional level and national level, and what about, let's say international level? It could also be interesting for you.
- JT – Yes. In the scale of the project we are now. I think these kinds of projects are not so broad. I mean, the geographical area is not so large. If I run some project, which is broader and covers a large geographic area, then yes, some international funding could be also fine.

5.11. Appendix 11. Task 5.3, Case #3 Citizen science. Project ‘L’Observatoire Agricole de la Biodiversité’ (OAB) . Interview 1

Protocol – Interview with Romain Juillard

Date of the interview: 21st December 2022

Part 1: About the project

- **What is the name of the CS project?**
Is there a website or source material we can refer to?
Please explain briefly what the purpose of the project is.
- It’s a french citizen science project, called „L’Observatoire Agricole de la Biodiversité (OAB)“ (<https://www.observatoire-agricole-biodiversite.fr/>)
 The project is an initiative of the “Ministère en charge de l’Agriculture” and was launched in 2011 to compensate for the lack of surveillance concerning biodiversity. Its aim is to establish a link between biodiversity research and farmers as well other stakeholders around farming in order to record relevant biodiversity data. In order to do so OAB provides the participants with five different protocols.

Protocol	Associated agricultural topic
Solitary bee nest boxes	Pollination, Landscape quality
Butterfly transects	Pollination, Landscape quality
Earthworm plots	Soil fertility
Terrestrial invertebrate plots	Pest monitoring, Crop auxiliaries
Bat recordings	Crop auxiliaries, Quality of landscapes

Regarding stakeholders

- **Who are the citizens in the project, and what data did they need to collect (and how)?**
- The citizens involved are farmers, and what they are doing is collecting data guided by one or more of the above-mentioned protocols. Furthermore, there are also facilitators who are e.g. working in farmers organisations. These facilitators recruit interested farmers to participate in the project and assist the farmers by providing advice. Every facilitator supervises 10 to 15 farmers.

How many farmers and facilitators are involved? On the whole 1700 different farms are participating.

The Museum for Natural History in Paris is the project lead. It is a research institution in Paris, not only with a large exhibition, but rather also home of 16 different research

groups. Further research institutions act as scientific collaborators. Furthermore, the largest national organisation for farming “L'école Chambre d'agriculture” is an important partner.

The project is funded by the French Ministry of Agriculture. Since 2011 the funding has been renewed every year.

- **Did you have support from the administration – in what form/who?**
- Yes. There is support with the scientific coordination provided by the museum administration and leadership, even though the overall project was not financed by the museum itself.
- **Did you have help from the university IT?**
- Up to now, no. But there has been centralization in the past 5 years concerning IT-supports in the museum, which is really dedicated to specific IT-support for citizen science. There is a larger number of CS projects, but this unit is able to support 5 to 10 projects every year in France. The IT-Team is financed through the respective project-funds.
- **Did you have help from the university data lab or similar?**
- No.

Part 2: Experiences running the CS project

- **Which CS activities were/are in your project?**
- Cf. above.
- **Was the project a negative or positive experience?**
- It's both. One positive thing is that many stakeholders involved in general are very positive about the project, e.g. farmers and farming organisations.
It was a success with regard to capacity and awareness building. Another success concerns the data collected. The project provides important insights concerning biodiversity and farming due to robust and accurate data.
Problem: More farmers wish for research results which are directly applicable to their daily practices. That's why many farmers leave the project after 1-3 years (fortunately others are willing to join new). So, there is a mismatch between the participants' aim and the project's aim. More practical use is needed.
- **What was the greatest challenge you faced during the project?**
In the beginning the website was poor, so it was difficult to collect complex data. “It was a nightmare.” In order to work well as a platform for CS projects it should be well-structured for the analysis, user-friendly and appropriate for science. In 2019(?) a new web portal could be created. 2022 seems to be the highest participation rate ever.
- **What was the greatest success experience you had during the project?**
So many different stakeholders are still interested in the project and its topics. Twice a year there is a meeting for the representatives of the organisations involved and they are very positive about it.
- **What could have gone better in your project?**

The project is successful in recruiting farmers for participation but they are expecting something else (cf. above). There should be better conversation tools for interaction, but we need some help for that. We are still very good with regard to stakeholders engagement, but we are still lacking of something for the continuous participation of the farmers. It must be a project that must make sense to the farmers. In this sense we need to reach them better.

Romain Julliard

5.12. Appendix 12. Task 5.3, Case #3 Citizen science. Project ‘L’Observatoire Agricole de la Biodiversité’ (OAB) . Interview 2

Protocol – Interview 2 with Romain Juillard

Date of the interview - 9th February 2023

Part 1: Support for citizen science

We would now like to enquire into the support you received during the project. Then we’ll ask about the support that perhaps was missing and you needed (or vice versa, support you received but did not need!). In the second part of the interview we’ll talk about the training and skills needed to take part in a citizen science project.

- How is CS promoted/supported at the Museum of Natural History? Who promotes it?
- CS showed up for the first time as a topic in a research scheme in 1998. In 2005 dedicated CS projects started and CS was taken up by the head of the museum as a strategic topic.

For a long time there was no organisation between the head of the museum, i.e. the strategic level, and the researchers performing CS-based research-.

In 2017 more systematic coordination was started, so that the CS became part of the museum’s organisational structure in 2018. Since then it’s in the organigram.

- **Are there policy papers specifically on CS at your university? Strategic/political aim (policy papers/position papers etc.)?**
- Yes there is a strategic paper (from 2018, before not).
- **Are there CS associations, CS platforms or other information services on CS at your university? If so, please specify them. Which technical infrastructure(s) provided support in your project? Which human infrastructure(s) provided support in your project?**
- The support unit MOSAIC [i.e. Romain’s unit] was installed in 2020: <https://mosaic.mnhn.fr/> Our unit is mostly for supporting new projects in cs; researchers that want some help for their projects; but there is also a bottom-up network of researchers interested in cs topics (Sorbonne and the museum, roughly half of the people of the museum).

Sorbonne University CS is currently a strategic topic at the university level, but there is no explicit support infrastructure/no mediating level between researchers and university leadership. In this respect the situation at Sorbonne is similar to the situation at the museum before 2018.

We (the museum) offer infrastructure not only support, but also infrastructure for communication, data storage and presentation. Here we guarantee the technical sustainability of the outputs.

- **What requirements or needs exist for handling, cleaning, storing and sharing data in CS projects? Which gaps in support do you see? Which support is needed, what do you miss?**
- A central challenge is the research design and “coconstruction of research questions” (project design, analysis tools); The question is: How can we build an easy-to-use platform, that citizens can use and deliver relevant data? Because citizens are involved in data collection this has to work right from the beginning. You have no second chance, because if it does not work right from the beginning, people will not be willing to participate further.
We need to be able to improve the user experience to foster participation.
In the biodiversity projects that’s the crucial role of the facilitators. These try to push the farmers (lack of motivation on side of the farmers).
- **How are the researchers best supported in connection with CS projects at the moment and how could this be optimised?**
- One key aspect is the facilitation of community management; it’s not necessarily a fulltime job, only part time, but it needs to be done constantly and with high dedication. You need some communication and animation; its really about activating and keeping them to the scheme and to engage in interaction with feedback and so on.

Part 2: About skills and training

- **Which skills do each stakeholder group need (including yourself in running and administering the project)?**
- We have the farmers and facility managers to explain things to the farmers, scientists and so on. For each of these groups. What are the most important skills to participate in the project?
- **Farmers and Facilitators, which skills do they need?**
- They should be open to the project of general interest; facilitators: We really rely on the large numbers of farming organisations (and similar institutions). Farmers and facilitators need a special kind of training to be fit for the project; there is a training session every year, it is about one day in late winter, so that the new facilitators are ready; and then there is another session in autumn on feedback. The topics of this training contains basic information about the project and how the data collection works.
- **Is there communication training for facilitators?**
- Unfortunately not that much, but I’m no expert.
- **And for the researchers? What do you think about their skills needed?**
- They should really trust and believe in the CS, i.e. that CS is a useful tool. Otherwise it just wouldn’t work. The researchers need to trust the participants in the sense that they trust with regard to their capacity and that they really can provide meaningful content for the project. It is really a commitment. A real engagement of the researchers is needed for CS. (Data quality, innovation, etc.). Necessary: communication skills.
- **Are there more technical skills that people need to have?**

- My experience is that many of these projects rely on the quality of the protocol for the data collection. It's not comparable to the lab, because there is no second chance to redo the experiment with measurement and all that stuff. So a one-to-one counselling for projects with our unit is helpful.
- **Does the museum run CS courses or training programs (on which level)?**
- One course per year (25 participants/candidates); different topics, my group is considering the project very specifically (support, tips, and so on). The course is a joint offer by the museum and Sorbonne University.
- **What skills do you need (your group)? Training?**
- The team is organised around my own experience in the field; other team members contribute specific skills and knowledge. I, as a researcher, bring in knowledge on data collection, research design etc. Other people have domain knowledge on user-friendly interface design or similar topics.
- **Which gaps in skills development do you see?**
- I already stressed the facilitators. Often we rely on external people for example from NGO's. There is not always a match between NGO-goal and the museum's goal. We are more in the research project and in cs, whereas the NGO might be more interested pushing its agenda. Facilitators are more often really dedicated to cs, so that there is a good match/coherence. Optimally universities should have their own services for cs and facilitations to create a win-win-effect by internalising facilitation into the university.

Romain Julliard

5.13. Appendix 13. Task 5.3, Case #3 Citizen science. Project ‘L’Observatoire Agricole de la Biodiversité’ (OAB) . Interview 3

Protocol – Interview 3 with Romain Juillard

Date of interview - 5 May 2023

- **How was the project funded?**
- The Ministry for Agriculture funds the project. In a narrow sense of funding this is the only funder. In a wider sense, there is also” indirect funding” by the farming organisations, which support the coordination of the project. They offer infrastructure and support for this, but no money. Additionally, the MOSAIC infrastructure [i.e. Romain’s unit; <https://mosaic.mnhn.fr/>] offers technical and organisational support.
- **Tell me more about your funder, are they national, international, institutional or a mix?**
- It’s national funding. The funding is not part of a specific funding programme for which there has been an open call for proposals, rather it results from an individual decision by the ministry to set up such a project. The budget coming from the ministry is appr. 60 k euros per year.
- **What are the requirements from your funder?**
- Since there is no specific funding scheme there are no specific formal requirements. The funding must be renewed every year, i.e. there is no long-term guarantee for the funding. That does also mean that there can be only one-year-working contracts. But the cooperation with the ministry is very good. The last ten years the project was very high on its agenda and there is still some motivation and engagement.
- **Are there mandates related to open science, e.g. mandatory open access for publications?**
- That was more implicit. There is no obligation for open access. With regard to open data there are of course legal requirements. E.g. you are not allowed to deliver specific data for the individual farmers, but only anonymized data and aggregated statistics.
- **What does the funding cover/not cover? (budget costs)**
- The funding covers the position of a project coordinator. The ministry also funded the technical infrastructure. Additionally, the project can make use of the centrally funded infrastructure provided by MOSAIC.
- **What are your experiences regarding getting EU funding?**
- There is experience with EU funding, but not specific for CS projects.
- **Any particular difficulties or opportunities is getting CS projects funded? Do you know of any other funding possibilities for CS projects? Do you think funders are well enough aware of CS methods and projects?**
- In general, there are many opportunities. Besides the public funders, private funders are interested in CS.

In France the most important funding agency ANR explicitly dedicates 1% of its budget to funding for projects on “participatory research”, which includes but is not limited to CS:

One major difficulty with regard to funding is the following: For CS projects community management is crucial. This is not the same as outreach or administration and typically there is no specific funding for that. E.g. in our project the facilitators [mentioned in the first two interviews] are highly relevant for the project’s success.

This type of community management is typically not a full-time job. Rather one person could do this for e.g. 10 projects. Here it would be good to have means to pool smaller shares of positions from several projects in order to then compile a full position CS community manager from them.

At the moment we often do this community management in cooperation with interested partner organisations. In the farming projects there are the farming organisations, but it could also be NGO’s.

- **Have you tried to crowdfund your projects? Third party funding?**
- I think crowdfunding for CS really has to be handled very carefully because of engagement and willingness, especially in France. You can’t force anyone to pay for it.
- **Do you think that the right Funding schemes are available already?**
- There is a mismatch between funding schemes and the needs of CS projects. Typically, you can apply for relatively short-term projects for two or three years and whether an extension/follow-up project is possible is unclear.

But typically, CS project need more time to start because everything needs to be planned and prepared more carefully before involve the citizens in e.g. data collection. The infrastructure used, e.g. web interfaces for data acquisition, must also be designed more sophisticatedly and be optimised in terms of usability. This needs more time than it does in other research projects.

And also, with regard to the research topics themselves, CS projects are almost always long-term projects.

- **Which model of investment would you like to see?**
- A sensible financing method would be some kind of conditional financing of long-term projects. Of course, financing for 10 years should not be distributed in an uncontrolled manner. But there should be opportunities to make such long-term funding possible through clearly defined agreements on project aims. Funding should be secured as long as these goals are met. In other words: You apply for a project consisting of step 1, step 2 and step 3, initially only step 1 is funded, but if this is successfully mastered, then step 2 is also automatically funded, and so on. This would both safeguard the funding and give the possibility to stop projects that do not work.

(Of course, in the case of long projects, there must be procedures to adjust the project planning and target agreements).

Romain Julliard

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